

**QUESTIONING FRENCH LANGUAGE MAINTENANCE AND SHIFT TO
ENGLISH WITHIN SHORT-TERM MOBILITY: EXPERIENCES OF
ALGERIAN PHD STUDENTS IN THE UK**

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Declaration

I hereby certify that this thesis is based on my original work except for the quotations and citations which have been duly acknowledged. I also declare it has not been previously and is not being currently submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.

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Dedication

“you have been all the time and still my rock”

This research project is duly dedicated to the crew members to my family:

To my loving mother, *Malika Chebira*

To my inherently caring father, *Said*

To my fiancé and future husband, *Bilal Grine*

To my siblings, *Yasmina, Meriem, Islam, Mohamed and Aya*

To my nephews, *Anes, Diaa and Joud*

To my brothers in law: *Khaled and Radwane*

To my dearest friends, Dr. *Linda Merzougui* and *Amina Abdesselem*

To my blood relatives and friends all over the world

“Without your ongoing support, my international study-abroad experience would not be of incalculable worth such a lot! “

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Abstract

This study examines the sociolinguistic interface between language and transnational mobility as a lived experience. From a range of sociolinguistic practices, it covers an investigation of French language maintenance (LM) and language shift (LS) to English among a specific ethnolinguistic friendship group of Algerian PhD students, identified by their transition to the UK in the light of internationalisation of higher education, mobility and exchange programmes. The focus is on their use of French language (a colonial heritage) alongside other linguistic resources (Algerian Arabic and English) during languaging, for the competitive status it holds in Algeria, especially regarding English. The transition of students towards the UK is thereby assumed to trigger more complexity at the level of their verbal repertoires. To analyse this complexity, the study followed a mini-ethnographic case study methodology. Based on that, a corpus of data was obtained following a sequential mixed methods design. Two types of speech data were sought: self-report perceptions and observed actual behaviours to get more “tick” descriptions of LM/LS. Semi-structured interviews among a group of 6 ethnically related Algerian PhD students in Scotland to elicit perceptions were complimented by web-questionnaire results from a larger sample for the purpose of contextualisation. Focus group sessions were organised among the 6 aforementioned participants to observe their perceived linguistic practices in practice. Subsequently, observation of speech practices embedded within everyday activity was conducted as a supplementary method to strengthen focus group results. The LM/LS framework is usually applied over an extended period of time. Although this framework poses considerable challenges in the context of this research, the interplay of findings proposed a novel and useful application, well-suited to situations of short-term mobility. These two processes (LM/LS) were deployed with considerable caution in the specific form of sojourn being studied, and thereby they were presented as non-deterministic processes, reflecting temporary and potentially nascent stages of LM/LS. Furthermore, the application of LM/LS in this specific context suggested that participants straddle two contexts: an international context and a traditional inward-looking Algerian context bound by current Algerian language policy which explicitly promotes English at the expense of French. Therefore, this research is building bridges between traditional perspectives and new ones. The short-term mobility of stay also appeared to affect perceptions more than behaviours. At a broader level, the study

affirms the need to adopt translanguaging as a new approach in LM/LS which favours the co-occurrence of linguistic behaviours in concert with each other. Putting all these together, this research project has led to more nuanced understandings of LM/LS, especially in an era where globalised communication has changed the nature of migration studies.

Keywords: *actual behaviours; language maintenance; language shift; self-report perceptions; short-time mobility; translanguaging*

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List of Abbreviations

AA: Algerian Arabic

CL: Community language

EFL: English as a foreign language

EL: English language

FL: French language

Eng.: English

Fr.: French

LM/LS: Language maintenance and language shift

LM: Language maintenance

LS: Language shift

L1: First language

MSA: Modern standard Arabic

QP: Questionnaire's participant

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION AND CONTEXT OF THE STUDY

1.1 General Background to the Study

The contemporary world embraces a multitude of languages as a product of historical developments, mingled with the linguistic influences of globalisation. When different languages interact, complex social communications arise. Algeria could be viewed as an example of a site of language interaction which triggers linguistic complexity. The source of this complexity stems from the prevalence and maintenance of different linguistic legacies left by colonialism, recently consolidated with the forces of globalisation. This thesis focuses on an important linguistic legacy left by French colonisation and its survival in post-colonial Algeria. Thus, the contextual background primarily includes French language (FL) use but shifting the focus from nation states (local practices) to globalised communities of interest: focusing on transnational individuals instead of local language users. In the transnational setting (UK), the study addresses French language maintenance (LM) and language shift to English (LS) in the context of short-term mobility to the UK, a context that one may reasonably view as problematic for the application of the LM/LS framework. From a large set of Algerian mobility patterns, the researched population consists of a professional group of PhD students, who were transitioned to the UK to develop their academic trajectories in the light of internationalisation of higher education, mobility and exchange programmes. Hence, the study is an exploration of French LM/LS to English within globalised communication practices: among Algerian PhD students in their daily life face-to-face interactions, during their time in the UK.

As a well-grounded point of departure, this study nested some theoretical resources as influencing constructs. In the first place, it is theoretically driven by new lines of thinking about language and globalisation contributed to by scholars such as Blommaert (2010), Blommaert and Rampton (2011), Wei and Hua (2013), Otheguy, García and Reid (2015), Pauwels (2016), Blackledge and Creese (2017) and Canagarajah (2017). With the diffuse nature of mobility flows since the 1990s, there has been a diversification in mobility patterns with different motives and interests (Blommaert and Rampton, 2011). Part of this globalised mobility is the creation of communities of interest, with people moving in very different ways

for very different reasons. A new interest in professionals and how they are becoming globalised has emerged, superseding the limited traditional concern of migration which often focused more on economic migrants and migrants with a long period of settlement.

The study sheds light on a specific group, crossing borders for academic purposes within a mobility programme: “the Multi-million Pound Scholarship Programme” (British Council, 2014). This programme is characterised with an almost guaranteed return to the country of origin. Transnational (short-term) mobility is used in this project as a key concept to describe how distinct this group is, in part because of its association with internationalisation of higher education (Jenkins, 2017), and in part because of the privileges they have in terms of opportunities to travel and keep links with communities back home and close proximities in the new setting (Wei and Hua, 2013), let alone the conditional return to the country of origin.

In terms of linguistic practices, there is an increasing emergence of new perspectives in the study of language and multilingualism as a result of global technological changes (Blommaert, 2010, Pauwels, 2016, 2019, Canagarajah, 2017). Linguistic practices are becoming viewed as more fluid, flexible and dynamic. In symmetry with this, the main concerns addressed here are how this new class of professionals and short-term mobile students form their linguistic practices in the global space, and how LM/LS can happen within their daily practices, with regards to these new perspectives.

LM/LS is considered as the fundamental theoretical stance within the study’s theoretical framework. This framework was chosen to study the sustainability of linguistic practices and potential changes that may occur as part of students’ study-abroad experience on the premise that study abroad can affect students’ identity (Bodycott et al., 2012, Kinginger, 2013), intercultural communication (Terzuolo, 2018) and even language use (Pearson-Evans, 2006). According to Pauwels (2016), the need for education is among the multiple reasons of mobility that can trigger effects in language use: “all these forms of mobility, voluntary or forced, short or long term, are most likely to involve contact between speakers of different languages or language varieties” (p.17). However, she critically reflected that migrant and territorial minority settings are two key settings for the study of LM/LS, because of the potential significant effects that may happen, unlike the short-term language contact, with less linguistic effects (Pauwels, 2016). Therefore, while the application of LM/LS can be

challenging within the context of short-term mobility for some reasons that will be detailed in Chapter Three (section **3.3.4**), it can be an important exploration for this study.

Following Fishman's conceptualisation, LM/LS is used and even sustained in contemporary situations to mean the continuous use of one language, without being succumbed to competition with another (LM), and the replacement of one language with another (LS). The use of languages in LM/LS was emphasised as a binary choice; "either/or". This implies separation and viewing languages as "bounded entities", a view that was criticised by prominent scholars in language and multilingualism (Pauwels, 2016). This study, while still adhering to the dominant LM/LS perspective, elaborates further on the original conceptualisation of LM/LS by looking at it within a range of linguistic resources (looking at French LM within Algerian Arabic/ AA and English), rather than in isolation. As a mid-range influencing theory, the translanguaging perspective affects this research because of the fluidity, flexibility and dynamism in using languages. This perspective implies switching between different resources as an everyday spontaneous practice (Mazzaferro, 2018a). It is also used to mean the flexible deployment of individuals' full linguistic resources in their repertoires for the purpose of meaning-making, in more fluid and dynamic ways (Otheguy, García and Reid, 2015). Central to the basic principles of a translanguaging perspective, LM and LS are studied in this project within their occurrence alongside different linguistic resources, in concert with each other, instead of the exclusive practice that LM and LS were traditionally associated with.

Taking this perspective, the study sets out to look at these new forms of French LM/LS to English during languaging (beside AA), and how these mobile students mix their languages during their interactions as part of their international experience.

As a tightly focused theoretical influence, this study is also informed by the social-psychological approach to understand the decisions behind language choices and behaviours. Social-psychological perspectives pertain to how social factors influence us and also how we read or view social interaction, without separating our definitions from social situations. This study seeks to interpret observed linguistic behaviours through the lens of understanding attitudes, beliefs, aspirations, imagined identities and motivations, that contemporary social psychologists allude to (Giles, Smith and Robinson, 1980, Pauwels, 2016). This mediating

influence of social-psychological constructs in interpreting behaviours during social interactions is highlighted in LM/LS studies who adopt this approach (Pauwels, 2016).

As a starting belief, this project assumes that people's decisions are contextualised, flexible and derive from a mix of social factors, a common focus between social psychologists and social constructivists. Following social constructivists' beliefs, this research project sets out to explore through employing different methods how participants construct and make sense of their sociolinguistic experiences within their transition to a new sociocultural setting (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). It underlines the role of society and context in the construction of participants' social experiences and interactions. In light of a social constructivism stance, a mini-ethnographic case study is a methodology that was adopted in this study to address language use as an everyday practice during the short-stay period. Mini-ethnographic case study methodology joins together elements from both case study and ethnography (Fusch, Fusch and Ness, 2017). These theoretical and methodological stances laid the ground for the methods I have chosen (see Methodology chapter for a full rationale).

1.1.1 Thesis Outline

In terms of organisation, the project is structured around three theoretical chapters (the contextual scope, literature review of my research, and methodological chapter), findings chapter, discussion chapter and conclusion chapter respectively. The division of literature review chapters is aligned to the research questions. The main aim is to ease the readers' understandings of the theoretical basics upon which these questions are established.

Chapter 1 briefly presents the key theoretical influences underpinning this research. It also maps the different stages that the present research went through. As an introduction to the study's context, it further discusses the multilingual nature and the language issues in Algeria across different successive invasions, the last of which was French colonisation. The discussion goes further to briefly highlight the use and challenges of the French language (FL) in the post-colonial era, with the introduction of English language (EL) in a globalised context. It then addresses the motives that led me to embark on this project. The last section of this chapter sketches the significance of the study.

Chapter 2 goes deeper into the contextual background to outline the current linguistic situation in Algeria. It explains in-depth the position of FL, function, attitudes of the population, and uses in different domains especially among students. It also presents the complexities that the use of FL triggers in the contemporary Algerian speech community. It further discusses the linguistic conflicts that have emerged from the competitive statuses of French and English in Algeria. These have led to the prevalence of two groups: ideologists/adherents of additive multilingualism and ideologists/adherents of subtractive multilingualism. Within this chapter, some potential attempts to address subtractive/additive tensions are also mentioned.

Chapter 3 develops a succinct overview of recent trends in the concept of migration and how it was developed into “heightened mobility” as a result of new perspectives. From general to specific, it starts with presenting an overview on recent Algerian mobility patterns and the development of outward mobility programmes, a type of global mobility that the research participants experienced. It then addresses some potential sociolinguistic outcomes of transnational mobility and diaspora. Within this widely varied arena, the chapter reflects on some applicable theoretical concepts to keep the research within a guided theoretical framework. It therefore sheds more light on the fundamental scholarship on LM/LS, and the application of these theories among minority languages’ speakers. It further surveys similar related works about Western and Arab communities. As a critical point, the study also discusses the limitations of applying LM/LS within short-term mobility. The chapter also describes some dimensions of LM/LS such as attitude-behaviour relationships and the linguistic behaviours that these two phenomena may trigger.

Chapter 4 presents the methodology that guided the fieldwork. It specifies the main research questions and the aims, research paradigm and theoretical assumptions, within which this study is positioned. Following a mini-ethnographic case study methodology, the chapter goes further to provide a full description of the mixed methods sequential design adopted, the research instruments and the approaches followed to manage and analyse data. Ethical issues from this research positioning are also elucidated, in addition to the pilot study and how the research endeavoured to achieve validity and reliability.

Chapter 5, which is longer, consists of data analysis. It sequentially presents the findings of interviews, questionnaires, focus group and observation sessions.

Chapter 6 discusses the main findings in relation to the existing literature. It presents an attempt to answer the research questions, either aligning with what has been stated in literature or producing countering evidence.

The last chapter gives a summary of the research project. It recaps the main findings that represent new knowledge in sociolinguistics. It explains how this new knowledge offers contributions to the sociolinguistic discussion and LM/LS, acknowledges the major limitations imposed by this study, and explains how these limitations can be overcome in calling for future research.

1.2 Socio-historical Overview

1.2.1 Linguistic Imperialism

“Nowhere else in Africa has the language issue been so central in the fight against colonialism [as in Algeria]” (Djité, 1992, p.16)

Algeria could be viewed as a fulcrum owing to its central geographical location, as part of the Maghreb (the Berber world) and northern African continent in general (see **Figure 1.1**). It can be likened to a “a hub uniting Europe, Africa, the Middle East and Asia” (Stora, 2001, p.2). Its vast size, diversified natural resources and geographical situation as opening onto the Mediterranean basin, could be seen as the main elements that shaped its uniqueness and made it the target of some foreign powers. Throughout history, it has been through a long period of foreign exploitation that resulted in the rise of cultural and linguistic pluralism (Benrabah, 2014).

Benrabah (2013) used the concept of “linguistic imperialism” as a phenomenon which dominated the Algerian speech communities throughout history because of different successive invasions. Thus, one may consider the linguistic imperialism established by past foreign powers as a key factor contributing to Algeria’s current linguistic richness and cultural diversity. For this main reason, there should be a thorough reference to its history and how past colonisation affected its linguistic situation before embarking on the introduction to its

current language profile. In this context, Hannoum (2010, p.1) similarly reflected “It is extremely difficult to write about Algeria without reproducing colonial understandings, categories and so forth”. To be more critically reflective in examining the Algerian linguistic history, one may further correlate it to the point that politics and linguistics in Algeria are intertwined, as either implicitly or explicitly claimed by Benrabah (2004), Belmihoub (2012, 2015, 2017) and Bagui (2014).

Figure 1. 1: Algeria’s geographical location (created through ARCGIS)

1.2.2 Language Variation during the Colonial Era

The linguistic situation of Algeria fluctuated from one colonial rule to another, resulting in a blended portrait. The ancient history dating back to 4000 B.C.E reveals that the Berbers or the so-called ‘Amazigh’, which means the ‘free men’, were the indigenous people (Stora, 2001, Belmihoub, 2012, Bagui, 2014, Benrabah, 2014). With their language “Tamazight”, they were the first to leave traces of linguistic history. Afterwards, the coming of the Phoenicians from Lebanon and their contact with Berbers gave rise to the Libyco-Berber language variety (Belmihoub, 2012). The Roman invasion contributed to the integration of Latin as part of

Algeria's diverse linguistic landscape, followed by the Vandals, the Byzantines, the Arabs, the Portuguese, the Spaniards, the Turks and, most importantly, the French (Stora, 2001, Belmihoub, 2012, Benrabah, 2013, 2014). The aforementioned conquering groups, especially the Arabs and the French, altogether left behind them many languages and varieties that paved the way to multilingualism (Benrabah, 2014). Benrabah (2005) raised an interesting point that the Algerian society was bilingual during the Phoenician period, trilingual under the Roman rule and multilingual since the Ottoman reign.

The medieval period was punctuated by the Arabic invasion of North African countries, known as the Islamic movement. The Arab mission was not limited to spreading Islam, but also to *Arabising* the country. At the linguistic level, Classical Arabic gained momentum because of Islam, a religion that was adopted by the overwhelming majority of Berbers at that time (Chebchoub, 1985, Belmihoub, 2012). Belmihoub (2012, p.2) made a point:

It is understood by many that classical Arabic is the miraculous language of the holy book of Islam (the Koran), it is thought that to be a Muslim (e.g. to pray), one needs to identify with and use this language. It seems that this idea helped Classical Arabic maintain its influence in North Africa to such a point that most natives who converted to Islam became 'Arabs'

Therefore, a strong relationship was built between Berbers and Arabs. Based on that, it is more likely to think that Arabic, a language that was widely introduced through religion, is among the languages with a considerable sociolinguistic effect and a long-term potential to fully *Arabise* Algeria in the coming centuries. Therefore, the Arabic invasion can be considered as a turning-point in the history of Algeria, in the sense of wiping out what is introduced by previous invasions and implementing their own processes: Islamisation and Arabisation. Both processes continued to represent Algerian identity up to today (Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008). The Arab conquest of Algeria was followed by the settlement of the Portuguese and Spaniards in the 15th century who seemed to last briefly according to what is articulated in literature.

In 1516, the Ottomans (Turks) started their mission in Algeria. To maintain a powerful control over the whole population, they divided the country into different tribes, and each tribe had the freedom to maintain its existing linguistic practices, open to multiple ethnic groups and languages. Herein one can confirm Benrabah's (2013) assumption that the Ottoman rule gave rise to multilingualism in Algeria, in the sense that the rulers fostered a linguistic policy in

favour of multilingualism and diversity. Many languages and language varieties including colloquial Arabic were consequently the outcomes of the Turkish tribal division. For example, Algerian Arabic (AA) emerged as a consequence of this linguistic diversity (Benrabah, 2005, 2013, Belmihoub, 2012). Despite the linguistic diversity among the Ottomans, it could be noticed that the Ottomans' linguistic contributions were temporary as such and less evident today, compared to Arabic, French and some Berber varieties that can be considered as the backbone of contemporary Algerian verbal repertoires.

1.2.3 French Colonialism

Starting from 1830, Algerian history witnessed the most dominant epoch, “the French colonisation” (1830-1962). The French colonisation did not seem to be limited to exploiting Algeria's natural resources but also to imposing different policies. By so doing, it was meant to make Algeria administratively an integral part of French land “L'Algérie française” (Ball and Marley, 2017). In line with this, Maamri (2009, p.77) said:

When France colonised Algeria in 1830, it was not merely economic exploitation or political domination it sought, but a comprehensive annexation that aimed at eliminating its culture. The French controlled education, government, business, and most intellectual life for one hundred and thirty-two years

The French colony triggered profound linguistic impacts. Albeit within a relatively short period of time, it achieved a completely fragmented society (Benrabah, 2013). For Benrabah (2013, p.24), “the influence was so deep that Algerian society was never the same again”. While the Arab settlement seemed to widely colour the Algerian society with their Islamisation and Arabisation policies, the French colonialism - by all means - tried to annihilate indigenous languages in a deep way that influenced Algerian society more widely. That could be translated as a climax of change from a peaceful linguistic influence to a suppressive and subjugating regime.

1.2.3.1 Major Sources of Linguistic Expansion

1.2.3.1.1 *Frenchification: A Complete Policy of Cultural and Linguistic Transformation*

With the implementation of strict French policies especially assimilation, the Algerian linguistic profile was affected. Assimilation policies entailed the conversion of the whole society into a French one through imposing the exclusive use of FL in different domains such as education, administration, economy, business and even public life (Benrabah, 2005, 2007a, 2007b, Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008, Suleiman, 2013). For the colonisers, colonialism was perceived as a civilising mission, with the aim of freeing Algeria from its cultural backwardness (Benrabah, 2005, 2007b, 2007a, 2013, Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008).

As a basic component, the French specifically designed the educational system to deliberately create the so called "new men". Education was only allowed in French schools, while closing all the Quranic ones. The latter was meant to reinforce more contact with and exposure to FL use, and therefore establish more French dominance. In the first 50 years of French rule, French was given the status of a national language *per se*, while Arabic was designated a foreign language in 1938 (Rezig, 2011). With regards to the educational opportunities, the French authorities established a few schools, designed merely for the Algerians in 1885. However, Berber/Kabylian were more educationally privileged than the Arabs for some reasons that literature did not explicitly explain (Benrabah, 2005). Meanwhile, some political leaders over the period organised some Islamic associations that encouraged the maintenance of Arabic use among the Algerians (Benrabah, 2005). In a word, the French policies, mainly acculturation and assimilation, seemingly tried to eradicate local languages that were mainly AA and Berber at that time.

1.2.3.1.2 Contact with '*Les Pieds-Noirs*'

Among the most important strategies to boost the linguistic subjugation and spread of FL during the French colonial era was the Algerians' contact with "*Les pieds-noirs*". According to Arfi (2008), "*Les pieds-noirs*", or sometimes called Colons, are European groups, mainly French, Italians, Portuguese, Spanish and Swiss, brought by France at that time to expand its influence and power over the Algerian community. These European settlers were more based

in coastal Mediterranean strips, especially in the west of Algeria. Interestingly, there was social interaction between those settlers and the Algerians. Hence, the Algerians' settlements beside the French-speaking regions resulted in reinforcing FL use (Benrabah, 2007b, 2013). Benrabah (2013) further considered contact with *Les pieds-noirs* as the major tool to subjugate linguistically and culturally the colonised Algerians. From anecdotal evidence, there is more French use in cities that were populated by the French Colons, than those that were not settled by the aforementioned European groups, namely middle and Saharan cities.

1.2.4 The Linguistic Situation from the Eve of the Post-Colonial Era Onwards

1.2.4.1 Arabisation: A Regime for Linguistic Reconstruction

By the time Algeria was liberated from the brutal French imperialism in 1962, the Algerian linguistic and cultural identity has been described in literature as "forced", in as much as it was highly influenced by French colonialism. In other words, it was not regained immediately upon decolonisation; French policies were still in action and the language situation remained unsteady (Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008, Maamri, 2009, Suleiman, 2013).

In order to restore the cultural identity, Arabisation policy was among the first implementations in various Algerian domains with the aim of eradicating other languages such as AA/Berber and the colonial language "French" (Belmihoub, 2012, Benrabah, 2013, Ball and Marley, 2017). Classical Arabic whose modern version is "Modern Standard Arabic" was the language that pro-Arabisation people aimed at implementing at different levels. For them, the Algerian true identity could be regained only through the lens of Arabisation. In this vein, Maamri (2009, p.82) stated that "The Algerian society whose true identity had been denied for a hundred and thirty years could therefore not begin to reconstruct itself without restoring the bedrock of that identity: the Arabic language". At the sociolinguistic level, the period following the independence witnessed some sociolinguistic conflicts among policy makers, taking the issue of Arabisation and the status of FL as the core of debate (Benrabah, 2013). Consequently, a sociolinguistic division was made among the Algerian community; Arabophones; proponents of Arabic as the official language and Francophones; advocates of Arabic/French bilingualism (Maamri, 2009).

At the beginning of the post-colonial era, Standard Arabic was declared as the official language of the country, while French was seen as the language of the coloniser (Benrabah, 2013). So, Arabisation started to be more ambitiously applied after independence. One way to illustrate this is the decision of stakeholders to limit education in the elementary education solely to Arabic in 1964 (Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008). However, dialectal Arabic speakers and Berbers opposed the early regime of Arabisation as their languages were excluded (Mouhleub, 2005). Nevertheless, the chief aim of Arabisation was more to eliminate the role of French from public life, to reflect the Arab-Islamic identity, and to create a sense of belonging to the Arab World (Grandguillaume, 2004, Belmihoub, 2012, Benrabah, 2013).

As time went by, Arabisation was more strictly applied. Henceforth, it was fully implemented in schools in 1980, and started to pervade one domain after the other up until 1990 (Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008). The regime of intensive Arabisation, however, was rejected by one of the Ministers of Education at that time who preferred the idea of gradualism; the gradual implementation of Arabic-French bilingualism (Benrabah, 2013). The purpose behind pursuing Arabic-French bilingualism was perhaps to preserve the language of the culture "Arabic", and, at the same time, to maintain the language of technology - "French" at that time.

In the 1990's, Arabisation was deeply implemented in different university domains, such as social science and humanities. Notwithstanding, opportunities of jobs related to scientific disciplines were only given to the elite who studied exclusively in French (Benrabah, 2013). Students' inclination towards such a language is fully understandable since the issue is related to a more serious socio-economic necessity, which is employment. The valuable role of French in accessing job opportunities in the modern world was also acknowledged by Aitsiselmi and Marley (2008). Actually, the Algerian economic system was heavily dependent on the French economic system and administrators. The Algerian economic sector in independent Algeria had to maintain its integration with the French one.

The receding of Arabisation as an exclusive policy started in 1999. The Algerian president Abdelaziz Bouteflika explicitly expressed the failure of Arabisation which was, for him, the wrong approach towards modernity. Instead, he encouraged multilingualism and diversity, and supported French LM in particular. He publically announced that it is irrational to learn

nine years through Arabic as a language of instruction when it is not the language of technology and science (Benrabah, 2013). Regarding his attitudes towards FL, the president, in 1999, stipulated that “Algeria doesn’t belong to Francophonie but there is no reason for us to have a frozen attitude towards the French language which taught us so many things and which, at any rate, opened [for us] the window of French culture” (Cherrad-Bencheфра and Derradji, 2004, cited in Kaplan and Baldauf, 2007, p.10).

So, it could be deduced that this is the turning point from a hard-line policy towards multilingualism. Since then, FL maintained a strong presence (See Chapter Two for a detailed analysis of current status, attitudes and use).

It is enlightening to draw a conclusion about Arabisation in Algeria. According to many sociolinguists, Arabisation was doomed to failure (Grandguillaume, 2004, Mostari, 2004, Benrabah, 2007b, Belmihoub, 2012). Benrabah (2007a, p.3) further declared “Arabisation or the language policy implemented to displace French altogether, failed. From a quantitative point of view, today’s Algeria is the second largest French-Speaking community in the world”. According to Aitsiselmi and Marley (2008), Benrabah (2014) and Belmihoub (2015), the failure of Arabisation could be related to the facts that:

- Discarding FL was not easy owing to the advantages associated with it: French was positively perceived as a modern language, in the sense of giving access to a wide range of opportunities in the modern world.
- The policy makers’ decisions were not utterly based on pedagogical concerns, but rather politically driven.
- The policy was based on exclusion, rather than inclusion; which implies decreasing the opportunities for Algerians to become multilinguals (Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008, Belmihoub, 2015).

According to this chronological review, Algerian linguistic and national identity seemed to be threatened by continuing sources of contention: past imperials, especially French. One may further observe that LM/LS practices were happening ever since the existence of Berber (the indigenous people) and earlier empires.

1.2.5 The Linguistic Situation in a Globalised Context

What is noteworthy in the linguistic landscape of Algeria is the resilience of the FL throughout history. With the weakening of Arabisation, FL maintained its vibrant status (Benrabah, 2007b). Despite all efforts to establish Standard Arabic as the main tool to communicate formally and informally, French is still powerful and prevalent. The Arabisation policy also aimed at substituting French with English (Benrabah, 2007b, Benrabah, 2013, 2014) (See details in Chapter Two).

In the current linguistic situation, there is an increasing awareness to develop the status of English as a step to become part of the globalised context (Belmihoub, 2012, 2015, 2017, 2018a, Benrabah, 2014). Chapter 2 explains the rapid diffusion of English in different sectors including its use among Algerian adults. One of the attempts towards developing the status of English in Algeria is the development of mobility and exchange programmes with Anglophone countries (Belmihoub, 2012, 2015, 2018a, British Council, 2014, Chellia, 2018). The Multi-million Pound Scholarship Programme - related to the sample population of this research project - is a recent programme that was devised to build cultural bridges with the UK and improve EL status (British Council, 2014, Chellia, 2018). The linguistic situation in the globalised context is still based on exclusive policies, with a strong political desire to switch from French to English in different domains including higher education (Ghanmi, 2019, Teller Report, 2019).

1.3 The Research Rationale

The rationale of embarking on this research is informed by personal, theoretical as well as policy-related motives. As an insider researcher who has grown up in a multilingual context, my inclination was drawn towards researching languages in society. My first motives towards expanding issues around FL in academia had emerged from its vibrant status, especially with the introduction of English in Algeria. According to Aitsiselmi and Marley (2008), North African countries are a fertile area of sociolinguistic research due to the linguistic conflicts therein. Of a particular mention, FL status seems to - by and large - call for more research. In line with this, the writers alluded:

The role and status of French in North Africa has evolved in a way not foreseen by the language planners of the newly independent states some fifty years ago, and its continuing role as a prestige language means that there are still several interesting areas of research to pursue

(Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008, pp.2018–2019)

The confluence of different linguistic resources in Algeria, in both post-colonial and globalised times, has led to the rise of additive and subtractive ideologists (Benrabah, 2007b, Belmihoub, 2012) (See Chapter 2: Section 2.5 for definitions of additive/subtractive multilingualism). The multilingual situation served as a linguistic conflict, more than a linguistic gain because of the subtractive policies that the planners and policy makers have delivered (Benrabah, 2014), and are still delivering. In the light of the subtractive tension, it could be an even more complex situation where English is perceived as competing with French.

I placed the focus on Algerian EFL students as an important type of people, where I could problematize the use of English and French linguistic resources. Unlike other patterns of the Algerian population, this type of persons has a more abundant use of English in their repertoires because of the academic focus they have in their higher education, and therefore it is a more appropriate sample to study FL/EL linguistic conflicts.

With the academic mobility these students are involved in, I was drawn to better understand how the FL of this community of interest would survive as Algeria is increasingly engaging with globalisation and diversifying its international partners. I started further problematizing the effects of short-term mobility on FL (a language which is usually perceived as a second language) and questioning how this type of mobility including students with an academic focus would affect their use of French and how this could inform policy debates. Algerian students in France, for example, may receive less mobility effect on their code choice. At the opposite extreme, in my research, the new destination is an Anglophone country (UK) where French could find significant competition with English. What could leave room for more debate is that these people are “knowledge-seekers”, with a highly intellectual profile and academic focus, a significant factor that would definitely affect the way they view and use community languages in general and FL in particular. So, this research addresses a cohort who can be open and receptive to new ideas, perhaps more than other mobility groups. They could be in turn more informative on future Algerian policy debate.

In terms of theoretical framework, LM and LS were chosen to offer new understandings in the field through investigating their applicability within short-term mobility, and therefore broaden their scope. This application certainly triggers some challenges that I will detail (see Chapter Three; section 3.3.4). This study addresses temporary mobile students as a category in the new mobility processes. One of the reasons for focusing on this type of mobility is that the world is facing a sharp increase in different types of mobilities including short-term mobility and so this is an interesting type of heightened mobility to address. It is high time, one may say, to expand different concepts and adjust them to different mobility patterns. Instead of discarding traditional concepts related to migration and associate them only with traditional perspectives, it would be of interest to start relabelling them in an attempt to make them well-suited to different mobility patterns. This study then will apply LM/LS in a way which matches a context of short-term mobility.

So, the focus of this study is the use of FL at an informal level, among Algerian ethno-specific friendship groups in UK institutions. I used Pauwels's (2005) call for further research as a supportive point which emphasises the need for researching the maintenance of community languages among adolescents in friendship domains:

I believe that there is an urgent need to undertake more research on CL use in adolescence. This research should be ethnographic and focus specifically on adolescent friendship groups and networks to discover their language practices and the impact this may have on CL maintenance

(Pauwels, 2005, p.129)

Therefore, this research is designed to analyse the new linguistic repertoires of Algerian transnational students within globalised communication practices to investigate French LM/LS to English, and to see how, in what ways and to what extent their pre-mobility experience with FL is affected by the transnational mobility or not.

There is also a policy rationale behind this research (related to the country of origin) as an important context that Algerian students will function in, after their study abroad experience. Regarding English and French, there seems a deliberate policy to encourage LS in the Algerian society, more than LM, with structural-functional views being predominant. In other words, language policy in Algeria is wedded to an LM/LS subtractive multilingualism - French out; English in. By ways of illustration, the Algerian Minister of Higher Education and Scientific

Research, Tayeb Bouzid, recently declared his strong tendency to reinforce the status of English at the expense of that of French in higher education: “The French language does not get us anywhere”, quoted in (Ghanmi, 2019, n.p). Ghanmi (2019) further made a point that the Minister had decreed the use of English, instead of French, at the level of Algerian universities and higher education institutes. However, subtractive policies are viewed by others as the wrong approach for Sociolinguistic Peace in Algeria (Benrabah, 2007b) (See definition in Chapter 2: Section 2.6). Concerning English, for example, Belmihoub (2012, p.225) explained that “its growth does not have to be mutually exclusive with that of French”.

According to Belmihoub (2018b), language planning in Algeria recently appeared to shift from a hard-line policy towards a more softened one. Tamazight has been given an *official* status equal to Standard Arabic, and this can be seen as an initiative in favour of additive multilingualism. Therefore, this study is founded on acceptance of this theory by reinforcing its implementation with regards to the status/use of FL/EL in Algeria. The study then sets out to investigate French LM/LS to English within a range of different linguistic resources, rather than isolation, and therefore, encouraging the incorporation of new perspectives in Algerian future policy debates, based on fluidity, flexibility and dynamism, rather than exclusion and determinism.

1.4 Significance of the Study

The study’s significance lies in the fact that this is an area of a current interest (As explained in **Section 1.1.1**). Within LM/LS scholarly literature, some research around language attitudes, LM/LS among Arab communities in the UK was recently undertaken: namely in Jamaï (2008) (on Moroccan community in the UK), Othman (2011) (on Arab communities in Manchester), and Bichani (2015) (on two Arab speaking communities in the UK). Despite that, studies that focus exclusively on LM/LS among Algerian communities in the UK do not yet feature. Therefore, this thesis, although conducted in a different context, short-term mobility, is the first to inquire into these two key concepts among an Algerian ethnolinguistic community in the UK.

This research is emblematic and illustrative of the new kind of globalisation because it addresses the study of linguistic practices within a specific type of mobility - short-term movement. Far from the traditional scope of migration, it explores the linguistic practices of

a specific “transnational population”, identified by its transition to the UK in the light of internationalisation of higher education, mobility and exchange programmes. The study then provides new insights to approach a specific type of mobility pattern: newly-arrived communities especially in an era where globalised communication practices play a significant role in LM/LS (Pauwels, 2016). As a matter of international perspectives, whilst there are critiques of the economic and political drivers of globalisation, some of its characteristics, such as increased interconnection and communication are indisputable. As a consequence, I believe that research updates in LM/LS are worthwhile. Therefore, this is an interesting case of wider trends that are important to understand (LM/LS within globalised context).

The study is also a step to generate new understandings around the concepts of LM/LS, from their traditional application on long-term migration and settlement contexts, to a specific application. It is therefore meant to shed light on a context that is characterised by a (very short-term) mobility rather than migration, with an almost guaranteed return to the country of origin. Consequently, it addresses potential, non-canonical, new forms of LM/LS. The thesis also focusses on a colonial language, usually perceived as a second language among the Algerian new generations and used as an embedded code within AA speech practices. Moreover, LM/LS in this project is based on a translanguaging approach to study language use for the purpose of promoting the additive multilingual orientation in Algeria (see details in Chapter Three).

Another way in which this research departs from the wider literature is that previous LM/LS studies drew data more from reported language use. This thesis incorporated two types of data: perceived language use and a direct observation of actual behaviours. It is thereby, a step to go deeply into the study of LM/LS, not only based on reported attitudes but also actual behaviours. By so doing, the thesis will not only make an attempt to provide more fine-grained analysis through employing comparative data, but also strengthen the case for diversified research methods to understand different language practices.

In terms of policy, it is of importance to look at this special mobility group due to the role they play in Algeria’s EL development in the future. Martin Daltry, the director of British Council in Algeria, in stating the ambitions of the Multi-million Pound Programme, expected:

(...) We are also keen to develop new relationships and partnerships linking British and Algerian universities to strengthen English language teaching, learning and research here. I believe this initiative over the next decade has great potential to develop English skills in Algeria and greater mutual knowledge and understanding between our two countries more broadly (...)

(British Council, 2014, n.p)

This study is then important in terms of Algerian education, culture and international trade policies. From the sociolinguistic aspect, there is little published articulation of the policy rationale behind the Multi-million Pound Scholarship Programme. My research helps to articulate this in the sense that the outcomes of this research are addressed to the Algerian policy makers in their development of language policy and planning. It is then hoped that the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research considers lessons from this study (regarding both attitudes and use of FL/EL in their daily practices), especially from this professional group with an international experience, to inform future policies.

CHAPTER TWO: FRENCH LANGUAGE DIFFUSION IN THE CURRENT ALGERIAN SOCIOLINGUISTIC PROFILE

Due to different factors such as colonialism and related policies, many languages are eventually the outcome, enriching Algerian society and representing its linguistic nationalism, culture and identity. Among all resources, FL was noticeably maintained.

The purpose of this chapter is to discuss - at length - the current status of French in Algeria. It also highlights the dimensions and various uses of this language in different domains and among various speakers, including students in higher education. Subsequently, the chapter documents the linguistic challenges regarding this colonial language, especially in a globalised context, explaining how the conflicts between two western languages (English and French) added more complexity to the Algerian speech community. Within this chapter, I will add how Peace Sociolinguistics is proposed in Algerian speech communities in the light of additive/subtractive tensions. Before that, the chapter retraces briefly the languages that make up the contemporary profile of Algeria to help situate FL status. One of the reasons in providing a detailed description of the Algerian linguistic profile is that it is important for the context of this study to describe the pre- and post- study linguistic landscapes that the participants were/will function in.

2.1 Languages and Recent Linguistic Reforms

Linguistic pluralism coloured the Algerian landscape with different languages: Modern Standard Arabic (MSA), Tamazight, French, AA and its varieties, Berber varieties and recently English (Chemami, 2011, Belmihoub, 2012, Berabah, 2013, Worldatlas, 2019)

Modern Standard Arabic (MSA) and Tamazight are two official languages in Algeria (Worldatlas, 2019). MSA is the modern version of Classical Arabic (Quranic), with the interventions of "some foreign words that may fulfil the needs of the contemporary world" (Kadem, 2015, p.36). MSA is the official language of the country (Belmihoub, 2018b), as clearly stipulated in Article 3 of Constitution (1996) "the Arabic language is the national and official language" (Mouhleb, 2005, p.11). In addition to being the language of religion, it is also the language of instruction throughout different educational phases (primary, middle and

secondary phases), as well as some domains in higher education such as art, literature and humanities and the language of law and media (Mostari, 2004, Chemami, 2011). MSA is more considered as a written language than a spoken one (Benrabah, 2005).

Dialectal Arabic (Algerian Arabic/ AA) and Berber varieties are daily-spoken varieties and mother tongues of Algerian communities. They have been considered as two mediums of informal interaction in Algeria (L/"low" languages). Benrabah (2014) highlighted two types of dialectal Arabic: AA speech communities in the North of Algeria and AA speech communities in the South (Saharan desert). In a similar fashion, Berbers vary in their spoken language. According to Aitsiselmi and Marley (2008), those dialects are the languages used in everyday conversations, and have no written forms. Benrabah (2014) interestingly made a recent classification of Berber-speaking communities (micro-ethnicities) and their varieties (at least the live ones):

<i>Berber ethnic groups</i>	<i>Berber spoken varieties</i>
<i>Kabyles</i>	<i>Kabyle or Takbaylit</i>
<i>Shawia</i>	<i>Shawia/ Chaoui</i>
<i>Tuaregs</i>	<i>Tamashek</i>
<i>Mozabites</i>	<i>Mzab</i>
<i>Chenoua</i>	<i>Chenoua</i>

Table 3. 1: Berber ethnic groups (micro-ethnicities) and spoken varieties in Algeria according to Benrabah (2014, p.45)

Among all of the mentioned Berber ethnic groups, Kabyles represent two-thirds of the whole Berber population in Algeria (Benrabah, 2004, Mouhleab, 2005, Benrabah, 2014). Occupying a large proportion of the whole Berber population would help explain Kabyles' active involvement and resistance to the central authorities for their linguistic rights, culture and identity throughout history.

Recently, policy debates in Algeria seem to have started moving towards more openness to diversity. A poignant example of this is making Tamazight an *official* language instead of a merely national language (Belmihoub, 2018b). In March, 2016, Berber/Tamazight was officially declared as a national and official language (BBC News, 2016). Furthermore, the

Minister of National Education Nouria Benghabrit-Remaoun sanctioned the use of Dialectal Arabic in education as a medium for young pupils to facilitate learning Standard Arabic (Temlali, 2016).

2.2 French Language Profile

2.2.1 Status and Function

Despite whatever reforms have been introduced to minimise the role of FL in Algeria, they seem no avail, in that it is almost impossible to detach it from Algerian society. Regarding that, Maamri (2009, p.88) argued:

The colonial heritage has left an even deeper wound on Algeria. French culture provoked a sort of paralysis in Algeria. It has so blanked out the natives' lives that to this day, despite massive and intensive efforts at *Arabising*, the Algerian population continues to be affected by the French linguistic impact

Across the existing literature, French in Algeria is considered as a *lingua franca*, either a second language or a foreign language (Hassaine, 2011), the native language for some people (Battye, Hintze and Rowlett, 2003), and has a competitive status with MSA (Mouhleb, 2005, Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008). French for Benrabah (2007a, p.203) is "usually acquired as a second language", a common status between all Algerians. To illustrate the wide range statuses of FL in Algeria, Battye, Hintze and Rowlett, (2003, pp.1–2), speaking about North African French users as part of "La Francophonie" world, maintained:

(...) as in north Africa for instance, French may be a language with a special status, widely used by intellectuals or educated elites for academic or cultural purposes. As for individuals, they may be mother-tongue speakers, having acquired the language in childhood, and French may be their usual or vernacular language. Others may speak French as a second language, having acquired it through education generally, and/or have been taught, wholly or in part through the medium of French (...)

At the formal level, it is used in sciences, international relations, commerce and media (Mouhleb, 2005, Benrabah, 2007b, 2013). Also, it is represented as the language of power and technology (Benrabah, 2007b, 2013, 2014). Alongside MSA, it is used in producing governmental documents (Benrabah, 2005, 2013). Its use is additionally viewed as a sign of prestige, gaining respectability and a gateway to joining the modern world. At this level, Aitsiselmi and Marley (2008, p.202) explained "French is simply a synonym for modernity for

many *Maghrebians*, and speaking French is a means of improving one's social standing". French is used at both informal and formal contexts as a prestigious language. It tends to retain a strong presence that it is used – alongside standard Arabic – in naming streets, roads, cafes, towns and other venues such as hospitals (Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008).

In education, French occupies a prominent role. Recent reforms introduced by the planners in the Algerian curriculum allocated French as the first mandatory foreign language which is taught in the third year of the elementary education from 2006 onward (Benrabah, 2013). In Algerian secondary schools, students/pupils who opted for options like mathematics, science and technology could benefit from extra FL classes to prepare them for higher education, where French is the language of instruction (Benrabah, 2007b). In the contemporary time, courses in the departments of IT, biology, chemistry, medicine, pharmacy, technology and mathematics are mostly taught in French. This could be a stumbling block for some students whose FL proficiency was low before, and those may not be motivated enough to learn through a foreign language.

With the advent of the cyberspace era, the internet has slowed down the displacement of FL in the sense of giving greater incentives and materials to increase fluency in this language (Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008, Belmihoub, 2017). From anecdotal evidence, as a user of many social media platforms, I notice that many Algerian Facebookers master the use of FL and use it in their daily life posts, as well as in private conversations, and that it is almost impossible to receive texts without FL being used alongside AA. French has also a vital status in digital media tools like mobile phones (Mostari, 2009).

Regarding the administration sector, French was the dominant language during the colonial era. In post-colonial Algeria, its use in the administrative field has been diminished. In current times, the majority of the Algerian Ministries, such as the Ministry of Justice and Religious Affairs are almost de-frenchified (Benrabah, 2014). The administration sector is bilingual (Arabic-French) so far. In municipal affairs, official documents such as bills for utilities and taxes are issued in both languages (Arabic, French) as well as postage stamps and bank notes. In the domain of health, pharmaceutical names and medicines are bilingual, while medical prescriptions are written in French since medical students are taught in French during their tertiary education (Ali Chaouche, 2006).

By ways of illustration, recently issued Algerian identity cards (by 2015) include a bilingual use of Arabic and French. Passport documents - within the same year - are trilingual, with the inclusion of Arabic, French and English. Surprisingly enough, registration cards in the Algerian Consulate in London (UK), despite them being issued in an Anglophone country, follow a bilingual use of language (Arabic-French).

Indeed, there are countless examples that illustrate the status given to French in different Algerian contexts, among different Algerians of different socio-economic profiles. Kadem (2015, p.37) best summarised this view regarding the status of French and the policy planners' attitudes to this situation:

The widespread use of French in different domains such as education administration press and the mass media and family reveals that this language is deeply implanted both as formal and informal levels, and remains a significantly important language in Algeria, in spite of the official marginalisation and the concentrated efforts made by the government to get rid of it

2.2.2 Attitudes and Usage among Algerian Speakers

Algerians have been through "a reversal in attitudes" towards French, from those associated with bitterness, usually among old generations, towards more openness. In other words, while elders feel resentful and have bitter memories regarding FL, these attitudes seem to fade away among newer generations (Benrabah, 2007b, Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008, Kerma, 2018). In the present time, perceived views towards FL revealed that some Algerians are still confused as to whether it is a mere foreign language or part of their identity (Hassaine, 2011). Ali Chaouche (2006, p.38) expressed: "In reality, we know that French is a part of the Algerian patrimony and it allows the opening of the world".

Although French use in Algeria is appreciated and deeply rooted, according to Ali Chaouche (2006) the policy-makers' endeavours to detach it from the Algerian speech community could carry another feeling that its status is muddled. The Algerians' ambivalence towards French in which this language is part of their national identity, a language of the coloniser and the language of technology and prestige, might be resembled to the case of Danish nationals. Danish people seem to have a mixture of feelings towards the German language: either

considering it as one with enemy associations that threatens their national identity due to past colonisation, or tending to valorise it (Thaler, 2009).

2.2.2.1 Among General Population

French is even omnipresent among ordinary speech communities, including the illiterate population in Algeria. People who live in urban areas are known for their intensive use of French (Mahdad, 2014). It could be assumed that people in urban areas are keener on being prestigious than those in rural ones, which is why they could tend more to use French. There is plenty of evidence about lexical borrowing in their linguistic practices such as “ménage-household” and “stylo-pen” (Mahdad, 2014). French seems to invade different Algerian contexts, regardless of the educational level of Algerian people.

Among Elites

Throughout history, Algeria became home to French-speaking elites who contributed to French LM in different formal and informal settings for many decades (Benrabah, 2007b). Contemporarily, French is mostly used by the educated elite: those with an intellectual background and a high professional profile, such as university lecturers and medical practitioners (Hassaine, 2011).

Kerma (2018) mentioned one of the elite categories: Algerian AA-French bilinguals. This category, for him, usually received education in French or English. These type of people “view Arabic French bilingualism as a sign of openness and a source of enrichment” (Kerma, 2018, p.138). Occasionally, some of the Algerian educated elites are said to be French native-like in that they became so ‘*Frenchified*’ (Hassaine, 2011). The purpose in bringing together these observations is to show that FL has a more significant status among Algerian elites, being either used alone, or beside other linguistic resources such as Arabic and Berber dialects. In this vein, one can think that French use in Algerian speech communities is more associated with social status. University students are then thought to valorise FL and its use because of likely high social status, to which they may aspire.

2.2.2.3 Among Algerian Students: Attitudes and Use

This section reflects on some findings from FL attitudes and use among Algerian students. It further casts some light on the use of this language among EFL students for reasons of research contextualisation. Benrabah, in 2004, studied language use and attitudes among 1,051 Algerian teenagers in secondary schools. He found that the majority of them did not consider French as a “foreign language”, nor associated it with a painful past (colonialism). They rather considered it as part of Algeria’s history and heritage (Benrabah, 2007b). This could confirm the reversal in views among the newer generations against the old ones.

French seems to find a convenient scope of use among university students. Students of FL would understandably prefer the use of French more than others across different fields (Yahi, 2015). This might be linked to their actual learning careers. A recent study by Yahi (2015) on code-switching among Arab students studying French revealed that 60 % of them prefer to speak both AA and French (according to their perceptions) (Yahi, 2015). Students studying English, on the other extreme, had a perceived multilingual profile, where the use of French did not seem to be affected by English (Kadem, 2015). This example of the wide range of use is significant for this project as it focuses on LM/LS within a range of different linguistic resources, rather than in isolation.

According to students’ reported behaviours discussed in Kadem (2015), French is used in different domains by EFL students (Algerian EL students) including classrooms, which is a formal context. Despite EL use, French is the predominant unmarked (embedded) variety alongside AA, and thereby, AA-French is the predominant code-switching pattern adopted by EFL students.

Although the aforementioned findings can provide insights for this project, they could be viewed as less representative of the whole Algerian students’ speech community. Not only because of the small-scale samples, but mostly because the sample of each of these studies belongs to a particular area of the country (mostly the West of Algeria).

2.3 Complex Verbal Repertoires

In Algeria, socio-historical factors have led to the emergence of a complex linguistic make-up, with the deployment of different linguistic phenomena, such as code-switching, code-mixing, bilingualism, multilingualism and diglossia (Mouhleb, 2005, Bagui, 2014). Regarding this point, Mahdad (2014, p.12) described:

The Algerian linguistic situation is known by its complexity: it is diglossic, characterized by the use of Algerian Arabic and MSA; bilingual by the use of Arabic and French; and even multilingual by the use of Arabic, French and Berber though this latter language is restricted to just a few areas in the country

The use of different language varieties depends on different factors related to individuals' professional status, geographical location and social environment (Mouhleb, 2005). More than anything else, Algeria's current complex linguistic conflicts are related to FL and its status (Benrabah, 2013). Maamri (2009, p.88) similarly supported this view: " (...) that this influence has continued after independence may explain the complex nature of the changes and readjustments that Algeria has been undergoing". Consequently, FL use in individuals' day-to-day communication triggers different speech behaviours and sociolinguistic phenomenon. For instance, both ethnic groups, Arabophones and Berberophones, tend to switch from Arabic/Berber to French in their daily interactions. The field of music is also full of code-switching (Mouhleb, 2005). Text messaging through different devices of mobile technology plays an important role in the way the Algerian people communicate and elucidates more AA-French code-switching (Mostari, 2009).

2.4 From French to English: A Call for Language Shift

The current status of EL in Algeria is a second foreign language after French (Benrabah, 2005, 2013, 2014). In 1993, English had been given a chance to get the status of a "first foreign language". Pupils/parents, in their fourth level of the primary school, could choose either of the two foreign languages: French or English as the first to be taught. In practice, most parents preferred French to English. Currently, English is taught as a second foreign language in the first year of the middle school (Benrabah, 2007a, 2007b, 2013, 2014, Mostari, 2009, (Belmihoub, 2018a).

With the advent of globalisation and the boost of science and technology, English seems to ambitiously accelerate its competitive journey to supersede French. The competitive status of French and English seems to constitute a large part of the linguistic conflict in Algeria. Concerning this conflict, Aitsiselmi and Marley (2008, p.219) contemplated: “While French has held its own despite Arabisation, there are growing indications that the next generations may find English a more useful language”. The high status of French among Algerian future generations, thereby, is subject to doubt as English is a real competitor, and Algerians’ awareness about English’s global value seems to be increasing.

English is thriving in different domains such as higher education, commerce, international business, tourism, journalism, scientific research, cyberspace and even in the daily life use of the Algerian society (Kadem, 2015, Belmihoub, 2018a). What is more, some Algerian adults tend to acknowledge the vitality of English through their engagement in listening to English music and watching English movies broadcast on some TV channels like MBC action, MBC 2 and MBC 4. Consequently, English words have started to establish their presence within the Algerians’ verbal repertoires (Kadem, 2015).

Hassaine (2011) questioned university students matriculated in medical science about language issues in Algeria. As concerns language choice and attitude, findings clearly indicated the students’ tendency towards English and their acknowledgment of its value. In this respect, the majority of students related their inclination towards English to the extent that it is an international language (Hassaine, 2011). Although they are medical students - where French is still the language of instruction up to the present time - they showed their inclination towards English as an international language. It could be reasonably inferred that this preference is related to their desire to join the global world. For example, some people prefer online shopping which makes them prefer EL. Also, there are some international brands whose instructions are expressed in English. Thereby, such a language is, for them, a window towards a modern life. In the same vein, Benrabah’s recent study (2014) showed that there is a dramatic increase in the awareness of the Algerian population about the value of some languages worldwide in general and a gradual inclination towards English among Algerian Master’s (MA) students in particular. He questioned 204 Algerian students who were matriculated in three varied language departments (Arabic, French and English), with a special focus on their perspectives towards the language of the most global value among 10 other

languages. According to the results, 188/204 students opted for “English”. Algerian English students (65 ones) represented the largest sample who considered the global value of English, followed by French and Arabic students respectively (Benrabah, 2014). So, English is progressively magnetising Algerian adults’ minds. However, Algerian students’ awareness of the international status of English does not reflect their real EL proficiency, and Algerian English-speaking proficiency is among the lowest among Arab countries (Benrabah, 2014).

What seems paramount to mention is that French often gives the impression that it is abhorrently preserved (especially by the elderly people). English - on the other end of the spectrum - does not suffer from the same “baggage” among Algerians across generations. This could be a good boost for the power of English in the future of Algeria. In terms of social use, although French does not seem to be affected due to its deep rootedness, it is predicted that it would lose ground to English in the future. Belmihoub (2012, p.7) made a point:

In fact, from a quantitative point of view, Algeria is home to the largest number of French speakers in the world, only after France. English, considered as the second foreign language after French, is not widely spoken in Algeria today, despite recent growing interest in it. It is however the most likely to replace French as the latter language is in an insecure position, partly because of government efforts to drop it in favour of English

Recent policy debates consist of a stronger call for LS, encouraging the full switch from French to English. Ghanmi (2019), on the basis of voices coming from Algerian stakeholders and policy makers, ministers and political writers, detailed the proposal to reinforce the status of English as a main foreign language at the expense of French for a better visibility in the global world. According to Al-Fanar Media (2019), French presence in Algeria is being challenged in the light of new global developments. In this respect, it was argued that “French is no longer a language of science (...) its global role is smaller than it was, and the international job market now requires English rather than French” (Al-Fanar Media, 2019, n.p).

While LS to English would assist Algeria’s cultural independence and open more opportunities at the global level, “Replacing French with the English language is taking the risk of severing Algeria’s ties from its environment and isolating it”, it was critically predicted by Makhoulouf Mehenni, a political writer (Ghanmi, 2019, n.p).

This view elucidates the competitive statuses of the two languages in Algeria, a situation that - one may reflect - was created by the state. In the coming section, there is a further explanation of how the two western languages are reflected in the Algerian speech community and policy debates.

2.5 Additive and Subtractive Multilingualism

Although English has gained ground in the Algerian linguistic landscape, it would not entirely and easily supplant French, mainly because of the multilingual orientation of the Algerian population. A few years ago, Benrabah's study (2007a) on Algerian high school students revealed that the majority preferred additive multilingualism (Belmihoub, 2012). Benrabah (2007a), within the same study, found out that the majority of students did not prefer the replacement of French with English in Algeria and the use of English as a language of instruction in scientific subjects. Language attitudes among Algerian engineering students in Algeria also revealed a multilingual orientation (Belmihoub, 2018b). All languages were considered as equally important by these students through their additive views towards multilingualism. Additive multilingualism is defined as the confluence of different linguistic resources and interaction between them based on equality (Benrabah, 2013). In another study among Algerian university students (2014), he found out that the majority of students did not consider French and English as rivals, meaning using English need not entail excluding the use of French (Benrabah, 2014). As a reaction to the recent call for switching from French to English in higher education, a medical student stated his opposition to the exclusive policy which urges the entire shift to English: "I myself am not ready to continue my medical studies in English. I may rely on English for research, or to improve my educational performance and future career status, but to change everything to English would be difficult, if not impossible" (Al-Fanar Media, 2019, n.p).

So, in Algeria's linguistic context, additive multilingualism is a linguistic ideology which fosters diversity of languages, without being hostile to any. However, the authorities made some linguistic resources insecure in position because of their exclusion policies (for example, English versus French; Tamazight versus Arabic (Belmihoub, 2012, 2015). The authorities' linguistic ideology towards the status of French and English is based on subtractive multilingualism, which implies "one language taking the place of other languages" (Benrabah,

2013, p.97). Belmihoub (2012) forecast that French status will be dropped in the future, just because of the government's exclusive ideology regarding these two languages. Speaking about English, he said that "It is however the most likely to replace French as the latter language is in an insecure position, partly because of government efforts to drop it in favour of English" (Belmihoub, 2012, p.7).

2.6 Peace Sociolinguistics in Algeria

According to Belmihoub (2018b), the hostile attitudes towards additive multilingualism among policy makers appeared to become less rigid, however, through their recent decision to give Tamazight equal official status to that of Arabic. However, when it comes to English and French, subtractive multilingualism tends to still be the predominant ideology which does not at all embrace linguistic diversity, based on equality.

In sociolinguistics, Friedrich's concept of Peace Sociolinguistics was introduced to study the relationship between communication and peace within minority communities with linguistic struggles. As a recent concept, it is defined as "a discipline engaged in investigating the place of peace through language in society, with the main charge of looking into peace (within and among languages) (...)" (Friedrich, 2007, p.76). The main purpose of Peace Sociolinguistics is to establish linguistic harmony in situations of linguistic conflict through different steps such as considering the population's freedom of choice (Friedrich and Francisco, 2009, Benrabah, 2013, Belmihoub, 2015).

In Algeria, the planning process is viewed as one which is based on "top-down" arrangements". This implies that the decision making is entirely based on the policy makers' and planners' own ideology (subtractive) and excludes the voice of population/electorate. For Benrabah (2007, 2013, 2014), and Belmihoub (2012, 2015), the majority of Algerians have positive attitude towards additive multilingualism. Peace sociolinguistics was proposed by Benrabah (2013) and Belmihoub (2015) as a potential solution to reduce linguistic conflict, by proposing taking the attitudes of the population into the process of planning. Benrabah (2013) further emphasised the need to consider these attitudes and multilingual orientation to foster linguistic peace: " (...) a 'bottom-up' approach to language planning activities is more likely to suit the population's multilingual orientations (...)" (169).

If the linguistic situation in Algeria were looked at through the lens of the population's attitudes, the relationship between English and French languages would not be represented as a rival one, it seems. Benrabah (2013) argued that the misrepresentation of French-English competition "does not account for input from the community's language practices and attitudes" (p.98), but rather reflects that of the planners.

According to this linguistic situation, I believe that the future could lie in applying much more of a bottom-up approach to planning. No one can ignore the country's mixed and complex history and recently globalised linguistic system. All these jointly construct Algerians' multilingual inclination. Peace Sociolinguistics, the desired outcome, can be only promoted through more openness to the additive multilingual orientation.

As a critical component, one may add that structural-functionalist approaches, to some extent, inform language policy in Algeria. Structural-functional views suggest that people make macro choices about how they express themselves in a social context. According to Martin-Jones (1983), structural-functional views of language believe that language choices in social activity are guided by wider societal norms. For him, "they are seen as mere reflections of community-wide norms" (p.108). Therefore, power is dominant, instead of giving freedom to individuals, to actively contribute to definitions of the process of variation. Structural-functional views have been described as static (Martin-Jones, 1983), therefore hard to account for language change over time.

Algeria could be likened to a patchwork. The introduction of English alongside FL triggered a complexity which turned the country into a messy speech community, from a subtractive viewpoint. If the current linguistic situation is looked at from an additive multilingualism perspective, linguistic diversity would be a linguistic gain, rather than a conflict. What may add new lines of thinking to the current policy debate is speech samples and attitudes from transnational individuals who crossed borders towards Anglophone countries. In this case, mobility can be an important factor which either supports additive multilingualism or promotes subtractive multilingualism. This project further raises questions about the differing additive and subtractive models in that it provides specific data to test in the case of young internationally mobile people, through the study of French LM/LS to English during languaging practices. In the next chapter, I go on to discuss the concepts and theories that are deployed

to structure the theoretical framework of this study. Before doing that, I will provide a snapshot of Algerian mobility in globalised times and the development of mobility programmes, as a way to aid understanding the linguistic outcomes of mobility.

CHAPTER THREE: POTENTIAL SOCIOLINGUISTIC OUTCOMES OF SPATIAL MOBILITY

The chapter's purpose is to provide a general understanding on potential sociolinguistic outcomes that can be encountered among mobile communities, particularly those that impinge on community language(s) use. The linguistic behaviours which may potentially occur with regards to pre-migratory languages use, other than L1 (the first language) were not given a direct focus. Even though, research related to L1 can still be informative. In the case of Algeria, I have already explained in the previous chapter the scale of cross linguistic influence between both languages (AA and French). I have also expounded the potential status of FL within the verbal repertoires of Algerian communities. In this chapter, I will explain how the relationship between migration and minority languages is socio-linguistically understood. Therefore, it sheds light on three important issues: recent trends of migration patterns and Algerian developments of transnational mobility; LM/LS as the focal point of this inquiry; and other linguistic behaviours that may impinge on LM/LS at the micro level.

3.1 Applicable Theoretical Concepts

Existing research on language use among immigrants in the diaspora (the dispersed presence of minority groups in non-native countries) can tell that there is not a consensus and a common sociolinguistic theory. In the case of Arab communities, Miller and Caubet (2010), speaking about the local practices, inferred: “the Arabic-speaking world presents a number of situations which do not fit with the dominant models of western sociolinguistics” (p.249). It may differ because of the complex linguistic systems which prevail in Arab communities in comparison to Western ones. Hence, one may additionally surmise that if the linguistic situation therein is already complex, the immigrant situation would be more complex, and that can result in less alignment with previous theories across a wide range of linguistic minority situations.

Different theories have been developed to explain language use in migratory settings. Within these theories, I situate my study on LM/LS areas. Although both theories present a wide array of models, taxonomies, and typologies that would assist in explaining the present research, none, by its own, can be used as an explanatory framework for the specific studied

context: short-term mobility. Because the paradigm of migration is shifting, especially with the advent of digital communication within 'the cyber space era' and the boom of globalisation, this project is not strictly confined to any of these. It rather uses explanations of positional beliefs from some of them. Accordingly, this chapter will only shed light on potential influences that I believe have some purchase or traction on my research. At the other end of the spectrum, because this project includes further the analysis of observed behaviours, the focus will be extended to considering related communicative behaviours. The theoretical framework, therefore, is based on influences from different theories (strongly based on LM/LS), models and concepts that I will jointly use for the purpose of this study: revealing the complexities underpinning the use of French language among Algerian students with their transition to the UK.

Above all, it is noteworthy to mention that the subfields of language contact are largely interconnected. This is illustrated in the works of many sociolinguists who studied a mix of variables for one purpose. Jamaï's (2008) sociolinguistic research is substantial to provide evidence about the overlapping of fields and the intermeshing of variables. In exploring LM among Moroccan nationals in the UK, he approached the issue in a number of ways, engaging the focus on other linguistic issues such as code-switching and mixing, bilingualism and shift (Jamaï, 2008). Pauwels (2005, 2016) emphasised the interdisciplinary nature of LM/LS, illustrating the high integration of LM/LS within other fields including applied linguistic studies.

3.2 Rethinking the Scope of Migration: Trans-migration, Super-diversity and Language

Above all else, the geo-political, economic and technological developments in the world since the early 1990s have led to a tremendous increase in migratory movements worldwide (Pauwels, 2007, Parkin and Arnaut, 2014). Among the results of these changes is the multiplicity of migration modes which altered the nature of migration to "heightened mobility"; from being depicted as only diverse to what is called by Vertovec (2007) "super-diverse" (Blommaert and Rampton, 2011, Pauwels, 2014). Super-diversity entails the growing variety of migration categories not only in terms of ethnicity, nationality, religion and language but also in terms of itineraries, patterns and motives (Blommaert and Rampton,

2011, p.7). An example of this would be the motive of Algerian PhD students who currently reside in the UK as sojourners to develop their academic careers, and to enrich their linguistic profiles, whereas the motive of the Syrian refugees, who came as asylum seekers, is to live securely. One may then assume that approaching migrants' linguistic practices requires not only a consideration of their linguistic practices, but also the circumstances of migration/mobility and the differences in modes and motives accordingly. It is noticed how different migration 20 years ago is from today in terms of facilities associated with the latter. In discussing the new developments in the global world and their effects on minority languages, Pauwels (2007) observed:

These developments are likely to impact also on the ways in which transnational movers that is migrants, refugees and other sojourners, keep in touch with their home or former communities. Similarly, long-distance travel has become within reach of many more people on a more frequent basis. This has impacted on migration and settlement patterns. For example, there is greater evidence of transnational movement and mobility by 'migrating' people who perhaps 20 years ago would have settled in a new environment with limited travel to and from their previous country

(Pauwels, 2007, p.1)

Actually, with such technological developments, the term migration is viewed as less appropriate in approaching recent patterns of transnational space crossing. In this regard, Schiller, Basch and Blanc (1995) maintained "Contemporary immigrants cannot be characterized as the uprooted. Many are trans-migrants, becoming firmly deep rooted in their new country, maintaining multiple linkages to their homeland" (p.48). A critical component in this view would be that the transmigration concept best matches long course movements with accessible opportunities to keep sporadic links with former communities. This type of migration could be appropriate for the Algerian-British Community in the UK who secured a good position within British society. They are therefore more privileged to make movements, unlike undocumented people and refugees.

In Tovares and Kamwangamalu (2017), return migration is used to imply a reverse meaning to the one-way movement of traditional migration. Return migration entails coming back to one's country to resettle for good (Tovares and Kamwangamalu, 2017). It could be an appropriate description aligning with this project sample's circumstances for the conditional return they are committed to. However, short-term movements such as study abroad as a

facet of internationalisation of higher education would be much better described as mobility, as pointed to by (Wei and Hua, 2013, Jenkins, 2017) because of the academic nature associated with it. According to Canagarajah (2017), mobile individuals have already different opportunities and resources to settle down, unlike migrants who seek opportunities to stay in the host country: "In policy and public discourse, the privileged who enjoy the resources and access for travel are considered mobile, and the less privileged are referred to as migrants" (P.5).

3.2.1 Transnational mobility

In this study, mobility is used as a key concept to mean temporary mobility as opposed to permanent migration (Bell and Ward, 2000). It is also used to address transnational student-semi-migrants, as opposed to the transnational "student-migrant" category noted by (Soong, 2016). Soong (2016) focused on students who seemed to migrate "for good"; students whose "lives [are] situated within the nexus of education and migration" (p.4). As opposed to his own description of his case study, students in this project can be described as those whose lives are situated within the nexus of education and "conditional return". Mobility is specifically viewed as having a tied relationship with internationalisation of higher education in the sense of claiming an international status (Jenkins, 2017).

This study accordingly places the spotlight on transnational, short-term mobility as a specific form of sojourn. Transnational space crossing, as a new form of migration, is viewed as strikingly different from the traditional migration because of ways of staying in touch which is eased by global technologies (Levitt and Jaworsky, 2007, Wei and Hua, 2013, Budach and Saint-Georges, 2017). For Wei and Hua (2013), the transnational concept implies "individuals whose life has been materially affected by global and transnational processes of migration" (p. 518). Transnational individuals are said to cross borders, without losing or cutting-off contacts with the origin country and culture. Therefore, their lives are characterised with "tensions between their way of being and way of belonging" (Wei and Hua, 2013, p.518).

In the field of LM/LS, these transformations in migratory movements gave rise to new perspectives to approach language use issues. The new perspectives require an account of whether it is a short-term or a long-term form of mobility. Each mobility pattern has its own

characteristics. Hence, there should be a thorough consideration of the types of mobility in approaching the linguistic practices of mobile communities. As a significant way of illustration, Pauwels (2016, p.17), speaking about multiple reasons of mobility and their linguistic consequences argued:

(...) All these forms of mobility, voluntary or forced, short or long term, are more likely to involve contact between speakers or different languages or language varieties. Short-term language contact between individuals or groups is not likely to induce (major) changes in linguistic constellations or the language practices of the speakers (...) conversely, long-term contact between people is much more likely to have a linguistic effect

At the verbal repertoire level, super-diversity among individuals would bring more changes and complexity to the linguistic practices of minority groups. Blommaert (2014), in this respect argues that “in super diverse environments (both on-and offline), people appear to take any linguistic and communicative resource available to them – a broad range, typically in super-diverse contexts – and blend them into hugely complex linguistic and semiotic forms”(Blommaert, 2014, p.8).

Interestingly, super-diversity consists of a huge number of languages within mobility settings, turning them from merely described as multilingual to hyper-lingual (Pauwels, 2014). Not only this, but super-diversity can also address mobile individuals having more than two languages within their verbal repertoires (Pauwels, 2014), a state which features the target case study in my project. Pauwels (2016, p.177) further echoed this view: “the radical changes in mobility patterns not only affect the linguistic landscapes of many cities and, sometimes, even countries around the world, they also reveal an increasing number of individuals with complex linguistic repertoires”. Blommaert (2010) describes the multilingual repertoires of new minorities as ‘truncated’ in the sense that the new linguistic practices are the result of immigrants past linguistic trajectories and the linguistic outcomes of the present mobility setting. For him, the multilingual repertoires could be described as “highly specific ‘bits’ of language and literacy varieties combine in a repertoire that reflects the fragmented and highly diverse life trajectories and environments of such people”(Blommaert, 2010, p.8), using West African (Nigerian), Turkish and Moroccan migrants’ practices in Berchem as ways of illustrating this.

Actually, Blommaert (2010) and Pauwels (2016) presented cases of complex verbal repertoires that can be considered as fine examples of super-diversity. For example, Pauwels (2016) used cases of a Tran family and Dutch aid workers as rich illustrations of complexity, because of the very diverse linguistic repertoires of these cases as a result of their life trajectories. From a critical point of view, the present study might not reach this level of complexity because of the limited life trajectories and linguistic experiences of the sample population under study. However, the availability of different linguistic resources at the level of the target population's verbal repertoires and the interaction between these resources may trigger complexity, especially with the transnational mobility, and therefore would contribute to super-diversity.

3.2.1.1 Recent Patterns of Algerian Mobility

The migration of Algerian communities was traditionally more associated with France due to political reasons. Recently, the Algerian migration profile is characterised by a diversification of destinations (Collyer, 2005). With global technological transformations, diversification of motives among Algerian migrants also increased. While France is still the largest host home for the Algerian diaspora, other Algerian communities are currently dispersed in different countries in the world. According to MPC Team (2013), in 2012, Algeria's outward mobility reached 961,850 Algerian migrants abroad as the most recent available data. These statistics represent the Algerian population residing in European Union (France, Spain, Italy and the UK), Southern-Eastern Mediterranean (SEM) countries (Tunisia) and other countries (mainly USA and Canada). The USA is now a recipient of an overwhelming number of Algerians due to the American Diversity Visa program (or Lottery visa) (Belmihoub, 2017, 2018a). In a micro reference to recent statistics, it is recorded that the Algerian population in the UK was estimated around 22,000 in 2012 and more concentrated in London (MPC Team, 2013).

In the mid 1990's, Algeria witnessed a sharp increase in migratory flows towards France for economic reasons. Algerian immigrants kept searching for better job opportunities and chose France to enhance their living, with the hope of offering economic support to their families back home. This had a great role in French LM since such immigrants had a language influence on their families through their contacts (Benrabah, 2007b). According to Belmihoub (2018a), the USA today is a recipient of many Algerians with different profiles including employees

working in a low-skilled labour. Other outer movements of Algerians are related to political reasons. Actually, the 1990's period was punctuated by a political event known as the civil war. Various Islamic groups rebelled against the Algerian government because of its negation of the Islamist electoral victory. This has led to many violent and bloody massacres, equivalent to terrorism in Algeria. Due to these political circumstances, the population had been through what is known as the "black decade", during which the flow of Algerian migration was intensified (Collyer, 2005). Most of these Algerians predominantly migrated as refugees and asylum seekers. Asylum seeking is regarded as the most significant means of reaching Europe as whole.

By the end of the civil war, Algeria built some driving ambitions which entail the full transition towards a free-market economy due to the rise of oil prices. This prompted a large demand for developing the status of English, an important element to enter the global market economy and maximise the chances of free trade (Benrabah, 2007b, Belmihoub, 2017). To realise this economic potential, many ambitions have been set out to develop the status and use of English. In addition to the government efforts to ease the diffusion of EL at the national level through education, there was also an increased awareness of international mobility and exchange programmes to promote EL skills.

3.2.1.1.1 The Algerian Development of Outward Mobility Schemes

Algeria's ambitious plans to achieve globalisation and internationalisation of higher education are underway. The so called "LMD system", which was adopted following Europe's Bologna Process, is among the recent policy updates that the Algerian government implemented in higher education for the purpose of being internationally recognised (Belmihoub, 2017). Following the Bologna agreement as a model was meant to bring reforms to its higher education system.

At the international level, Algeria became more aware of the importance of cross-border collaborative programmes to align with the global world. Accordingly, different academic programmes were evolved from one period to another. The movement of the Algerian professionals from Algeria to France for professional reasons started with French imperialism (Christelow, 2012). French educational institutions, among the European ones, were the most

popular destination for Algerian students owing to the political and economic ties that both countries have had (Döring et al., 2010). France was the first to negotiate contracts with the Tunisian, Moroccan and Algerian universities, and that had led to a high level of cooperation between France and Maghrebi lands (Benhafaiadh, 2006).

In the late of 1970's and early 1980's, Algerian students were awarded scholarships towards the USA, with the intention of going back to share with their Algerian fellows the scientific knowledge they acquired. Such students were sent off to highly-ranked American universities such as University of Wisconsin, Michigan and Illinois (Arfi, 2008). This initiative is considered as the starting point of Algerian exchange programmes with Anglophone countries. However, some highly qualified students did not come back to serve their country, especially with the economic instability that Algeria faced in the 1980's, mainly with the slump of oil prices (Christelow, 2012). On the other hand, the social problems and the fragmented society encountered by those who came back gave them fewer chances to develop academic research and to practise their roles as ambassadors (Arfi, 2008). Accordingly, one may say that the current Algerian PhD students in the UK, when returning to their homelands, may face multiple challenges in realising their dreams regarding enhancing the Algerian higher education system. This could be also considered among the potential long-term demerits of mobility programmes.

In the contemporary time, the Algerian initiatives to enhance the higher education system are further growing through the inclusion and adoption of different academic programmes and signing agreements. With the diffusion of EL in Algeria, the USA and UK established some engagements in academic and cultural exchange with Algeria (Belmihoub, 2017). The USA was among the welcoming destinations for Algerian students through launching a lottery visa programme where many students sought to pursue their careers in the US relying on a private sponsor. Not only this, but it is brought to notice that the US embassy in Algeria provided a variety of programmes for Algerian citizens such as the Fulbright and Youth Leadership Programmes (Belmihoub, 2012). Both of these, nonetheless, were limited to graduate studies. The target of the Fulbright programme is to maintain an educational cultural exchange, as is mentioned on the website of the US Embassy, cited in (Belmihoub, 2012).

Regarding the UK, an ambitious plan was recently drawn up by Algeria to enter into international partnerships with the Anglophone world. The UK government and the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education worked towards an agreement to send up to 500 PhD students, who are in receipt of a fully funded scholarship to pursue a career leading to a doctor of philosophy award (British Council, 2014, Chellia, 2018). One of the long-term objectives of this academic exchange is to build cultural bridges between both countries (British Council, 2014, Chellia, 2018). According to the director of the British Council in Algeria, the aim behind such an initiative is to foster an educational relationship between Algeria and UK, internationalise the Algerian higher education system and enhance its educational system (British Council, 2014). By the time of writing, the scheme reached the fourth cohort. As a member of the first cohort (2014-2015), I could notice that Algerian students are now dispersing around different UK higher education institutions. The majority of students from the 1st and 2nd Cohorts concentrate as minority groups in University of the West of Scotland, Northampton, Southampton, Canterbury, Portsmouth, Leeds and Lancaster universities, all of which represent an important sample of Algerian diaspora in the UK. Actually, the UK is not the only destination for PhD students. In 2018, in one of the meetings that are annually held at the level of the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, I could notice a growing diversity of destinations for Algerian students. The Algerian time schedule for the bursary renewal process shows that Algeria is further building educational ties with different countries such as Belgium, Canada, Emirate, Egypt, Greece, Hungary, Tunisia, Norway, Portugal, Jordan, Swiss and USA (See **Appendix 8** for more details).

The evolving of the Algerian internationalisation programmes to the UK and other Anglophone countries could be also a means to develop the presence of English in Algeria and minimise more likely that of French. Algerians' engagement in mobility for academic reasons in the UK will not result in a permanent settlement, because they signed a contract (as I did), giving a commitment to return to Algeria. This could even be termed a "conditional/guaranteed return". At the linguistic level, it could be thought that these Algerians' attitudes towards community language(s) use depend on their future plans. Knowing that they must return to Algeria, could affect their attitudes towards language use, and so, they differ in that respect, perhaps, from other members of the diaspora.

In the light of these migratory patterns and categories, Algerian short-term and long term-mobility were intensified. As the research study restricts its scope to mobile students with a short stay period (see Methodology chapter for more details), the study addresses potential linguistic practices that I believe match short periods of stay.

3.2.1.2 Reflections on FL among Algerians in the Diaspora

It is important to consider FL use among Algerian minority groups in the Diaspora to lay down some backgrounds, closely related to this research context. The settlements of Algerian communities in France could be an important factor to reinforce FL use through making familial contacts with their relatives and extended families back home (Benrabah, 2005). This point was best reinforced by Aitsiselmi and Marley (2008). In discussing the status and value of French in the three countries of the Maghreb, they speculated: “The existence of a large North African diaspora in France does contribute to the maintenance of French among families back home” (Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008, p.219). For newly-established Algerian minorities in France, French seems to have a crucial importance (Arfi, 2008). Using French would enable them to join the French society, access different privileges and get admitted to high-skill labours. Among Algerian interethnic groups, Kabylis in France tend to speak more French especially with their children (Arfi, 2008).

In Anglophone countries, Algerians in the USA tend to use English and a mix of Arabic and French especially in social media Facebook groups (Belmihoub, 2017). Actually, evidence of the use of AA-French and English among Algerians in the UK is also made clear in some social groups in Facebook. At the time of writing, groups such as Algerians in the United Kingdom and Ireland, (11 K members), Algerian community in Great Britain (7.9k members) and Algerian community in the UK (6.3K Members) in 24/03/2018, illustrated worthwhile examples of community language use. Within the three groups, where I am also a member, Algerians discuss different issues with a flexible use of linguistic resources. They use AA, English and sometimes mix between AA-French or AA-English, with French being conspicuously present.

As a matter of attitudes, Arfi's (2008) study revealed that Algerians in the USA acknowledge the importance of English and show their appreciation to the society *per se*. With this in mind,

English is substituting French swiftly within their repertoires, while totally depleted among their offspring.

The linguistic practices among the Algerian community in the UK have been little studied. Bichani (2015) studied the patterns of language use, identity and attitudes among two Arab migrant groups from various Arabic countries and included an Algerian family that illustrates the possible language shift taking place. According to the reported findings, the mother used a mix between dialectal Arabic (AA) and French, with little proficiency in English. Interestingly, when asking her to speak briefly about her current linguistic practices, she put "(...) my first language is Arabic, then French and then English(...)" (Bichani, 2015, p.191).

Arfi (2014) offered a tangible expression that illustrated a confused view towards FL, as part of the mother tongue for some Algerians. In the opening of the chapter, Arfi (2014, p.89) highlighted an utterance of a father encouraging Arabic LM among his son:

“Hdar bil ‘Arbia! Ma: tqulsh **pen!** Qul stylo! “

Speak in Arabic: don't say “pen”, say “Stylo”

“stylo “is a French word. However, the speaker seemed to unconsciously consider it as an AA word, and therefore used it instead of “9alam”. While ordering the interlocutor to speak in Arabic instead of English (using the word pen to exemplify), he produced the word in French. This example is illustrative of the potential dynamics that I will further examine in this study. It indicates the high integration of French in Algerians’ repertoires in general and mother tongue in particular. Before doing this, it is important to discuss LM/LS theory.

Language Maintenance and Language Shift: The Traditional Dominant Framework:

Initial efforts in LM/LS go back to scholars such as Einar Haugen, Max Weinreich, Uriel Weinreich and Nils Hasselmo with their studies on the influence of English on immigrant languages (Pauwels, 2019). Several researchers who contributed to the field: Fase, Jaspaert and Kroon (1992), Clyne (2003), Van Aswegen (2008), McDuling and Barnes (2012), Pauwels (2016) and many others pointed out that the terms LM/LS were first introduced by the American sociolinguist and key figure, Joshua Fishman in his paper “language maintenance

and shift as a field of inquiry” (1964). Afterwards, with his publication “Language Loyalty in the United States (1966)”, research in LM/LS received attention and blossomed (Habtoor, 2012). In the context of migration, LM/LS, unlike some other sociolinguistic concepts, are not a sphere of controversy. Therefore, LM was commonly used to mean the continuous use of community languages without succumbing to competition with the dominant language in the host country. The concept of language shift has been used to refer to the gradual or rapid shift from using one language to another (Pauwels, 2004, 2016). So, it is the tendency of communities to substitute one language or more in their repertoires by a language (s) that they may think is (are) more socially functional. The shift can be gradual as it can be rapid.

In literature, the issue of whether LM/LS are conscious/unconscious phenomena, has received less attention. For LS, there seems less commonality on whether LS is conscious or not. Buda (1992) considered it as rarely conscious. For him “the phenomenon of language shift takes place out of sight and out of mind. Individuals are rarely conscious of a subtle and gradual loss of language” (Buda, 1992, p.80). Offiong and Ugot (2012) realised that while the Efik minority group in south eastern Nigeria is unconscious that they are gradually losing their language, “Efik language”, and shifting to English, they are simultaneously conscious of a need to maintain their minority language.

As indicated previously, LM/LS processes can be related to other concepts such as language endangerment and death (see Pauwels, 2016, p.2). While LS stands for the gradual shift from using or speaking one language to another, language attrition is more used in the field of psycholinguistics to mean a decline in the language proficiency and skills of an individual. De Bot (2001) considers language attrition as a subset of language loss (as cited in Clyne, 2003, p.5). Like other concepts in the field of sociolinguistics, this term is used to indicate a change that results from language contact such as LM, LS and code-switching.

Language attrition can also occur with regards to a second or a foreign language if the learner of that language has not enough exposure to use it (DeBot and Weltens, 1991). This latter can be illuminating and informative to the present inquiry as it focuses on French, a language that is usually perceived as a second language among Algerians. The context of this research is strictly related to the informal aspect of FL use in the daily life interactions. Attitudes towards using French among the Algerian students in the UK were extended to mentioning the effect

of residing in the UK on their FL skills. This was suggested by some participants in interview data, where, for example, the effect on other FL skills – writing and reading – was mentioned (see data analysis section). Thus, in terms of De Bot and Weltens' findings (1991), the lack of exposure to, or requirement for, reading or writing French in the host context for these Algerian students, could affect French LM in those specific language modes, even although their spoken FL use may be less affected. Arfi (2008) explored supporting data in this respect. Accordingly, she found out a significant attrition of FL and its replacement with Arabic and English. Not only would language attrition be the only outcome, but also language death and decay. From a critical point of view, these are phenomena which may require a longer time to occur.

3.2.2 Main LM/LS Influencing Theories and Models

To understand the dynamics of LM/LS, different models were considered by scholars as explanatory and predictive frameworks for different situations (Clyne, 2003). The common focus of these main theories and models is the various factors which either promote or hinder both behaviours. Benrabah (2007a, p.196) questioned the predictive power of these factors: “In fact, there is considerable consensus in the subfield of LM/LS in the sense that there is no single set of sociological factors that can be used to predict maintenance or shift”. In a similar fashion, Myers-Scotton (2006, p.70) argued “we can predict, but we can’t promise”. In what follows, I shall start by reviewing literature on the major western theories that marked the history of LM/LS. The main aim is to present only potential explanatory factors that can fit into the context of this study.

Within an American immigrant context, Kloss (1966) identified some factors that impinge on language use patterns among German minority groups. These factors are categorised as “clear cut” and “ambivalent” ones (Clyne, 2003, Pauwels, 2004, 2016), and were viewed as measurable and applicable in other speech communities (Clyne, 2003). Clyne (2003), for example, in his study on immigrants in an Australian context explained the factors that can be more applicable to his context of research.

Among Kloss’s ‘clear-cut’ factors, the most influencing factor that could be relevant to the target population in the UK, and can potentially influence FL use, is the pre-migratory

experience. As I mentioned previously, according to some findings in Kadem (2015), Algerian EFL students tend to have positive attitudes about FL and tend to use it as a sign of prestige. In the new setting, Algerians' positive experience may positively affect the current use of FL. The situation of FL in Algeria is already discussed in previous chapters and implies that it has a high perceived functional status. FL is also maintained among the new generations of Algerian speech society (Benrabah, 2007b). Algerian students' attitudes can be influenced by that. Participants in interviews were asked to provide their individual accounts with this language, both before mobility and currently (See research questions: section 4.1 in methodology chapter). By so doing, it is aimed to explore the extent to which negative pre-mobility experience affect the current one and the vice versa.

From Kloss's ambivalent factors, however, the factors that could inform this research study are the educational level of participants (high proficiency would trigger LM and vice versa) and the numerical strength of the group in the host country. This research specifically addressed participants who are based with other Algerian students in different UK universities. One aim of this is to explore the extent to which their existence as ethnolinguistic groups stimulates LM. In this main vein, Pauwels (2016, p.102) postulated that "groups that are numerically stronger may be better placed to maintain the language, as there are more people with whom and contexts and occasions in which to use the language".

Later, in 1983, Conklin and Lourie extended Kloss's list of factors and grouped them into political, social and demographic, cultural, and linguistic factors (Clyne, 2003). These factors were grouped and explained as follows:

Figure 3. 1: Conklin and Lourie (1983) factors of LM/LS according to Clyne (2003)

From the first category, recency of arrival is a factor that can influence FL use among Algerian PhD students in the UK. The targeted sample is a new group of students who settled not more than three years ago. This can strongly secure the status of FL use within their repertoires, one could assume. More than that, the extent to which the mobile students return/travel to Algeria from time to time during their residency in the UK is a factor that can affect FL use. The educational level of students is also an important influencing factor, and it is already acknowledged in Kloss's ambivalent factors. Conklin and Lourie further highlighted an important cultural factor: strong attachment to the local culture of immigrants might result in community languages being maintained, simply because it is commonly argued that language and culture are interconnected. Language status of the community language has been classified as a linguistic factor that may impede LM or promote LS.

In 1977, "Ethnolinguistic vitality" was introduced by the sociolinguists Howard Giles, Richard Bourhis and Don Tylor as an informative theoretical framework to the study of LM/LS (Allard and Landry, 1992, Clyne, 2003, Pauwels, 2004, 2016, Myers-Scotton, 2006, VanAswegen, 2008). Ethnolinguistic vitality is that "which makes a group likely to behave as a distinctive and active collective entity in intergroup situations"(Pauwels, 2016, p.109). In other words, it is the group's attempt to protect its co-existence and survival as a distinctive minority. In this theory, a taxonomy of three structural variables was set out to measure and determine the

group's vitality: status, demographic, and institutional support. The three main variables further consist of sub-sets of elements to assist in the process of measurement. Among these variables, status variable (economic, social and socio-historical) and demographic variable (concentration of the group) can be used as influences to the present research. Therefore, if the status of language X among a community group Y is high and positive, widely used and supported in different domains, this would enable that group to exist as an ethnic minority with distinctive linguistic behaviours. Other factors such as institutional support might be pertinent to the Algerian communities in the UK with different generations, who migrated a long time ago, but not relevant to Algerian students as newly established minorities in different UK universities. It is claimed that depending on these variables one can determine the degree of vitality among a particular group – as to whether it is high or low. Consequently, if the group vitality is high, this would more likely lead to its ethnolinguistic survival. Conversely, if the group vitality is low, that would result in threatening the existence of the linguistic practices of the group as a distinct one (VanAswegen, 2008).

All previously mentioned approaches are situated within structural –functional approaches to the study of LM/LS, as explained by Pauwels (2016). The salient feature of structural functional studies is that their major focus is on the group level rather than the individual one (Pauwels, 2016). However, Potowski (2013, pp.322–323) touched upon an important point with regards to LS. For him, LS is basically an individual phenomenon, including personal factors such as proficiency and attitudes. Therefore, recent approaches that have attempted to identify factors more indicative to LM/LS at an individual level are worthy of consideration.

Social network theory was developed by Lesley Milroy (1983) as a sound way to investigate the role of social ties that surround individuals on language change, mainly varieties of English in working-class areas of Belfast (Sallabank, 2010). In 2002, Milroy applied this framework in a context closer to this research and used it as a framework to explore the role of social ties in the maintenance of endangered community (language) varieties. Since then, many researchers on LM/LS, such as Zentella (1997), Stoessel (2002) and Rocchi (2008) informed their studies with the social network analysis. The main findings revealed that an individual's social network and ties have a greater explanatory value and influence on language choice (Sallabank, 2010). Stoessel (2002), in his small-scale study with ten different immigrants in the USA, concluded that the stronger ethnic support is for individuals, the stronger possibility

of LM and *vice versa*. In this study, this theory can be influential in some ways. It can inform in identifying how intragroup interactions among Algerian students and their coexistence as ethnically connected groups can be considered as a social network factor in empowering FL use, and therefore, it can trigger French LM. Hence, being influenced by Stoessel's study, social network will be used as a factor to examine the role of ethnic support triggered by the friendship domain in French LM.

In Pauwels (2005), it is documented that the friendship domain is less influential to LM than other domains such as the family domain. The latter is more promoting for LM. In a study among Vietnamese, Greek and German adolescent communities in Australia, the use of CL among the so-mentioned communities was reported as very low, in comparison to other domains. Interestingly, in an observation of Greek adolescents in friendship intragroup interactions, while the host language was used more, few instances of code-switching with CL were recorded, and that was just perceived as a marker of solidarity (Pauwels, 2005).

In a similar fashion, Othman (2011), in investigating Arabic LM among Arab communities (parents and children) in Manchester, highlighted the social network support coming through interactions with relatives back home as stronger for Arabic LM than that coming from intragroup interactions with the same ethnic groups in the new setting, especially for children. For this main reason, social-network related factors will further include the family and relatives' support in this study. At this point, because this research targets the perceived experience of FL use both before mobility and with transition, the social network element plays a dual function. At one end, it will highlight the family and environment support to FL in pre-mobility. At the other of the spectrum, it will consider the support coming from the friendship domain during the current stay.

Moreover, it is noteworthy to consider the role of social media in the light of new technological developments in the world, which triggers facilitating virtual contacts with family and former communities back home (Pauwels, 2007, 2016). The latter can be considered as an important factor which promotes CLM (See section 3.3.2 for more details). Accordingly, the social network factor will also consider this point.

3.2.2.1 Further Factors Affecting LM/LS

Drawing on the aforementioned theories, other factors have emerged in different contexts to regenerate and create knowledge in the field of LM/LS. In what follows, I will discuss other factors as a result of key studies and the relative merits of these studies. The discussion is always restricted to the framework of this research: LM/LS within short-term mobility.

Clyne (2003), in his overview of different theories and models, highlighted three categories of LM/LS. Among these, I selected the most relevant factors to the present study context:

Figure 3. 2: Factors influencing the dynamics of language shift according to Clyne (2003, pp.68–69)

Language proficiency is an individual factor that can be indicative in favour of LS. Drawing from Kloss's factors, he similarly stated that the group number and pre-migratory experience are powerful group factors that affect LS. While Kloss considered the pre-migratory experience as a factor stimulating LM, it was distinctively categorised as an element stimulating LS in Clyne. Pre-migratory experience can include issues of prestige and status as well as attitudes. Building on Clyne's categorisation of pre-migratory experience as a shift factor would build the assumption that LS to English among participants in this research could be related to the effects of colonial attitudes. Stoessel (2002) provided an important case of Taiwanese immigrants who came from an environment which is characterised with linguistic struggles between two dominant languages, Taiwanese and Chinese. Taiwanese is perceived as the CL, unlike Chinese which is viewed as a mere imposed language. Immigrants' attitudes towards their community languages were influenced by this linguistic situation back home. In this research, I would problematize how Clyne classified pre-migration experience at the group level and not at the individual level, and therefore I will use it at the individual level during data presentation in my research.

Clyne (2003) added two important general factors: time of migration (long stay – short stay) and the place (social, isolated/formal /informal), key elements that this research will take into account. In a similar manner, Potowski (2013) classified LM/LS factors among communities, be it migrant or non-migrant ones into neat categories: individual, community and broader societal factors. The figure below documents only relevant factors:

Figure 3. 3: Factors influencing the dynamics of LM/LS according to Potowski (2013)

As illustrated before, proficiency in the CL was commonly considered as a predictive factor in LM. Holmes (2013), Potowski (2013) and Onadipe-Shalom (2014) classified attitudes towards the minority language as a factor in favour of LM/LS; positive attitudes result in LM and negative ones trigger LS. Regarding LS, Kische (2017) posited that negative attitudes towards a language can accelerate LS. For him, LS occurs “when the ethnic language is not highly valued and is not seen as a symbol of identity” (P.73). One critical component provided by Potowski (2013, p.323) is the fact that “positive attitudes are not enough for language maintenance to occur”, an important point which is taken into account in the present research. Within Potowski’s individual factors, the role of family is a powerful LM factor (Stoessel, 2002, Pauwels, 2005, Canagarajah, 2008).

LM can also occur as a product of the linguistic similarity between the minority language and the host language. In line with my study, FL and EL do have some similar words, but pronounced differently. For example, the word, université - university. Finally, similar to Conklin and Lourie (1983), language status is considered as an important factor, promoting either LM or LS (Clyne, 2003). A language with a strong status would not easily succumb to competition with another one and vice versa.

Holmes (2013) maintained that LS may arise due to: economic, social and political factors, demographic factors, attitudes and values factors. Minority groups’ communities tend to shift

to a language that is economically advantageous and would give them access to gain job opportunities. Minority communities would also shift to a language through which they access major institutional domains, and therefore, would enable them to successfully achieve social inclusion. As a demographic factor, Holmes (2013) further maintained that communities in rural areas are less exposed to LS because they are isolated from the wider social groups. Similar to Clyne (2003), Holmes argued that the size of the group lived among has a powerful influence on language use. For her, “to maintain a language you must have people you can use it with on a regular basis” (Holmes, 2013, p.62). So, it could be concurred that the smaller in size the group is, the larger the tendency for LS to occur. A common point introduced by Potowski (2013), is that positive attitudes by the majority can contribute to LM. Conversely, negative attitudes would lead to shifting to another language. Holmes (2013, p.63) said “the status of a language internationally can contribute to these positive attitudes”. On this premise, one may assume that English – as the most international language - receives higher value among Algerian communities than FL.

Kishe (2017), discussed some important factors that can reinforce LS. In addition to some recurring factors such as demographic, attitude and economic ones, the power of global languages was further highlighted. For Kishe, community languages might be substituted by international languages such as English and French. English is internationally recognised as a global language, and that makes it more powerful than other languages. It could be therefore assumed that French among Algerians in the UK would lose ground to English.

In practice, these theories have been applied widely across different contexts. While the product of these theories revealed some recurring factors, still they can belong to different categories. Latham Keh and Stoessel (2017), as an instance, made a point that language use is affected by both societal and individual factors. In researching CLM and LS among bilinguals from German-Polish families in the USA, Latham Keh and Stoessel (2016), not only underlined the role of attitudes, but also network-related factors. In other words, German LM was perceived as useful, for example, to establish connections with German-speaking families and friends. Therefore, the role of family and friends can be considered among social network related factors.

In a non-African context, Canagarajah (2008) stated that family reinforcement is crucial to preserve community languages among Sri Lankan Tamil diaspora in the UK, USA and Canada from both children's and parents' perspectives, a point that was also agreed on by Pauwels (2005) and Potowski (2013). Perera (2015), however, in investigating LM/LS among Sri Lankan migrants in Australia, found out that three main factors that promote their CLM or LS to English: the role of one's experience with EL before migration, the desire to maintain cultural connections, and the functionality of their community languages in religious practices. So, similar to Kloss's clear-cut factors and Clyne (2003), pre-migratory experience was further highlighted as an important factor in LM/LS.

In a closer examination, Michieka (2012) detected some factors influencing ethnic LM among Kenyan university students. Different factors were deemed to promote LM/LS to other languages such as English. Among other factors, context of one's upbringing (whether it is rural or urban), the educational level of parents and attitudes were identified, and these could be influencing findings in the present context scenario.

LM/LS were also extended to researching Arab communities in migratory contexts. Jamai (2008), in exploring language use among young Moroccan immigrants in the UK, found out that the community was experiencing a shift towards English for socio-economic reasons and the desire to minimise social exclusion. Receiving little access to institutional support also proved a significant LS factor as well as other factors related to globalisation, where the need for English is significant. At the other end of the spectrum, community LM (Arabic) was triggered by the low level of proficiency in English and using Arabic when talking to relatives in Morocco.

Othman (2011) reported that Arabic was maintained because of its functionality among Arab families and the positive attitudes towards their CL. It was also maintained because of the ability of their children to use it in various communicative tasks and importantly the effect of globalisation which seemed to ease Arabic language maintenance (See Section 3.3.2 for more details on which globalisation I mean)

Dweik, Nofal and Qawasmeh (2014), in reporting language use and attitudes among Arab community in Vancouver (Canada), found out that Arabic and English were used side by side.

While Arabic was maintained and used because of the positive attitudes towards it in the sense of representing their Arabic identity, LS to English and its use was linked to positive attitudes towards English as a prestigious language and socio-economic functionality.

Bichani (2015), in reflecting on the linguistic practices of two Arab communities as mentioned earlier, found out evidence of LS among the young generations, unlike the older generations who tended to maintain Arabic. While the latter considered Arabic as a core value in their identity and a language that represented their culture and identity, the children overlooked the role of Arabic in shaping their identity, and this could be viewed as an important shift factor (Bichani, 2015).

The quality and transferability of these studies were assessed in terms of sample choice, size and also their own argumentation of findings. Although they have some common concerns with this project, still they cannot function as explanatory frameworks in the current study due to the following arguments:

- The afore-mentioned studies shed focus on L1 but did not sufficiently account for a pre-mobility L2 (French in the case of the present research).
- Those studies did not explore in depth the effect of globalisation, with a specific type of mobility.
- They were seemingly approached from subtractive multilingualism perspectives which imply deterministic and unidirectional and “all or nothing” LM/LS processes, while this research takes a translanguaging perspective.
- The difference in circumstances that the targeted study population was transitioned in the light of (academic short-stay translational mobility), that none of the aforementioned studies dealt with. Although this is an original point itself and can spark some interest, short-term mobility troubles the application of LM/LS. Consequently, these concepts (LM/LS) require a careful usage in my research. Section **(3.3.4)** presents the challenges that may arise from LM/LS framework within short-stay periods.

3.2.3 LM/LS and Globalisation

With the advent and ubiquity of globalisation, communication technologies and internet networks have sustained sporadic links with the homeland. As a result, they contributed to community LM in diaspora (Androutsopoulos, 2006, Pauwels, 2016). Owing to the emergence of new and diverse platforms of interaction, people all over the world started to access easily and cheaply different resources that support virtual LM. To highlight the role of the cyberspace era in promoting LM, Pauwels (2016, p.172) summed up:

The arrival of the internet and other forms of computer-mediated communication not only have made it easier, cheaper and quicker to keep in touch with speakers of one's language(s) around the world, but it has made a wealth of language resources, many of which are interactive, accessible to such communities

In addition to promoting LM through easing virtual contacts within the ethno-specific minorities circle, Pauwels (2016) speculated that the internet can further reinforce the efforts of LM institutions and activities. Internet can promote community-based education, offers online classes among ethnolinguistic minorities, and gives access to a wide range of online minority media (Pauwels, 2016).

Recently, there seems a growing awareness of the role of globalised communication connectivity in retaining community languages. Sallabank (2010) underlined the role of social networking through online communication as a potential strategy to revitalise minority language among Guernesiais speakers in the Channel Islands. Not only did globalisation afford easy and fast communication in favour of LM, but also triggered advances in the world transportation. In the contemporary situation, the world increasingly witnessed fast mobilities with different options and facilities that would allow for in and out movements. As noted earlier, Othman (2011) explained the effects of globalisation on Arabic LM. For him, transportation made it easier and faster for the participants to visit relatives back home and to receive visits from people back home as well. Othman (2011) further noted the role of regular virtual interaction between children and parents with people back home via telephone and internet, all of which favour LM.

3.2.3.1 LM and English as a *Lingua Franca*

While globalisation is a good promoter of LM, the dominance of English as a global language has been considered as a threat to multilingualism and minority languages in transnational contexts. For example, Pauwels (2007) regarded English as a challenge to the maintenance of minority languages in both Europe and Australia. However, challenges imposed by contexts on whether English is a national and official language or merely a foreign language differ. In this research, English is de facto an official language in the researched context (UK). Consequently, the menace could be intense concerning minority languages. Actually, English as a *lingua franca* can function as an explanatory factor and can inform participants' choices of LS to English in terms of functionality.

3.3.3 Expanding the Paradigm of LM/LS: The Need for New Perspectives:

The majority of studies in LM/LS can be argued as discussed in relation to Fishman's concepts of LM/LS. In their traditional sense, languages were viewed as bounded entities, and this implies the notion of separate languages (See definitions in Section 3.3). The ongoing mobility in the world opened new lines of thinking in the study of language and multilingualism. Regarding LM/LS, Pauwels (2019) emphasised the need to adopt new perspectives as a result of that. Reflecting on how globalisation altered the concept of migration and how this affected LM/LS, she maintained:

(...) Rather than seeing it primarily as a process resulting in 'permanent' (re) settlement in another location, migration increasingly results in ongoing mobility. Such changes are likely to affect language practices in diaspora contexts, sometimes quite drastically, which may entail a rethinking of what constitutes LM or LS and how LM can be practised in such situations

(Pauwels, 2019, p. 236)

Linguistic practices are becoming viewed as more fluid and dynamic. Martin-Jones (1988) suggested an alternative approach to research language use including LM/LS. He emphasised the need to move beyond a phase of using functional/ structural approaches that are guided by communicative conventions:

While it is important to take account of the fact that the communicative resources that bilinguals draw on in their everyday discourse are socially determined, it is also important to emphasize that individual speakers do not just draw on these resources or follow communicative conventions in a mechanical fashion. Individual bilinguals in majority communities draw on the linguistic resources in their repertoire in strategic and creative ways. Language use among bilinguals is complex and variable and generally involves much more than a two-way choice of code. Communicative resources are combined and juxtaposed in subtle ways through code-mixing and code-switching (...)

(Martin-Jones, 1988, p.123)

The alternative approaches should be based on more fluidity, instead of unidirectional processes of language use. More than that, most LM/LS approaches received some critiques in the light of new ways of thinking. For example, the sociology of language is criticised because it considers language as “a whole, bounded system”(Pauwels, 2019). Recently, initial suggestions emerged to align with new lines of thinking in the study of language and mobility. Pauwels (2016) views that LM/LS are no longer between two national languages. LM/LS are better explained through the lens of multiple practices (languaging); LM (the maintenance of multilingual practices), LS (a shift to a reduced set of practices):

(...) rather than seeing LS as a process of (gradual or rapid) shift from one language to another language, we may conceive of it as a gradual reduction in the multilingual nature of a person’s or group’s language repertoire or language practices’ and that ‘LM could be conceived as the maintenance of a multilingual repertoire even if the languages or codes upon which the individual or group draws change (...)

Pauwels (2016, 183–184)

Pauwels (2019) further drew on some points characterising the linguistic profiles of new minority groups that are: “ (1) an inability or unwillingness of individuals to identify one language as one’s native, first, or heritage language; (2) language choices that defy clear associations with domains, interlocutors, and social networks; and (3) occasional or even regular changes in the languages that make up one’s linguistic repertoire” (p.248). Mazzaferro (2018b) assumed that the idea of heritage languages as unchanging and stable has been challenged within the new perspectives in the study of language and multilingualism. However, one should reflect that these can happen to individuals with long periods of stay. In situations of short-term mobility, the interpretation of LM/LS may not encounter practices as such.

Actually, the dominant traditional framework (LM/LS) can be still useful in some linguistic situations. In supporting this view, Pauwels (2016) states “(...) of course, there continue to be linguistic situations involving several languages that are less affected by the hypermobility associated with western forms of globalisation and whose study may be less challenging to structural-functional approaches to LM and LS” (Pauwels, 2016, P.183). One of the potential situations where traditional LM/LS can be still useful, I suppose, is short-term mobility, where individuals in question would be still influenced by the country of origin’s own policies. Of course, if the country of origin’s related policies are based on linguistic hybridity, flexibility and include the creative nature of social and linguistic practices, then structural-functional approaches would be less influential.

3.3.3.1 Translanguaging as an approach to LM/LS

Recently, translanguaging has been developed as a new paradigm within critiques of structural functional approaches. Translanguaging was introduced to develop understanding of language in use (García and Li, 2012, Otheguy, García and Reid, 2015, 2018). It was used as opposed to code-switching (Otheguy, García and Reid, 2015, Otheguy, García and Reid 2018, Mazzaferro, 2018b). Recent research in multilingualism generated a lively debate to capture nuanced differences between translanguaging and code-switching. According to Otheguy, García and Reid (2015) and Otheguy, García and Reid (2018), the translanguaging perspective came to wipe away all those notions of named and discrete languages that are dictated by code-switching and similar behaviours. Otheguy, García and Reid (2015, p.281) provided a thorough definition to translanguaging as “the deployment of a speaker’s full linguistic repertoire without regard for watchful adherence to the socially and politically defined boundaries of named (and usually national and state) languages”. So, in translanguaging, languages are regarded as “part of a single integrated system” (Baty 2016: 83). A translanguaging perspective tolerates the use of plurilingual resources without any regards to separate systems in which the purpose is meaning-making (Baker, 2011, Blackledge and Creese, 2017).

In the course of this study, LM/LS are looked at through the lens of the very basics of translanguaging approach: their existence within a range of different resources, rather than isolation. This translanguaging perspective is used to investigate the reshaping of students’

verbal repertoires, with a peaceful occurrence of resources. However, because structural-functional approaches are still dominant in the Algerian society (the context of this research), this may suggest that traditional LM/LS can be still useful. In my study, French LM is studied as part of the repertoire (AA and English). When it is used as a predominant embedded code, this would explain a case of LM, when English is used as a predominant embedded code (alongside AA and French), this would indicate LS. By so doing, it would mediate between the traditional and new scholarship of LM/LS. Before that, it is yet important to acknowledge the limitations of LM/LS within short-term mobility.

3.3.4 A critical appraisal of the use of LM/LS to study short-term mobility:

In the past, migration was equated with “one-way movements”, often leading to long-term settlements. The geo-political, economic and technological developments in the world since the early 1990s have led to a tremendous increase in migratory movements worldwide (Pauwels, 2007, Parkin and Arnaut, 2014). Among the results of these changes is the multiplicity and dynamicity of mobility processes which have altered the nature of migration to “heightened mobility” (Blommaert and Rampton, 2011, Pauwels, 2014). Short term-mobility in the light of internationalisation of higher education, mobility and exchange programmes, became an important type of spatial mobility processes within globalisation. As explained in the rationale of this study, one of the reasons for choosing a context of temporary mobility in this research is that the world is facing a sharp increase in short-term periods of stay, and so this is an interesting mobility experience to address.

In terms of linguistic practices, the theoretical framework of analysis chosen in this research (LM/LS) is one which was originally developed for the analysis of long-term migration and settlement contexts. The context for analysis within this thesis is one that is characterised by (very short-term) mobility rather than migration, with an almost guaranteed return to the country of origin. This context thus poses considerable challenges for the application of the LM/LS framework because of:

1. The likely fewer changes that can impinge on language use. Building on this assumption, the continuous use of linguistic practices would be a major and a dominant outcome, while language change is less likely to happen. It would be then worthwhile to explore this, drawing from two types of data: perceived behaviours and actual ones. With the arrival of minority communities, LM can happen as maintained

by Conklin and Lourie (1983) and Clyne (2003) who placed recency of arrival among the factors influencing LM. Traditional LS, if it is evident in data, one may say that it could be already happening before mobility, and mobility is just a reinforcing factor. More than that, however, if seen from the new perspectives suggested by Pauwels (2016), LM/LS in longer periods of stay can be studied in terms of multiple practices within the repertoire. Within short-term mobility, the maintenance of multilingual practices, one may reflect, would be a major outcome, while decreased multilingualism is less likely to occur. In this sense, the pre-mobility experience of participants could be stronger in influencing both LM/LS, while there might be fewer opportunities to explore factors related to the current setting because of the likely limited experience that can be gained from short-stay periods. This would suggest that LM/LS can be challenged in terms of equal involvement during application.

2. The conditional return to the country of origin after this very short-term mobility. Individuals, while travelling abroad in that sense, still have definite return plans in addition to the normal modern ways of maintaining connections with communities back home. This would definitely affect their linguistic affiliations and perceptions. Again, situations of LM/LS within this type of mobility is problematic because decisions will be more related to mainland Algeria. According to this limitation, it would be hard to claim that LM/LS are actually happening, but rather they could be assumed linguistic practices, related to aspirations. Given the fact that language issues in Algeria are still structural-functional, individuals' perceptions and reflections might be influenced by the community-wide norms. According to Martin-Jones (1988, p.110), in the structural-functional approach, "communicative interaction and code choice among bilinguals is seen as a mere reflex of macro-level statuses and structures". French is still functional in different domains in Algeria, including daily life interactions. However, LS to English is a desired practice among the policy makers, as mentioned in Benrabah (2013, 2014). In this case, perceptions and dispositions towards language use can be a result of power dominance, triggered by the country of origin. Language policy in Algeria is firmly based on an LS basis, where the policy intention is to see English increasing at the expense of French.
3. The majority of previous LM/LS theories and models widely include different domains during the process of analysis and exploration because of the depth of experiences

gained from long-term migration and settlement contexts. Unlike this, domains within short-term mobility, such as those traveling for the purpose of tourism, study-abroad and professional training, can be restricted. In this study, while this is a limitation *per se*, targeting the friendship domain is deliberate as it emerged from a call for further research, as mentioned in the rationale of this research.

Despite of all these limitations, it is of significance to make the study of LM/LS well-suited to different patterns of mobility. To counteract these challenges above, this thesis will carefully address LM/LS, with sensitivity to the short-stay period, the guaranteed return to the country of origin, as well as the new perspectives in the study of language use.

Regarding the first point, one can say that this research deals with situations of earlier, or nascent, stages of LM/LS that can be triggered by short periods of stay. Therefore, LM/LS are not deterministic in this project: that is, "either/or", as they were used in contexts of long settlements. Instead, they work in much more dynamic ways. This research is building bridges between the past and current approaches: i.e. Algerian policy suits the traditional LM/LS framework, but the short-term mobile participants have a multilingual repertoire which may have some internal movement but essentially maintains an LM profile (according to Pauwels' suggested understanding of the term within the world of superdiversity). LM/LS will be identified during data presentation in two ways:

I. New perspectives: Pauwels's (2016, 2018) initial suggestion:

According to Pauwels (2016), LM/LS are ill-suited to the rapid changes in globalisation in terms of mobility and language use (such as social media and world transportation). She suggests that the notion of shift is better suited to a consideration of a person or group's language repertoire: LS would be where these resources declined; LM would be where a multilingual repertoire was maintained, even if the individual languages or codes used change. If seen from this perspective, LM is the maintenance of a multilingual practices, while LS is a shift to a reduced set of practices.

II. Traditional Perspectives: the 'dominant' framework:

The research is also related to a structural-functional context because language policy in Algeria is still subtractive when it comes to French/English statuses. In other words, despite

individuals' multilingual repertoires, the aim is of English supplanting French (Benrabah, 2013, Belmihoub, 2012. 2015, 2017, Ghanmi, 2019). Thus, Algerian language policy is based on the notion of LS – French to decline, English to increase. In this sense, the analysis will focus on the amount of FL use and English that is embedded within research participants' Algerian Arabic and repertoires in their daily life interactions. This research will address the traditional focus of LM/LS within the participants' repertoires to mean:

LM: while both FL and English are used as embedded resources, the degree of the first is more than the second in terms of use (Arabic-French-English).

LS simply entails: while keeping the use of French, English is used more than French (Arabic-English-French). LS will be used to express a temporary change where English is used as a predominant embedded code choice. In other words, while different resources are used, the main focus is to find out which one is predominantly used (of course beside the matrix language). In this vein, this research offers a quite different interpretation of LM/LS. It was traditionally used to talk about switches between languages, but it is more interesting in a globalising world to talk about either a maintenance or shift in languaging. One of the reasons is that while there are national languages, within that there is a mix within national repertoires.

Given the specific circumstances of the research participants, drawing conclusions during the discussion of the findings will be carefully addressed. For example, in eliciting participants' perceptions regarding factors behind LM/LS, the word "factors", in some instances of data, will be used to mean "aspirations", to avoid any strong, deterministic claims.

As for the issue of dominance and power triggered by the consideration of the structural-functional approach to LM/LS, the second phase of the field work will incorporate actual instances of language use. One of the aims is to analyse perceived LM/LS within participants' repertoires in the context of daily interactions. Martin-Jones (1983) alluded that a fine-grained investigation of LS can be accomplished through accounting for "social and linguistic processes operating at the micro-level of interaction" (p.113). Therefore, this entails focusing on the process itself rather than the structure which, according to Martin-Jones (1988, p.114), implies "passively observing idealized norms of language allocation".

3.3 Language Attitudes

In the literature, the study of speakers' attitudes has been placed at the core of investigating language issues. At both the acquisitive and use levels, researchers such as Karahan (2007), Zhang and Slaughter-Defoe (2009), Garrett (2010) and Bichani (2015) highlighted the importance of positive language attitudes in the acquisition and use of a particular language. For them, the more positive attitudes individuals have towards a particular language, the better outputs would be realised (in linguistic performance, for example). In LM/LS, the role of attitudes in maintaining community languages or shifting to others is emphasised. Accordingly, positive attitudes are important in the maintenance of community languages (Raeda Al-Nahar, 2009, Othman, 2011, Dweik and Al-Obaidi, 2014, Dweik, Nofal and Qawasmeh, 2014). Onadipe-Shalom (2014, p.78) claimed that "attitude plays a significant role in LM/LS. While a positive attitude results in language maintenance and growth, a negative attitude can eventually lead to LS, loss or even death".

Garrett (2010), Onadipe-Shalom (2015) and Bichani (2015) maintained that language attitudes are related to the psychological aspect of people. In other words, attitudes are just a state of mind, and this does not translate into reflecting the real practice of people under investigation (Bichani, 2015). In LM/LS, the so-claimed tied-up relationship between positive attitudes and LM has received valuable critiques. Potowski (2013, p.43) maintained that LM/LS are not always the product of positive or negative attitudes; "Positive attitudes are not enough for language maintenance to occur". From a critical point of view, the role of positive attitudes should not be overlooked, but should not be overemphasised. To react to this point, the study places the exploration of the attitudes-behaviours relationship as one of its research aims.

3.3.1 Attitude-Behaviour Relationship: Social-Psychological Approach

In literature, the debate on the extent to which attitudes about a linguistic phenomenon can reflect actual behaviours is ongoing (Pauwels, 2016). While some researchers believed that attitudes identify behaviours, others countered this point. Baker (1992), for example, argued that attitudes can identify how a particular person behaves. At this level he elucidated:

Attitudes are a convenient and efficient way of explaining consistent patterns in behaviour. Attitudes often manage to summarize, explain and predict behaviour. Knowing someone's attitude to alcohol, for example, may sum up likely behaviour in a range of contexts over time

(Baker, 1992, P.11)

In another section, Baker (1992) questioned the validity of this, arguing that speakers may shape their attitudes to be appealing to the audience. In the context of research fieldwork, Bichani (2015) argued that some factors such as the presence of researcher may affect the way participants express their attitudes, and therefore, self-report methods are not enough to explain their behaviours.

In LM/LS research, the social-psychological approach was suggested as an attempt to investigate to what extent minority linguistic groups' attitudes influence their behaviours (Ladegaard, 2000, Pauwels, 2016). So, the adopters of the social-psychological approach believed that the study of attitudes and beliefs (what individuals think) are fundamentals and primordial to investigating behaviours (what they are actually doing).

In modern times, the social-psychological approach was simply defined as "the study of the ways that people interact with and are influenced by others in their lives" (Mateeva and Dimitrov, 2012, p.209). According to Giles, Smith and Robinson (1980, p.2), the main concern is to study "the mediating influence of social-psychological constructs such as attitudes, motivations, identities and intentions in determining language behaviours". Therefore, what people think, can help in making decisions about variations and in interpreting behaviours.

The social-psychological approach is usually deployed in the study of both intergroup and intragroup situations. This study addresses Algerian students' interactions with each other, identified as an "intragroup". Shedding the focus on intragroup dynamics, individuals are "the primary focus of analysis, examining the processes within a person that shape the way he or she behaves in response to others, real or imagined, in group, organizational and social settings" (Mateeva and Dimitrov, 2012, p.209).

In LM/LS, ethnolinguistic vitality theory, that was influenced by the social-psychological approach, holds that depending on the subjective ethnolinguistic vitality of the group, their attitudes influence what languages they use, where and when (Myers-Scotton, 2006). However, this theory is much more useful in exploring LM and LS in intergroup dynamics.

Within the social-psychological approach framework, Ladegaard (2000) admitted the lack of studies which incorporate behavioural aspects beside language attitude in their design. He further argued that even those tiny minority studies which elicited behaviours often used indirect means of measurements such as the matched-guise method and indirect interviews. In exploring the relationship between reported attitudes and behaviours among Danish male and female participants about local varieties and vernaculars, he came into a significant point. While he confirmed that through attitudes one can predict broad behaviours, the relationship between the two elements is still complex to explore, because he could not create a clear significant relationship between both. Actually, Ladegaard's (2000) attempt can be considered as a crucial effort in the study of the attitude-behaviour relationship in the sense of giving more insights to explore the attitude-behaviour relation in terms of methodology.

This thesis similarly made this attempt in reaction to what some researchers emphasised. For example, Othman (2011) alluded to the study of actual behaviours for a more fine-grained analysis of LM/LS. In this regard, he called for a further research on Arabic LM/LS through the analysis of recorded conversational data. The following section discusses further some linguistic behaviours because, in order to facilitate this analysis, it is important to examine the potential markers of LM/LS.

3.4 Language Choice: Micro Choices

The second phase of my field work is designed to capture some naturalistic data regarding code choice (French versus English). For this main reason, the literature of my research includes a consideration of the micro choices that the speakers make and the meanings behind them. By micro choices, I mean the potential linguistic behaviours (markers) that the speakers use to identify their maintenance of a particular language or shift to another. In literature, some researchers such as Clyne (2003) and Mazzaferro (2018b) described code-switching as an important sign preceding LS, and therefore a promoter of it. In practice, Jamai (2008) realised that the Moroccan community in Britain started to shift to English in their utterances, therefore, use Arabic-English code-switching. For him, LS also resulted in a change in the sociolinguistic patterns among this ethnolinguistic community. Consequently, LS to English triggered different patterns of code-switching that might be different from that used before. It could also trigger linguistic growth in terms of adding languages to the pre-

migratory verbal repertoires. Othman (2011, p.233) also emphasised the study of code-switching when he stated: “it should be noted that code-switching is of concern to the study of LM/LS in immigrant contexts and should be taken into consideration in future research”. Both Othman’s and Jamai’s views were supported by Pauwels 2016 “In some ethnicity friendship networks of some migrant and minority groups, there is a considerable amount of conscious code-switching or code-mixing often to denote solidarity or to enhance loyalty to the group(...)” Pauwels (2016, p.93).

3.5.1 Code-switching

The co-occurrence of several languages in one space would result in the appearance of certain types of bilinguals’ speech production such as code-switching. Code-switching is considered as a conventional concept, and that may suggest the deployment of separate languages. In other words, the alternation of languages may imply moving forwards and backwards between different, separate systems (Batyi, 2016). The separate languages are “switched” or “manipulated” according to their context of use (Macswan, 2017). According to Kishe (2017), code-switching occurs at a larger space of conversation, and does not require the interaction of grammatical rules of used languages. Each language is being separately used.

The term code-switching as a micro linguistic behaviour can be applicable to the context of this research in the sense of switching between linguistic resources within one speech conversation. Within the syntactic unit, the code-switcher produces two patterns: the matrix language (the dominant language) and the embedded language (the host or inserted language) (Myers-Scotton, 2002, 2006).

In the present research, AA is set out to be the matrix language. Part of the objectives, however, is to question the nature of the predominant embedded/inserted language (French versus English). The focus is further extended to study the frame within which the use of both languages is structured: sentence level (code-switching) or word level (code-mixing).

3.5.2 Code-mixing as an Influence on Embedded Language Use

Many scholars considered code-switching and mixing as two ends in a continuum. Matras (2009), for example, used them interchangeably. However, it seems that there is a difference

between both. Mabule (2015) defined code-mixing as “expressions in which a mixture of the grammar of one language and another language is used without altering the grammar of the first language used” (p.311). Unlike in code-switching, the interaction occurs between grammatical categories and syntactic rules during the speech event. An example of code-mixing from an Algerian context would be the word “Tarkizaiychen” to mean concentration. The Arabic word “tarkiz” is mixed with some elements of grammar from English “tion” to indicate that it is a noun.

With regards to this micro linguistic behaviour, Arfi (2008), at the practical level, demonstrated at length the level of grammatical interaction between French and Arabic among Algerian immigrants in the USA at the words’ level. The following examples, from Arfi (2008, pp.88–91), explain how French words were used and adjusted to Arabic morphology, syntax and even phonology:

1-(sufra) from **Il a souffert** in the past tense –*he suffered*

2-(remarkithaa) from **Je l'ai remarquée** in the present tense –*I noticed her*

3-kifaach (nexpilihak) from **comment je t'explique**– *how I explain it to you*

The bracketed underlined verbs are French words but conjugated and inserted into an Arabic grammatical frame. In Arfi’s findings, less code-mixing from English was detected, except for two words, huggini and, raytit. Both are English verbs “hug me” and “I wrote”, but the speaker applied the Arabic grammatical rules.

This study is confined to code-switching as the most likely potential behaviour to occur (at sentence level), followed by code-mixing as a sub-behaviour (at word level). Influenced by Kishe’s (2017) conceptualisation of code-switching, I will apply it in this study to mean the use of different systems (Arabic - English- French/ embedded language) within a speech event, without any grammatical interaction between the matrix language (Arabic) and the embedded language (English/French). However, code-mixing will be used in the course of this research to mean switching at the word level, with grammatical interactions. So, it will be used to identify intra-word influences (Kishe, 2017). This project further interrogates which linguistic markers can influence French LM/LS to English. Therefore, code-switching and mixing can be both used as potential linguistic markers to both LM/LS at both sentence and word levels, although hard to determine fully in situations of short-term mobility. The

research extends its focus to discover meanings behind the predominant embedded code choice (French/ English) for more in-depth understanding.

3.5.3 Factors behind Code Choice

3.5.3.1 The Linguistic Domain

It is important to speak about the “linguistic domain” before engaging in discussing code choice factors. Fishman (1971) defined domains as “the institutionally relevant spheres of social interaction in which certain value clusters are behaviourally implemented “(cited in Stoessel, 2002, p.101). Clyne (2003) similarly associated domains with home (family), work, neighbourhood, church and school. Holmes (2013) explained the concept of domain in terms of participants, setting and topics. Arfi (2008) elaborated the concept of domains by including discourses about past/present and home/host situations as part of domains. Recently, social media can be also considered as an important domain of language use. Because living abroad, according to Holmes (2013), would result in a restriction in domains, I tightened the focus more to the friendship domain, especially in observed behaviours. Within the ethno-specific friendship domain, factors behind code choice are set out in this study to answer questions like who is varying (while maintaining or shifting), with whom (Arab/ Berber interlocutors), for which purpose and in which social settings, with regards to the predominant embedded code choice (French/ English).

3.5.3.2 WHO, with WHOM, (WHAT, WHY) and WHERE?

Since the start of the field, the focus of analysing speakers’ choices in multilingual settings was commonly placed on recurring factors related to WHO speaks, with WHOM, WHAT, WHERE, and importantly WHY (Fishman, 2003, Matras, 2009, Coulmas, 2013, Holmes, 2013, Ritchie and Bhatia, 2013, Pauwels, 2016). Ritchie and Bhatia (2013) for example, summarised the key components that the speaker considers in his/her interaction. At this level, they maintained that “(...) based on a number of factors such as with whom (participants: their background and relationships), about what (topic content), when and where a speech act occurs, bilinguals make their language choice “ (Ritchie and Bhatia, 2013, p.378).

I. Speaker and his background

The speaker and his/her backgrounds is viewed as an important factor, largely influencing language choice. Fishman (2003) highlighted who speaks as the first element to account for in analysing language use in multilingual settings, a common notice in Clyne (2003) and Pauwels (2016). Under this factor, informants' backgrounds such as attitudes, proficiency and pre-migratory experience can play a significant role to either support minority LM or hinders it.

II. Interlocutor

The person whom the speaker interacts with is regarded as an important factor accounting for participants' behaviours and their choice on whether to use a particular language or shift to another. In the existing studies, Holmes (2013) and Ritchie and Bathia (2013) emphasised the relationship and social distance between participants and their roles in code choices. The social distance can create solidarity between ethnolinguistic speakers. In a closer focus, Gardner-Chloros (1991), in investigating language choice between French and Alsatian among French nationals in Strasbourg, found out that the switching occurring between both codes is constrained by the identity of interlocutors and relationship between them (as cited in Matras, 2009, p.115). In an Arabic context, according to Dweik, Nofal and Qawasmeh (2014), Arabic was perceived as mostly used among the majority of Muslim Arabs in Vancouver when they interact with their colleagues, bosses and Arabic customers in the workplace. Othman (2011) interestingly found out that Arab community members and their children in Manchester tend to use Arabic and English depending on the type of audience, as to whether it is an intragroup audience or an intergroup one.

III. Topic and function

The topic of discussion was commonly agreed on as a significant component among factors influencing code choice for researchers such as Matras (2009) and Holmes (2013). Lawson and Sachdev (2004) significantly found out that language use among Sylheti-Bangladeshi speakers in London varies with the topic of conversation. Accordingly, English was used with topics related to media, social affairs and schools, while Bengali was used in family and household related topics (p. 54). Bichani (2015) made an important point regarding language

use among Arab communities in the UK. Arab children at home use Arabic-English code-switching when they speak about school issues according to self-reported language use. Arfi (2008, 2014) found out that Algerian immigrants in the USA mix between the three languages, specifically using their community languages (Derja and/or French) to speak about past situations and mix between and code-switch with English to express their present experiences (Arfi, 2014). Past situation entails the participants' pre-migratory experience in homeland (Algeria), while present situation is related to the current experience as Algerian American nationals.

Ritchie and Bhatia (2013) placed message-intrinsic factors as linguistic and pragmatic considerations in code alternation. By message intrinsic, it implies some discourse functions. At the linguistic level, code choice occurs either to produce direct or reported quotation, reiteration (paraphrasing either using a literal equivalence of the other language or explaining it differently), message qualification, topic comment or interjection. Holmes (2013) considered function of the interaction among the key dimensions of sociolinguistic analysis. For Holmes (2013, p.449), two functions can be as useful dimensions of analysis and obviously affect the linguistic forms of language: referential and affective (social). To explain more, some types of information are high in content and this can trigger a referential meaning. For example, sport commentaries. Social interactions, however, such as friendly gossips can hold an affective meaning. Bichani (2015), as an instance, found out (according to perceptions) that one of her participants switches from Arabic to English when she comments on her children's behaviours to make them understand fully. This may imply being serious in so doing.

IV. Setting and dimensions of formality

Fishman (2003) and Holmes (2013) classified the social context of interaction as an important factor that can impinge on language choice, and therefore an important element to consider in sociolinguistic analysis. Clyne (2003), in a closer context, highlighted the physical setting as a powerful indicator in LS. To illustrate this point in practice, Gardner-Chloros (1991) study highlighted the formality of the setting as a powerful element influencing code-switching between French and Alsatian in Strasbourg.

This chapter highlighted the theoretical lenses that identified the theoretical influences of the study under research. While LM/LS were set out as the main variables informing this research, the discussion around these two key concepts created other threads of discussions. These choices were based on an already chosen sample, given the current state of what is known and needs to be known about LM/LS. Up to this point, what is noteworthy is the specific application of LM/LS in the present study: applying the two concepts on a colonial linguistic resource within globalised communicative practices, and importantly among a specific group as a result of a specific pattern of migratory processes (short-term mobility) are the main elements that would differentiate this study in terms of originality. Indeed, globalisation, despite posing some challenges to traditional LM/LS, is making the field so special to explore. The next chapter will discuss the methodology of this study as a bridge to the analysis of findings.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESEARCH METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

This chapter is a gateway to the core of this thesis. After developing an analytical overview of the significant literature, I shall move to discuss and outline how exploring French LM/LS to English will be approached. Following a structure based on Wilson's (2014) honeycomb model of research methodology, this section presents a thorough description and justification of the methodology, defends the study design, and describes the fieldwork in practice. Each justified tool is followed by an acknowledgement of its points of strength, main challenges, and how this research aimed to overcome the latter. Subsequently, it highlights the main ethical considerations that surround the project, and importantly explains how the study was designed to achieve validity and reliability. In the second part, the pilot study phase is described, and its role outlined in improving the reliability of the methods.

4.1 Research Aims and Questions

In investigating FL use among Algerian international students in the UK, I developed a twofold research aim, which covers both expressed perceptions and observed behaviours. As a macro-focus, the study aims at conducting a sociolinguistic comparison of the verbal repertoires of this chosen cohort, targeting pre-mobility experiences and current ones. Addressing both pre-mobility experience and current one is an important component in understanding LM/LS from the new perspectives: "The incorporation of the 'transit' experiences and of pre migration attitudes can allow researchers to assess both the impact of past and present experience in the linguistic behaviour and attitudes of members of different communities" (Tawalbeh, 2019, p.36). Not only this, but pre-mobility/ migration experience can also enhance our understanding in forecasting the future behaviours of individuals in question (Tawalbeh, 2019).

The focus of exploration is more restricted to changes in FL use at the level of repertoire. After identifying the perceived sociolinguistic stance of participants on whether they conceive themselves as "maintainers of FL", or "shiffters to EL" (considering both traditional and new perspectives in LM/LS), the research further aims at identifying the different factors that inform their reported sociolinguistic stance. The main objective herein is to highlight what is new regarding this type of sojourn within globalised mobility.

The second research aim seeks to compare and contrast previous expressed perceptions with observed actual behaviours. It is further set out - within the boundaries of spoken data - to:

- Draw potential markers of French LM/LS to English identified in the observed behaviours.
- Identify the factors influencing the predominant embedded code choice (French/English).

To fully understand the research aims, the present thesis addresses the following research questions as steppingstones:

- i. What retrospective reflections about their pre-mobility experience with FL do Algerian PhD students hold?

Through analysing the participants' reported views, this research question seeks to identify their perceptions of FL and its use before mobility. The pre-mobility experience comprises the following elements:

- ✓ The set of beliefs and linguistic ideologies underneath FL among this specific sample population, the perceived social status (prestigious, colonial, historical...etc) and perceived functionality.
- ✓ Its status at the level of participants' verbal repertoires in terms of use (vis-a-vis English) and estimated frequency of use.
- ✓ The dimensions of use, across different linguistic domains, especially in the friendship domain (among Algerian EFL students).

- ii. How do these individuals view the effect of their transition to the UK on their use of and attitudes towards French?

The second research question focuses exactly on the linguistic change. It seeks the perceived outcomes of students' transition on FL. Concerning attitudes, for example, Latham Keh and Stoessel (2017, p.13), in addressing individuals' linguistic repertoires concurred that their attitudes and efforts "may fluctuate through life as they experience new circumstances". Accordingly, this research question is primarily framed to investigate to what extent participants' attitudes towards French and its use can be changed over time and space (as a

result of their short stay in the UK). A further question may assist in explaining the focus of this umbrella research question:

- ✓ How do participants interpret their sociolinguistic stances as a result of their transition (maintainers of FL/ shifters to English)?

iii. What are the perceived push and pull factors/aspirations contributing to LM/LS?

By addressing this question, the main objective is to highlight the factors which promote the continuing use of FL as a predominant embedded language after Arabic, and the factors that militate against it (LS). A further sub-question is therefore:

- ✓ For this participant group, what do globalisation and the specific form of their mobility add to previous explanatory factors in relation to French LM/LS to English?

iv. How are the participants' previous expressed perceptions presented in practice?

The second phase of the fieldwork was set out to get observational data based on the observed behaviours of participants. The main concern of this research question is to track their performance in order to compare expressed perceptions with actual behaviours. In literature, Pauwels (2016) highlighted the potential of this exploration in LM/LS. As part of this project, focus group sessions, followed by observations were used to explore this link after self-reporting methods.

v. What are the linguistic markers among the participants suggesting potential French LM/LS to English?

In the second section of the previous chapter, I elucidated some potential linguistic behaviours that may affect French LM/LS to English at the micro level. For more in depth analysis, this research question targets the potential linguistic markers by which both practices can be mostly suggested, especially in this context: short-term mobility. The focus goes further to analyse the factors underpinning the predominant embedded code choice (on whether it is French or English):

- ✓ What are the factors underpinning the predominant embedded code choice (French/ English)?

4.2 The Honeycomb Model

The research methodology of this research is framed around and guided by Wilson's (2014) "Honeycomb model". By so doing, it is hoped that it would be more effectively arranged, organised and systematic. The honeycomb model consists of six interwoven outer elements that describe the research methodology of the research inquiry and makes all the elements interconnected (see **Figure 4.1**) (See **Appendix 4** for the original design). Among these components, research philosophy, approach and strategy are viewed as highlighted, and therefore have the primacy of consideration. Because this model is open to flexibility, research philosophy, research design, data collection and analysis are highlighted in my research.

According to Wilson (2014), the model can follow a set of structures, without being strictly adhered to a linear fashion, unlike the other models such as Saunders et al (2006) Onion model, whose fundamentals are demonstrated as either "a linear-type diagram, or a series of layers" (p.7). Although following a typical numbered set of structures, the model resists a "phases and stages" ideology. So, it is more flexible to adapt to different research contexts. The Honeycomb model was firstly introduced in a business research project. However, its elements can be still potentially applied in other social research such as sociolinguistics because of the power of flexibility dictated by these social fields and their dynamics. In what follows, the discussion around the research methodology is respectively informed by the Honeycomb model components and its principles.

Figure 4. 1: The Honeycomb model according to Wilson (2014)

4.2.1 Philosophical Underpinnings: Social Constructivism

This study is more aligned with social constructivism's philosophical worldview, and therefore conducted through a social constructivist lens. According to Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018):

Social constructivism holds that individuals seek to make meaning of their social lives and that the researcher has to examine the situation through the multiple lenses of the individuals involved, to obtain their definition of the situation, to see how they make sense of their situation and to focus on interactions, contexts, environments and biographies

(Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p.23)

This research takes a social constructivist stance because it believes that reality is socially constructed. It underlines the role of context in the construction and development of participants' social experiences. So, the specific context in which such individuals reside is highlighted, trying to match between the cultural setting and the issue being studied. Social constructivist researchers give a great emphasis to interaction among individuals in the belief that individuals' subjective meanings are constructed and developed as they interact with one another (reality is socially constructed) (Robson and McCartan, 2016). In terms of data, the study sought to investigate participants' experiences with FL, relying on different sources of data that I will identify later. The combination between studying the participants' expressed

perceptions and their observed behaviours is a significant match that supports my conceptualisation of the researched phenomenon. This approach is viewed as equated with interpretivist in the sense that they both focus on how the social world is interpreted and perceived by participants (Robson and McCartan, 2016).

It is argued that research in general and choice of research methods - in particular - are either implicitly or explicitly the outcome of some ontological and epistemological questions (Gray, 2013). Taking a social constructivist ontology and epistemology stance assisted to a large extent in the interpretation of participants' experiences based on the social world, rather than as separate existence. The main concern of ontologists is "how we think the world is" (Wilson, 2014, p.11), which entails one's beliefs on the fundamental nature of reality (Hammond and Wellington, 2013). So, the focus of ontologists is on the essence of reality.

While ontology is what we believe exists, epistemology is viewed as how we understand it. It is that which "provides a philosophical background for deciding what kinds of knowledge are legitimate and adequate" (Gray, 2013, p.19).

From an ontological standpoint, social constructivist researchers view reality "as it appears subjectively or more commonly negotiated within groups" (Hammond and Wellington, 2013, p.114). They view that there are multiple socially-constructed realities (Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2009). In this vein, the ontological beliefs that underpin this research inquiry is that reality is viewed as subjectively constructed, and therefore, there are multiple socially constructed realities. With this standpoint in mind, the participants' attitudes and linguistic resources are not stable, but can be reshaped and reconstructed as they move from one setting to another. Epistemologically, the constructivist approach is premised upon the belief that the research and researcher are interdependent and inseparable (Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2009). Therefore, the researcher is implicated in the research project, and plays a vital role in the interpretation of participants' perceptions as well as their linguistic behaviours, rather than being fully "objective". Both aspects are crucial points in the constructivist approach.

However, one should admit that social constructivism is subject to many critiques amongst positivists and post-positivists. Social constructivists were criticised that they overlook the

hope that researchers can draw generalisations from behaviours, and therefore abandon the power of scientific procedures (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). This research is aimed at achieving more transferability than making generalisations. In other words, it may be that the findings are transferable to similar groups, instead of being generalised over a larger population. In the subsequent sections, my attempt to overcome such limits is highlighted, bearing in mind sensitivities in social constructivism such as researcher bias.

4.2.2 Research Design: A Mini-ethnographic Case Study Methodology

From a range of methodologies, this study can be more fitted into case study research. While arriving at a single definition of a case study is hard, Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) defined it as that type of research which consists of an in-depth understanding of a particular case within its specific context. It is viewed that case study should be identified as tightly bounded, either in time or space (geographical location). Echoing this definition on this study, the investigation covers an in-depth, holistic understanding of the linguistic practices of a group of Algerian mobile students who moved to the UK in a specific span of time, estimated no more than three years by the time of research fieldwork. Thereby, the targeted researched population has specific time and space circumstances.

In its nature, case study permits the eclectic use of different methods: “methodologically eclectic” (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p.385). The research employed a range of methods in data collection (semi-structured interview, web-based questionnaire, focus group sessions that had observation elements, followed by participant observation of ‘naturally’ occurring interaction), data types (qualitative and some quantitative), and approaches of analysis (thematic analysis, descriptive analysis as well as elements of discourse analysis). From different types of case study design, this research can be described as a mini-ethnographic case study due to its nature, which bands together different elements from ethnography and case study. One cannot deny that striking elements of ethnography are implemented in the present research such as the nature of fieldwork, the researcher’s role and the insider status allocated to her in the community which triggers her own immersion within the community in order to get stronger findings, and importantly the different contexts (locales) where data collection took place. Ethnography is viewed as an approach *par excellence* to get a well-grounded view in the study of the linguistic practices among members

of a particular community: their beliefs about language and the linguistic codes used (Meyerhoff, Schlee and MacKenzie, 2015).

Mini-ethnographic case study is defined by Fusch, Fusch and Ness (2017) as that which mitigates the weaknesses of both ethnography and case study, if detachedly applied. In ethnography, as an instance, the fieldwork demands a prolonged period of time. In other words, the researcher may take years to become immersed and enmeshed in the culture and social activities of participants. Due to the field nature, ethnography can take a very long period of time in sociolinguistic research (Meyerhoff, Schlee and Mackenzie, 2015). This might not meet the needs of all types of sociolinguistic research. However, mini-ethnographic research can be conducted in far less in time than ethnography (a week or a month of time) (Storesund and McMurray, 2009, Fusch, Fusch and Ness, 2017) and used when the research inquiry has a narrowed focus (Fusch, Fusch and Ness, 2017). Because the fieldwork in mini-ethnography is limited and bounded by time and space, one could incorporate it with case study design (Fusch, Fusch and Ness, 2017). Despite condensing the time required in any ethnographic research, this research considered some elements of ethnography such as writing some extensive notes about a series of interactions with the participant groups, taking field notes during data collection and writing some memos after interviewing every single participant and at the end of every session for later reflection. All these elements helped in the interpretation of findings.

Mini-ethnographic case study is viewed by Fusch, Fusch and Ness (2017) as one which incorporates both ethnography and case study in one research protocol and gets a blended design. In terms of gains, they state “One has the benefit of an ethnographic approach that is bounded within a case study protocol that is more feasible for a student researcher with limited time and finances” (Fusch, Fusch and Ness, 2017, p.927). Thus, mini-ethnography case study methodology was followed to answer the research questions, with the implementation of multiple methods and ethnographic elements.

4.2.3 Research Approach (Inductive) and Strategy (Qualitative)

This research is more inductive in nature. The aim is not to test a theory; the meaning is inductively constructed from data to develop a theory instead (Wilson, 2014). Inductive

research matches social constructivist principles, and is viewed as best fitting the qualitative paradigm (Brannen, 2005, Creswell, 2015, Robson and McCartan, 2016). For Brannen (2005), qualitative researchers typically locate themselves within interpretivist/constructivist philosophies. Thereby, an inductive approach underpins more the way this research project is approached. To be critical about this point, constructivist research can be also theory driven, particularly in theories of power.

4.2.4 Instruments for Data Collection

4.2.4.1 Mixed Method Design

In the realm of research, any project requires a wise pick of the data-gathering tools that will be brought to bear during the research process. Primarily, the field of research has recently shifted from the traditional view of “one best method” towards the idea of plurality of methods and theories (Phillips and Hardy, 2002). It could be that researchers can get more insights and stronger research findings by the application of different methods and approaches. As mentioned in the previous section, in case study methodology, using different sources of data is of a primacy to gain a more holistic understanding. Given the focus of my research, the nature of the chosen research questions requires a practical selection of research approaches. Thus, it is based on a multi-faceted methodology. I have chosen the use of a variety of complementary research techniques to find answers to the questions that can be portrayed as intricate and sensitive. What makes them complex is that their nature ranges between seeking perceptions and observing actual behaviours. In support of this, Rebekha, Gass and Mackey (2014) maintained that multiple methods is increasingly becoming an alternative for investigating complex research questions.

In sociolinguistics, methodologies have experienced a striking evolution over the course of their history. Currently, mixing qualitative and quantitative approaches has newly risen to prominence and awareness (Hernández-Campoy, 2014). This project ranges between qualitative and quantitative methods in consonance with these trends in approaching sociolinguistics studies. In details, further justifications of the research approach will be thoroughly explained in the following section. Although my research introduced some quantitative elements, still it belongs to the qualitative paradigm.

To analyse the complexity of linguistic resources used in the diaspora, Blommaert (2014) emphasised the need for developing a privileged set of instruments tailor-made to language change *per se*. In this respect, he articulated “we need methods that enable us to focus on change itself, on how and why sociolinguistic environments do not stay the same over time and in different conditions” (Blommaert, 2014, pp.14–15). The agenda of the methodology is made up of a triangular set of instruments for investigating the complexity of participants’ maintenance of FL and LS to English. I applied a methodology that can be described as multi-faceted and sequential, in an effort to monitor the changes that occurred regarding attitudes and use of that language with participants’ transition. In conjunction with Blommaert’s call, it could then add some contributions at the methodological level, mainly useful in approaching the complexity of language use within mobility.

This study is influenced by Creswell’s (2015) mixed methods exploratory sequential design (qualitative-quantitative) (See **Figure 4.2**). In addition to a qualitative/ quantitative format, it has incorporated other qualitative methods after the quantitative phase in a sequential manner. The qualitative and quantitative elements are not equally applied. In other words, the research is qualitative in nature, with the incorporation of some quantitative elements. While qualitative data plays a major role in my research, some quantitative elements with statistical frequencies and database (through a web-based questionnaire) were employed. The reason for incorporation of quantitative elements is to access a wider population and to broaden rather than deepen my understanding of the topic. In practice, the questionnaire helped to verify that the range of experiences and attitudes of the sample of interviews more closely were representative of students more widely. According to Creswell (2015), covering a large population would add value to research.

Therefore, my research was structured with the design, below, which is based on combining respectively different tools in a sequential manner with due regard for analysing the specific nature of the research questions as being complex. Findings were compared and contrasted across stages of research.

Figure 4. 2: Exploratory Sequential Design (Drawn from Creswell's (2015) mixed methods designs)

The sequence followed (see **Figure 4.2**) allowed each stage to build on the next stage, unlike the concurrent design where the whole data collection occurs at once (Creswell, 2015). In other words, it would not be possible for researchers to reflect the outcomes of one method upon the other.

4.2.4.1.1 Semi-structured Interview

In the first place, the semi-structured interview was employed as the first research tool in order to capture the voices of participants about their perceived language use. This research tool was specifically set out to explore the participants' self-reports about FL use, their pre-mobility experience with French, and how residing abroad affected their perceptions and use of it. Across a wide range of research disciplines, interviewing is worth utilising in research as a valuable strategy, because it builds a direct connection with the participants themselves (Robson, 2002). The choice of this potent method is also supported in previous research in the sense of generating a rich data and getting deeply into participants' views and, therefore, grasping firmly the phenomenon (DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006, Bloomberg and Volpe, 2012).

As a cross-disciplinary tool, interviews have been used in diverse fields either as a primary source of data or in combination with other methods; either as an opening medium or as a

follow-up method (DeFina and Perrino, 2011). In this research, it was used as an opening medium, followed up with web-based questionnaires, focus group and observation sessions. Out of a logical choice, this instrument was placed first for the purpose of informing the design of the subsequent tool. The use of interviews is illustrated as appropriate in exploring issues before a quantitative study takes place. Not only do interviews function as exploratory devices for the subsequent stage, they can further set out the background of participants involved in the focus group discussion (Robson, 2002).

From different types of interviews, the study employed a semi-structured type of interview. The semi-structured interview implies the non-strict adherence to a set of questions. In addition to the adoption of a specific guide which embraces a set of open-ended questions, the researcher can improvise supplementary questions as appropriate, based on the answers of participants (Richards and Morse, 2013). Hence, this type of interviewing highly values the unexpected questions and answers of the participants that can emerge from the dialogue between the interviewer and interviewee (DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006, Richards and Morse, 2013). To explain further, the semi-structured interviewer should be ready to be flexible in sequencing the questions and in the amount of time scheduled for different topics (Robson and McCartan, 2016).

Pauwels (2016) provided some insights on how interviews in LM/LS studies can be deployed. As a means beyond surveys, they are used in sociolinguistics to explore the dimensions of language use patterns. Unlike questionnaires, Pauwels (2016) noted that interviews are characterised by the use of open-ended questions, with more flexibility. On this matter, she articulated:

Open-ended questions tend to dominate in these interviews, allowing participants to freely report their language patterns and practices, to provide a personal narrative about their language experiences and history and to express attitudes and opinion about language matters without being constrained by interviewer-imposed formulations

Pauwels (2016, p.66)

In exploring the processes of sociolinguistic structuration within the Portuguese-Canadian community of Toronto and to study people's ideologies of language and identity, Silva (2011) applied semi-structured interview drawing primarily from six second-generation Portuguese-Canadians and members of their social networks. The main rationale underneath the choice

of this research tool is that semi-structured interviews tend to represent spontaneous interactions, with the use of flexible questions (Silva, 2011). One point to reinforce Robson and McCartan's (2016) claim about the flexibility of questions is what Silva (2011) discussed "Semi-structured interviews also provide the researcher with the flexibility to cater the questions to the specific experiences of the interviewee, by spending more or less time on certain topics" (p.34).

The time scheduled for the overall interview should not take many hours, and should not be less than half an hour (DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006). With regard to the time allocated for interviewing the six key participants, Silva's interviews lasted approximately an hour of time and 30 minutes for each participant. This could be itself a critical component, because the ideal semi-structured interview should take more than 30 minutes and ideally would not likely exceed an hour of time to avoid participants' fatigue as previously stated. In this research, with the informed consent of participants being gained, the interviews typically ran twenty to forty minutes, and were audio-recorded. Silva's interview guidelines revealed that the questions ranged between sociolinguistic history, experience of language use and thoughts on the future, followed by various probes. Silva (2011) implemented this tool as a secondary source of data to further follow the participants' trajectories. In my research, semi-structured interviews were conducted as an opening tool. One of the aims driving this choice is to set up the backgrounds of the participants who are taking part in focus group discussion and to get insights about their self-perceived linguistic behaviour (6 participants).

Semi-structured interviews in sociolinguistics research are, more often than not, central in the research design. As opposed to this, this research project used this method as an initial source of data followed by two other quantitative and qualitative instruments. As has been seen, semi-structured interviews can be used in a number of ways but to fulfil some common aims: that is, getting deeply inside the informants' experiences, and thereby, amassing stronger findings.

In practice, semi-structured interviews were conducted over the course of one week among the six participants. I was keenly aware from the onset that informants are comfortable in their natural surroundings rather than a controlled setting. Accordingly, interviews took place in student accommodation and the university, two spots where Algerian PhD students usually

spend their time in. The time of each interview depended on how participants viewed themselves as maintainers or shifters, but generally it took less than forty-five (45) minutes each. Questions did not follow on exactly in the way outlined on the schedule. However, additional questions were further asked. Interviews were afterwards manually transcribed for the purpose of gaining themes that could inform the design of the subsequent data collection tools.

Advocators of semi-structured interviews put forwards some advantages that motivate researchers to implement this type of research interviews. As a novice researcher, what really motivated me to use semi-structured interviews is the flexibility which is afforded by this sort of interview (Robson, 2002, Robson and McCartan, 2016). In fact, it is a point of strength, since the researcher is aware of getting what he wants through his occasional intervention rather than being restricted by prescribed guidelines. This point is overlooked in quantitative and even in some qualitative data-gathering tools.

One more point to evidence the positive points of semi-structured interview is the interactive power that this type of interview possesses. This conversational power would trigger participants' interest and lessen their lack of interest. However, the application of semi-structured interviews would pose some challenges. In my research, these drawbacks were carefully taken into consideration, trying wisely to mitigate them.

Commentators on semi-structured interviews have put forwards certain disadvantages as alerts to novice researchers utilising this type of interviews. In sociolinguistic research, Meyerhoff, Schlee and MacKenzie (2015) classified interviews as a direct method in studying people's perceptions and attitudes. While emphasising the fact that asking people directly might be an easy way to access their perceptions, data based on this approach might be less reliable. For them "people aren't always good sources of direct information on their attitudes. They may fudge (or even lie) if they think their answer might be interpreted negatively, or they may lack the necessary degree of introspection to answer your questions well" (p.82). On this matter, the semi-structured interview in this research included further indirect questions from the participants about their peer friends (See Interview Schedule in **Appendix 5** for details).

In general, although it has been widely cited that qualitative interviews are a powerful implement for the researcher, one point of opposition is that they are expensive in time (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). In recognising this problem, semi-structured interviews in this research project, were directed to a small sample (6 participants). Therefore, interviews with such a number of participants is time worthy. Another issue is related to the limited time between the question and answer which could result in the participants' obstruction and perplexity. However, it could be viewed as advantageous since these quick answers can be regarded as spontaneous communication.

Due to the flexibility demanded in this sort of interview, the researcher- more often than not - is required to have some considerable skills of professionalism and experience (Robson, 2011). Without these skills, the interviewer cannot follow up and proceed with questions in cases where s/he did not reach the point s/he wants. So, the use of this type of interviews should be underlined by the researcher's knowledge of the topic (Richards and Morse, 2013).

Furthermore, the semi-structured interview is characterised by lack of standardisation, and this can lead to less reliability (Robson, 2011). The lack of standardisation may lead to the unconscious missing of some questions. It could be, therefore, of significance to stress the roles of probing questions. In my research, the semi-structured interview was piloted, and so, therefore, several probes and different sub-probes that may arise during conducting the interview, were considered. In practice, however, my experience as an interviewer proved that the success of semi-structured interviews greatly depends on the researcher's skill and expertise to fit in a dual role: an interview designer and a conversation prompter.

4.2.4.1.2 Web-based Questionnaire

In the second place, data was further sought by means of online questionnaires as a way of contextualising interview data within a larger population. I updated and edited the database of the web-based questionnaire according to the findings gathered through the semi-structured interview. The use of this method essentially reacted to one limitation of interviews use; the limited number of participants interviewed may lead to less reliable findings. By doing this, it was aiming at achieving more reliability. Questionnaires have been widely used as a useful tool for collecting survey data (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018).

Robson (2011) asserted that questionnaires can be both used as a primary and a secondary tool.

Questionnaires can yield structured data (Gillham, 2008). Being structured denotes that the researcher arranges the list of questions, and the answers he aims at finding are anticipated. Because all the questions and answers “patterns are determined beforehand, discovery is lessened” (Gillham, 2008, p.2). In this research, the questionnaire functioned as a means to broaden my understanding and to get complementary secondary data. It was also web-based to access a broader population. QuestionPro was used as a useful software to deliver it. The whole number of responses (n=32) were gained in a period of ten days.

In this research, participants are spread all over the UK, and the time-span for data collection was not sufficient for either making visits, or gathering the participants in one setting. Brace (2008) cited the main approaches of Bradley (1999) on how to deliver the questionnaire through the internet. According to him, six online ways can be used:

- Open web: this website is open for anyone who visits it
- Closed web: this website invites the participants to complete the questionnaire
- Hidden web: the questionnaire appears for visitors only when triggered by some mechanism such as a date, a particular interest in a specific page or visitor number
- E-mail URL embedded: the respondents are invited to the web by e-mails to the survey site, then the e-mail contains a URL or web address on which respondents click and access the questionnaire.
- Simple email: participants are sent an email that contain the questionnaire
- E-mail attachment: the questionnaire is sent as an attachment to an email

(Brace, 2008, p.30)

In this project, the questionnaire was restricted at this point to E-mail URL embedded, as it seems a more academic way of delivery than other networking platforms through which Algerian students in the UK maintain connectedness with each other (such as Facebook, Messenger, Skype and WhatsApp).

Sociolinguists who implemented questionnaires in their fieldwork seemed to have a common aim: exploring the participants’ attitudes and perceptions regarding a particular linguistic

practice. What is also noteworthy is that some researchers use survey questionnaires as a focal means of inquiry, while others use it as a secondary tool. In other studies, questionnaires function as a comparative tool. As an example of this, Jamai (2008) carried out a cross-national comparative research of language use among Moroccans in Morocco and United Kingdom. Questionnaires were similarly used in the two different socio-cultural settings.

Questionnaires can be set up as a supplementary research material as referred to by Robson (2011). For example, Bortolato (2012) implemented questionnaire in her fieldwork for the purpose of setting the sociolinguistic backgrounds of the participants. In this regard, the questionnaire was distributed to discuss particular linguistic habits and attitudes among the Venetian-Italian community in Anglophone Canada. One more example, where questionnaires were used to support the field work alongside other methods, is the study of Hamid (2005), in studying LM/LS in the Sylheti community in Leeds. Hamid's study encouraged me to adopt the questionnaire method, because it has a similar function in my study.

One more point to consider is that the questionnaire can be devised in two languages: the community language and the one of the host countries. In this research, potential participants have the same educational profile as doctoral postgraduates, with an EL ability being expected to be high in the 4 skills. Consequently, the web-based questionnaire was designed in EL in which participants were not expected to have issues with comprehension.

This method of data collection has been widely used in the field of LM/LS to investigate various forms of social behaviour and practices (Pauwels, 2016). Pauwels (2016) elucidated some key concerns of questionnaires in LM/LS. The main ones are seeking sociodemographic information (including sex, age, education and occupation), linguistic history and how individuals use their language in various contexts. In my project, questions were devised in a funnel fashion: from general to specific, starting from very general background to those related to the research focal point. The questionnaire comprised three distinct sections that can investigate language use patterns (see the questionnaire sample in **Appendix 6**). Even though, not all questions had to be answered by everyone and participants can skip a question/s if not relevant to their previous answers. This framed design is based on Pauwels

(2016). My project is influenced by that to keep within the boundaries of the field and reinforce its methodological design.

Personal profile	Participants' sociodemographic information
Linguistic history	Perceived language-use patterns before mobility and currently
Current language use	Reported FL use in the UK

Table 4. 1: Web-based questionnaire structure

Methodology designers set up some powerful criteria for the use of questionnaires that can appreciably encourage researchers across disciplines to adopt this research tool, whether they are web-based or paper questionnaires (Brace, 2008). They further demonstrated some weaknesses. The major weaknesses that can accrue from using questionnaires in this research is that answers obtained from questionnaires can be very limited in nature and no space for following up details and expression can be yielded, and therefore spontaneous responses might not be allowed (Kumar, 2014). Moreover, survey questionnaires, especially online ones, may pose the absence of the fieldworker's guidance and intervention in case the informants require that. In this framework, Chelliah (2013, p.60) maintained "The fieldworker cannot expect speakers to directly answer questions from a questionnaire, since in most cases the speaker will not be familiar with linguistic terminology". In this research, the participants were EFL students before, and had been equally exposed to the basic language sciences in their bachelor's degree as well as those who got a Master exclusively in linguistics and language sciences. Therefore, this point has less impact in this research.

In sociolinguistics research, methodology designers placed this data-gathering tool among the primary fieldwork methods (Hernández-Campoy, 2014). However, questionnaires were viewed as not well suited in carrying out exploratory research (Robson, 2002). As for data itself, a qualitative method was developed further in which the potential participants were given a larger space for expression and a chance to interact with one another in the focus

group/ observation sessions. This interaction was meant to elicit observed data (actual behaviours).

Questionnaires can be subject to self-selecting bias, which means that researchers may not receive response from all participants. Being so may imply that not all participants have attitudes and motivation to contributing to research (Kumar, 2014). This would make the findings less representative of a total population; mainly if the response rate is low. In my case, the web-based questionnaire was preceded by an-email in which participants were given a chance to either confirm their agreement or rejection to complete it.

4.2.4.1.5 Focus Group Discussions: Natural Group

Although this research implemented the questionnaire method to supplement the semi-structured interview, the likely failure of quantitative research in providing further explanations is one of the issues that stirred up my interest to have a further qualitative instrument. As an actual behaviour eliciting method, the research further employed focus group sessions. The sessions included intragroup interactions of an Algerian ethnolinguistic group of six students (as opposed to inter-group).

Focus group sessions were conducted as the third enquiry technique of this research project to put the participants into a real linguistic practice of FL, moving from reported behaviours to observed ones. As a crucial research instrument, it was aimed at capturing actual speech data among the selected cohort about FL use that may not be absolutely gained through a mere self-report. The participants were left to freely interact, introducing the topics of discussion in AA. The aim was to investigate the codes that they alternate with beside the use of Arabic. In practice, participants were deploying different resources from their verbal repertoires, where Dialectal Arabic (AA) was the base language.

Focus group research simply implies the organisation of a group discussion to draw insights upon participants' views of a particular issue, and how their interaction influences each other in their processing of thoughts and discussion (Hennink, 2014). Focus group sessions can be flexibly employed, as Hennink (2014, p.35) explains: "There is no definitive correct way to conduct focus group research. Each study is shaped by the specific research questions, theoretical framework, study context, and characteristics of the study participants". Focus

groups can be described as “natural”, rather than constructed. Natural focus groups entail that participants are pre-existing social groups. In other words, they know each other before, such as friends, neighbours, classmates, as opposed to constructed groups (they did not meet before) (Leask, Hawe and Chapman, 2001). Participants in my research have met before and can be identified as an Algerian ethnolinguistic friendship group, hence, likely qualified as a natural group.

In my research, the focus was to shed light on how the group members naturally discuss issues as part of their daily life activities in a variety of social settings (dinner gathering in accommodation, in campus and off-campus). The group members were invited to debate various pre-set topics that were already suggested by them in interviews. These were categorised according to commonality of their interest, British/current context related, and Algerian-context related ones. However, the focus of my research was not only based on the discussion around the pre-set topics. During the analysis, I also considered other topics that participants naturally produced within the focus group sessions. One reason for this is that individuals tend to produce a wider range of speech genres in their daily life activities more than being in an interview setting (Schilling, 2014), and that was taken into account.

Different views have been put forward regarding focus group composition and each proposed a given number, but all agreed on the point that they should be restricted in size (Robson, 2011). Hennink (2014) ideally suggested that it ought to range between six to eight participants and my research is no exception to this rule. In conjunction with one of my research aims that I stated previously, mainly comparing between self-reported behaviours and observed ones, the focus group involved the six participants who already participated in the semi-structured interview. Among the premises of using six participants rather than more, is that by doing so, the discussion would be easily moderated, and participants’ interaction can be more controlled. In the long run, in analysing data, I shed light on each individual’s reported and actual behaviour and constructed a match between both elements. To collect focus group data, a recording device was used in the three social settings.

Over the course of history, this purely qualitative technique is increasingly gaining momentum among researchers across multiple disciplines, who seem ever more to appreciate the advantageous use of it (Hennink, 2014). This research method seems to be less prominently

implemented in the sociolinguistics field of inquiry but is usually used to elicit perceptions and opinions of a particular ethnolinguistic community about their minority languages practices. Silva (2009) implemented interviews excerpted from focus group meetings. Arfi (2008), in like manner, used this research strategy to back up the primary tool for data elicitation. As a supplementary research instrument, Arfi recruited one focus group consisting of seven women in a public park to record their language use. The topics of interviews were about family history and other semi-structured questions around language use. Noticeably, Arfi did not restrict the language of the focus group sessions to one language, but rather allowed for multilingual use. On this matter, the focus was dual: getting insights about their language use and observing their actual behaviours in tandem. This further drew my attention to a couple of issues: the sample size and the context choice where the focus group takes place.

Since the focus is on language choice among Algerian students as ethnolinguistic friendship groups, then the fieldwork took place in friendship-related settings. After considering the responses gained from both questionnaires and interviews, I could devise some topics for focus group sessions that were run in dialectal Arabic. Actually, these topics were previously mentioned by participants, during their exemplification regarding French/English use contexts. I organised three sessions for one focus group in three milieus. The first one took place in the campus PhD office where the participants usually study. The second session occurred in the student accommodation where the six participants live. Finally, the same participants were gathered again for dinner in one of restaurants in Glasgow - "World Buffet". The average time devoted for each session was 60 minutes. In actual sessions, more time was devoted, because the first discussion in each session was considered as a pilot study (See Pilot Study Section).

Methodology researchers believe that this research material is powerful due to the group environment. It has also the potential of making the participants feel more comfortable and make them easily involved (Kumar, 2014). The group environment can make it amenable for gaining a rich volume of data (Hennink, 2014). This rich data can be used to explore a vast variety of issues (Kumar, 2014). To capture naturalistic speech data, this method is suitable (Robson, 2011). Hennink (2014) highlighted the flexibility of this method in the sense that it can be used in mixed methods research.

Research methods designers see eye to eye regarding the challenges that a focus group could have. Initially, data might be difficult to investigate succinctly, since the number of participants involved is restricted (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). By the same token, it allows for asking only a few questions because of the limited time devoted (Robson, 2011). Then, it is hard to consider the findings reached by this method as representative of a wider population (Robson, 2011). In the educational research context, however, the focus group instrument has been seen better to triangulate with other research tools such as traditional interviewing, observations and questionnaires because, if used alone, it yields less reliable findings (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). This is another rationale justifying my implementation of this potent method in the present study.

As concerns the group dynamics, informants may not equally take part in the group: some of them might not be involved or have a dominant participation, and others' voice might not be heard (Hennink, 2014). Hence, it really requires a skilful moderator. In this particular respect, I ensured the equal involvement of all participants through making some probes and stimulating their participation. More than that, the analysis of focus group data is criticised because it is time consuming and costly (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). In my research, this point was given a crucial consideration in the time scheduled for data analysis.

4.2.4.1.4 Participant-Observation

To elicit more actual behaviours, participant observation was further implemented as a method over the course of a few weeks. What makes observation different from other sources of data is the fact that researchers can establish direct access to data as it is naturally occurring. At this level, Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018, p.542), citing Wellington (2015) posited: "the distinctive feature of observation as a research process is that it offers an investigator the opportunity to gather first-hand, 'live' data in situ from naturally occurring social situations rather than, for example, reported data". In terms of involvement, the researcher should be fully involved looking, listening and asking (Bonner and Tolhurst, 2002).

In sociolinguistics, this research method is not new to the field. As an ethnographic method, it is viewed as a powerful method to elicit naturally occurring speech and could give researchers direct access to participants' actual behaviours (Meyerhoff, Schlee and

MacKenzie, 2015, Pauwels, 2016). During the field work, recording could be an important technique (Meyerhoff, Schlee and MacKenzie, 2015, Pauwels, 2016). In the course of this study, participants were recorded for some hours (from one to three hours per session and participant), through either making visits to the places where they reside, or meeting at the university (two locales, where Algerian students usually meet). Participants were recorded while doing other social activities in a natural manner.

The purpose of seeking more natural speech data in this method is to compare it to previous expressed perceptions, as noted in the research aims. Pauwels (2016) highlighted the appropriateness of participant- observation to be used against other self-reporting methods. In this respect, she put "If participant observation forms part of a multimethod approach to examining language use, then the researcher can contrast actual language behaviour with reported language behaviour"(Pauwels, 2016, p.72). While Pauwels (2016) associated the appropriateness of participant observation with a long period of fieldwork, this research is a mini-ethnographic case study, where researchers can conduct shorter fieldwork periods.

The observations were based on recording as an important technique which is labelled by DeWalt and DeWalt (2011) as part of field notes. For them, recordings are a good source to evidence the occurrence of data and events: " if we don't record observations, conversations, events and impressions in our field notes, then it is difficult to document these actually occurred" (DeWalt and DeWalt, 2011, p.177).

Although the effect of the researcher on the fieldwork is tolerated by researchers from a constructivist point of view, his/her presence might affect the participants' behaviours in the field work. Not only does observation trigger the researcher paradox, but so does the focus group, because both methods have similar features. Because the focus group is influenced by observation, elements that affect this research tool must be addressed. One of the situations where focus group and observation can be disadvantageous in sociolinguistics research, accordingly, is the fact that they can be affected by what firstly pinpointed by methodology researchers as *observer paradox*. The researcher's presence can impinge on the behaviour of participants, which is a serious issue. Participants' attention might be driven away due to the fieldworker presence and informants might not be naturally deploying their linguistic behaviours. However, in literature it is widely admitted that *observer paradox* is hard to

overcome. Regarding this, Schilling (2014) maintained: “we can never truly remove observer effects on speech – nor do we necessarily want to, since speech is always being observed by some listener, in both research and non-research contexts” (p.112). In the case of present research, I tried to make the participants deeply involved on the belief that the more participants are involved, the more their linguistic behaviours are natural - not to mention the choice of the topic itself that must be of interest to the participants. Also, the designed questions should yield natural, connected speech, rather than isolated speech forms (Schilling, 2014). This point was carefully considered in the design and construction of instruments.

4.2.5 Data Analysis Techniques

After data collection, processing and management, the data analysis stage was brought to focus. This stage consists of conducting an analysis of different textual materials through implementing different analytical approaches (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Before that, the audio recordings of interviews and focus group sessions were converted into a written form and submitted to a verbatim transcription relying on dictation software, Transcribe wreally software (<https://transcribe.wreally.com/>). Web-based questionnaire data was generated within QuestionPro software (<https://www.questionpro.com/>). Observation recordings were not transcribed because of the specific focus which selectively drew on a focused data.

4.2.5.1 Processing Interview Data: Thematic Analysis

Before analysing the data, I had hours of transcribing the recordings. With the advent of technologies, there are plenty of software packages which facilitate transcription and help researchers to consume less time. I used transcribe Wreally transcription software, with a one week free access, during which I could transcribe all the interviews. The beauty of this software is that it allows the researcher to either speed up the voice or slow it down.

From a wide range of interview data analysis approaches, thematic analysis approach was followed, because the main concern is to get themes and patterns that would describe the phenomenon under study. The combinations of these themes should assist in answering the research questions. Thematic analysis seems to be useful because, in this approach,

categories are created from data, without following a theory-based categorisation (Elo et al., 2014).

In interviews, data derived from each participant was given an individual focus, comparing between perceived pre-mobility experience and current one. The aim behind this individual classification is related to the researcher's assumption that everyone has his own unique experience, especially with the different backgrounds that participants came from back home. One more reason for the idiographic individual focus is to ease tracking the actual performance in focus group and observation sessions later on. After getting the transcribed data ready for coding, steps of analysis were drawn from Braun and Clarke (2006). I started reading and reading through all manuscripts for familiarisation with data and searching for common patterns between participants. Subsequently, I generated initial notes from each case, searched for themes and sub-themes within each case and finally revised them (Braun and Clarke, 2006) (See **Appendix 3** for illustrations). Although these steps are drawn from thematic analysis, it is recently viewed that there is no clear cut relationship between qualitative content analysis and thematic one, thus they can be used interchangeably (Vaismoradi, Turunen and Bondas, 2013).

After each individual case was analysed, cross case analysis was implemented. That is, common elements between participants were identified at the discussion stage to answer the overarching research questions, where evidence from literature was considered.

4.2.5.2 Processing Questionnaire Data: Question-Pro

Questionnaire data was generated by the survey technique: web-based questionnaires. Owing to QuestionPro software, I could have access to different patterns of data and reports that display raw data - reports with charts and statistics package (SPSS). However, I preferred to copy and paste the findings as they appear in the survey dashboard because the tables therein include both statistics and bar graphs within tables (see Data analysis Section: **5.2**). In terms of analysis, descriptive analysis was implemented, with simply reporting, describing and presenting data as it is through numeration and organisation (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Due to the specific nature of my research (a small-scale study, with a small sample population/ n=32), statistical packages and tests were not utilised. Basically, the aim of

questionnaire is not to get generalised results that could represent the linguistic practices of the whole Algerian students' community in the UK, but rather to contextualise the results of interviews within a larger community (n=32) than that employed in interviews (n=6).

4.2.5.3 Processing Focus Group and Observation Data

In this piece of inquiry, the focus group and observation sessions as part of the qualitative data adopted some elements of Discourse Analysis (DA) as a constructionist approach. Despite the fact that there are various forms of textual analyses, it can be said that DA has the potential of analysing the complexity of language use issues due to many reasons.

As a matter of focus, the main concern of discourse analysis is to uncover hidden behaviours by analysing the way people discuss specific issues (Hennink, 2014), trying to explore the relationship between the content of the issue (*text per se*), the context (when/where) and the discourse (language/speaker/interlocutor) (Phillips and Hardy, 2002). So, unlike the other approaches such as content and thematic analysis whose focus is only on the content, considering language as only a medium to reflect reality, this approach believes in the power of language in the construction of text. For example, in investigating language use, one needs to go through the whole narrative discourse to unveil what, how, when, where, by whom and why a particular code is used or disused.

To illustrate the appropriateness of discourse analysis in probing language use studies, Van Dijk (1981) put forwards "In linguistics, it was observed that language use cannot properly be accounted for in terms of isolated sentences alone "(p.1). Analysing break-up sentences rather than the whole narrative is the primary preoccupation of thematic and content analysis (Hennink, 2014). This latter were criticised for "decontextualizing data from the social processes they are meant to represent "(Gray, 2013, p.621). Gray (2013) also highlighted the main concern of discourse analysis: that is investigating "how both spoken and written language is used in social contexts "(p.622). So, the role of context is accordingly emphasised. On this occasion, discourse analysis could be viewed as a means *par excellence*, in underlining the role that context can perform (Song, 2010). Context plays a vital role in the discursive interaction of participants and in language choice among Algerian students. Context which is

generally a foreign environment could have the power of affecting many aspects: their identities, personalities and language behaviour.

The field of LM/LS is known for content analysis, but the use of DA recently rose to prominence. In interviews, for example, Pauwels (2016) added that discourse analysis is starting to be considered by LM/LS researchers “especially if they focus on questions of language use, multilingualism and identity” (p.70).

Aligning with the nature of this research, as a part of sociolinguistics, the dimensions of sociolinguistic analysis were used to frame the analysis of both focus group sessions, and subsequently observation. In the analysis accordingly the dimensions of analysis are based on Pauwels’s revised version of exploring language use patterns. One of the reasons is that this frame aligns tightly with a discourse analysis approach which includes different facets of exploration, beyond only the content.

Like interviews, the analysis of focus group data was processed case by case. The number of words in each code was recorded in order to identify the stance of participants, on whether they are maintainers (more French words are used after AA) or shifters to English (more English words after AA). The topic of discussion, among other elements, seemed to influence code choice (French/ English). On this matter, rich transcripts from recordings were used for the purpose of illustration instead of analysing all transcripts (See Data Analysis section). Regarding this choice, Nagy and Sharma (2013, p.252) maintained that “transcription for qualitative sociolinguistic analysis is naturally far more time-consuming and is therefore frequently limited to carefully selected extracts”.

Subsequently, in observation sessions, the focus of analysis further considered the role of topic in predominant embedded language use (French/ English), because of the participants’ emphasis on this point in their previous expressed perceptions, and because of the need to get more findings about the role of topic in actual behaviours.

The analysis of focus group sessions included word count and statistics to measure further French LM/LS to English. Although observation has a similar focus, statistics and word count were not included. The main reason is that the former is driven by the need to assess how the participants linguistically behave when discussing topics that the researcher asks them. So, it

is more like a group interviewing with some observatory elements. The latter, however, was employed, not only to be compared against interviews, but also to check the validity of focus group sessions' findings (topic role).

4.3 Researcher Positionality and Reflexivity

In interpretivist/social constructivist research, it becomes necessary to address the positionality of researchers especially in fields where "there is a greater asymmetry between the researcher and the researched" (Hammond and Wellington, 2013, p.118). In this context, Hammond and Wellington (2013) illustrated that educational research conductors who have been pupils/ students before, and linguists who have been users of languages might be affected by their backgrounds and beliefs. In contexts as such, positionality could be a sensitive issue due to the subjective interpretation it triggers.

Actually, I have many things in common with the participants as Algerian graduates from various Algerian EL departments and current doctoral postgraduates in the UK. The relation which is created between me and my potential participants is both friendly and professional (academic). Coming from similar backgrounds prompted me to introduce my voice and draw on some of my own experience, as a researcher-student during my research through the process of critical reflexivity. First of all, reflexivity is used in research to report on the relationship between the researcher and the subject being studied. It is the researcher's awareness and consciousness of the role he plays in different ways. It came to emphasise the role of researcher and to deny the assumptions that he is a mere "neutral-observer" (Gray, 2013). Therefore, there is a need to bridge the gap between the personal and professional self in a very ethical way.

Gray (2013) distinguished between two forms of reflexivity: epistemological and personal reflexivity. In the former, researchers reflect on how their epistemological stances or their views of knowledge affect their engagements in the research i.e. their awareness of the extent to which their positionality in knowledge influences the way they process the research. On the other end of spectrum, personal reflexivity implies researchers reflecting on the extent to which their personal experience, beliefs and attitudes influence the way they engage in the research process. This must be accompanied with honesty, objectivity and openness. As an

insider researcher, approaching participants from the same cultural backgrounds, I was carefully reflexive of the influence of these elements on the design of tools, the analysis and the interpretation processes.

Silva (2009) has drawn from his own 32 years' experience of living with a Portuguese-Canadian community in the conduct of research. He put "Through the process of critical reflexivity, I problematize my position as an insider-outsider and I highlight the instances when I introduce elements of my personal experience or my understanding of things within the community" (p.11). In a similar fashion, Arfi (2008) considered this approach in her own inquiry. Arfi maintained "Through reflexivity, we are not shy to say that as researchers we are affected by our informants and they are affected by us" (p.17), in which it is self-evident that the relationship between researcher and his participants can truly impact the whole research process. Briefly, Arfi is an Algerian researcher, who has a common indigenous background with her participants as Algerian immigrants in the USA. In a similar respect, my research is also affected by my own experience as a PhD student and some elements of my personal elements were introduced (either implicitly or explicitly) during this project, whenever necessary.

One way where the application of critical reflexivity was useful is in the design of methodological tools' questions. I drew from my own experience of FL use. In both semi-structured interviews, focus group and observation sessions, my role was not only limited to record and guide the fieldwork, but also to taking field notes during the collection and writing some memos after interviewing every single participant and at the end of every session for latter reflection. My role was also illustrated through my occasional illustrations and exemplifications from my own experience to help the participants produce their own ones.

However, doing so is deemed to impose bias (Tong, Sainsbury and Craig, 2007, Hammond and Wellington, 2013). Therefore, to increase the credibility of the findings and reduce bias, Tong, Sainsbury and Craig (2007) suggested that qualitative researchers should make clear all the common issues with their potential participants for the readers and the relations that links him to participants. This could be done through recognising some personal information such as identity, occupation, gender, experience and training. By so doing, "readers would be able to assess how these factors might have influenced the researchers' observations and

interpretations (p.351). A full description about the researcher is introduced alongside the socio-demographic information of potential participants in (**Appendix 2**).

My self-perceived sociolinguistic stance is a “shifter to English” (from the traditional perspective), with an additive and translingual mind-set. By shifter to English, I am aware that I started using English as a predominant embedded code alongside AA (the matrix language) and French. I am maintaining a multilingual repertoire (AA-English and French), and therefore likely a maintainer (according to new perspectives in ML/LS). Some instances of the data set are similar to this, while others are not. However, having a different position than participants does not entail being incapable of standing in the researched’s shoes and understanding their experiences (Hammond and Wellington, 2013). I am also critical that LM/LS are challenging in situations of short-term mobility, and therefore cautious in making claims. So, through positionality, one can see the barriers and limits of understandings.

4.4 Sampling Frame and Participants’ Recruitment

Any research project should identify the suitable population sample that it is based on. Sampling size and strategy should be interconnected with the type of methods and research questions. Educational research studies have used a bewildering array of sampling techniques that they chiefly adopt from different social sciences disciplines (Buchstaller and Khattab, 2014). In linguistic studies, researchers more often than not rely on reduced - in size - samples of informants than that used in other social sciences (Buchstaller and Khattab, 2014). It might be related to the enormously rich data obtained from participants.

My research project was set up to gain data from Algerian doctoral postgraduates, a population who travelled to the UK in the light of academic mobility and exchange programmes. Similar to my case, they all formerly graduated and were awarded a Master degree from different EL departments (faculties) all over Algeria, and majored in different branches: Language sciences, Literature and Civilization. This would confirm the different ethnic backgrounds that we came from. We were in receipt of a scholarship to undertake research leading to a Doctor of Philosophy award and are committed to go back to transmit the academic knowledge we picked up from Great Britain in order to improve educational research quality in Algeria. During our course here in the UK, some of us, including me, joined

the School of Education and Social Sciences in the University of the West of Scotland, based on Paisley Campus, while others fanned out all over the UK. This targeted population is characterised by a mixture of ethnic backgrounds. Some of them are Algerian Arabs, while others are Algerian Berbers. The sample consists of both male and female participants and are aged between (24-26 years old by the time of data collection).

The whole sample engaged in my research consists of thirty-eight participants (n=38). Six participants, who are based in UWS, were deliberately chosen for the interviews, focus group and observation sessions. This small size cohort was opted for the employment of the aforementioned methods, in the sense that such qualitative methods ideally require a small manageable sample. This sample of Algerian students was approached because of their availability close to the researcher's own place (we study at the same university). In this main respect, the sampling strategy which is sought is convenience sampling. The target convenience sample was used to gain data on both students reported and observed behaviours.

Convenience sampling entails selecting the easily accessed respondents as they are quick and available at a near hand, and then the researcher further seeks more respondents to get the required sample size for the whole research project (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). The main drawback of convenience sampling, however, is that the results obtained from this type of sample are hard for generalisation (Buchstaller and Khattab, 2014). However, as a response to such a challenge, the sample was extended to a larger population by means of web-based questionnaires. Thirty-two students were selected to participate in a web-based questionnaire according to one important criterion which is their coexistence with other Algerian students from the same ethnic group as communities in different UK universities. Therefore, another type of sampling was introduced which is purposive one. This purposive sample can be categorised as a small-scale population, because it represents almost a quarter from the whole number of Algerian students studying in the UK under the academic programme.

Purposive sampling implies working on a sample that was chosen for a specific purpose (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018), mainly because it illustrates some features that researchers are interested in. Recent Algerian sociolinguistic research, such as in Kadem

(2015), although investigating different sociolinguistics behaviours, came to the outcome that Algerian English students maintain their use of FL in their informal interactions. So, my research purposefully targeted a cohort whose main feature is that its members were formerly Algerian English students all over Algerian universities and currently are mobile students. The purposeful sample was specifically selected to investigate their experiences with FL use with transition.

4.5 Ethical Considerations

In social sciences, educational research is immensely filled with ethical puzzles (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Namgyel (2003, p.97) stressed the seriousness of ethical dilemmas in educational research “Ethical concerns encountered in educational research in particular can be extremely complex and subtle and frequently place researchers in moral predicaments which may appear quite unresolvable”. For this particular reason, linguists should be far-sighted and raise their attention to the point that research is strictly governed by some moral principles before they embark upon their inquiry journey. Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) and Bloomberg and Volpe (2012) argued that all research phases must be underpinned by ethical guidelines, from the nature of research to reporting data. Research ethics refer to a set of moral codes that keep the research inquiry within proper boundaries (Gray, 2013). It could be that researchers who surround their research with ethical guidelines will certainly achieve valid work that can be in turn reliable for future research. Therefore, what research ethics embody is worthwhile to detail.

The ethical framework generally urges conducting a study which:

- is harm-free for the participants
- ensures informed consent of participants
- respects participants’ privacy
- avoids any deception (Gray, 2013, pp.73–80)

However, the ethical issues depend on the context of research being undertaken, and any field has its specific ethics (Robson, 2011). This study has nothing to do with medical studies

that may expose participants to any physical harm. Algerian mobile students' participation was confirmed by means of receiving their full agreement as expressed through consent and agreement letter so as to avoid any deception. On this matter, according to UWS Code of Ethics, providing participants with enough details about the research issue and having their consent are considered as important steps for good research practice (University Ethics Committee, 2016)

4.5.1 Informed Consent

Before setting the scene and collecting data, one should make the inquiry more enjoyable and ethical by fully accessing participants' informed consent to take part in research. In this study, respondents' participation was accompanied by their self-determination in which they freely decided whether they would like to take part in research or refuse participation, rather than compelling them.

To inform their decision, they were given a thorough explanation about the study through "informed consent" (Hennink, 2014). Informed consent is one of procedures that researchers should implement in order to maintain the balance between research ethics and the subject being studied. Bloomberg and Volpe (2012) and Meyerhoff, Schleef and MacKenzie (2015) emphasised the significance of informed consent and place it at the heart of research ethics. Its long-term goal is to give participants the freedom, whether they appreciate collaboration or refuse it after providing a full and sufficient explanation to some issues that inform their decisions (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018).

In the actual field work, a fully detailed information consent form was submitted for review by the ethical committee members of the UWS and administered to the chosen participants after getting a full approval. I made them also informed that I will quote from their productions when reporting the findings of the study, while maintaining anonymity. Moreover, at the end of observation sessions, participants were asked to confirm their willingness to share the data of recordings, and that they have the right of withdrawing the recordings, in case they realised that they unconsciously spoke about topics they do not want to share (personal, sensitive issues).

4.5.2 Confidentiality

It might be of significance to concentrate on confidentiality as a separately discussed point. Williams (2015) emphasised the point that confidentiality in cross-border research can be of a more essential concern. Therefore, research ethics fundamentally highlight that data and participants should be protected and disguised through secrecy, anonymity and disclosure. In my research, although the participants are all Algerian students, it still belongs to cross-border research rather than local ones. My role, henceforth, abides by keeping confidential the issues discussed by participants especially those in the focus group within the research scope. It is also committed by maintaining anonymity of participants. However, it remains problematic since it is tough to guarantee that participants will not disclose the discussion content to others (Hennink, 2014). One convenient way to minimise informants' disclosure to the discussed issues is by encouraging them to keep confidential and avoid divulging the content of discussion outside the group.

4.5.3 Researcher's Safety

The world of ethics does not only consider the safety of participants, but also the safety of researchers, and view both as equally important. Considerations of risks that research may pose do not only apply for participants but also for researchers. In my research, the main potential risk may come from the fact that the inquirer was doing a fieldwork in different social settings. Interviews, focus group and observation sessions were conducted in many places. What could be risky is that the researcher can move from one situation to another, rather than doing it in one place. So, there might be some physical risks such as injury and accidents. As the fieldwork was arranged in different social settings, this was arranged by a system of 'check in and out' with the supervisor, to ensure compliance with researcher safety guidelines. My research also involved evening fieldwork. For example, participants in focus group were invited for a dinner in a restaurant. All these issues were proceeded with alongside 'check in and out' with my supervisory team.

4.5.4 Mixed Methods Ethics

Using a variety of methods can create many sensitive issues. For example, in the case of the current project, it followed a sequential mixed methods design that compared one stage with another, and each stage was elaborated by another. There was a more ethical awareness of mixing the qualitative and quantitative approaches from the very start. Hesse-Biber (2010) posits “establishing your ethical standpoint from the outset can help stem the ethical issues tide that can easily raise in carrying out a mixed methods design “(p, 58).

The sampling pool and participation of Algerian students in Paisley were subscribed in different ways: semi-structured interviews, focus group recordings and later observation sessions. Some findings of web-based questionnaires gained from 32 Algerian mobile students all over UK were to some extent used in the design of focus group sessions. In this regard, my inquiry was tied by a full access to respondents’ original consent and confidentiality agreements that their collaboration will work in many ways and data will serve to design a follow-up study.

Focus group, specifically, seemed to require more ethical awareness due to the evolving naturalistic data it was based on. Because of the intensive interaction of participants, it was anticipated to pose some ethical challenges (Hennink, 2014). For this particular reason, it required a continual account of the ethical issues. One of the issues is that during the data collection, the flow of discussion deviated to other topics that were not outlined by researcher before. In this main regard, participants were made aware and informed that I will also focus on their natural speech even though they deviated from the context of the topic.

4.6 Validity and Reliability

To keep the research within methodological boundaries, it set out to achieve two important research criteria that can be used to assess any research. More often than not, research may find it demanding to meet the measures of scientific rigour. The present research, however, strived to realise these two vital components and place them among the primary aims. In qualitative research, it is difficult to achieve validity and reliability due to the specific nature of data that could be described as sensitive (Gray, 2013). Hence, issues related to validity and reliability should be addressed carefully. Even though, it has been maintained that getting

data through mixing methods can boost the validity and dependability of data and augment reliability of their interpretation (Zohrabi, 2013).

4.6.1 Validity

Validity in research denotes the extent to which what researchers claim they are observing, identifying and measuring is true (Gray, 2013, p.622). To make it clear, it has been set as an umbrella term for other measures: “trustworthiness”, “credibility” and “legitimacy” (Hennink, 2014, p.175). So, researchers should simply maintain the balance between these three criteria so as to achieve a valid research. In the present research, the fact that there is a mixture at the level of methods *per se* is a giant attempt to achieve validity. Validity is about fit for purpose. In each method in the fieldwork, the factors that affect validity were highlighted with due regard to how I coped with them. To achieve the internal validity of the present work, a pilot study was implemented in order to test whether I was asking the right questions or not (See details in Section 4.7).

However, there are still other noteworthy issues that may further pose serious risks threatening the validity of this research. Piloting and trialling interviews and focus group methods is one of these issues. The issue of the convenience sample’s limited size can affect participation approval. In other words, asking participants to take part in the research several times may lead to their loss, especially that interviewees were already sought to participate in three ways: interviews, focus group and observation later on. That is why this specific convenient sample (n=6) was employed only in the main study (mainly interviews, focus group and observation).

In this main respect, Teijlingen and Hundley (2002) pointed out some cases where the conduct of pilot studies is problematic. The inclusion of participants of the pilot study in the main study may lead participants to respond differently and to change their behaviours. What is more is that the pilot study can minimise participants’ interest in following a protocol which is not novel for them, thereby, reduce their motivation to join the main study (Teijlingen and Hundley, 2002). To this end, a pilot study of focus group sessions was implemented as part of the main study (Hennink, 2014). In other words, a few minutes from each focus group session

was considered as a pilot, to both make the participants fully immersed and to spot any challenge accordingly.

To realise the external validity of this research, access to a purposeful sample of different Algerian PhD students from various UK universities was sought through web-based questionnaires. This method helped to see if the views of participants I did closer interviews with were consistent with the more general group sampled in the questionnaire (N=32).

Researcher bias is also highlighted in my research because of the socio-constructivist nature of belief. Zohrabi (2013) placed the inquirer's bias among the issues that affect the external validity of any inquiry. The researcher may not convey the meaning as exactly expressed by participants, but rather impose his own meaning. In my research, this point was emphasised from the start and was avoided as a result of my own awareness of the "objectivity" ethical issues. Although I introduced my own voice during processing data, when relevant, that was in a critical reflexive way.

4.6.2 Reliability

Reliability refers to the extent to which the results gained from the research are dependable, consistent and replicable (Zohrabi, 2013). The quantitative data may not pose reliability issues (since it is straightforward and more identical), unlike the qualitative findings in which data is unique and more subjective (Gray, 2013, Zohrabi, 2013). In my research, data was collected through both quantitative and qualitative means. By doing so, the aim is to make this research more dependable. According to Zohrabi (2013), reliability can be achieved through providing a full explanation to all phases of inquiry, rationale and the research design – not to mention the incorporation of different research instruments.

4.7 Pilot Study

After gaining the ethics approval by UWS ethics committee, a pilot study was conducted, successfully resulting in refinement of research instruments. To address the internal validity of the present work, the semi-structured interview was trialled and piloted. The pilot study included participants other than the main study one. The initial element to cover was the recruitment of participants. I have approached different Algerian students in England.

Depending on how busy their schedules were, they could decide on whether to take part in the pilot study (online interviews at this stage), or contribute to the main study later on (web-based questionnaire). Actually, the pilot study was more demanding in terms of time than questionnaires themselves, and the majority opted for the main study.

The web-based questionnaire, however, was exempted from pilot, because it acted as a follow-up tool to involve other participants from all over the UK universities. The content of the web-based questionnaire is somehow the same as interviews. The difference only lies in the type of instrument that I used to seek data. So, trialling the interview could be sufficient, and could be used as a pilot-test for the questionnaires simultaneously. As mentioned before, a pilot study of focus group sessions was implemented as part of the main study, because the small number of participants may lose interest in taking part in the following methods. Observation was not scheduled, but rather emerged during the field work. It included the same participants. For this reason, it was not considered for pilot.

In interviews, six PhD students were invited to an online interview through both Messenger and Skype, depending on which one the participants do use most. The pilot study was quite useful in identifying some potential practical problems that I refined some questions accordingly. I re-oriented some questions from general to specific, and re-worded and re-scaled some questions that were not answered as expected. I further discarded all unnecessary difficult and ambiguous questions.

In the focus group sessions, the scheduled time for each session was preceded by some time which allowed the participants to interact freely before the main session had started. In particular, participants in focus group sessions were given topics to discuss, other than the planned ones. The main topics were introduced when potential participants showed their full immersion in discussion.

In this methodological review, I have tried to highlight all aspects that identify how I approached the present inquiry. Each undertaken step was aimed to be justified, and ethical issues were considered on the premise of meeting the study's aims. What research literature in methodology suggests are not strict guidelines that give the researcher a guaranteed success in the fieldwork. On this matter, House (1994) contended "There is no guaranteed

methodological path to the promised land", cited in (Plano Clark and Creswell, 2008, p.15). However, keeping the study within the proposed design and underlining ethical bounds would increase the potential for sound research. In the next chapter, I present the findings that were reaped from the mixed method design.

CHAPTER FIVE: ANALYSIS OF THE FINDINGS

After conducting the pilot study which had successfully resulted in instruments' refinements, the research considered the second phase of the field work: the main study. To study language use and practices among Algerian ethnolinguistic transnational movers, methods that I thoroughly detailed in the methodology section were, in practice, employed. The research findings presented herein are based on two types of data collection: expressed perceptions (through the lens of interviews and questionnaires) and observed behaviours (through the lens of natural focus group discussions and participant observation). It would be worthwhile to stress the point that this research takes a social-constructivist view in which it targets both participants' perceived data and my perceptions of their behaviours. So, what will be presented in this chapter is a plausible interpretation of perceived definitions coming both from the researcher and the researched.

5.1 Interviews' Baseline Data

This section interprets identified themes from the stories and experiences of participants, using case by case (individual) analysis. I have chosen to present data in an individual case by case form as opposed to other choices for the purpose of individual comparison with the findings of focus group and observations session later, and therefore comparing each participant's perceptions with his/her actual behaviours. During data presentation, I will put certain phrases in bold to indicate the main themes that will be further discussed in the discussion chapter (See **Appendix 3** as a sample about earlier organisation of themes). Pre-mobility experience will be addressed separately because of the researcher's previous assumption that it plays a significant role in interpreting LM/LS in situations of short-period temporary mobility.

Participant 1: *Sonia*

Sonia is an Algerian female. She is originally Berber; mainly Chaoui. Chaouia is one of the spoken varieties among Berber people. *Sonia* was born and bred in Khenchla, an ancient metropolis in the middle areas of Algeria. Despite being Berber, *Sonia's* mother tongue is AA and reported second language is French. In terms of exposure, *Sonia* started learning French

since the fourth grade of the primary education, and further received learning French as an additional foreign language at the university for a period of five years. In terms of French proficiency, despite of the long-time exposure, she views herself as a less competent user.

Sonia travelled to the UK approximately two years ago by the time of data collection. She tends to travel to Algeria once per year, in accordance with the institution policy that every PhD student is entitled to one annual leave per year. During the interview, the participant seemed very concerned and worried about the perceived linguistic change she is going through. During her stay in the UK, *Sonia* maintained her socialisation with Algerian fellows, using multiple languages, instead of being a full user of English. If seen from the new perspectives in LM/LS, one can say that she retained a multilingual repertoire. Even though, slight changes are worth consideration.

-Pre-mobility Experience:

According to pre-mobility experience, *Sonia* had a multilingual repertoire (AA-French-English). She particularly associated French domination in Algeria with the **geographical location** where the speaker lives. So, language choice depends more on the setting. According to her, people from coastal areas speak more French than those of interior cities. In this main regard, she put:

(...) it depends on the setting (mmm). For example, if you go to the interior cities, they speak a mix of AA and French. So, both languages have the same position, but if you go the north, mainly in the administration, it is about using French. If you use French, you will achieve your aims for going to the administration destination, but if you don't use French, you will not get what you want easily (...)

In terms of attitudes towards it, French was perceived as her second language and part of AA. Following this, she claimed: "(...) French is a step in our language, like you cannot speak AA without French, AA is mixed with French, we code switch (...) French has been in Algeria for hundreds of years, so we can't neglect it (...)". The passage emphasises two points: FL **had a high status** within *Sonia's* verbal repertoire and was **highly attached to first language (L1)**. This does not go with the idea that heritage language is unchanging and stable (Mazzaferro, 2018b). She was speaking about her heritage language in terms of a set of practices (AA/French translanguaging).

Sonia had different aspirational identifications behind FL use that are mostly driven by structural-functional forces. French was used because it is so **functional in Algeria**. It also indicates **professionalism** and **prestige**. With appreciation and pride, *Sonia* put “I grew up in an environment where if you speak French, it means something, it means that you know, and it means you are from high class family (...)”.

Although she had a long period of learning, *Sonia* thinks that learning English had affected her competency in French, and this has resulted in the so-called **language attrition phenomenon**. In this main respect, she further elucidated “when I started using English, I neglected French (...) when I started learning English, my level in French has been decreased from what it was before”. This would minimise the role of mobility later on. It could be said that the sufficient formal exposure to learning a particular language does not necessarily result in positive attitudes and preference of use. The use of English according to *Sonia* was limited to her own preference and relevance to classroom.

According to *Sonia*, she did not have a stimulating familial social network that promotes the use of FL (as part of AA). Despite the fact that her father is a FL teacher, he is in favour of Arabic language use instead. So, the **negative family support** and the **influence of EL learning** could result in a beginning of LS, from appreciating and using French to English.

With her colleagues, Algerian EFL students, *Sonia* used to use French as part of AA in their daily life interactions. The participant also showed positive feelings towards the use of French among her colleagues before her transition to the UK. French was welcomed as it would open more horizons to **additive multilingualism**. In this vein, she claimed: “We did not want French to go, it is a good thing to learn three languages”.

-Current Experience:

According to the current linguistic experience of the participant, residing in Scotland for approximately two years by the time of reporting the data resulted in a slight reduction in the use of French. Unlike pre-mobility experience, where French had a status of a second language within *Sonia*'s verbal repertoire, English is becoming her second language instead, in terms of the amount of use (according to her perceptions). Hence, FL use retreated in use.

From the traditional perspective, **LS** is seen as the most potential linguistic behaviour with *Sonia's* transition. Following this, she said:

I think I replaced French with English in position, I mean I started making words in English suit my interaction and speech. I started using English as I used to use French before (...) I started code-switching with AA and English more (...) French is less used, I started worrying about my French language

According to her perceived linguistic behaviours, she thinks that she replaced French with English. Therefore, some changes occurred, identified as traditional LS. One can draw some specific characteristics of LS within short-term mobility. LS within short term mobility can be displayed through processes of code-switching and code-mixing instead of a full shift to the dominant language. Therefore, the multilingual nature of repertoires of individuals is less affected than in situations of longer stay. In Pauwels's suggested understandings of LM/LS, this is a case of LM because the participant maintained a multilingual set of practices (LM) according to her reported behaviours. The multilingual nature of repertoire did not decrease. This would entail that LS did not happen.

Sonia's thinks that she creatively uses English in her academic life, French with French people and AA-English-French code-switching with Algerian students in the UK. This could be due to restrictions on the domain of use that LM/LS within short-term mobility can encounter.

The participant strategically engages in FL use depending on her lexis and the Algerian interlocutor's one. In this regard, she maintained: "The use of French sometimes depends on my knowledge or the Algerian person I am talking to (...) if I don't know the word in English, I use French, if I feel that the Algerian person did not get the word in English, I express it in French, but usually English gets a priority(...). AA-English **code-mixing** is also evident according to *Sonia's* perceptions: "we make the word in English suits our speech to make the Arabic sentence looks grammatically correct (...)".

To make it more clearly, the participant offered this example to illustrate the difference between her previous interactions with colleagues and her current ones:

1) Before mobility: "haya nrawhou '**la restaurante {Fr}** naklo haja "

2) With transition: "haya nrawhou '**la restaurante {Fr}** wanhaviw **something**"

Translation: Let's go to restaurant and have something

Example (1) can explain a case of AA-French code-switching

Example (2) can explain a case of AA-English-French code-switching and also AA-English code-mixing (wanhaviw, from the verb to have).

As far as the reasons behind her perceived **LS to English**, *Sonia* emphasised that the impact of doing a PhD in an English context as a factor that affected her use of French, and therefore, triggered LS to English (shifting to a language which she think **matches her academic identity**): "We are English students, that's why we use English more than French words in our daily interactions (...) What you study all the time can affect your use of language". According to this assumption, **LS** cannot be deterministic in this sense, because it is more related to an aspiration: linguistically behaving in a way which is more compatible with her academic identity, as a result of the academic mobility.

She also views herself as predominantly using English as an embedded code because of her **positive attitudes** towards English as a language. More importantly, English –at an international level - represents the **language of dominance and power**.

However, as viewed from *Sonia's* responses, she also expressed her fear of losing FL as a result of her stay in the UK. In this regard, she placed into words: "I started using English more, and started worrying about my FL". Her current feelings also revealed that there are other factors that stimulate her slight use of French. These factors are related to the community wide norms. French is **communicatively functional in Algeria**. *Sonia* wanted to maintain it for **future/post-mobility considerations**. In here, she expressed:

I want to keep French because, as a sponsored student, when I come back to Algeria, if I don't speak French, it does not matter if I speak English(...)It matters if I speak English only in the classroom, but what about outside !!! I need French to show high status and prestige and my position as a doctor in the university. When I communicate with other doctors from other fields, they would use French, and I started considering the need to start learning French from scratch, not from scratch but I would like to be fluent in it (...)

The participant made macro choices about how she expresses herself in a social context. Unlike English whose function in Algeria is limited, French is very **functional** as a **facilitator language**. It also denotes a **high-profile status** and **prestige**. In the same context, *Sonia*

considers the maintenance of FL among her colleagues as a positive point due to its value in communication with colleagues across different fields back home.

To be critically reflective, the continuous use of French for reasons related to the country of origin is obvious within the circumstances of the research participants (travelling for a short-term mobility, with a guaranteed return).

The slight continuous use of French for *Sonia* is related to her coexistence within the Algerian community; Algerian colleagues. Usually, Algerian PhD students meet in the accommodation kitchen, shopping centres, gym and university office. So, the **ethnic support** can be a factor that stimulates *Sonia's* slight maintenance of French.

At the end, *Sonia* considered her experience with FL in the UK in terms of use as somehow negative. At the same time, studying abroad, for her, is an opportunity to communicate with French students. This would enable her to increase her proficiency, and that will definitely help her in the future. Concerning the use of French among her colleagues, she thinks most of them are maintaining the use of it, especially Kabyle students whom she thinks they use French more than Arab and Chaoui people. *Sonia* seems in favour of **additive multilingualism** among the Algerian ethnolinguistic groups. Regarding this, she put: “ (...) for me, more than one language is good”. The tension between structural-functional views of language and the new perspectives is made clear.

So, going through the whole may suggest that *Sonia* tends to appreciate a set of linguistic practices/ languaging (that one can interpret as LM). However, she also assumes that English replaced French (traditional LS), when relating her experience to Algeria. Not because of mobility, but because of the structural functional context she is related to, through both pre-mobility and post-mobility pull and push factors. In other words, mobility just strengthened her disposition towards English, but may not actually trigger LS.

Participant 2: Karim

Karim is an Algerian Arab male participant from one of the Mediterranean cities in the east of Algeria. *Karim* had lived in the UK for almost two years ago by the time of interviewing. In Algeria, *Karim* studied French for almost ten years. As concerns proficiency, *Karim* believes that his level is moderate in terms of the four skills. Similar to the previous participant, he thinks that his level has decreased as soon as he started learning English. During the interview, the participant showed some feelings of disappointment towards the status of French in Algeria, and a real excitement towards EL and its use, as well as his willingness to assign EL a high status in the future of Algeria rather than French.

-Pre-mobility Experience:

Similar to *Sonia*, the setting plays a pivotal role in language choice according to *Karim's* pre-mobility language use experience. In this main respect, the participant explained: "it depends on the person you are speaking with" (interlocutor). In another extract, he maintained " (...) it depends where I am" (physical context/ locale). *Karim* used to speak French out of habit because it is already **part of the AA**. He repeatedly articulated that AA is made of both Arabic and French. This goes against viewing languages as bounded entities in a time of globalisation. In connection with this, whenever he used to speak Arabic, French was included therein.

Karim admittedly expressed that French has some useful implications in Algeria, especially in administration. The use of French also can indicate prestige. Concerning this, he reported: "some people including me are sometimes using it to show off". The use of French according to *Karim* also entails intellectuality. For him: " (...) Sometimes you find those people who only use French and then if you reply to them in Arabic, they think you have no idea of what you are speaking about". *Karim's* attitudes towards FL domination in Algeria revealed a deep frustration. He seemed to oppose its official status as a second language, because he believes it is less functional for both the country and individuals. In this main respect, he said:

It really makes me frustrated seeing French as a second language instead of English back home which is (anger) (...) it is true when we say French language, it sounds really good but as a matter of a good positive side of it, it seems nothing (...) it does not really help our country in anything. I do believe that if English is a second language, it would be much better for our country, in terms of education, economic and especially for people (...)

Karim had a **strong family support** in favour of FL use. In this sense, he expounded “the more we are grown up and then we find our uncles and aunts those who study sciences use French, so we find ourselves automatically using French“. Although *Karim* had a strong family support that would promote FL use, he had French negative attitudes. Instead, he was preferring the use of English for multiple purposes. For example, EL was a means for him as a student and a teacher to practise his profession. With his colleagues, he used to use AA-French-English before his transition to the UK. He further considers the use of English as a linguistic behaviour that was unusual among his colleagues. On this matter, he noted “I was the only person who uses English words even outside to a point that my classmates used to think of me as showing off“. More than that, he was against the use of French among his colleagues. For him, English can rather give them a global access to the world.

-Current Experience:

In the perceived pre-mobility experience, *Karim* thinks he used to use French as a second language alongside AA. Unlike this, he believes that he is currently using English as a second language instead. So, residing in Scotland for almost two years by the time of data collection resulted in an assumed LS; from French as a previous second language to English. Accordingly, *Karim* views himself as a **shifter** in a traditional sense (English language superseding the position of French). In this main vein, he articulated: “I think I am more using English. I am maintaining French but unconscious (...) I think I am losing it to be honest“. The unconscious perceived use of French denies the strategic linguistic choices. Even though, French is hard to lose, and therefore, appeared to be slightly maintained when he interacts with his Algerian colleagues (according to his self-report practices). In one of the extracts, *Karim* interpreted his linguistic experience as follows:

(...) If there is always people from other countries, I use English. However, I use Arabic with my Algerian colleagues here in the UK; only if we are Algerians. When I use Arabic, French is unconsciously part of it. In terms of ranking, before, French was ranked second but now English is ranked second after AA (...)

This suggests that the participant draws on a set of multilingual practices, which can be seen as a case of LM (maintaining multiple practices). However, his perceived sociolinguistic stance is a shifter to English because of the subtractive views of the participant. Similar to *Sonia*, LS was identified in relation to the amount of French use, which was decreased, according to him. For him, the use of French also depends on the interlocutor (Algerian students), as a way to show solidarity. So, the slight use of French became limited only to the friendship domain and this is an important characteristic of LM/LS within short-term mobility; restriction in the domains use. In other passages, the participant mentioned that he still uses some French with an Algerian Kabyle student. To describe the use of French with this specific micro-ethnic group (Kabyle), he reported:

To be honest, I think I find myself using it only with one person who came from a different background as us which is Kabyle. So, she tends not to speak Arabic the way we do. She came from a different city in Algeria where they only use French so much. I think she is the only person whom I use French with, but with other Algerians, we tend to speak normal Arabic mixed with English

Again, his disposition towards using languages is derived by a structural-functional view that Kabyle people use more French than other ethnic groups in Algeria.

Some linguistic behaviours were recorded upon *Karim's* stay in the UK. With Algerian colleagues, *Karim* thinks he uses some French words while discussing some life issues as food and fashion, but not research: "(...)about research we don't really tend to use French terms, we only use EL, even like we speak Arabic but when we speak about research we use English terms". Accordingly, the topic of discussion was also highlighted beside the interlocutor as informing the predominant embedded code choice (French/ English).

The participant – by definition - did not show any interest in maintaining French despite its dominant status back home. For this main reason, more emphasis was put on some aspirational identification of LS to English. *Karim* seemed to be influenced by his **professional career** and **academic identity** as a PhD student, and is willing to use English accordingly. He clearly expressed:

I think it is always related to me as an English student. It is always good only to keep myself in that circle of English language (pride), and I wish that one day English language will take over French back home and everybody will speak English as a second language instead or even as to use it with Arabic in our slang (...)

Another factor that could justify his perceived LS is his **positive attitudes** towards English as a language: “I like English as a language”. What further inspired him to shift to English is that English would be more **functional** back home in various domains like tourism, education and economy –not to mention its international status that implies **familiarity with the world**. According to this, LS could be more related to aspirations that are related to the country of origin.

Karim views the use of French among his colleagues in the UK as something obvious. He put into words: “it is no way to blame them why you are still using French because it is part of us as Algerians” which implies **attachment to L1** and the inevitable high status of FL.

Unlike *Sonia* who tends to appreciate a set of hybrid linguistic practices, *Karim’s* experience suggests that he is more influenced by the structural-functional views related to Algeria. Importantly, the subtractive views and his deterministic negative attitudes towards FL are what, perhaps, pushed him assuming that he shifted to English with mobility. While, in fact, the occurrence of this linguistic phenomenon is challenged with short-term mobility.

Participant 3: Sara

Sara is an Algerian female student who belongs to one of the Algerian ethnic groups: Kabyle. Kabyle people are originally Berber. *Sara* lives in Béjaïa, a Mediterranean port city in Algeria and one of the largest Kabyle-speaking cities. From anecdotal evidence, people from this specific area are known for their linguistic affiliations towards French. Accordingly, *Sara* considers French as her native language alongside Kabyle, a Berber variety. What is highly noticeable is that the participant has very positive attitudes towards French to the extent of considering it as her native language. One way to illustrate her high appreciation of French is when she said: “French! (Appreciation and pride), I consider it as a native language; Kabyle and French are attached together (...)”. This is another point highlighted in the new perspectives in LM/LS, which goes against the view of “one nation, one language”. According to Pauwels (2019), identifying one language as a native language is challenged in the new perspectives of LM/LS. The participant started learning French since the pre-school period to the high school and seems to be a proficient speaker of French. With other Algerian students, *Sara* crossed borders towards Scotland to conduct a PhD research, where she spent there

almost two years by the time of interviewing. The participant showed a great excitement to share her French linguistic experience.

-Pre-mobility Experience:

According to *Sara*, the setting again is an element influencing the dynamics of spoken languages before mobility (especially interlocutor). She used to use it on a daily basis, either as part of Kabyle language in her city or with family members in France. She also used to use Arabic mixed with French with Algerian colleagues from other cities.

Unlike *Sonia* and *Karim*, *Sara* was exposed to a stronger family support that stimulated the use of French. The latter can result in lifelong positive attitudes and use of that language. One of the outcomes of **the rich exposure** could be that the participant was using that language as a daily necessity. In this regard, she expressed:

(...) We are like obliged to speak French. (...) mmm according to my view, actually, I love French language. It is like obvious (appreciation) yeah! You know because when I was like a kid, in my hometown, we were raised with this language to speak in French because for us it is like prestigious or something like this. It is like in our daily life we use French, and especially you know if we go to administration or wherever, we are like obliged to speak in French. So, we need to learn this language in an early age. Before I reach school, my parents used to teach me French and before this I used to be exposed to TV especially cartoons in French till high school (...)

In this extract, the **positive pre-mobility environment** regarding FL is made clear. The participant's use of French can be related to structural-functional benefits. The participant further showed her **positive attitudes** towards French due to its **functionality** in different Algerian domains such as higher education and administration sector. It is also a **prestigious language** and a **language of intellectuals**. *Sara* considers FL domination as obvious and worthy. In this view, she concluded: "actually I love FL, it is like obvious to dominate Algeria". She also stated that people in Algeria are used to French's longstanding high status back home. In higher education context, *Sara* showed a high admiration to students who use FL and interpreted it as something which fosters **additive multilingualism**: "(...) I really appreciate this, because I don't know it is a plus, I have also got this point of view that when someone uses French, he is so knowledgeable". This implies her openness, which can be further developed by mobility.

-Current Experience:

With transition, the participant conceived not to undergo many linguistic changes, especially when it comes to FL use. One way in which this can be evident is when she said: “living here doesn’t really change my view towards French (...) I still use French, exactly the way it used to be in Algeria”. This may suggest the less linguistic changes affecting minority languages within short-term mobility. While interacting with her fellow students that usually takes place in accommodation, *Sara* thinks that she is using AA- FL-English code-switching while discussing various issues. She also indicated a large interest in preserving FL through different strategies such as using it in social media and interacting with French students. Thus, according to the participant’s perceptions, LM from both traditional and new perspectives occurred. The multilingual practices of the participant were maintained, and FL was also maintained as a predominant embedded code choice within her repertoire. At this point, one can reinforce the likely obvious changes triggered by short-term mobility. In another area, she said: “for me I still consider French as more important even when I live here”. She is also using French to maintain communication with some members of her family in France: “For me I still think that French is still useful even in the UK (...) yeah, actually because it helps me a lot even when I travelled to France, I didn’t find difficulties to interact with people”.

As a current consideration, *Sara* showed some motivations to retain French as long as it **facilitates interaction** with French people because – during her stay in the UK – she occasionally travels to France. Usefulness in **expressing identity** is another motive in favour of French maintenance according to *Sara*: “I cannot express myself without using French language”.

Sara’s attitudes also revealed a deep **attachment to the pre-mobility environment** and its linguistic practices. Therefore, FL is maintained due to that. *Sara* wants to maintain French because of the **high status** that it holds, and the **good impression** that individuals’ users would give –when using it. The reverse is true when someone does not use French. For the participant, the disuse of French holds a negative impression. *Sara* summed up: “For the future, I do think French is going to be still important even for my future kids (...) As long as we speak it back home, I keep using it (...) When someone does not speak this language, it is like a shame, it has a high status in my hometown”. French is also preserved due to

future/post-mobility considerations: it could be useful for her kids and coming generations back home. Thinking backwards and forwards during making linguistic decisions can be an important feature in approaching temporary mobility linguistic practices.

Despite perceiving herself as a maintainer, *Sara* views her fellow Algerians as shifters to English (using English as a predominant embedded code alongside AA). She thinks that being a shifter is reasonable enough, because English is more functionally important and has an international value. Consequently, they use it as a pre-dominant code alongside AA. According to her, among the reasons of LS to English is that they are influenced by their pre-mobility experience, where FL was not highly used in their verbal repertoires, totally different than her case. With that in mind, she stated: “Most of the Algerian students who live here and do not use French, they don’t really use it in Algeria”. This can, to a larger extent, emphasise the role of pre-mobility experience in either French LM or LS to English. The role of pre-mobility experience is predominant in interpreting situations of LM/LS within short-term temporary mobility.

Finally, the participant confidently expressed her willingness to preserve the use and status of FL in her repertoire. She confidently placed into words: “I am not gonna lose it anyways (...)”.

Participant 4: *Amin*

Amin is also an Algerian male student, from the first cohort of mobility programme. He belongs to a Berber ethnicity group, namely Chaoui. Before mobility, he was living in one of the interior cities, specifically populated by Chaoui people. Despite being ethnically non-Arab, *Amin’s* mother tongue is AA. Across his educational trajectory, *Amin* learnt FL since the fourth grade of elementary education till high school. In terms of proficiency, he considers himself as an average French speaker. By the time of interview, he has lived in Scotland for almost two years already but tended to travel to Algeria once per year. With his transition to Scotland, the participant maintained a high socialisation with his colleagues who are also based in the same institution (UWS). *Amin* gave me an impression that he likes foreign languages, regardless of being restricted to any.

-Pre-mobility Experience:

Similar to *Sonia*, *Karim* and *Sara*, the setting is a common factor in code choice. Exactly like *Sonia*, *Amin* thinks that French linguistic domination depends on the **geographical area** in a structural-functional Algerian context. Therefore, it is more dominant in big cities and less dominant in small ones. *Amin* lives in a one of the smaller interior cities, where he thinks FL is less used. Following this, he articulated:

(...) I live in a small town in the east of Algeria, where French does not have a bigger impact, if we compare it with bigger cities (...) we live in a small city, and a lot of people come and prefer using AA for communication. In trade, for example, a lot of traders find AA as a means to communicate rather than French

Amin had a **supportive home environment** which helped him to develop FL use. In other words, he has been widely exposed to French TV channels and has been influenced by his father who is competent enough in French: “ (...) in my situation, my father speaks French very well because he studied French before. We used to watch television in French when we were younger. We were exposed to that language in a very young age and for the environment, it does have an impact”. As previous participants, some aspirational identification of languages used before mobility were detected. French, as a second language was used in the English department, where he got his previous academic degrees. For *Amin*, FL is more functional and appropriate than English in that academic environment, because students are less competent in English. This may result in communication breakdown, by its use. On this matter, he stated:

(...) for example, in the English department in XX university we use French instead of English, so if we want to speak in the administration we have to use French or Arabic not English. The environment limits our English ability to communicate with others since the majority of people in my point of view still have lack of competence in English, and we try to compensate that with the use of another language like French in this situation (...)

With his Algerian colleagues, he used to use French as a sign of prestige: “ (...) it depends on the situation, sometimes we use French to show that we belong to a high status, using French is to get higher status conversation”. *Amin* also used to use French alongside AA because he thinks that both languages are attached together: “As a matter of fact using AA means using some French words (...)”. This may propose the inability of identifying languages as bounded

autonomous codes, a new perspective in the study of globalised communicative practices (Taylor and Snoddon, 2013). However, he was not in favour of the use of French at the expense of English use among his colleagues. In light of this, he explained: “ (...) using French instead of English is like unfair, using French and English together is better (...)”, where a call for **additive multilingualism** is clearly evident. At this point, one may think that the participant would maintain French with his transition to the UK, mainly because of his multilingual translanguaging orientation.

-Current Experience:

The participant importantly pointed out that residing abroad for a shorter period could not impinge on people’s linguistic practices. Regarding this, he maintained: “ (...) you cannot lose a language only in three years, it’s a short period of stay”. He added: “(...) you might think of losing French in twenty years further”. This could be a real challenge for the application of LM/LS in this research as mentioned earlier; the short period of stay would lead to fewer linguistic changes.

According to *Amin*, residing in Scotland so far did not affect his use of French. He viewed himself as retaining the use of French as a predominant code choice within a repertoire (traditional LM) and maintaining a multilingual repertoire (suggested definition of LM according to Pauwels (2016)). During the current stay, *Amin* code-switches between AA, French and English with his Algerian fellows: “ (...) it depends on the other party, when I am speaking to Algerians, I definitely use Algeria Arabic, French and English (...)”, and code-switches between French and English with French students to maintain a successful communication. Therefore, the use of French depends more on the interlocutor, which looks to become limited, in comparison to perceived pre-mobility experience. The limited type of interlocutors may become various with longer periods of stay.

As a previous student in applied linguistics and a current student in the School of Education, *Amin* has a deep interest in learning languages in general. This could highlight the influence of the positive attitudes. For him, any language has its value. In this context, he stated:

(...) In my situation, I consider French as an important language and the same as any other language since I studied linguistics. So, any language has its importance, has its strengths. So, the more languages I learn whether English or recently I started learning like Chaoui, Kabyle. The more languages I use, the more I am satisfied about myself, French is no exception to this rule (...)

The **positive attitude** towards French is made clear in this extract, an important factor that can promote the continuous use of FL. In another passage, he further showed appreciations towards French as a language: “ (...) I consider French as an important language, any language has its importance”. It is made evident that the participant has no intention to stop using FL. Therefore, this may suggest that maintenance is related to his willingness to acquire a multilingual identity which favours different languages. He is in favour of **additive multilingualism**.

Like some previous participants, *Amin* showed a strong interest in preserving French because of macro interests (structural-functional motives). French use for the participant is **economically functional**, mainly in French speaking countries: “ (...) French, it’s a bit limited but definitely it gives you the opportunity to work in France speaking countries (...)”.

What is interesting in situations of interpreting LM/LS within short-term mobility, conditioned by return, is the act of looking forwards towards the future. Like other participants who assumed LM, *Amin* has also some **future considerations**; when he goes back to Algeria in the future. French is still a **language of prestige**: “ (...) French is still in a higher status language in Algeria (...)” and **functional in different domains**. French use gives a better impact (**prestige**): “ (...) It is still useful in Algeria in terms of giving a good image”.

Amin, when meeting with other Algerian fellows, uses French with AA and English in discussing any topic, without being restricted to a specific issue. However, when speaking about research, he would code-switch between AA-English. Unlike his situation, he thinks that his Algerian colleagues in Scotland as more shifters to English **to match with their academic identity**. Situations of LS is then more related to an aspirational academic identity.

At the end, the participant described his **positive experience** regarding FL, considering the English setting as a supporting element in preserving FL and a good opportunity to learn different languages:

(...) I found that living here is really helpful in maintaining French...it is a good way for socialising with people, not only just with French people, I learnt from students coming from French speaking countries like Belgium and Canada. It is a good way for socialising and ice breaking and I keep my point of view is like, the more languages you learn, the better you feel (...)

This may propose more openness towards languages as part of the international experience.

Participant 5: Souzan

Souzan is an Algerian female student, who used to live in the West of Algeria before mobility. Her mother tongue is AA. *Souzan* was exposed to learn FL since elementary school to high school. Despite the long-time of exposure, the participant perceived herself as less proficient in that language. The participant has stayed in Scotland for one year by the time of interviewing. This participant showed a lack of enthusiasm to speak about FL, but was very motivated to do regarding English.

-Pre-mobility Experience:

The pre-mobility experience revealed that the participant used to use FL according to the setting. So, the setting is a common theme between all previous participants. With a particular focus on FL domination in Algeria, *Souzan*, with a full sense of dissatisfaction, expressed:

(...) Well, unfortunately, it is still dominating in higher education, in administration, and the worst thing is that if you go to the Algerian consulate in London, documents are still issued in French, it is disgusting and even in HE institutions as English department, teachers are switching to French, the administration, the papers you are supposed to sign are in French though they are belonging to the English department. The worst thing that ever happened to me is that when I was preparing for my scholarship, the instruction to write a proposal are in French and the thing that I suppose to bring the document are in French (...)

Despite of the widespread dominance of this language in Algeria, *Souzan* projected that English will rather dominate the future of Algeria: " (...) I think that French is going to vanish in the 20 years later in Algeria (...) there is an increase use of English among the youth and an increasing interest among them (...)".

Unlike other languages in her verbal repertoire, French was rarely used before she travelled to the UK, according to her perceptions. *Souzan* had no interest to use French because of

negative attitudes. For her, it was just habitually used, mainly because some words are already adjusted to AA through the mixing process:

(...) Not really, I was not really using it, except for the case of code-switching, there are some terms in French that become more Arabic. You know! Some words in French, because of the continuous use, they became as if they are integrated in the Arabic repertoire. For example, if I say “normal”, I write in Arabic letters, so I think it is Arabic

Consequently, she was using it very rarely with Algerian colleagues and was preferring the use of English instead, to align with her academic identity as an EFL student:

(...) I used to use it very rarely because we think that we belong to the English department and it is not obligatory to practice the language, but it is more a kind of our identity that I am an English candidate student. It is not about showing off, but to show to other people that we are worth belonging to the English language department (...)

Souzan did not have a strong **family support** in favour of FL use. In addition to the fact that her parents are not users of French, the environment she was brought in, is less stimulating as well: “(...) I think this is due to the rural environment that I was living in; that if you compare it with an urban like the case of my relatives in the city, they are more exposed to French (...)”. This datum aligns with *Sonia’s* and *Amin’s* perceptions that the **geographical location** plays a significant role in FL use.

For *Souzan*, the use of French among her colleagues before mobility holds negative connotations. For her, it either implies a lack of competence in English or showing off linguistic abilities. Her linguistic affiliations towards EL seems at the expense of supplanting French. This could imply the subtractive views inspired from wider community norms, an important feature in structural-functional contexts.

-Current Experience:

According to expressed perceptions, the participant’s current experience may suggest that she underwent slight linguistic changes, identified as **LS** (FL use has declined within the repertoire). She considers AA as her first language; English is her second language and then French comes last. This justifies her maintenance of a multilingual repertoire (LM in the initial suggestions of Pauwels (2016). One reason to justify the so mentioned classification is that

the environment - she is currently in - prioritises the use of English. With negative expressions towards FL, she maintained:

(...) I am using Arabic with a lot of English, English is my second language and if I would change language planning in Algeria, I would make English the second language because of many reasons. I am using French rarely; you know that it is getting worst and it is good news for me because I don't like it. It shouldn't be there. I am using English and defending English and its rank and see it as the best and I think it is the right rank in Algerian society to see English as the second language (...)

The **negative attitudes** towards the status and use of French seem to be clearly transferable from her pre-mobility environment. In terms of use, she further claimed: “(...) I am a shifter since I was in Algeria, the change already took place (...)”. LS was not a result of her stay, but rather already took place before mobility. In this sense, mobility could be a reinforcing factor to a previous linguistic change, a key point to consider in approaching LM/LS within short-term mobility.

With her Algerian colleagues, *Souzan* thinks that she uses AA-English-French code-switching. She also uses AA-English code-mixing. To illustrate this, she exemplified “ (...) we do transfer the grammatical features from Arabic and adjust them to English words such as “pound/pounda”. There are also some verbs like “expect” becomes “expectini”, “wish” becomes “wishini”. This can present earlier stages of LS, which imply AA-English code switching and mixing processes.

Even so, *Souzan* acknowledged that she still uses some French words as part of AA in some topics such as food, songs and movies. Regarding this, she claimed: “ (...) it was five percent, now it is one percent (...)”. These words are already adjusted to the spoken variety, which could explain the nature of AA as a mix between Arabic and French. Actually, the slight use of French is limited to her interaction with her Algerian fellows: “It’s a kind of searching identity with each other because we are far from home; in a foreign setting (...)”.

According to *Souzan*, she assumed LS because **English is more relevant** and **functional** in the current context; partly because she is in an English environment, and partly because she is doing a full time PhD research in English, and therefore, **to align with her professional/academic identity**. In the latter, she expounded: “ (...) I am doing a full time PhD in English “.

Souzan also has **negative attitudes** towards FL due to **historical** and **political reasons**. To express her negative views towards the French colonisation in Algeria and the linguistic heritage left behind it, she stated: "It left bad heritage, if we have been colonised by the British Empire, Algeria would be better, because the British empire whenever it goes, it builds, the French does not, it destroys". On the other end of the extreme, with a deep enthusiasm, she confidently showed her **positive attitudes** towards English: "Unlike French, English is more liberating and international (...) English denotes you are from high class". For her, unlike French, the use of English implies **a global access** and **prestige**. In this sense, she drew a comparison between using FL use and English: "when you say {Hello}, it gives you a sense that you are international, even if you are in Algeria but you are connecting to the world, but if you say {bonjour}, you are connected to very limited geographical frame". These assumptions could be drawn from a subtractive society dominated by exclusion policies.

At the end, *Souzan* seemed to be very satisfied in assuming that she is losing FL: "I am always saying (pride) I am proud to lose it, I am not a performer of that language anymore, because that language means nothing for me, it meant for the generation before". LS within short mobility is challenged to happen, let alone language loss which is far away from happening in contexts of short-term mobility. Accordingly, the participant assumed the shift because of an imagined linguistic situation driven by structural/ functional forces, rather than individual micro-choices in variations.

She also considered the maintenance of FL among her colleagues as irrational. Following this, she said: "the maintenance of French is a resistance against personal development and achievements". This implies that English is more useful for their personal developments as academics.

Participant 6: *Schahin*

Schahin is an Algerian male participant with Arab ethnic origins. Before mobility, this participant has lived since birth in one of the Mediterranean cities, located in the west of Algeria. *Schahin's* mother tongue is AA. *Schahin* exposed to French learning for nine years and admitted his full proficiency in that language. With other Algerian students, he crossed borders to conduct his PhD research in Scotland, residing for almost two years by the time of

starting the fieldwork. During the interview, *Schahin* did not express his enthusiasm to speak about FL for some reasons that will be explained in the subsequent section.

-Pre-mobility Experience:

All previous participants pointed out that the setting is an important element influencing language use. *Schahin's* reported linguistic practices were no exception to this rule. Drawing upon the findings from his data, *Schahin* perceived FL in Algeria as less dominant than it used to be. Following this, he said:

(...) mmm to be honest, the domination of French language starts to decrease since independence. If we go back to the period after independence, we find a lot of people and even the educational system was in French. Also, if we go just to the seventies when my father was working on the phone services, before the emergence of the internet, people were using French between them. However, the new generation are nowadays more aware about the use of Arabic in all domains. So, French is losing its status by time, not 100 percent, but gradually becoming less used (...)

In terms of use, he used to use FL daily as part of AA to adjust to the Algerian environment he grew up in. This would explain the nature of AA as a hybrid mix of Arabic and French. With his Algerian colleagues, he used to use this language outside the classroom. In this vein, he stated: "I used to use it with Algerian colleagues when we were talking so friendly". To illustrate the use of French mixed with AA, *Schahin* provided this example, speaking about mobile phones with his Algerian colleagues:

"Adyh aw **sharjih {Fr}** rahi al **batterie {Fr}** tayha" to express "essayer de le recharger, **batterie faible {Fr}**" which means in English "try to charge it, battery is low"

Schahin had a **sufficient exposure** to that language through his **strong family support**:

(...) Yeah to be honest, because I grew up in well cultivated environment and because I am the last boy in my family, and all my family members are well educated, so they use a lot of French in front of me (...) we can say the overwhelming majority of people were Francophone and I can say that at home, my mum is francophone, my father is francophone, and the result me (...)

Despite all of this, the participant strongly forecasted that the use of this language is gradually decreasing by time, and that may result in language loss in the future. In addition to that, he

regrettably expressed his former use of French with his colleagues which is for him a wrong way. In this vein, he concluded:

(...) I could see it as a habit that we are English students, but we were still using French outside the university and that had a negative impact on us and unfortunately we have just realised that when we come here (...)we were just losing our time in practising French because if that time was just given to practise English language, we wouldn't have difficulties at the beginning of the migratory journey, I can see in myself when I came to England for the first time, I found myself as if I never learnt English before, I found it so complicated, just because we were using a lot of French (...)

The sentiments embodied in here could confirm the participant's willing of a linguistic change. That also could entail that the participant would shift to English as soon as he is transitioned to the UK.

-Current Experience:

According to *Schahin's* perceived current experience, residing in Scotland had affected his FL use. If seen from the traditional dominant definition of LS, it could be said that he is gradually shifting to English. In one extract, he posited: "we are not using French that much, it starts to vanish away, and it starts to be decreasing, while English is increasing in our personal repertoires". As concerns the current linguistic behaviours, *Schahin* conceived that he maintained a set of linguistic practices. Therefore, he can be identified as a maintainer according to new perspectives in LM/LS. He seems to deploy the linguistic resources according to the interlocutor more than other elements of code choice. The nature of these resources is multilingual. Accordingly, he thinks he is using French with some FL teachers and his French flatmates, AA-English-French code-switching with Algerian colleagues. One example to justify this when he produced: "(...) When we were in Algeria, we used to say "sbah Alkhir" or "bonjour" to Algerian colleagues, but here we unconsciously start using "good morning (...) ". In another example, he expressed: " (...) in the past, I used to say "je suis vraiment mal a laise", now I am saying "I am upset". He further provided an example of AA-English code-mixing, such as "cleani" for the verb "to clean".

Unlike previous participants, what is interesting is that the participant further pointed out the role of topic in his language use. In this vein, he thinks he uses French words when he speaks about specific issues: " (...) sometimes when we want to speak about administrative things

and Algeria's past events (...)''. In another passage, he illustrated: "(...) Last time, for example, when my Algerian colleague asked me for some ideas in methodology, we were using English words besides Arabic, because the conversation required English instead of French".

Different aspirations informed *Schahin* perceived sociolinguistic stance as a shifter. He is ambitiously in favour of LS, because English is needed in his academic world, in both his current stay and in the future. So, the use of English alongside AA **is more relevant to his profile and academic identity**: " (...) Yeah it is because we need English, we are in an English setting, and we are researchers, so we need to use English (...)"'. English can also give him a **global access** to the outside world. Apart from education, it is an **international language**: " (...) now I am speaking with every person around the world".

Unlike some previous participants who assumed the maintenance of French **for future consideration**, *Schahin* wanted to preserve English for **future considerations; to align with his academic identity as an educator**: " (...) I recognised that I will need English in my world of research in the future as a university teacher (...)"'. Relating linguistic choices to the future is an important characteristic of LM/LS within situations of short-stay periods, with guaranteed return plans.

Although the participant was not in favour of FL before mobility, he did not seem to be satisfied at losing the FL. In this respect, he acknowledged: " (...) To be honest sometimes I am losing it, it is somehow negative, living here impacted negatively my level in French, but I don't want so (...)"'. This latter is against his planned goals: "(...) I don't want to lose what I already built, still I need FL and I still need foreign languages when you speak three is better than two, when you speak two is better than one (...)"'. In this expressed view, his inclination towards **additive multilingualism** was made clear.

Schahin has some motivations to maintain French, namely for **future functionality**. He may join conferences in France, an appropriate context for the use of that code. This, if used alongside English, would give better impact according to *Schahin*: " (...) I can use it alongside English and this really gives a good impression, and even gives you a good position and shows you are well cultivated and open to the world (...)"'.

Moreover, the participant has an interest to maintain French because learning languages is recommended in his religion (Islam): “ (...) as you know learning foreign languages is important and we don’t need to ignore that, it is stated in our religion to learn languages because the prophet said “try to learn all people languages to avoid their harm”, so it’s very good to learn others’ languages (....)”’.

So, while the participant is in favour of LS, he wants to maintain French because of the strong linkages that he still has with his country of origin: Algeria. According to this, one can notice the fluidity of LM/LS as a result of a short stay period. LM/LS are not unidirectional exclusive processes.

At the end, *Schahin* thinks that his fellow colleagues are more likely to be shifters, with few of them being maintainers.

Looking on the interview data in a general sense may suggest some pull and push tensions in interpreting LM/LS in this specific context. Participants were explaining situations of LM/LS in progress, instead of illustrating deterministic LM/LS. The former can be a result of the temporary mobility that these participants have, while the later can emerge with longer periods of stay. Linguistic practices were explained in terms of repertoire: pluralistic communicative resources. If explained from Pauwels’s initial definition of LM, participants were all assuming to maintain a multilingual repertoire, thereby, can be identified as maintainers. LM within temporary mobility is realistic because of the early establishment of individuals, a factor that Conklin and Lourie (1983) and Clyne (2003) argued as influencing LM.

Data also hold principles of the dominant framework. Perceived maintenance and shift were only presented in terms of the amount of FL/EL use alongside AA. LM was explained in terms of the continuous use of French as a predominant embedded code alongside the matrix language; AA and English through processes of code-switching and mixing. LS was identified as using English as a predominant embedded code beside AA and French. Traditional LM/LS mostly seemed to be assumed when participants think in relation to the country of origin, with a two prevailing influencing views: additive and subtractive multilingualism. Perceived LM can also inform new line of thinking in the theory of LM/LS.

That LS is less likely to happen in situations of short-term mobility was carefully addressed during the presentation of perceived data to mean a temporary assumed LS, a sociolinguistic stance that might be constructed with participants' mobility and their academic focus. The perceived linguistic change can be also represented as a beginning stage of LS, that can start by processes of switching and mixing. All of these will be discussed in depth in the discussion chapter.

5.2 Web-based Questionnaire Database

The purpose of the second stage, as explained in the methodology section, is to contextualise the findings of interviews. This section provides analysis of the data generated by the survey technique through using descriptive statistics. However, for some open-ended questions, where answers varied widely, items were qualitatively analysed. Owing to QuestionPro software, I could have access to different patterns of data that display raw data - reports with charts and statistics package (SPSS). However, I preferred to copy-paste the findings as they appear in the survey dashboard because the tables therein include both statistics and bar graphs within (see below). The count usually represents the number of participants, but on some occasions, it represents the whole number of ticks that participants produced in the case of multiple choices in one question (mainly in **Q8, Q9, Q10, Q15, Q16** and **Q20**).

Question 1: Participants' gender

The questionnaire purposefully included participants who live in the UK as ethnolinguistic communities. The gender issue was not regarded as the main criteria of selection. Introducing it, however, can be worthy as demonstrated in LM/LS research, mainly because of its potential as an influencing factor. Surprisingly enough, female students occupied the larger proportion as clearly shown in the graphs, in which their number is approximately triple to that of male students (71.88%). This gender split might lead to a less representative sample over the whole cohort under study. To counteract this bias, the speech data in interviews, focus group and observation sessions included an equal involvement of both male and female (See the Sociodemographic Information: **Appendix 2**).

Answer	Count	Percent	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
Male	9	28.12%					
Female	23	71.88%					
Total	32	100 %					

Table 5. 1: Distribution of participants by gender

Question 2: Participants' ethnicity

In a similar way, this question was asked because ethnicity is a key sociodemographic factor in studying language use and explaining linguistic behaviours (Pauwels, 2016). **Table 5.2** illustrates the number of participants with regards to their reported ethnic backgrounds. As explained in the literature review, the language issue in Algeria is not only an individual element, but also depends on macro elements such as the ethnic backgrounds (Benrabah, 2013). According to the results, participants belong to two ethnicities: Arabs and Berbers. Actually, because the number of participants from both ethnic groups is almost equal, ethnicity here might function as less explanatory, in comparison to gender. From a critical perspective, descriptive statistics are limited in their explanatory power anyway.

Answer	Count	Percent	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
Arab	17	53.12%					
Berber	15	46.88%					
Total	32	100 %					

Table 5. 2: Distribution of participants by ethnicity

Question 3: Participants' micro-ethnicity

Unlike the previous question which introduced the macro-ethnicity (Arab versus Berber), this question is optional, mainly addressed the micro-ethnicity of participants who are Berber (micro-national grouping). Benrabah (2013) made a clear categorisation of Berber sub-ethnic groups (See **table 3.1** for details). According to the results, Berber participants belong to two different communities: Kabyle and Chaoui. Six participants were identified as Kabyle, while nine as Chaoui. In the literature review of this research, I pointed out that Algerians' linguistic

variations can be related to their ethnic variation. The recruitment of participants in interviews, focus group and observation sessions considered both micro-ethnicities for the purpose of comparing both groups' speech behaviours. One of the participants who is originally Kabyle (*Sara*) interestingly claimed maintenance of FL in comparison to the two Chaoui participants.

Question 4: Participants' home area

As shown in **table 5.3**, participants from different Algerian geographical areas took part in this research. The majority of Algerian students came from coastal cities; mainly "East" (50%), preceded with students from both the west and non-coastal interior cities (18, 75%), while very few lived in the south of Algeria (12.5%). Similar to previous sociodemographic information, this variable can play a significant role in studying the linguistic differences at the level of the Algerian speech community. In interviews, the six students belong to different parts of Algeria (as charted below), for the purpose of identifying the linguistic differences between all.

Answer	Count	Percent	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
Mediterranean cities "East of Algeria"	16	50%					
Mediterranean cities "West of Algeria"	6	18.75%					
Middle cities	6	18.75%					
Saharan cities	4	12.5%					
Total	32	100 %					

Table 5. 3: Distribution of participants by their home area

Question 5: Participants' length of residence in the UK

The period of stay of individuals abroad is viewed as an important determinant influencing language use (Pauwels, 2016). Although the Algerian-UK scheme of studying abroad was launched four years ago, participants of the questionnaire did differ in their duration of settlement, depending on their starting period of research. By this question, my aim was to

get the average length of participants' residence to relate it to the linguistic outcomes resulted from the mobility period. By the time of data collection, the duration of residence ranged from one year to two years and six months. Ten participants stated that they spent one year in the UK so far. Ten of them reported that they already lived in the UK for two years. Seven participants clarified that their period of stay in the UK ranged from one year and three months to one year and ten months. The remaining five participants stated that their period of stay extended from two years to two years and six months. Alongside with interview data, one can allocate two years period as the most detected mobility period among participants.

Question 6: Travelling to Algeria during study abroad

In the theory of language contact, ease of travel to homeland is viewed as one of the factors that can promote LM (Clyne, 2003). As I mentioned before, Algerian PhD students in the UK are residents for a short period of stay. The period of their stay depends on the university policy and the sponsor's requirements. Although students are doing a full-time PhD research degree, they are entitled to annual leaves. With regards to that, the results show that the majority of participants (90.62%) travel to Algeria from one time to another during their periods of stay in the UK, while very few ones do not, similar results to those detected in interview data. One can then highlight ease of travel to homeland as a potential factor influencing the continuous use of FL.

Answer	Count	Percent	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
Yes	29	90.62%					
No	3	9.38%					
Total	32	100 %					

Table 5. 4: Travelling to Algeria during study abroad

Question 7: Self-reported French language proficiency

This question was set out to find out if proficiency in FL is an influencing factor on French LM among participants. A number of ten participants (31.25%) viewed their level of proficiency as advanced, while only a few considered it as elementary. The findings significantly showed that the participants' average rate of their language proficiency in French is intermediate (50%). As will be discussed later, this could be problematic because the literature suggests

that maintenance is related to high language competence and proficiency (Clyne, 2003), whereas this group is only ‘intermediate’ in terms of self-reporting. Relating this to interviews, focus group data and observation results suggested that this factor is more powerful in French use, as the majority of participants who viewed their level as either intermediate or advanced, were using French as the predominant code choice in observed data.

Answer	Count	Percent	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
Very Advanced	2	6.25%					
Advanced	10	31.25%					
Intermediate	16	50%					
Elementary	3	9.38%					
Beginner	1	3.12%					
Total	32	100 %					

Table 5. 5: Self-assessment of French language level of proficiency

Question 8: Languages that participants’ family mostly use in their daily conversations

This question was mainly asked to see the influence that home environment can have on participants’ linguistic practices. More than half (28/32 students) reported that their parents tend to use AA, followed by/or mixed with French. The findings also showed that some participants’ families use Berber dialects. English is not used among participants’ families according to data. It could be deduced that participants could be influenced by their family members, while their parents would not appear to be, given the 0% score for English, despite the children being students of that language. In interviews, some set of data suggested that students who have a strong family support to FL, perceived themselves as FL maintainers.

Answer	Count	Percent	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
Algerian Arabic	<u>28</u>	54.9%					
Berber dialects	<u>8</u>	15.69%					
French	<u>15</u>	29.41%					
English	<u>0</u>	0%					
Total	51	100 %					

Table 5. 6: Languages that participants’ family mostly use in their daily conversations

Question 9: Languages that participants were informally using with their Algerian colleagues before mobility

This question addressed the deployment of languages among participants during their intra-group interactions in their non-academic networks before mobility. This question was limited to the friendship domain. As findings displayed, participants were using a range of linguistic resources (repertoire). In a closer look, participants were not used to being much influenced by the academic course they were undertaking in higher education (using more English alongside AA). As a result, they used to use FL more than EL, regardless of the type of encounter, with whom they interact. In details, the majority of them expounded that AA was the most used code, followed by FL and Berber dialects respectively. English was slightly used among these participants. In interview data, the majority of participants emphasised the interlocutor as an important element influencing their previous use of English, but French was used more. Only one participant reported that she used to use English more than French, and that can be referred back to the strong interplay between the academic identity and her social use of language.

Answer	Count	Percent	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
Algerian Arabic	<u>29</u>	46.03%					
Berber dialects	<u>8</u>	12.7%					
French	<u>19</u>	30.16%					
English	<u>7</u>	11.11%					
Total	63	100 %					

Table 5. 7: Languages that participants were informally using with their Algerian colleagues before mobility

Question 10: Languages that participants are currently using while interacting with their Algerian PhD colleagues

This questionnaire item refers to the languages that Algerian PhD participants are currently using within the ethnolinguistic friendship domain, with their transition to the UK. According to the table below (Table 5.8), participants seem to maintain the use of AA as the matrix language, despite living in a purely English setting. However, what is highly noticeable is that the degree of EL use has risen, compared to the table just before (Table 5.7), where FL is ranked second after AA. Within a short period of stay, approximated at two years, a slight linguistic change happened according to their perceptions (English became used more than French). This situation can display temporary LS, from a traditional perspective in the study of language use. The continuous use of the same resources within their repertoires could illustrate the case of LM according to new perspectives. Results from interviews supported these pieces of data due to various (perceived) factors.

Answer	Count	Percent	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
Algerian Arabic	<u>30</u>	39.47%					
Berber dialects	<u>4</u>	5.26%					
French	<u>15</u>	19.74%					
English	<u>27</u>	35.53%					
Total	76	100 %					

Table 5. 8: Languages that participants are currently using while interacting with their Algerian PhD colleagues

Question 11: Frequency of French language use among participants before mobility

Moving from general linguistic practices to the use of FL, the majority of participants reported that they were not using French in their repertoires so often (alongside other resources), when they were residing in Algeria. Just under a third of the whole student cohort stated that they were occasionally using it. Five students revealed that they used to speak it rarely, and other five ones perceived that they were using it “always”. From the whole questionnaire sample, two participants denied (rejected) their use of FL when they were residing in Algeria. In interviews, the majority of students similarly articulated that they were often using French as part of AA in a daily basis.

Answer	Count	Percent	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
Never	<u>2</u>	6.25%					
Rarely	<u>5</u>	15.62%					
Occasionally	<u>9</u>	28.12%					
Often	<u>11</u>	34.38%					
Always	<u>5</u>	15.62%					
Total	32	100 %					

Table 5. 9: Frequency of French language use among participants before mobility

Question 12: Frequency of French language use among participants in the UK

In this question, it is clear that there is a decrease in the frequency of FL use from being often used among the majority of Algerian PhD students to rarely be. Table (5.10) shows that there is a slight drop in the reported use of French compared with its use before mobility. It could be assumed that the degree of FL use could decrease with longer periods of stay. A similar trend of data was highlighted in interview data by the majority of participants.

Answer	Count	Percent	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
Never	<u>3</u>	9.38%	█				
Rarely	<u>9</u>	28.12%	████				
Occasionally	<u>13</u>	40.62%	████████				
Often	<u>4</u>	12.5%	████				
Always	<u>3</u>	9.38%	████				
Total	32	100 %					

Table 5. 10: Frequency of French language use among participants in the UK

Question 13: Participants' self-perceived sociolinguistic stance with transition

In order to further examine patterns of FL use, participants were firstly asked to clarify their sociolinguistic stance: maintainers or shifters. As explained in different previous sections, LM/LS in this context is problematic, not only because they are applied on L2, but also because these two processes take time to happen. Therefore, their use in this research context is not canonical. By maintenance, it means the continuous use of FL as a predominant embedded language alongside AA. LS implies substituting their previous use of FL with EL as a predominant embedded language. With this specific LM/LS application, more than two thirds of participants perceived themselves as shifters to English (22/32), while only just above one third of the whole sample considered themselves as maintainers (10/32). In the same fashion, the majority of participants perceived themselves as shifters in interviews. Actually, this specific application of LM/LS is also challenging in the new lines of thinking (LM/LS in terms of repertoire).

Answer	Count	Percent	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
More maintainer of FL	<u>10</u>	31.25%					
More shifter to English	<u>22</u>	68.75%					
Total	32	100 %					

Table 5. 11: participants' self-perceived sociolinguistic stance with transition

Question 14: Participants' explanations of their perceived sociolinguistic stance

The previous question was followed by the participants' justification of their sociolinguistic stance (assuming being maintainers/shifters). In Chapter 3, I explained what I exactly mean by LM/LS in this research based on how some participants in the pilot study perceived they maintained FL and how others viewed they replaced it with English (LS). According to participants' answers, maintainers (assuming LM) defined LM as their predominant continuous use of FL alongside AA and English, which implies using different resources. Some participants explained it as the sustainable use of it as part of AA; at word level (code mixing). At the other end of the spectrum, the majority of participants' shifters argued that French is becoming less used alongside AA, because English has replaced it and became more used than French (while French is maintained, English is used more). Both pieces of data could lend support to my previous assumptions of the nature of LS and LM within the context of this study, where linguistic resources are deployed in concert with each other.

This may also suggest that LM/LS within a context of short-stay period can happen through processes of code-switching and mixing, rather than unidirectional deterministic processes. Therefore, one may also say that these perceived linguistic behaviours represent earlier stages of LM/LS, starting by moving forwards and backwards through a playful mix of resources. Some participants further assumed that they view themselves as shifters because in addition to French decrease of use with Algerian colleagues, their FL skills have also declined (language attrition). This can illustrate the strong relationship between LS and language attrition.

Question 15: Reasons why participants (assuming LM) think they retained the use of French language in their repertoires

This question was optional, mainly relevant to those who viewed themselves more as maintainers. Various recurring factors were detected and listed according to the responses given by participants of semi-structured interviews. In questionnaire, participants stated that they prefer to maintain it alongside AA more for **future considerations**: because it can ease interaction with their Algerian colleagues (similarly revealed by *Sara* in interviews), and it is very **functional in Algeria** (Similar to *Sonia, Sara, Amin, and Souzan*). Some participants think that they want to maintain French use within their repertoires because it has a **prestigious status** in Algeria (*Sonia, Sara, Amin and Souzan*), and it shows that they are bilinguals/multilinguals. Interpreting linguistic behaviours in relation to future aspirations (related to the country of origin) can be an interesting characteristic of LM within short-term mobility. Other participants viewed that they maintained French for **current functionality**; because they can use it as a linguistic means to socialise with French international students (*Sonia, Sara, Amin and Schahin*). One participant considered FL as part of L1, thus uses it whenever she uses Arabic/Berber.

However, the majority of participants did not seem to be restricted by the multiple options given in this question. Consequently, the largest proportion of participant maintainers further provided details about the reasons that influenced their perceived maintenance of FL use in their repertoires when they interact with other Algerians. The extra motivations that informed participants' choice to assume French LM according to their report can be related to:

- Its **attachment to L1**. For example, **QP1** maintained "(...) I may appear odd if I use another language to mix with Arabic instead when, I interact with my relatives ". In addition, **QP2** put "(...) it is part of our dialect and the majority use it as it is integrated in our speech"
- **Ethnicity representation/ Inability to identify one language as a native language**: as indicated by **QP3** "(...) it represents me as a Berber because French is used so much in Kabyle dialect (...) "

- **Stimulating additive multilingualism**, as clearly expressed in the following quotes:
QP4: “To show off abilities that I have many languages in my repertoire (...) “, and **QP5** “It is simply another language that I do not want to forget “
- **Current functionality: QP6**“(...) for research purposes, because the research I am undertaking is based on francophone Algerian literature”. Current functionality was also revealed by some participants in interview data, when they claim that FL is useful to maintain communication with family members in France (*Sara*), and it is useful in communicating with French students in the UK (*Sonia, Amin, Schahin*). Actually, this item was already ticked by a number of 4 students in the option list to indicate the current functionality of FL (to socialize with French students).

Answer	Count	Percent	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
It has a prestigious status in Algeria	4	12.12%					
It indicates being a bilingual /multilingual	4	12.12%					
It facilitates interaction with your Algerian PhD colleagues	6	18.18%					
It can be used as a code to socialise with French students	4	12.12%					
It is very functional in some domains in mainland Algeria	6	18.18%					
It is attached to L1	1	3.03%					
Others (please specify)	8	24.24%					
Total	33	100 %					

Table 5. 12: Reasons why participants conceived they preserved the use of FL in their repertoires

Question 16: Strategies that participants (assuming LM) perceived they usually follow in order to preserve FL use in the UK

As a follow-up question to participants who considered themselves as maintainers, this question mainly enquired into the perceived means/strategies through which they retained the use of FL (alongside AA). The majority of participants' maintainers considered talking to their relatives and family back home as the most common strategy and interacting with other students from the same ethnic groups in the UK. Some of them use it on social media platforms such as Facebook and interact with French students in the UK. In interview findings, these strategies were also mentioned by participants who assumed maintenance.

A small percentage of students further gave mention to other strategies such as translating some French passages related to their research, listening to some interviews with Algerian francophone writers (2 participants), and reading books in French and listening to French music on YouTube.

Answer	Count	Percent	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
Using it while talking to your family /relatives /friends in Algeria via social media	<u>13</u>	25%					
Interacting constantly with your Algerian fellows	<u>12</u>	23.08%					
Interacting with French students in the UK	<u>7</u>	13.46%					
Using it to post, blog and comment in social media platforms	<u>12</u>	23.08%					
Others (please specify)	<u>8</u>	15.38%					
Total	52	100 %					

Table 5. 13: Strategies that participants’ maintainers perceived they usually follow to preserve FL use in the UK

Question 17: Participants’ views on the relationship between French language use and the topic being discussed

As noticed, more than two thirds of the sample participants believed in the power that the topic of discussion could have on FL use. They viewed that FL use differs from one issue to another. Back to interviews’ results, two participants considered the topic as a key element determining whether they use AA-French code-switching or AA-English. For example, *Amin* thinks that he uses AA alongside French in different topics, but in research in which he thinks English is more relevant than French. At the end of the extreme, some participants seemingly did not believe in the power of the topic in FL use. Inability to associate one language with the topic of discussion is an interesting point that can be added to the challenges of LM/LS within new lines of thinking in the study of language, mobility and globalisation. However, it can be considered as less problematic in this context (short-stay period), because of the structural-functional views dominating the country of origin these participants are coming from and going back to.

Answer	Count	Percent	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
Yes	<u>23</u>	71.88%					
No	<u>9</u>	28.12%					
Total	32	100 %					

Table 5. 14: The relationship between the predominant use of FL and the topic of discussion

Question 18: Participants’ views on the relationship between FL and the physical setting where interaction with Algerian students takes place

According to **Table 5.15**, half of the student population viewed that the physical setting is an influencing factor in the predominant FL use (alongside the matrix language: AA), while half did not. In interviews, the physical setting was not regarded as an important element influencing FL use in the current setting, unlike before mobility where the physical setting seemed to be highlighted as a prevalent factor. This could be related to the restriction of domains of use, with transition. Restriction in domains of use can be related to the limited period of stay.

Answer	Count	Percent	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
Yes	<u>16</u>	50%					
No	<u>16</u>	50%					
Total	32	100 %					

Table 5. 15: The relationship between the predominant FL use and the locale where conversation takes place

Question 19: Participants’ views on the relationship between the predominant use of FL (alongside AA) and the person interacting with (interlocutor)

Unlike the physical setting, more than half of the participants viewed that their use of FL (embedded within AA) depends on the person they interact with. Comparing this piece of datum to interviews’ findings, five participants were of a similar view (*Sonia, Karim, Sara, Amin and Schahin*). They consequently think that they use FL alongside AA, whenever they

interact with Algerian students. Just under half of the sample population considered the interlocutor as less influential.

Answer	Count	Percent	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
Yes	<u>20</u>	62.5%					
No	<u>12</u>	37.5%					
Total	32	100 %					

Table 5. 16: The relationship between the predominant use of FL (alongside AA) and the interlocutor

Question 20: Participants’ motivations behind perceived LS

These findings concern the participants who classified themselves more as shifters to English. Several reasons justified participants’ motivations to shift to EL as a predominant embedded code alongside AA (the matrix language) with their transition to the UK. According to the statistics presented in (Table 5.17), the majority of participants argued that the use of English alongside AA is more important in relation to **their academic identity** as both current PhD students and future academics. In interview data, all participants, who assumed LS, revealed the relevance of English use with their academic professional careers (*Sonia, Karim, Souzan, and Schahin*). Half of the whole sample population considered the use of English (alongside AA) as more relevant to the UK context, unlike FL use.

Other participants perceived they shifted to English (alongside AA) because of its global status as an international language. In interview data, this factor was acknowledged by all participant shifters who view English as a language of dominance and power, and of a global access. Small proportions of participants conceived that they shifted to use English (as a predominant embedded language alongside AA) in their repertoires because they prefer English as a language. This gives the feeling that perceived LS to English is more informed by functionality than positive attitudes. In comparison to interviews, the same datum was detected. Only some participants viewed their assumed LS as related to the fact that it is a prestigious language, and very few of them (only 3) think that they shifted to use more English alongside AA because it is becoming functional in Algeria. A number of 2 participants further mentioned other factors behind their perceived LS to English:

- **Lack of FL competence:** QP1'' (...) well! I use English with Arabic because my linguistic capacity in French is limited (....)''.
- **English is a *lingua franca* after Arabic:** QP2''(....) the Algerian students came from a diverse environment where not everyone can understand French words, but definitely they understand English, so I use English as a second *lingua franca* after Arabic (...)''

Answer	Count	Percent	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
As a matter of preference, you like English	<u>4</u>	6.78%					
English is a language of prestige	<u>4</u>	6.78%					
Living in the UK is more relevant to English language use	<u>16</u>	27.12%					
English is more important in relation to your present and future career	<u>18</u>	30.51%					
English is more important as an international language	<u>12</u>	20.34%					
English is more functional back home	<u>3</u>	5.08%					
Others (please specify)	<u>2</u>	3.39%					
Total	59	100 %					

Table 5. 17: Participants' motivations behind perceived LS

Question 21: Participants' description of their experience with French language use

As a concluding question to this section, participants were further required to describe their journey with FL use in the UK. I provided three options that I think could be used to feature (describe) a sociolinguistic experience within a short period of time. Half of the whole questionnaire population described their experience as "complex". One may associate complex experience with the fact that participants have some struggles and competitions

within their verbal linguistic repertoires. The feelings of linguistic competition can be related to the subtractive processes inspiring them, especially that they mind the return plans during the interpretation of their linguistic experiences. These subtractive processes entail using one code at the expense of the other, and they are mostly driven by structural-functional factors related to the country of origin. Just above a third of the whole proportion of students considered FL experience as negative. The amount of FL use embedded within AA in their repertoires has declined and English has increased. Five participants perceived it as positive, which could be interpreted that the EL pressure over FL is denied. In this main respect, one may perceive a positive conceptualisation of LM/LS within short-term mobility, with the incorporation of linguistic elements in concert with each other and drawing upon different languages with no linguistic exclusion.

Answer	Count	Percent	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
Complex	<u>16</u>	50%					
Positive	<u>5</u>	15.62%					
Negative	<u>11</u>	34.38%					
Total	32	100 %					

Table 5. 18: Participants’ description of their experience with French language use

Question 22: Further details that participants wish to add

Surprisingly, some participants did not let this part slip away. Consequently, they added interesting qualitative comments that can be thematically coded as following:

- **Short stay period is less influential:** Similarly, *Amin’s* interview revealed this.
- **LS already took place in Algeria:** In reporting his/her perceived experience, one of the participants, *QP1* put “(...) I have lost my French over the last years, before coming to UK, primarily because I've been studying English at university, dealing almost exclusively with English-language texts (...)”. In interviews, *Souzan* and *Karim* had similar experience regarding that.
- **LS is dominant:** *QP2* “(...) so for me AA is becoming more Arabic mixed with English rather than mixed with French”

- **Hard to lose FL because it is part of L1: QP3**” (...) I think that as a Berber, though I am using English more than French since I lived in UK. I may not lose my French because the Berber language, I speak, includes a lot of French words, and I am using it in my mother tongue every day. Thus, I am using French alongside it”
- **QP4** “with using the Algerian dialect, we have considerable French words that are 'Algernised”.
- **-Pre-mobility experience influence:** Positive home environment resulted in French LM: **QP5**“(...) I personally use the FL, because I was brought up in a family that uses a mixture of Arabic and French (...)”. In interviews, *Sara* had a similar view.

As stands out from these comments, very rich data could be deduced in this part. For this main reason, linguistic behaviour issues could be ideally investigated by means of qualitative methodologies. Fortunately, interviews have been conducted earlier to provide enough space for participants to express freely views concerning their linguistic practices and followed up in focus group and observation sessions.

The combination of perceived data from both interviews and questionnaires can present new forms of LM/LS, and therefore would give credit to the LM/LS theory, influencing both LM/LS traditional and new perspectives. Actual behaviours data that will be presented in the following section, seem to rather reflect micro-choices and fluid practices that can be less suited to the study of LM/LS, especially within short-term mobility. However, although this research commenced with assumptions inspired by LM/LS as a framework, data presentation will question the validity of French LM/LS to English, principally because of the short-term period of stay experienced by the participants.

5.3 From Perceived to Observed Actual Behaviours: Focus Group and Participant-Observation Sessions' Findings

Tying back to research objectives, the main concern in this section is to investigate the relationships between how participants portray their current language behaviour, and what their observed linguistic practices show. In both focus group and observation sessions, the research subjects were using different linguistic resources (AA, French and English). Actually, their practices can be much more indicative of flexible translanguaging than they are LM/LS. However, because the study initially departed from perspectives drawn from LM/LS framework, the study questions the validity of these linguistic phenomena on actual behaviours. In interviews and questionnaires, LM was identified by participants as using French as a predominant embedded code alongside the matrix language (Arabic) and English. Assumed LS was identified by them as the predominant use of English as an embedded language. In actual behaviours data, that all research participants continued to use AA, French and English together can be explained as a case of LM (according to Pauwels's suggested understanding). LS, from this perspective, did not happen (a reduced set of practices).

In participants' perceived understanding of LM/LS (as shown in interviews and questionnaire), however, there was some evidence of traditional LM/LS (one language taking the place of another). In this section, it is important during the analysis to consider participants' perceived definitions of LM/LS, alongside the researcher's critical reflection. The critical reflection considers the challenges of LM/LS within short-term mobility and the new perspectives in the field of LM/LS. One of these issues is considering LM/LS as nascent stages instead of deterministic, canonical LM/LS. Any linguistic changes can be temporary as they can be already happening before mobility.

Their practices can also suggest some linguistic behaviours such as (AA-French/AA-English/AA-French-English code-switching) and also (AA-French/AA-English) code-mixing. The occurrence of such behaviours is not surprising because some of them were already acknowledged by participants in the previous section.

In processing focus group data, I quantitatively relied on counting the number of words articulated by participants in all codes, across all topics and social settings. The analysis comparatively shed more light on the use of FL and EL to identify and examine – as mentioned previously - any matching between the perceived linguistic stances (maintainers/shifters) and observed ones. For more rigorous analysis - as strongly recommended in discourse analysis - I extracted samples from some topics; mainly rich transcripts using Romanised Arabic; Arabizi (See **Appendix 1** for correspondence between Arabic letters and Romanized Arabic). According to Cotterell et al.'s (2014) model, Romanised Arabic includes not only Latin letters, but also some symbols like numbers (5, 3, 9, and 7). For this reason, in the font choice used during Arabic transcription, some symbols will appear as numbers. Within the analysis of the transcripts, the social factors influencing the predominant embedded code choice (French/English) within interactions will be considered.

What is also worth mentioning is the use of Standard Arabic in most utterances. However, this study has no focus on the diglossic use of Arabic (High and Low languages). AA is meant to refer to both forms of Arabic. In addition, participants in expressed perceptions did not mention the use of standard Arabic, because they might be aware of its formal status in Algeria as a written language, as opposed to spoken languages and varieties.

In the focus group interactions, all participants were deeply involved in the sessions according to their interest in the topics of discussion. However, prompts were carefully taken into account to maximise equal involvements. Unlike this, in observation sessions participants were freely interacting, naturally discussing whatever topics. In focus group findings, FL/EL use seems to depend more on the topic (mode of discourse and the topic's function) than other elements. Participant-observation was partly set out to investigate the validity of this. In what follows, each participant's practices in the focus group were followed by his/her record in observation sessions. In the former, participants were restricted by topics to discuss, while in the second, the field was free from the researcher's-imposed topics (more naturalistic fieldwork). Comparison between both is of significant importance to strengthen the validity of findings.

Participant 1: *Sonia*

Social context	Topic	Total number of words used	Percentage of AA words	French words	English words
Office	(1)Food	115	85.23%	8(6.95%)	9(7.82%)
	(2)Research	80	41.25%	7(8.75%)	40(50%)
	(3)International political issues	283	88%	17(6%)	17(6%)
Accommodation	(4)Fashion	271	77.5%	25 (9.22%)	36(13.28%)
	(5)Movies	216	68.99%	16(7.40%)	51(23.61%)
	(6)British culture	260	73.48%	28(10.76%)	41(15.76%)
Restaurant	(6)Marriage	382	82.73%	60 (15.70%)	6(1.57%)
	(7)Songs	55	74.56%	13(23.63%)	1(1.81%)
	(8)Algerian culture	107	85.99%	11(10.28%)	4 / (3.73%)

Table 5. 19: *Sonia's* linguistic practices according to topics and settings

As clearly shown in the table, the participant overall used more English than French. This may suggest an alignment with her previous claim "I think I replaced French with English". She also used FL as she reported previously, but English was generally used more. However, she used multilingual resources (AA-English-French) during interaction. This can be a fine example of LM mentioned in the initial suggestion of Pauwels (2016) (if compared to her perceived mobility experience). So, if seen from the new LM/LS perspective, it would be hard to say the participant is a shifter (traditional definition of LS).

The recordings implied that the use of French differs from one topic to another. One can reflect that the predominant use of French/ English can be more explained in relation to the topic of discussion, than explained as LM/LS. However, the fact that the participant perceived some linguistic changes that appeared in actual behaviours may suggest some traction of traditional LS (from using more French alongside AA to English instead). As noted earlier, LS can be temporary as it can be an early stage of actual LS. By ways of illustration, *Sonia* used more French than English when discussing the topic of marriage, songs and Algerian culture respectively. On the other remaining issues, the participant was using English as a predominant embedded code instead. Actually, it could be that the use of French by *Sonia* is more associated with private topics and those related to home, while the use of English is more related to public issues and the current setting. To illustrate the former, speaking about marriage, she expressed:

“(…) Machi ‘nti X raky sauvity {Fr} (...) par exemple {Fr}, ‘hnaya man7asch ba ‘l’âge {Fr} (...) fadzayar nhas ba l’âge {Fr} (...) kinrawhou tam awal question {Fr} kachma jabti rajal ?{worry} (...) ‘ahna ‘yzidou ‘3lik stress {Eng}, la société {Fr} y5alik thas bali l le problème {Fr} fik”

Excerpt 1

(...) I am not speaking about you X, you already found your soulmate. For example, I don't feel I am getting old here in the UK, but in Algeria I do. When I am back, the first question people usually ask me is whether I found a good match or not; people make you feel stressed. Society makes you feel that you are too old (...)

This part of transcript is considered as worth analysing in the sense that it can partially reflect the percentage mentioned above that *Sonia* used more French words than English in discussing marriage issue. What is also highly noticeable is that this extract consists of code-mixing (at word level/intra word mixing according to Kische's (2017) definition). The participant used the grammatical frame of AA and adapted it to the French word “sauver” to express a mixed word “sauvity” which means “to manage” in this specific context. Actually, code-mixing occurred only in this word by the participant in speaking about the marriage issue as a whole. *Sonia* was expressing this issue deeply and showed some sense of worry and apprehension. It could be drawn that FL can be switched to when the speaker is speaking about sensitive issues. Speaking about sensitive issues can potentially make the linguistic behaviour unconsciously produced. Thus, this would lead to think that the participant is sometimes unaware of her FL use. In another passage, *Sonia* spoke about a personal view in relation to Algerian culture:

“Sawti par exemple {Fr}, kayan hadouk ‘liychoufou est que {Fr} ‘klyna maklinach wkayan ‘o5rin non {Fr}, ca dépende {Fr} “

Excerpt 2

I have two types of brothers; those who worry about us, and those who don't do... It depends!

This example is also powerful in illustrating the use of French in expressing sensitive personal issues at an informal level. The use of French could also construct part of the participant's identity and culture. As an Algerian student, I can concur that what *Sonia* discussed can imply part of the Algerian culture and norms. FL/English seems also to depend on the function of

the topic. Speaking about marriage back home where FL was used more than English, could imply affective/social function as defined by Holmes (2013).

Sonia used AA-English code-switching more than AA-French code-switching (apart from the topics of marriage, songs and Algerian culture). Compared with her perceived pre-mobility experience, this could suggest some evidence of LS (albeit possibly a temporary change where English is used as a predominant embedded code choice). So, LS seems to be illustrated in this context through AA-English code-switching and AA-English code-mixing. Both patterns can represent earlier stages of traditional LS and important markers/ signs of it. Both patterns can also emphasise the need to research LS in terms of repertoire, instead of focusing on bounded entities, isolating codes.

To illustrate more the role of the topic function on the predominant use of the embedded code (French/English), *Sonia*, in talking about research context, said:

(...) Mazalny **mavansitch {Fr}** chwya bah 'ndir **transfer event**, ana **participants** l 3am lifat 9a3da m3aham fal **Facebook** ghyr la '**data collection** 7abit **nconducti controlled groups** 5atar taqadri 'diri fi **pla9at {Fr}** ma '**testi data par exemple {Fr}** adiri **pre-test and post-test** ba9a7 qrib lal **positivism, quantitative more than qualitative(...)** **Excerpt 3**

(...) I did not make enough progress to do my transfer event thus far. Last year, I spent a long time contacting the participants via Facebook. Actually, I want to conduct controlled groups, because one can design a pre-test and post-test instead of testing the data. It is more positivist; more quantitative than qualitative (...)

The content of this extract also presented some aspects of the participant's academic identity as a current PhD student. Speaking about research, *Sonia* used the accurate technical words related to her profession as a researcher. Hence, she was switching to English more than French to match her academic identity and the group concerns as academics. Concerning the topic's function, it could be regarded as a public topic, because it is an educational one rather than personal/ private. The function of the topic is referential (high in information) rather than social (affective).

The conversation took place in a formal setting: the office where the research participants usually gather to study in campus. It might be argued that the formal setting is a factor in switching to English rather than French. However, in topics like food and international political issues, percentage of French words use and English are approximately equal. In previous perceptions, the participant did not consider the physical setting as a factor informing her French/ English use. Actually, this is not surprising, because the role of physical setting on language use is a structural-functional factor that can be more influential in situations of long settlements contexts: migration.

Reflecting again on the passage, although *Sonia* used so many English words during her interaction, she simultaneously used some French words and applied code-mixing between AA and French. The word **maavansitch {Fr}** (je n'ai pas avancé), and **pla9at {Fr}** (place) are French words in which the speaker introduced the grammatical structure of AA and adjusted it to them, to stand for “I did not make progress “and “In place of “respectively. In this vein, it could be stated that FL is regarded as part of AA, because *Sonia* used French words, despite trying to express that in English. She also code-mixed between English and AA: **“nconducti”/conduct “ntester”/test**, where the speaker used the grammatical structure of AA to produce two English verbs. In previous perceptions, the participants confidently expressed “we make the word in English suits our speech to make the Arabic sentence looks grammatically correct (...)”. This implies her meta-linguistic awareness. From a personal observation of my colleagues who took part in my research, some English words became fixedly adjusted to AA through code-mixing especially in the context of research and shopping.

In a few words, many instances of data implied that the topic and its function is more influential in the predominant embedded code choice (French/ English), than other factors. For example, the physical setting is a less influencing factor. The less influence of the physical setting on language choice triggers less power and dominance, as it could also deny the influence of structural-functional views. There seems more evidence of micro choices during variation, than macro choices, deploying flexible and fluid linguistic practices.

Subsequently, the participant was observed during her interaction with other two Algerian students including the researcher during our visit to her in the accommodation. *Sonia* usually spends her time in the accommodation where she lives. Accordingly, the conversations took

place in the kitchen, while she was preparing evening snacks for us. At the linguistic level, the participant seemed to deploy different linguistic resources during her interaction: AA- English-French code-switching and also code-mixing (at the word level). In most cases, English was used as the predominant embedded language, rather than French. Observation data, to some extent, supported focus group findings in the sense that the topic of discussion (mode of discourse and the topic's function) influenced more language use.

In the first place, the topic of discussion was coincidentally about research. The participant was asked to proofread a piece of writing by her friend who is a Master's student. The topic was about her challenges in reviewing her friend's dissertation. She was seeking help from me (the researcher) and two other Algerian students on how to insert the reference list following Harvard style. In almost all interaction, the use of Arabic-English was thriving with a little use of French. As an instance, she put:

(...) X **please check the references** (...) X mat3arfich a **rules** nta3o! Ena na5dam bal **APA** (...) be9ah chouf ena wesh dawakhni fal **Harvard**, kayan okhrin ynahiw l fasla wkayan okhrin maynahlwch (...)

Excerpt 4

(...) X could you please check the references[...]X do you know the rules of Harvard style, I am using APA instead (...) what made me confused in Harvard style is that some people put the coma others do not(...)

In this excerpt, English is the embedded language. As previously stated, this could be related to the participant's academic identity as a researcher. It could also suggest that the participant uses more English to convey a referential (informative function). However, when shifting back to her previous degree in Algeria, she narrated:

" (...) Ana manakdabch 3likom qrit **Anglais {Fr}** besah mahatitch fiha **les efforts {Fr}** za3ma fal **grammaire {Fr}** wle **vocabulaire {Fr}** (...)"

Excerpt 5

(...) Honestly, I studied English, but I did not exert too many efforts in learning its grammar and vocabulary (...)

One may think that because the dimension of the topic was shifted to her previous university degree in Algeria, French was used as a predominant embedded code. This is compatible with *Schahin's* assumption that he uses AA-French code-switching when talking about past events.

In addition to the topic, the interlocutor also seemed to impinge on the predominant embedded code choice as she was interacting with two researchers, whom she thinks have similar linguistic practices. Within the same speech event, the participant was talking about "Eid", a cultural religious event which annually takes place. Speaking about Eid's preparation in Algeria, the participant used Arabic and French with less use of English. This could illustrate the importance of topic dimension in code choice. As an example of this, *Sonia* narrated:

"(...) Alkisan nta3 a' **service {Fr}, la base {Fr}** nta3houm fada, besah yahasbo fihoum 'r5as (...) nachfa X 5oya chralha **micro-onde {Fr}** farhat bih, wena **service {Fr}** nta3i mtayach fi **couzina {Fr}** wahad madaha fih [laugh]

Excerpt 6

(...) I remember that I bought a set of cups whose base was silver, but my family thought they are not that expensive (...) my brother bought a micro wave for my mum and she was too happy with, but my cups set was just ignored in the kitchen, no one valued its's worth [laugh]

She also compared how she spends Eid here in the UK and back home. Within that, she used English as the predominant embedded code, followed by French. In this regard, she explained:

" (...) 'Hna nasabho raqdin, **you take your time**, besah 'lhih **obliger {Fr}** 3lik adiri l **minage {Fr}** wat7ati **la table {Fr}** nta3 laftor"

Excerpt 7

(...) Here we don't need to get up earlier "during the Eid", you can take your time, but in Algeria, one is obliged to do housekeeping and prepare the breakfast table

In another topic, the participant deployed Arabic, English and French code-switching, where English was used more than French. Again French and English use seemed to depend more on the topic and its context. Speaking about the world cup and football supporters, *Sonia* used English as the predominant embedded language to quote herself, with a referential function. As an instance to this, she narrated:

“ (...) Ana nhar la3bat sou3odia, postit {Eng} congrats for Russia! W3andi friend so3odi gali I will retrieve my friendship with you gotlo: yes no problem you can go off the list whenever you want (...)” [angry] Excerpt 8

When the Russian team won against Saudi Arabia, I posted in Facebook “congrats for Russia!”, then a Saudi Arabian friend got upset and told me: “I will retrieve my friendship with you”. I replied: “yes, no problem you can go off the list whenever you want... [Angry]

According to this, only a few factors are influential in the predominant embedded code choice. This could go back to the specific context of this study: short-term mobility, given the fact that contexts as such would not lead to major linguistic changes. Elements such as “who speaks, what language, to whom, when, where and for what purpose” can be problematic to explore within situations of temporary mobility. So, short-term mobility would not only trigger restrictions of domains, but also restrictions in the factors influencing code choice at a micro-level (in actual interactions).

Participant 2: *Karim*

Social context	Topic	Total number of words used	Percentage of AA words	French words	English words
Office	(1)Food	71	81.07 %	10 (14.08%)	3 (4.22%)
	(2)Research	201	57.22%	44(21.89%)	42(20.89%)
	(3)International political issues	47	87.24%	4(8.51 %)	2(4.25%)
Accommodation	(4)Fashion	47	87.25%	5(10.63%)	1(2.12%)
	(5)Movies	48	72.92%	9(18.75%)	4(8.33%)
	(6)British culture	203	82.28%	30 (14.77%)	6(2.95%)
Restaurant	(6)Marriage	494	74.51%	98(19.83%)	28(5.66%)
	(7)Songs	105	79.06%	11 (10.47%)	11 (10.47%)
	(8)Algerian culture	201	78.11%	40 (19.90%)	4 (1.99%)

Table 5. 20: *Karim’s* linguistic practices according to topics and settings

If compared to his pre-mobility perceived linguistic practices, *Karim* seemed to continue using a multilingual repertoire, and so that can be explained as LM (in the new perspectives). Within a set of practices, the participant employed French as a predominant embedded code choice beside Arabic and English. This, although hard to maintain in situations of short-term mobility, can be explained as also LM (from the traditional perspective), of course when compared to perceived pre-mobility experience. Referring to previous attitudes, *Karim* assumed that he is a shifter (English became more used than French). In the previous section, he articulated:

“before, French was ranked second but now English is ranked second after AA”. However, it could be observed that - according to the table - the results appeared to be in contradiction with that. FL use comes second after AA instead of English. Surprisingly, *Karim* also professed: “ (...) but with other Algerians, we tend to speak normal Arabic mixed with English (...)”, which is not the case in the observed sessions. That would be likely interpreted as related to some immediate decisions in reporting linguistic behaviours. When interacting with his Algerian colleagues, he further emphasised that he code-switches between AA and English, but sometimes uses French unconsciously: “I can’t really know but I think I am more using English, I am maintaining French but unconscious (...)”. In here, his inner linguistic struggle and strong desire for a linguistic change are both made evident. The inner linguistic competitions can be related to the structural-functional subtractive views acquired as a result of power and dominance in the country of origin (as interpreted previously in his perceived views).

In practice, in discussion, at no time was English used more than French. Even so, when speaking about songs, the number of French words and English were equally used in the whole section about songs. The use of French words was included within AA clauses, while the English ones were contained in one clause; “**My favourite music: come on come on turn the radio on**”.

Excerpt 9

In this regard, it could be said that the participant may use English to produce any expression that he thinks the group is more or less familiar with. The song “Cheap thrills” by the singer Sia witnessed a widespread popularity at the time of conducting the focus group sessions, and that exemplifies this point exactly. Quotation can imply a referential function, more than a social one, because the speaker is conveying thoughts of others.

Similar to *Sonia*, *Karim* used French as a predominant embedded code in speaking about the topic of marriage. Actually, both participants felt comfortable and interested to speak about this topic, and that resulted in recording the highest percentage in that topic within the whole conversation, in comparison with other topics in the different social settings. In one of the extracts, where *Karim* was speaking about his friend back home, he stated:

“kont na7ki m3a sa7bi, ‘7na qa3din qalak **la date {Fr}** rani **fixitha {Fr}**, **le seize et le dix-sept février {Fr}**, qali mawajadtch walou, aw **c'est vrai {Fr}** adhab **imajini {Fr}** chraholha **quatre jours {Fr}** qbal l3ars nta3o !! {Surprise} “

Excerpt 10

(...) I was speaking with my friend about his wedding event. He said that he intended to do his wedding on the 16th and 17th of February, then changed his mind, because he did not prepare for that. Could you imagine that he could be able to prepare the dowry just 4 days before his wedding!

The participant used AA-FL code-switching patterns and the switching occurred more with FL. In addition to the switching at the sentence level, code-mixing at word level also occurred: “**fixitha**” for “fixer” (set a time) and “**imajini**” for “imaginer” (imagine), where the speaker used the grammatical structure of AA and applied it in producing French verbs. So, LM within short-term mobility can happen through processes of code-switching and code-mixing. Regarding the content, I believe the participant linguistically may have behaved in that manner because the issue reminded him of his friend who is part of his hometown and cultural context. The issue is personal rather than public and related to back home with a social function as the spirit (tone) of the speech seemed to suggest a sense of amusement and comfort, and that implies more a social function.

Overall, there seemed no influence of the formal setting - the office where the three topics were discussed - on the predominant embedded code choice. This could be another characteristic of linguistic practices within short-term mobility, fewer factors affecting code choice during conversational interactions.

Unlike *Sonia*, *Karim* used more French words in a passage related to research. This would sound incompatible with his academic identity. However, there was a slight difference in the usage between English and French. Thus, the use of both codes was approximately equal. The participant, although using French as the predominant embedded code, EL was also used. The following example could illustrate that:

“Mana maditalhom Al **consent form** wa **participants sheet**, **alors {Fr}** da3atli wa7d **Les vingt jours {Fr}** ghir ta3 **les examens** wal **consultation {Fr}**”

Excerpt 11

I gave them the consent form and the participant sheet in the period of exams. So, I missed almost twenty days because of exams time and invigilation

As illustrated in the aforementioned sample, *Karim* deployed three linguistic resources (AA-English-French). What is worth mentioning is that the participant used English words related to his current profession as a research student: **consent form** and **participant sheet** (from the ethics semantic field). However, in portraying his experience, when he went back home to Algeria for data collection, although the subject of discussion was the same, he used French as the predominant embedded code. This can illustrate the driving power that the context of the topic could have on code choice: Algerian-related context issue. Narrating his experience with teacher participants during data collection back home, he angrily expressed:

(....) **les profs {Fr} (professeurs)** maykhadmouch, **for example** kima ana 'l asatida 'ltam yqariw **l'orale première année, trois {Fr}** mahabouch**they did not want to** wahad kan ybali **vraiment {Fr} busy** wzid 9alak l'orale machi **la spécialité{Fr}** nta3o, **mais les deux {Fr}** lokhrin ma7abouch (...)

Excerpt 12

(....) Teacher participants back home are less helpful. For example, I approached three oral expression teachers to take part in my research, but they did not want to. One of them seemed to be truly busy, and he is not specialised in oral expression, but the two others refused (...)

It could be argued that the participant tends to employ French words when talking about any issue related to back home and shifts to English to explain any topic related to the UK context as an English-speaking country. In the same fashion, he used AA-English code-switching in speaking about movies in this expression:

*"Ana n7abhom, they **are my favourite** {feeling of excitement}"*

Excerpt 13

I like them, they are my favourite

In this example, *Karim* switched to English in expressing his favourite movies; which are American ones in this context. So, AA-English code-switching can more occur when the participant is discussing current context related issues.

I believe that this can be a very particular to the context of short-term mobility, where individuals can stand between two positions: using more their minority languages because they are newly arrived and have return plans in mind, in the meanwhile, temporarily shifting towards using the language of the host country. The result of that would be a playful mix of resources. With longer stay periods, the tendency of shift would be stronger (one may predict).

What is also worth considering is that *Karim* structured the use of FL into more phrases and clauses than in single words. This could suggest strong French LM. What also controverts his strong claim as a full shifter is the use of AA-French code-mixing, rather than AA-English in all conversations. He did not, accordingly, use AA-English code-mixing.

To further inquire into his actual linguistic behaviours, *Karim* was further observed in the accommodation with other Algerian students. Again, the deployment of different plurilingual resources was evident in all interactions. As concerns the predominant embedded language, French seemed to be used more than English, a case that would suggest the participant's maintenance of both FL as a predominant embedded code choice and a multilingual repertoire.

In one of the occasions, I had a short interaction with him, while he was studying at the accommodation's study room. From the linguistic aspect, the interaction confirmed the strong relationship between the topic of discussion and code choice. For instance, in speaking about money exchange, he used English as the predominant embedded code choice in expressing the currency related to UK context (English pound, Scottish pound), and French in referring to the currency which is more familiar in Algeria (euro) (pronounced with French inflection). In recommending the avoidance of money exchange to euro, he expressed:

" (...) Ana manas7akch tbadal lal **euro {Fr}**, badal lal **pound** khir, washi howa madirihomch **Scottish**, wa7ad maychadhom 3lik fi DZ (...)"

Excerpt 14

(...)I don't recommend exchanging money to euro, try to use the pound instead, but not the Scottish because they are less known in Algeria

Similar to focus group data, French was used more in speaking about past events in Algeria. *Karim*, in drawing on his own experience with his pupils when he was a secondary school teacher back home, put:

Ena nchaja3 les élèves {Fr} nta3i biha katjihom bizard {Fr} kifach ostad echahada nta3 BEM {Fr}, w machi za3ma ki doublet {Fr} za3ma mana3rafch na9ra, non {Fr} ena mal primaire {Fr} tilmid mujtahid, kiwsalt la tas3a degoutit {fr} la9raya, tsoufajt {Fr} fetas3a, manba3d mathanawia wena nmajori ila yawmina hada, machi ma3natha khok ydoubli{Fr} a deuxième {Fr} wa troisième fois {Fr} ma3anatha masala7ch non non non {Fr} (...)

Excerpt 15

I always motivate my pupils (...) They got weird how I did not pass my BEM for the first time and I became a teacher later onwhen I failed my first year, it does not mean I am not a good pupil...no! I was a good pupil since elementary education, but when I reached my 9th year, I somehow got fed up of studying and therefore deviated. Afterwards, I had a good restart in the secondary school phase and started getting the best grades. When pupils fail their years once or twice doesn't necessarily mean they are not good pupils for the rest of their life careers (...)

The use of French in this excerpt tells that it is part of the Algerian linguistic practices. Despite being in the UK, the thread of discussion (an Algerian past event) had led the participant to shift from the use of English as an embedded language to French.

In another visit to the participant while having his dinner in his own kitchen, I noticed his significant use of French beside AA words, while inviting me to have some fruits right at the beginning:

Karim: Kol les fruits {Fr} kayan nectarines {Fr}, mandarin wal banane {Fr} Excerpt 16

Karim: Please have some fruits, there is nectarine, oranges and banana (...)

The researcher: Oh {appreciation} manish qadra, **already** tzawadt wjit Excerpt 17

The researcher: Oh {appreciation} I can't, I already had my evening snacks!

Karim : aki sérieuse (...) 3lach t9achar fiha 3azrine l vitaminat {Fr} kamal tro7 [laugh/sarcasm] de tout façon {Fr} l jus {Fr} aw9odamak Excerpt 18

Karim: Seriously! Why do you peel it, it must lose all vitamins (...) Anyway, have some juice, help yourself!

In here, the topic holds an affective social function. The participant was showing a sense of humour while talking. This might result in the use of French. Within the same speech event, the participant switched to speak about the tenancy and agreements of the accommodation where the use of English was striking instead:

“ (...) **short term** ay aghla 3la **long term**, puisque {Fr} **long term** atih b **ninety two** lal **week**”

Excerpt 19

(...) Short term contract is more expensive than long term, it is 92 pounds per week

In this utterance, the participant showed a strict sense of seriousness which implies a referential (informative) function.

Participant 3: Sara

Social context	Topic	Total number of words used	Percentage of AA words	French words	English words
Office	(1)Food	58	63.80 %	16 (27.58%)	5 (8.62%)
	(2)Research	104	58.66%	30(28.84%)	13(12.50%)
	(3)International political issues	45	71.12%	12(26.66%)	1(2.22%)
Accommodation	(4)Fashion	57	61.41%	21(36.84%)	1(1.75%)
	(5)Movies	64	54.70%	23(35.93%)	6(9.37%)
	(6)British culture	76	59.22%	30(39.47%)	1(1.31%)
Restaurant	(6)Marriage	83	66.27%	28(33.73%)	0(0%)
	(7)Songs	28	46.44%	6(21.42%)	9 (32.14%)
	(8)Algerian culture	56	64.29%	18(32.14%)	2(3.57%)

Table 5. 21: Sara’s linguistic practices according to topics and settings

In describing her current experience with FL use, *Sara* articulated “living here doesn’t really change my view towards French (...) I still use French, exactly the way it used to be in Algeria”. The results in **Table 5.21** can reflect her perceived linguistic stance as a maintainer (maintaining French as a predominant embedded code). This can be related to the short term-mobility. Actually, Conklin and Lourie (1983) and Clyne (2003) classified recency of arrival as a factor influencing LM.

In the observed sessions, the recorded results in all cases, except songs, showed that French is the predominant embedded code, followed by English. *Sara’s* attitudes about her current FL use matched with what was observed in practice accordingly. In her daily interaction with her Algerian colleagues that was brought to notice throughout my personal observation, *Sara* usually uses many French words and expressions - if not only French when she is encouraged to do so.

In the observed sessions, *Sara* was using a multilingual repertoire. If seen from the new LM/LS perspective, one can explain it as a case of LM. If seen through the lens of the dominant definition of LM, French is still used as a predominant embedded code choice, therefore, one can also define it as a case of LM. She was switching between AA and French in most cases to express different personal and public issues, home-related and international ones, regardless of the social setting. So, she maintained French through AA-French code-switching, in addition to English use. One may say that LM within short-term mobility happens through a playful mix

of resources. For instance, speaking about the topic of British culture which took place in a formal setting (the office), she expressed:

“La premiere des chose {Fr} liya3jabni hnaya les genes {Fr} [feelings of appreciation] kol wa7ad wchoghlo, wa7ad maya7sab ‘l wa7ad”

Excerpt 20

The first thing I am impressed with in this country is people [Feelings of appreciation], mainly because of the fact that everyone minds his own business, no one spies on the other

Although the topic of discussion was not home-related, *Sara* did not switch to English to speak about that. While showing a fine appreciation of how Scottish people behave, *Sara* used AA-FL code-switching (LM) more than AA-English. Actually, the whole findings related to British cultural issues recorded only one English word which is “pumpkin”, speaking about some celebrations that she was involved in with her accommodation mates at Halloween. It could be that the participant was not familiar with the act of pumpkin carving in Algeria; one of the activities related to the eve of the Western Christian feast day, and this has resulted in missing the right lexical equivalence in FL. So, the shift to EL could occur when the speaker expresses some events that do not occur, or rather rarely do in his/her own culture.

As noticed from the data, marriage, as a social public issue, recorded no use of EL by the participant. Speaking about Algerian traditions, she put:

“a7na liya9dar ayjib machi za3ma la parure {Fr}, za3ma ya9dar 3la un bracelet {Fr} (...) normale {Fr} {assertion/emphasis}”

Excerpt 21

Marriage in Kabyle area, unlike in other parts of Algeria, is not too demanding. Women dowry does not necessary consist of a whole set of jewellery, but can be a mere bracelet.

I was expecting her to shift to English with context shift (marriage in the UK) as in some cases. However, *Sara* did not shift to English which may suggest strong French LM. In this vein, she said:

“meme ici le marriage {Fr} ghali‘hnaya! “

Excerpt 22

Even here in the UK, Marriage is too demanding!

In speaking about research, the participant used English words more than in other topics. This can suggest the explanatory power of the topic's function on code choice. The topic of discussion is educational in nature i.e. research, with a referential function. In one of the extracts, she reported:

“lala chaque étudiant {Fr} ykoun 3andou **personal blog** khatar ra7 ‘ndiralhom **induction** bah‘nfahamhom bien {Fr} kifach wyorganiziw la blog et tous, donc {Fr} banatli **action research**”

Excerpt 23

NO! Every student should have a personal blog, and I am going to organise an induction in order to explain for them clearly how to use a blog, that is why it sounds to X as if I am doing action research

This passage presents some recent words that the participant could not express in French because they are part of her academic career. However, some words, although belong to the research semantic field, were expressed through the lens of FL. So, *Sara* used both FL and English to maintain the balance (bridge the gap) between what is already adopted in her daily life use as a previous EFL student in Algeria, and what is newly acquired, and also related to her academic identity and current profession and residence in the UK. Given her language profile and practice, one could anticipate that these newly acquired words in English will be turned into FL in the future as the tendency to use FL is stronger. They can also turn into FL because of the return plans to the country of origin.

Surprisingly, the topic of songs witnessed more use of English words alongside AA than French. In the previous section, I have illustrated how *Karim* used a whole clause in English to express something that his fellows are familiar with. One point to evidence this is that *Sara* – within the same discussion section- gave mention to exactly the following lyrics in the same song composition and continued singing “**It’s Friday night and I won’t be long**”. Quotation can hold a referential informative function, as the speaker just conveys the words of others.

As for code-mixing, *Sara* loaned the grammatical structure of AA and adapted it to express a few French words throughout the discussion such as “*taplikiwalha*” (tu l'applique), “*yripondiwlak*” (ils te répondent), *machanjthomch*” (je ne les ai pas changés), “*tutilizi*” (t'utilisé), “*yorganiziw*” (they organise), *timajiniha*” (tu l'imagine). It could be inferred that this is related to the participant's FL proficiency and deep use.

It is made clear that the use of French by *Sara* is deeply rooted. There is a slight influence of living in the UK, and the physical setting, social context, and the topic of discussion on the use of FL accordingly. In other words, *Sara* uses French as a predominant embedded language whenever she interacts with her Algerian colleagues (interlocutor). Fewer factors affecting code choice at the micro level could be an important outcome in contexts of short-term mobility.

Subsequently, the participant was observed in the place where she lives. In observing her actual linguistic behaviours, it was noticed that she was using French to a larger extent in her utterances alongside other codes. The observation output may suggest that the participant maintained French as a predominant embedded code choice and a multilingual repertoire. During all interactions, there seemed a strong relationship between the topic and its function and the predominant embedded code choice. In one of the casual visits to her, while she was organising her room, I could notice the deployment of AA-French- English code-switching with less use of English. As an instance to this, speaking about how people react to others' success back home, she reported:

Kayan 3bad nti nja7ti fi 7yatak **ycritiquik gratuitement {Fr}** (...) **yacritiquer parceque {Fr}** howa manja7ch ma9darch ydir kima nti man ba3d **yessayer {Fr}** yna7ilak kloch ...**livret de famille{Fr}** nta3ak yna7ih, kima hna t3alamt 7aja bali tani kayen **difference {Fr}** bin **real friends w acquaintances .. c'est pas obligé{Fr}** na3raf wa7ad n9olo he/she is my friend [surprise] kayen acquaintance, kayan **flatmate [...]** **c'est toujours X meme amie{Fr}** nta3ak **proche {Fr}** malazamch ediri **expectations** bah t3ichi **bien{Fr}** (...) لازم nat3almo kifach n3icho **c'est difficile mais {Fr}** لازم nat3almo **ça depend voilà{Fr}**!

Excerpt 24

There are some people who criticise you just because you succeeded in something that they failed in doing it. Then because you succeed, they try to harm you by all means. Here, I learnt that there is a difference between real friends and acquaintances. You should not build expectations even from the side of close friends. In this manner, you live peacefully. We should learn how to live in peace despite of being difficult.

In this transcript, the topic implies more a social function because the participant reported her personal experience with different categories of people. She seemed to express a mixture of feelings (worry and sarcasm at the same time) instead of reason. In my own involvement

during the interaction, I asked the participant about her reaction with that social category of people who look down at her. I purposefully used English as the predominant embedded code choice:

Researcher: wash rayak fi nas **who always look at you down?**

Excerpt 25

Researcher: How do you think of those who look at you down?

Surprisingly, Sara did not seem to be influenced by the interlocutor's own use of languages. Therefore, in her reply, she used French as the predominant embedded code choice:

*"(...) Ta3arfi **on ne peut pas plaire à tout le monde!** {Fr} wahad yhabak 'w wahad yakrahak **parceque** {Fr} manqdrouch **nsatisfiw** {Fr} enas kaml **normale** {Fr}!"*

Excerpt 26

(...) We cannot please everyone! There are those who like you, there are others who do not...Simply, we cannot satisfy everyone!

In here, although the researcher used English as the predominant embedded language, the participant used French instead. This confirms her strong maintenance of FL.

In addition to the topic function, the discourse mode has some traction in the predominant embedded code choice. In this example, the participant used more French words beside the matrix language when describing her mother back home, a description which is more linked to Algerian context issues:

*"(...) Mama mali kanat sghira edir **yoga** w3andha **des livres** {Fr} 3la yoga, **de genre** {Fr} mahich ta9ra bara **mais elle s'instruire** {Fr} w7adha **parceque** {Fr} 3adha **l'intelligence** {Fr}, 3ndha **les capacité** {Fr}, t3almat Irohha"*

Excerpt 27

My mum has been doing Yoga since she was younger, and even has some Yoga books. She is not joining any class, but built herself alone. Because she is intelligent and has some capacities, she could make her ways

However, she switched to use English as the predominant embedded code in addressing her accommodation mates. She was asked by the other interlocutors about her kitchen mates, she reported:

“They are nice people! W rahom active, Florine aw Andrew. Andrew yakhdam wa Florine ydir personal trainer au même temps {Fr} yakhdam (...)” **Excerpt 28**

They are nice people, and active as well. Florine and Andrew are working and Florine is a personal trainer. He works at the same time

In this passage, the influence of the topic dimension is clear.

The participant was further observed in another group interaction, where Algerians were sitting together for dinner to celebrate their friend’s wedding. Sara was using different linguistic resources, maintaining a multilingual repertoire. She used AA which is commonly used by all her Algerian fellows as a matrix language. French was usually the predominant embedded language; English was the second embedded code choice. She also employed a few words from Kabyle such as Taghat (goat). Unlike other occasions, Sara’s practices can imply French LM, with less regards to the topic and setting. FL was used in both home related and current context related issues.

A-A comparison between her Algerian accent before and now:

“(...) Bakri kanat 3andi accent algérois {Fr} (pre-mobility accent) (...) besa7 dorka c’est bon {Fr} (...) Ana dorka mon problem c’est que {Fr} rakom bezef eh tkhalt kamal les accents {Fr}, hada man centre {Fr} hada man char9 hada man lgharb ... j’ai mentionné {Fr} lgharb Menbe3d tkhaltoli kamel” **Excerpt 29**

(...) Before coming to the UK, I used to have Algiers accent. However, I missed this accent by the time I came here, because I interact with different Algerians from different cities (east, west and middle), I got confused.

In these utterances, despite speaking about both pre-mobility experience and current experience with an Algiers accent, French was predominantly used as an embedded language in both cases.

B- Future plans:

She was asked by *Souzan* about her future plans (both at the social and professional level), after she finishes her PhD. Her response unsurprisingly revealed more use of French:

“ (...) mazal 7na mazal hata nkamlo **doctorat {Fr}** lazam nkamlo mnba3d nchado **les postes {Fr}** nkouno hakda **bien placé voilà {Fr} assurés {Fr}** mnbe3d nzawjo” **Excerpt 30**

(...) We (I and my partner) are not planning to do our wedding, until we finish our PhDs, we have to finish first, secure jobs' placements back home, then get married.

The use of French as part of the pre-mobility experience and Algerian context was similarly noticed as in previous cases (*Sonia, Karim*). Within the same speech event, *Sara*, in advising her friend (*Souzan*) to go back to Algeria after finishing her PhD, used French as a predominant embedded code:

“(...) Lazam traj3o, **c'est juste {Fr}** bah maydirouch 3lik **une recherche! tu vas pas être recherché {Fr}**” **Excerpt 31**

You have to come back to Algeria after you finish your PhD, just to avoid troubles. Otherwise, you will be wanted.

What is noteworthy in *Sara's* linguistic practices is the maintenance of multilingual repertoire and FL in particular. The tendency of French LM is irrespectively stronger. Among factors behind code choice, the interlocutor and the topic of discussion seem to be more influential elements among other factors. The non-functionality of other factors can be related to the short-term mobility, the participant had in her stay.

Participant 4: Amin

Social context	Topic	Total number of words used	Percentage of AA words	French words	English words
Office	(1)Food	33	81.82%	4(12.12%)	2(6.06%)
	(2)Research	53	73.59%	8(15.09%)	6(11.32%)
	(3)International political issues	210	75.73%	48(22.85%)	3(1.42%)
Accommodation	(4)Fashion	26	80.77%	0(0%)	5(19.23%)
	(5)Movies	84	85.72%	6(7.14%)	6(7.14%)
	(6)British culture	114	85.97%	16(14.03%)	0(0%)
Restaurant	(6)Marriage	290	81.74%	51(17.58%)	2(0.68%)
	(7)Songs	90	71.12%	20(22.22%)	6(6.66%)
	(8)Algerian culture	155	81.95%	25(16.12%)	3(1.93%)

Table 5. 22: Amin’s linguistic practices according to topics and settings

Tracing back to the participant’s perceived behaviours about his current experience with FL use, Amin previously posited: “(...) you cannot lose a language only in three years, it’s a short period of stay”. A point which would suggest that LS takes time to happen. He added: “ (...) it depends on the other party: when I am speaking to Algerians, I definitely use AA, French and English (...)”. He could not separate French from a repertoire which means LM can be better explained in terms of multilingual practices. The observed sessions generally revealed that French use comes second after AA, followed by English. This was exactly in line with his perceived sociolinguistic stance as a maintainer, and evidenced his multilingual practices, deploying the linguistic resources in relation to the interlocutor (his fellows).

The participant was using French as a predominant embedded code in discussing marriage and international political issues respectively. The use of French words went up with the use of AA being increased. So, it could be said that AA and French are so attached to each other that they go hand in hand with each other. In explaining part of the Scottish customs, Amin argued:

“kayan les traditions {Fr}, kima par exemple {Fr} kayan hadouk liyalbsou les robes traditionnelles {Fr}’hna fi Paisely wa7ad par exemple {Fr} rajal ‘da wa7da Scottish ba3d ydiro les traditions {Fr} lazam ‘ykono”

Excerpt 32

Scottish people have some marriage traditions. For example, there are those who wear traditional robes here in Paisley.

The participant used more French words beside AA, than English, although the topic of discussion was shifted from marriage in Algeria to marriage in Scotland. This could suggest an alignment with the participant's stated claim that French is maintained in the current setting regardless of the topic. As clearly shown, however, the participant produced only two words in English "**Paisley**" and "**Scottish**". Both words are commonly used between Algerian colleagues and can be viewed as bizarre if heard in another code by any Algerian student in the UK.

In the same fashion, *Amin* used many French words in speaking about international political issues. The conversation took place in a formal locale: the PhD office. The locale did not seem to affect code choice, as he deployed a similar range of linguistic resources, be it in a formal or non-formal physical setting (university as opposed to accommodation). This can be because he is newly established in the host country. In justifying why Donald Trump, the current American president, did not once include Algeria among the blacklist, he argued:

"Adzayar machi 'f la liste {Fr} parseque {Fr} adzayar ma3adhomch machakil 'kbar, rahom 'b3ad '3la **ISIS** w la source {Fr} nta3hom rahom grab'3la l'europe {Fr}, aux meme temps {Fr} rahi lasga f l'afrique {Fr}, et en plus l'economie {Fr} mli7!"

Excerpt 33

Algeria was excluded from the blacklist because it has fewer political problems. It is far from ISIS and its source, and it has a good geographical location. It is near to Europe, part of Africa at the same time, and it is economically strong!

At this point, it could be concluded that *Amin* used French as the predominant embedded code because the dimension of discussion was related to the Algerian context. However, he maintained using French throughout the whole section even when he shifted to speak about other countries' political issues within the same speech event, such as **La chine** (China)-**Le Russie** (Russia) - **les chrétiens** (Christians) - **les musulmans** (Muslims).

British culture is a topic which is related to the recipient/host country. However, no English word alongside AA was recorded in discussing. Speaking about "the great fasting" day, he said:

“3andhom une histoire {Fr} kichghol ramdan, za3ma rab3in youm mayaklouch hadik ‘l makla, za3ma 40 youm manakoukch chocolat {Fr}”

Excerpt 34

Here, they have an event like “Ramadan” in our culture, they stop eating a particular type of food for 40 days. For example, chocolate!

So, *Amin* code-switched between AA and French despite the mismatch of the topic with the code switched to. What is noteworthy in this passage is the almost inevitable use of French and the less strong relationship between the topic of discussion and codes being used.

What is more, code-mixing occurred between AA and French instead of English in all *Amin*’s recorded discussions, as given here:

“**napripari**” (je me prépare) – *I prepare myself*

“**kitcompari**” (lorsque tu compare) – *when you compare*

“**ysilaksioniw**” (sélectionnent) – *they select*

Actually, the fact that, AA-English code-mixing did not happen throughout the entire interactions may imply the absence of influence that living in the UK may have on FL use. It seems also compatible with *Amin*’s supposition that LS cannot easily happen in a short period of stay.

Amin was observed in the accommodation while he was preparing dinner. *Amin* is not a regular goer to the university, but rather prefers to study at the accommodation’s study room. He was observed in a locale where he usually stays and was not involved in observation sessions more than once. In one of the casual visits to him, he was under observation for 3 hours long while preparing dinner with *Sara*, his betrothed.

According to the interactions, *Amin* seemed to deploy a multilingual repertoire in general. In most cases, French was used as a predominant embedded code alongside AA in particular. This certainly matched his prior perceptions that he maintained French. In the first place, the topic of conversation was the 3MT (three minutes thesis). *Amin*, while explaining the criteria of 3MT, used French beside AA, more than English. This may suggest beyond doubt French LM as a predominant embedded code. In comparing between the criteria followed in assessing 3MT performance in the UK and Australia, he professed:

“Hna l **criteria** nta3 a **three minutes**, machi kima ydirou fi **Australia**, hadouk ychoufou wa7ad kifach **kiyaprésender {fr}**, **la recherché {Fr}** nta3o tkoun **compliqué {Fr}**, howa t7ada had a so3oba, kima nta3 X, yakhdam **application{Fr}** mliha! **de tout façon {Fr}** lali marba7ch ya9dar ydirha fi **conference{Fr}** **Excerpt 35**

The criteria of three minutes thesis in the UK are different from Australia. In Australia, they check the complexity of the research, and how the researcher challenges this complexity. For example, in X research, he is working on a very interesting application. In all cases, there are other opportunities for the losers, they can present again in conferences

Although the topic is research related (3MT), the participant used FL as a predominant embedded code. This may suggest, as mentioned before, French LM, regardless of any factor, except the interlocutor (Algerian friendship ethnolinguistic groups). Actually, the interlocutor in this session, was Kabyle (See **Appendix 2** to check *Sara’s* profile). The use of French could be reinforced by that, despite that *Amin’s* practices in focus group sessions with different sub-ethnicities revealed similar linguistic practices (French LM).

More specifically, other sets of data may suggest LS to English (as a predominant embedded code); as a more relevant embedded code choice. *Amin* used English as a predominant embedded code choice with a shift in the topic of discussion to his current research. In describing the approach, he is following in his research, he explained:

“Ta9riban kima l **content** kima **thematic**, **je pense {Fr}** **thematic tesserayer {Fr}** tkharji **common themes**, Ena mdayar **deductive puisque {Fr}** jayab **themes** hadouk lakbar lilgithom min **literature review**, mnbe3d dart **categories** nta3 **data est que {Fr}** hadro 3liho” **Excerpt 36**

Thematic and content analysis are approximately the same. I think in thematic analysis, you can draw common themes (...) I followed the deductive approach, because I got themes according to the literature review, then I discussed data accordingly

In here, one can notice an interplay between the linguistic practices and the academic identity of the speaker. One may further postulate that English was used because of the referential function that the topic implies (check **Excerpts 4** and **19**). The topic is also related to a current

interest. However, *Amin* shifted again to use French as a predominant embedded code choice in speaking about Schengen states and France's VISA policy in particular:

Homa 3lah ymado l visa {Fr}, parceque {Fr} homa dork 3andhom la crise {Fr},
tzid takhroj l UK man L'europa {Fr}, donc {Fr} lazam yprofitiw {Fr} ydakhlo
draham plus {Fr}, kitrohi mana tachri les cadeaux {Fr}, tachri les
souvenirs {Fr}, transport {Fr}, C'est ça {Fr} a tourisme {Fr} lazam ykoun 'qwai
(....)

Excerpt 37

Have you ever questioned why France, as part of Schengen states, does not have a strict visa policy? They are going through an economic crisis, especially when UK gets its independence from Europe. Then, it should make advantages through strengthening its tourism field. Basically, tourists buy gifts, souvenir sets –not to mention- travelling fees and hotels. In a word, they make sure that the tourism field is strong enough (...)

The topic of discussion was in particular related to France. FL use was thereby reasonably anticipated. *Amin*, in recalling some moments that he spent in France, used so many French words. In this excerpt, he expressed his attempt to speak French:

"(...) Kima ro7na la France {Fr}, nas kamel y9olo ohh tu parle français parfaitement {Fr} wena ngasar bark, nessayer {Fr} nkharbat bark mais en fin {Fr} lqit ro7i sure tout {Fr} m3a ton oncle {Fr} (appreciation)!"

Excerpt 38

When we went to France, all people thought I am a good speaker of French. All were saying "Ohh you speak French fluently", and I was just giving it a try. Finally, I could make it with your uncle help (appreciation)!

Predictably, the speaker used French because the topic is related to France. The topic may imply more affective (social function), and that could result in FL being used as a predominant embedded code choice, instead of English. His linguistic practices could indicate that there are less mobility effect. What is probably new is the incorporation of English to the complex mix of resources.

Participant 5: Souzan

Social context	Topic	Total number of words used	Percentage of AA words	French words	English words
Office	(1)Food	37	72.98%	6(16.21%)	4(10.81%)
	(2)Research	223	52.93%	14(6.27%)	91(40.80%)
	(3)International political issues	142	77.48%	16(11.26%)	16(11.26%)
Accommodation	(4)Fashion	79	67.10%	10(12.65%)	16(20.25%)
	(5)Movies	130	65.39%	10(7.69%)	35(26.92%)
	(6)British culture	60	51.67%	5(8.33%)	24(40%)
Restaurant	(6)Marriage	420	78.10%	35(8.33%)	57(13.57%)
	(7)Songs	103	71.86%	9(8.73%)	20(19.41%)
	(8)Algerian culture	58	65.52%	5(8.62%)	15(25.86%)

Table 5. 23: *Souzan's* linguistic practices according to topics and settings

According to *Souzan's* previous perceptions, the use of French has declined since she was in Algeria due to the implementation of EL in her secondary school education. Regarding this, she reported "I am a shifter since I was in Algeria, the change already took place in Algeria". In another passage, she further expounded " (...) I am using Arabic with a lot of English, English is my second language (...) I am using French rarely".

During the intragroup interaction with her Algerian colleagues in the focus group sessions, *Souzan* seemed to use a multilingual repertoire, with FL being rarely used. If looked at from Pauwels's (2016) suggested definition, this could tell that she maintained multilingualism. In the meanwhile, the recordings in the observed sessions chiefly showed that, beside AA, English was used more than French, except for the issue of food. One may then say that this is a case of traditional LS, shifting to English as a predominant embedded code. This LS, one may reflect, already happened before mobility. Therefore, it can be an extended LS.

In the topic of food, *Souzan* did not speak too much, and that seemingly resulted in less observable linguistic behaviours. Actually, *Souzan* already acknowledged that she still uses some French words as part of AA in some topics such as food, songs and movies. These words are already adjusted to the spoken variety. This would also go against viewing languages as separate, bounded entities.

Code-mixing (at the word level) took place more with French, despite the participant identifying herself as a shifter in the sense of using English as a predominant embedded code. This can strengthen the point that FL is part of the Algerian spoken variety and hard to detach.

Similar to *Sonia*, *Souzan* used more English words alongside AA to discuss the topic of research. That could be always related to the professional identity developed by the participants upon their residence in the UK. In discussing research topic, although the dimension of discussion consisted of both research in Algeria and in the current context, she deployed more AA-English than AA-French code-switching. A good example of this is when she wondered, speaking about how she is going to collect the data of her research and approach the participants:

(....) 3andi **PhD students** ‘hnaya ‘w3andi **PhD students** fi bal 3abas wa7din man baskra , ‘w qonsantina (...)raham man **different places** fi **pla9a {Fr}** wa7da **and this is what facilitates it to me to find them** khatar **I am not sure** bali nalqahom...wana mada baya l **characteristics** ‘nt3hom ykono **static** balak na5dam ghir ‘m3a ta3 **LMD** ,,, chghol **age** wa7ad , nabghi kolchi **bien réglé{Fr}** , ‘wtabqali hadik **lpossibilité {Fr}** liqal 3liha X **cinquant pourcent {Fr}** bali qadrin mayatjawbouch ‘m3ak(....)

Excerpt 39

My research sample includes PhD students here in the UK and PhD students from different Algerian provinces such as Sidi Bel Abbès, Biskra and Constantine. They should belong to different places and study in one university. This is the only way that I can approach them easily. It is hoped that the participants’ characteristics would be static. I may approach LMD students with a similar age. I wish everything will be well organised. Even though, one should always expect, as X said, that 50% of the whole sample may not be responding

Notably, while speaking about her data collection plans back home, *Souzan* used AA-French-English code-switching. Yet, she used English as the predominant embedded code choice to detail how she would approach participants. This is in line with what she assumed earlier that English is her second language in rank. It can be said that AA-English-French code-switching represents earlier stages of LS. So, code-switching is an important sign of LS especially among newly arrived mobile individuals in contexts of short-term mobility.

The topic of research could be categorised as having a referential function (informative function), as referred to in *Sonia* and *Karim’s* cases.

Surprisingly enough, in discussing international political issues, equal switching with both embedded codes (French and English) was detected. One would predict more switching with English in non-Algerian related context issues instead, as assumed earlier. As an instance, the

American election - a prevalent topic in media by the time the intragroup interactions were held - the participant commented:

“Trump oui c'est vrai, he is a tough, basa7 min jiha rahi positive parce que {Fr} houwa mag3adch mdaraq houma yakarho les musulmans {Fr} whadi mahich 7aja jdida jabha trump 5rajha toul”

Excerpt 40

It is true that Donald Trump is tough, but it is very positive for Muslims when he was elected because he made the Americans' attitudes towards Muslims more explicit

As an illuminating point, the participant used the French word “**les musulmans**” instead of expressing it through the use of English “Muslims” to align with the nature of the discussed topic. This practice can be related to the willingness of the participant to express her identity through a code, which could be closer to her ethnic origins (ethnoreligious group). Although *Souzan* is not in favour of performing FL use, it is not easy to detach it from the linguistic history of Algeria, a Muslim country where she was born and bred. Using French words as such could denote a social function due to the social meanings attached to it.

On many occasions, *Souzan* tended to use English with a little use of Arabic and French words, regardless of the topic being discussed. This may suggest her strong tendency to be a full shifter to English as a second language. The decline in the multilingual nature of her repertoire (LS in the new perspectives), can happen with longer mobility periods. In giving her viewpoint about fashion, she discussed:

“Al fashion, for me hya tariqat labs machhora aw inchiharat because of celebrity, it does not mean it is not meaningful we cannot make it so! Of course, we can!” {emphasis}

Excerpt 41

For me, Fashion is a famous way of dressing, or rather a way of dressing that is developed because of celebrity. If something looks less meaningful, it does not mean, we cannot make it so! Of course, we can!

As seen, *Souzan* started using Arabic to define fashion, then – all of a sudden - moved to English. This could suggest how strong the tendency to use English was. In another extract, in debating feminism upon the marriage issue, she argued:

“(...) biologically they are different, but they should be equal in different ways. Feminism hya is that men and women should be treated equally ‘3la ‘l achievements liydirouha wal hard work liydirouha, yala fiha equal commitments”

Excerpt 42

Men and women are biologically different, but they should be equal in different ways. Feminism is that men and women should be treated equally on the basis of the achievements that they accomplish, hard word and equal commitments.

In both excerpts, the function of conversation seemed to trigger the predominant use of English. The participant tended to use English as an appropriate embedded code choice in utterances that carry a referential function (high information content). In both cases (**Excepts 41 and 42**), the switching between AA and English was not equal and English appeared as a base language instead. One may say that *Souzan* used AA just to fulfil the requirements of sessions’ instructions. She would probably have used only English – a point which is in favour of LS in the case of longer mobility.

In the observation sessions, participants were left freely to discuss whatever topics in intragroup interactions. The participant, as the case of the other research subjects, was using a playful mix of linguistic resources. In the first place, *Souzan* was observed while she was preparing for her wedding party. She got married to a Scottish Pakistani. While arranging for her wedding party, *Souzan* talked about research, a daily activity that she cannot seem to switch off thinking. By the time of observation, the participant had just passed her transfer/upgrade event. In this main respect, she joyfully expressed her happiness of receiving an email from her DOS (director of studies):

“ (...) Ba3tatli email qati well done for the presentation! gatli, I am glad that you did your best(...) kanat khayfa khatar fa sujet {Fr} nta3 social media hia khatiha ...hia fi gender”

Excerpt 43

My supervisor emailed me to express her joy that I did well (...) she was bit worried because she is not specialised in social media studies, but in gender!

As other cases, it becomes obvious that the use of English alongside AA was to match with her academic identity as a PhD student. What is more, similar to *Karim* and *Sara*, she used

English as the predominant embedded code to express quotations. As explained before, conveying words of others as they are, especially a written extract, may imply a referential function. This is not the only case where she used quotations. Speaking about her partner and the stress he was going through because of wedding preparations, she said:

“ (...) Howa broh7ah khowaf, gali **I am stressed** (...) had sab7a 9otlo nod dirli **rehearsal**, 9ali **you think I am sleeping; I am listening to you** (...)” **Excerpt 44**

He was worried (...) this morning, I awakened him to watch my rehearsal for my upgrade event, then he replied “ I am not sleeping, I am listening to you”.

In another excerpt, the participant was joyfully reporting her partner’s promise for a special treat because she successfully passed her transfer event:

“ (...) qali **I will treat you today, you did a great job** (...)” **Excerpt 45**
He said “I will treat you today, you did a great job”

So, on many occasions, *Souzan* used English as the predominant embedded code when drawing quotations of non-Algerians speakers (UK encounters).

Within the same speech event, she switched back to talk about her wedding preparation. Interestingly, *Souzan* used French (as a predominant embedded code) to describe her wedding outfit:

“Chrit sabat nta3 **la robe blanche {Fr}** t7abi tjarbiha? antia tlabsi qadi, **c'est a dire la taille {Fr}** nta3i? wachrit wa7d **des trucs transparents {Fr}** yatlabso m3a **la robe {Fr}** **Excerpt 46**

I bought shoes for my white dress. Do you want to try my white dress? I mean do we have the same size? I also bought some transparent braces for my white dress

The use of French could imply more a social function. Wedding outfit is a social (personal) aspect of the participant’s life, instead of an academic one.

On another occasion, *Souzan* invited me (the researcher), with other Algerians, to her kitchen for dinner. As usual, *Souzan*, in deploying multilingual resources, used English as the predominant embedded code beside the matrix language AA, either to quote her partner,

DOS, her kitchen mates, second supervisor and future mum in law. Her use of English was more related to the aforementioned interlocutors, as part of the current stay experience.

In the opening of the dinner, Souzan welcomed us: “ (...) **Thank you guys** 3ali jitou la **dinner**, dartalkoum 7rira wdartloukom **soupe {Fr}** wa **chips** Chritalkom **cake!**” **Excerpt 47**

Thank you guys for coming to the dinner, I prepared soup, chips and bought a cake for you!

At the linguistic level, one can notice the deployment of EL words as the embedded language during all interactions. By the time of dinner invitation, the participant was getting ready for a poster presentation in the annual research students conference. In this respect, she worryingly put:

“(...) Ana ghodwa **npresenti {Fr}** l **poster**, 9olili wesh homa l **criteria** bah ntaba3 3lihom, fi **school** nta3na kayan X w ena besa7 ma3labalish wesh ndir, manish mkamla **methodology** (...)” **Excerpt 48**

(...) I am going for a poster presentation tomorrow; guys tell me about the criteria to follow during my preparation. In my school, X and I are going to present, but I am not sure how I am going to manage the presentation, I did not finish the methodological chapter (...)

In this excerpt, the student’s academic identity as a researcher and the use of English as a predominant embedded code choice seemed to be matching. In another instance, the participant recalled her success in her transfer event, in which she was using English to quote or to report her assessor’s feedback:

“(...) Goltalha Al **assessor** nta3i ktabli **satisfactory progress... worth contributions to the field and that student well presented her work** (....)” **Excerpt 49**

(...) I was telling X that my assessor notified a satisfactory progress in my PGR platform, worth contributions to the field and emphasised that I well-presented my work (...)

In this section, the use of English for a referential function is made clear. However, outside academia, she switched back to use French as the predominant embedded code. *Souzan*, while thanking everyone for coming to the dinner at the end of it, was using multilingual

resources, in which French was the predominant embedded language. For instance, in making sure that we keep in touch with her in the future, she requested:

Labnat tfaraqna mara othra, tab9aw tjiwni, ali tabghi edir **conférence {Fr}** tji 3andi, makanch **hôtel {Fr}** l3am ljay tjiw tal9aw **petite {Fr}** X wela **petit {Fr}** Y ydour (...) **Excerpt 50**

Girls! When you leave the country after we finish your PhDs, you should maintain coming to me. If it happens and you come for a conference, you should not go to hotels instead. At that time, you will find my little girl or boy playing around (...)

The use of French to speak about issues related to the country of origin was also illustrated in many occasions of data set. For example, the participant, when replying to *Sara* who advised her to go back to Algeria during their intragroup interactions in my own kitchen, declared:

“(...) **oui {Fr}** besah ghir bah ndir **l'équivalence{Fr}**, wn9olhom bali nakhdam fi hadak **le poste{Fr}** mnbe3d nji (...) howa 9ali **we go for payment plan** besah bezef nkhalas l3am lawal etani etalath,,3am saba3 **non coupage {Fr}!** **Excerpt 51**

Yes! But just to do the equivalence, and get the specified job placement, then I will come back to Scotland (...) my partner asked me to go for the payment plan, but it is too much to pay back all this amount of moneyit's never ending!

Words like “**l'équivalence**” (equivalence) and “**le poste**” (job) seem to be more properly expressed in French as a more appropriate language to an Algerian context than English.

All things considered, it is clear from the findings that the participant's self-reported language use aligned with her linguistic behaviours in the observed sessions. This could confirm that the participant is aware of her linguistic behaviours. There seemed no obvious influence of the social setting (locale) on the produced linguistic behaviours and - in all settings, be it arranged or not - English was secondly used after AA, usually to indicate quotations. The fewer factors influencing LS at a micro level (during interactions) can be an interesting outcome of short-term mobility.

Participant 6: *Schahin*

Social context	Topic	Total number of words used	Percentage of AA words	French words	English words
Office	(1)Food	61	85.26%	5(8.19%)	4(6.55%)
	(2)Research	157	86%	12(7.64%)	10(6.36%)
	(3)International political issues	158	87.98%	12(7.59%)	7(4.43%)
Accommodation	(4)Fashion	110	71.82%	31(28.18%)	0(0%)
	(5)Movies	402	84.59%	53(13.18%)	9(2.23%)
	(6)British culture	307	78.84%	59(19.21%)	6(1.95%)
Restaurant	(6)Marriage	86	90.71%	3(3.48%)	5(5.81%)
	(7)Songs	46	84.79%	4(8.69%)	3(6.52%)
	(8)Algerian culture	26	80.77%	5(19.23%)	0(0%)

Table 5. 24: *Schahin's* linguistic practices according to topics and settings

In the previous claims of the participant, he assumed that FL use is about to be lost due to EL domination - at the level of his linguistic repertoire. To illustrate this, he pointed out: “ (...) we are not using French that much, it starts to vanish away, and it starts to be decreasing, while English is increasing in our personal repertoires (...)”. In another extract, he confirmed: “ (...) I do speak English more, I use more English words, and some French words have been replaced by English words”. Accordingly, this may suggest that he perceived himself as a shifter to English as a predominant embedded code during his interaction with Algerian colleagues.

According to focus group findings, multilingual practices did not decline, compared to his perceived pre-mobility linguistic practices, and this can be identified as a case of LM (in Pauwels’s new perspective). From a traditional LM/LS point of view, the status of French at the level of his linguistic repertoire was not retreated (this may suggest that he maintained FL as a predominant embedded code beside the matrix language AA and English). The percentages approximately showed that code-switching/mixing occurred more with regards to FL than English. Thereby, he alternated between AA and French codes more than he did with English. One can draw an important characteristic of LM within short-term mobility in relation to that. LM can happen through processes of code-switching and mixing (maintenance of multilingual repertoire).

However, on many occasions in the data, the participant code-switched and mixed with his community languages (AA and French) to shift back to home situations, and used AA-English-

French code-switching and AA-English code mixing to express present situations related to the host country.

To illustrate this, in speaking about marriage, where *Schahin* did not speak too much, the statement that was related to Algerian context was expressed through the lens of switching between AA (matrix language) and French (predominant embedded language). In comparing weddings in Algeria with the UK, he elucidated:

“**Voilà {Fr}** kima 7na ‘f **l’Algérie {Fr}**, kayan hadouk limayala7qoch, ‘ydiro 3ars bal **credit {Fr}**. ‘hna ‘ydirou 3ars fa **church** way5al9o ‘wtanik ‘tji **very expensive as well**” **Excerpt 52**

In Algeria, there are some partners who are unable to cover their wedding expenses and therefore borrow some money. However, English couples celebrate their weddings in the church, but still very expensive as well

In the first place, he used AA-French code-switching to explain some Algerian traditions. In the other part of the sentence that was related to the host context, AA-English codes occurred instead.

In another illuminating example, *Schahin* alternated more with FL when he spoke about research back home and switched to English instead when he did with the present lived-in context. Conversely, the majority of previous participants deployed AA-English code-switching in discussing research topic.

Speaking about the procedures that he followed in his research, he narrated:

“**les profs {Fr}** za3ma qalouli makach mouchkil wa3tawli **facebook** nta3hom mba3dika daro,,,w **le malheur {Fr}** ‘ydirlak **vue {Fr}** way5alihalak haka, ana **déjà {Fr}** manaqdarch nafrad ‘3lik **déjà {Fr}** | **ethics** hnaya yqoulak **don’t oblige them to participate** “ **Excerpt 53**

Some “teachers” promised me to take part in my research after I had approached them via Facebook. Unfortunately, some of them had withdrawn and what made me pissed off is when they had seen my text in Facebook and did not reply. I can’t oblige them anyways, aligning with ethics guidelines here!

So, it could be concurred that the tendency to alternate more with English than with French can occur with the dimension of discussion being shifted from one context to another (home/host). For more illustrations, the issue of Algerian culture (a homeland related issue), recorded no use of English words according to the findings disseminated above. Similar to *Souzan*, *Schahin* switched from English to FL use in some cases, because it seemed a more convenient way to express his identity. A clear example for this is when he shifted from using English to using French in discussing British culture issue:

“ana qatli ‘3liha X hadik ‘likanat m3aya **first floor**, hadik houma 3andhom fal’y3tiqadat ‘ysomo 40 youm mayaklouch 7aja moufadala 3andhom, hadak houwa **the great fasting** kima ‘7na **les musulments {Fr}** 3andna ramdan” **Excerpt 54**

My friend X, one of my previous accommodation mates, who used to live with me in the first floor, told me that they have some events like the great fasting. The great fasting is about preventing from eating a particular food for 40 days. It is remotely like Ramadan for us “Muslims”

What could be more informative in this analysis is the point that the participant used English as a predominant embedded code to express the host culture. In this respect, in the first statement, when he was speaking about the great fasting, the most important fasting season in the church for Christians, he used more English words. However, he shifted back to French in the second part and used the utterance “**7na les musulmans**, “**we Muslims**” to refer to the identical tradition for Muslims which is Ramadan. It is also significant to mention that *Schahin* used the pronoun “we” to single out his identity and express belongingness. The latter may suggest a social function.

The transcripts also detected further linguistic behaviours concerning FL use. As far as code-mixing is concerned, the participant applied code-mixing only once: “**puibliyethom** “I posted them” to speak about some extracts from books. He borrowed the grammatical structure of AA and applied it in the French word “**publier**”.

In a word, *Schahin* switched back and forth between the three codes AA, French and English which is exactly the case reported by him in previous perceptions. However, he put that English is used more than French in the current context, which is not the case. As long as his

perceptions did not exactly match with observed linguistic practice, one may assume that he was making immediate linguistic decisions that he is a shifter, while deterministic LS within short-term mobility may rarely happen. One may further reflect that the mismatch between perceptions and behaviours can be a result of short-term mobility, in which individuals tend to have unstable linguistic dispositions and practices.

However, in observation sessions, when compared to focus group sessions, French use decreased in use on many occasions, while English was used as the predominant embedded code. This would confirm *Amin's* assumption that LS can occur over a longer period of time. By the time of observation sessions, participants had more than a three years period of stay, unlike the focus group sessions, being held within a shorter period of stay (almost two years). One can say that LS started to happen with a longer time of stay. It can happen though AA-English-French code-switching (English was the predominant embedded code) and AA-English code mixing.

As previous instances of data, French was mostly used when speaking about topics related to back home. In one of the observation sessions that was held in the university library, where the participant usually goes, the participant was interacting during a break time with other Algerian students. *Schahin* seemed to use French in relation to the person he was speaking about (as part of the Algerian context). He used the French word “**connexion**” (network connection) in speaking about a failed call which he received from his sister back home:

“ (...) Okhti ma3andhach **connexion {Fr}** wt3ayatlimanich 3araf mnin bghatha tjiha **connexion {Fr}** (surprise!) (...)” **Excerpt 55**

My sister has a weak access to net, and she is trying to call me... How comes, she won't be able to [surprise]!

Within the same locale (café within the university library), he used French as the predominant embedded code to indicate his intolerance with French people because of historical reasons:

“Wa7ad man **frança {Fr}** b3atli **invitation, accepitah {Fr}** ghir bach ngolah rana ghir ayamat mali htafalna **ciq juiet {Fr}, jour de l'indépendance {Fr}** [anger!] **Excerpt 56**

A French Facebook user sent me a friendship request. I accepted him just to remind him of our Independence Day celebration that was held in the 5th of July (few days ago)

In here, *Schahin* deployed French words both in relation to back home historical event and in relation to the person he was speaking about (as indicated in the previous excerpt). However, LS to English as the predominant embedded code choice appeared to be linked to the topic (current context; UK one) and the interlocutor (the person speaking about). Within the same speech event, the participant, while speaking about commonwealth citizens, shifted to English as the predominant embedded code:

Britain kikharjat man almosta3marat nta3ha dartalhom **commonwealth**, yjiw ya9ro baltal as a **UK citizen** wya3tohom al **accommodation for free** wya3tohom **opportunities to work, the best example is X for free**, ghir tadi **bachelor** nta3ak **appliquer {Fr}** hna fil **UK**, wkiyadou al **visa** al **que** khfifa 3lihom, takhrajalhom fi **one week** **Excerpt 57**

The past colonies of the British Empire are more privileged due to the commonwealth policy. The former colonies, therefore, when coming to UK are treated as UK citizens. They are given the right for free education, free accommodation and many opportunities for employment. The best example is X. When he got his Bachelor, he easily started applying for research degrees in UK institutions. The least example is that there are less busy ques when they apply for visa, and they get their visas in one week

In recommending his friend (an Algerian newcomer) to opt for a flat, instead of student accommodation, he promised:

“ Dork nsaqsi **Let it** ila kayan **flat** fal **buiding** lirani fih ana (...), tkhalas ghir **electricity**, ‘I **electricity** matjich bezef, al **maximum {Fr}** falmachta tjik khamsin, (...) **non {Fr}** anti diri **viewing** wchoufi”

Excerpt 58

I will ask in LET IT agency, for available flats in my building! (...) Bills are not included! However, they are not too expensive; maximum of fifty pounds in winter (...) nope! You should go for viewing first!

This further may suggest the strong relationship between the topic, interlocutor (the person speaking about) and the code choice. The use of English words can be related to the topic of discussion (current context related issues). Regarding the function of the topic, the participant seemed to offer instructions and guidance that implied more a referential function as opposed to a social one. A similar function was illustrated in **(Excerpt 57)**, in which the participant spoke about a high- in-information topic, with a referential function.

To sum up, this chapter presented a detailed representation of the data that was mostly qualitative in nature. While interviews explained perceived linguistic practices, the questionnaire further included the experiences of a larger student population, thus strengthening the conclusions. According to perceptions in both interviews and questionnaire, LS was assumed more than LM. Findings from both focus group and observation sessions, as yet, may imply less evidence of LM/LS, and that was challenging to detect, as predicted earlier. The linguistic practices presented what would inform more interactionist perspectives, mainly the theory of code choice. The actual behaviours data can also inform new perspectives in the study of language, globalisation and mobility because of the flexibility and fluidity that characterise the participants' multilingual practices.

However, these findings can also explain nascent stages of LM/LS presented through processes of code-switching and mixing, rather than deterministic LM/LS. Having said that, from both Pauwels's (2016, 2019) new perspectives and traditional LM/LS, data suggested both the maintenance of multilingual repertoires and the maintenance of FL as a predominant embedded code choice, alongside AA and English. Results also revealed both alignment and inconsistency between perceptions and behaviours. This non-static relationship can be again related to the context of this research; short-term mobility, with a guaranteed return to the country of origin. The next chapter will present meaning making drawn of these interesting findings, and discuss them in terms of the research questions, in the light of existing literature and in relation to relevant theoretical stances.

CHAPTER SIX: DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The previous chapter presented the key findings about the linguistic experiences of Algerian students during their short period of stay in the UK. Given the complexity which is highlighted in the new paradigm of mobility studies by scholars such as Blommaert (2014), the present study, through employing multiple methods, attempted to grasp part of this complexity. In the field of LM/LS, Jamaï (2008) contended that “language use and maintenance among immigrant communities is a complex area of study for newly established minorities” (p.307). This study, as well as other studies around newly established communities, illustrated this assertion. While data gained from all tools confirmed some findings of existing research, others seemingly did not appear in alignment with it, and, in a very few cases, there is insufficient relevant evidence to generate a meaningful discussion. In general, the questions that I set out to guide all stages of my research inquiry were satisfactorily answered. In spite of the fact that this research departed from perspectives drawn from LM/LS as a theoretical framework, the discussion around the research questions altogether gave credit to a combination of other influencing theories and approaches such as translanguaging, language choice theory, social-psychological approach and social-identity theory.

Question one was designed to obtain a set of perceptions around the pre-mobility attitudes about FL and its use in the verbal repertoires of the selected cohort. On this point, two opposing views were drawn: while group “A” has a positive pre-mobility experience with FL, group “B” has not.

The second question explored the potential effects of crossing borders and living in the UK on both attitudes around FL and its use. Data, at this point, could propose a perceived language change, identified as traditional LS (one language replacing the other). Compared to pre-mobility perceptions towards FL and its use, traditional LS to English was more reported than maintenance of FL use. In other words, the majority of participants in both the interview and questionnaire data interpreted their perceived sociolinguistic stance as shifters to English. However, that the participants conceived that they still use a range of linguistic resources can explain the case of LM according to Pauwels’s (2016) initial definition. It is further reflected that these identified LM/LS practices are not deterministic. They might be rather

earlier/nascent stages of LM/LS, temporary linguistic practices as they can be extended processes.

Question three subsequently aimed at identifying the factors/aspirations that can play a critical role in both conceived behaviours (LM/LS). Sociohistorical, aspirational, current and post-mobility factors jointly contribute to constructing the push and pull factors influencing perceived LM/LS among the participants (short-stay students, travelling in the light of educational mobility). In this vein, data seemed to be more influenced by traditional LM/LS factors as the research subjects, in most cases, tended to be affected by the structural/functional policies associated with the country of origin.

Question four was meant to compare and contrast how previous perceptions are linked, or not, to the observed practices. In relation to this, unlike perceived practices which somehow revealed evidence of LM/LS, actual behaviours tended to be much more indicative of flexible linguistic practices, than they are LM/LS. In a closer examination, when reflecting participants' perceived LM/LS on actual behaviours, some findings suggested inconsistency between both types of speech data. The inconsistency can be interpreted as a result of an aspirational identity that participants built. Those assuming LS seemed to be more influenced by their academic/professional identity and thus assuming that English is becoming predominantly used as an embedded code beside AA, during their period of stay.

The last research question was devised to detect the linguistic markers through which assumed LM/LS can be illustrated in situations of short-term mobility. As an answer to this question, the discussion will touch lightly on two significant points:

- In presenting assumed LM/LS in actual behaviours, one may reflect that translanguaging, code-switching and mixing can be potential linguistic markers illustrating earlier stages of French LM/LS to English (identified previously in participants' perceptions). The study then could imply a strong relationship between these linguistic behaviours (translanguaging, code-switching/mixing) with LM/LS. What is also worth noticing is the peaceful relationship between code-switching/ mixing and translanguaging, seemingly occurring in concert with each other, instead of being opposing to each other.

- In detecting the social meanings behind code choice in relation to French and English, the topic of discussion (mode of discourse and the topic's function) is viewed as having a more explanatory power over other factors of code choice (such as physical setting). In other words, subjects' use of French and English varied according to the topic being discussed and the function of the discussion.

The discussion, below, is thereby modelled around answering thoroughly the research questions. Subsequently, the discussion section will briefly address a critical reflection on the usefulness and validity of LM/LS framework in the study of situations of short-term mobility as an important contribution to the field.

6.1 Pre-mobility Experience with FL

In order to discuss students' accounts of their experience with FL before transition, the following main points are addressed: attitudes towards FL, the perceived position at the level of their verbal repertoires (among other resources), the perceived functionality/status, the linguistic behaviours attached to it and the pre-mobility use of this language among Algerian colleagues (friendship domain) to align tightly with the context of the current field work.

As noticed, the findings generally revealed two major trends of data. Group **A** had positive attitudes towards FL, while group **B** did not. Benrabah (2007b) explained the complexity that portrays Algerians' views towards FL. For him, some of them viewed that French is a language which "symbolised foreign exploitation", and therefore should be eradicated, while others perceived it as universally valuable, a language of fraternity, and this can entail its maintenance worth (Benrabah, 2007b). Kadem (2015) mentioned an interesting point which slightly supports the second population trend of views in Benrabah (2007b). FL is no longer considered as the language of coloniser by the majority of targeted participants in his study who were Algerian EFL students, a closer context to my study (Kadem, 2015). It could be that they have no personal experience of the era of French colonisation, having all been born since 1962.

FL was perceived as a second language in the pre-mobility verbal repertoires of most participants in this project after L1. In this vein, previous research in the Algerian local context

revealed a paradox of views regarding the place of this language among Algerian verbal repertoires. For example, Hassaine (2011) claimed the duality of views prevailing in the Algerian speech community, one in which FL is a foreign language or of the other in which it is a second language.

In the findings, French was viewed as a native language (for example, *Sara* in interviews), a view that goes hand in hand with Battye, Hintze and Rowlett (2003)'s own assumption that French is considered as the native language of some Maghrebi nationals.

FL was also viewed by some students as strongly attached to L1, and therefore part of it. *Sonia*, for example, said: "Algerian Arabic and French, they go together (...) French is like a step in our language, you can't speak Algerian Arabic without French". In supporting that, Arfi (2014) elucidated the high integration of FL into AA words to the extent of confusion between words in both codes. The famous example mentioned in her study "Hdar bil 'Arbia! Ma: tqulsh pen! qul stylo!" (speak in Arabic: don't say "pen", say "Stylo"), where the speaker seemed to unconsciously consider the French word "stylo" as an AA one, is illustrative of participants' consideration of FL as part of L1 (Arfi, 2014, p.89). In the same fashion, Kadem (2015) found out that the majority of EFL students identified the nature of AA as a mixture of French and Arabic.

As for the perceived status and functionality in the Algerian landscape, there seems to be a strong link between previous research and my data. In common with scholars like Benrabah (2005, 2007a, 2007b, 2013, 2014), Aitsiselmi and Marley (2008) and Kadem (2015), it is associated with prestige; with Hassaine (2011), it indicates intellectuality; with Aitsiselmi and Marley (2008) and Benrabah (2007b, 2013), it holds economic value; and with others (Benrabah, 2005, Ali Chaouche, 2006), it is functional in different domains such as administration and higher education, therefore worth being used.

Interestingly, although acknowledging its high functionality and status, some findings implied attitudes of dissatisfaction and willingness of a linguistic change before mobility. Some participants viewed EL as a more worthwhile linguistic resource, in service across different domains and giving a better impact than FL would do. Benrabah (2014) proposed that there is an increasing awareness by Algerian youth towards the status of English as a global language since 2004. What is note-worthy in this study is that the findings generally supported

the misrepresentation of French/English as rivals in Algerian society, mentioned in Benrabah (2013). In other words, reinforcing EL status in Algeria and using it in the daily communication is not a prerequisite for eradicating French. This would also correspond with Benrabah's (2007b) findings, where the majority of high school students favoured additive multilingualism and linguistic diversity (Belmihoub, 2012, 2015). The subtractive desire is however, supported by the Algerian policy makers which is based on exclusion, as pointed to by Belmihoub (2012), Benrabah (2013) and Ghanmi (2019).

According to self-report, code-switching/mixing practices were acknowledged linguistic behaviours. Both phenomena were used to affect FL use among participants before their mobility. Tying back to the literature review, Kadem (2015) in his research -targeting Algerian EFL students- also made a point that the majority of participants admitted that they use code-switching.

AA-French and AA-French-English code-switching patterns are two most perceived practices that characterise the pre-mobility linguistic use of students. In intragroup interaction with Algerian students, AA-French code-switching pattern was the most adopted, with French being the predominant embedded code (as shown in the **Table 6.1**). These findings align with Kadem's ones that FL is the predominant unmarked variety (embedded code) alongside AA (matrix languages), and thereby, AA-French is the major code-switching form adopted by participants.

6.2 The Perceived Sociolinguistic Effects of Transition

6.2.1 Attitudes towards FL

According to some perceived views, there is what one may call "a shift in attitudes": a slight change in participants' perceptions towards their pre-mobility use of community languages in general and FL in particular. Latham Keh and Stoessel (2017) reasoned that individuals' attitudes and their linguistic efforts "may fluctuate through life as they experience new circumstances" (p.13). This shift in attitudes can be temporary and this is an important characteristic in interpreting individuals' linguistic practices in situations of short-term mobility, conditioned by return to the country of origin.

However, crossing borders did not seem to impinge on all participants' attitudes towards French (as a language). Some of them still hold positive views towards it, compared with opponents who conceived it as becoming less functional in the new context and irrelevant to use. Arfi (2008) and Jamaï (2008) drew similar conclusions regarding that, in the sense that the community languages became viewed as less functional among immigrants in the host setting (USA and UK respectively). From a critical point of view, Jamaï's and Arfi's studies represent cases of long-term migration and settlement contexts, therefore hard to be compared with the present research context (temporary mobility).

6.2.2 Verbal Repertoires Reshaping

FL was conceived by participants as retreated in status at the level of their verbal repertoires, while thought by others as either fully or slightly maintained in intragroup interactions. The following table (**Table 6.1**) importantly sums up the perceived code classification according to participants where LS (English became a predominant embedded code) seems to happen according to perceptions. This is quite evident in Mazzaferro (2018b) who claimed that code classification among immigrants is subject to restructuring. To expound this, he put "the reshaping of immigrants' linguistic repertoires has been conceived to happen through either additive and subtractive processes, commonly leading to the reallocation of immigrants languages at the High, Middle and Low steps of a hierarchal scale" (Mazzaferro, 2018b, p.89).

	Code classification in interview data (n=6)		Code classification in questionnaire data (n=32)	
	Pre-mobility experience	Current experience	Pre-mobility experience	Current experience
<i>Sonia</i>	AA –French	AA- <u>English-French</u>	1-AA	1-AA
<i>Karim</i>	AA-French- <u>English</u>	AA- <u>English-French</u>	2-French	<u>2-English</u>
<i>Sara</i>	AA-French Kabyle-French	AA-French-English	3-Berber dialects	3-French
<i>Amin</i>	AA-French	AA- <u>French-English</u>	<u>4-English</u>	-Berber dialects
<i>Souzan</i>	AA- <u>English-French</u>	AA- <u>English-French</u>		
<i>Schahin</i>	AA-French	AA- <u>English-French</u>		

Table 6. 1: A cross case analysis table summing up the position of FL within the verbal repertoires of students in intragroup interactions both before mobility and in the current setting

According to reported behaviours in (Table 6.1), participants started to use English either as a predominant embedded code, or beside FL as a predominant embedded one (identified LM/LS). What is noteworthy in major cases is the reallocation of resources without excluding any. Therefore, the additive multilingualism orientation among this professional group is clearly revealed. According to one of participants in interviews (*Amin*); “the more languages I use, the more I am satisfied about myself, French is no exception to this rule (...)”. Again, this can correlate well with Benrabah’s (2007b, 2013, and 2014) and Belmihoub’s (2018b) description of the Algerian population’s additive multilingual orientation.

6.2.3 LM/LS Practices

Before travelling to the UK, the participants had a multilingual repertoire according to their self-report behaviours (Table 6.1). With their mobility to the UK, perceived data may suggest that they maintained a set of linguistic practices. Pauwels (2016), in her last chapter, made an initial endeavour, suggesting that LM should be better studied in terms of multilingual practices: “(...) LM could be conceived as the maintenance of a multilingual repertoire even if the languages or codes upon which the individual or group draws change (...)”(pp. 183–184). That the participants conceived that they still practise multilingualism within the mobility context, one can say that they are maintainers (according to perceptions).

In a closer examination, results (Interviews: 4/6 participants and questionnaires: 22/32 participants) proposed that the codes upon which the participants drew changed. In other words, there is a shift in perceptions from considering FL as the predominant embedded code alongside AA, to English superseding it. Therefore, English currently appeared as the predominant embedded language alongside AA, getting a second position. A good example to define perceived LS is what *Sonia* summed up: "I think I replaced French with English in position, I mean I started making words in English suit my interaction and speech. I started using English as I used to use French before (...) I started code-switching with AA and English more (...)". From the traditional perspectives in LM/LS, this could represent the case of LS (it can be a temporary LS).

Jamai (2008), in a similar fashion, noted that Italian became the second language of Moroccans residing in Italy. Similar findings, but in situations of long-stay periods, were also discussed in Arfi (2008), who concluded that despite FL being embedded in the Algerian cultural and linguistic heritage, it has been replaced by English among Algerian nationals in America. Addressing language use among Kenyan university students, Michieka (2012) explored, by means of perceptions, that ethnic languages were losing ground to other languages, therefore Kenyan students shifted to other languages such Kiswahili, English, and Sheng.

Although LS was conceived as increasingly operating, for other participants an active French LM was acknowledged. Hence, other instances of data implied that French is not retreated in position and still used as the predominant embedded variety. In actual behaviours, maintainers retained AA-French and AA-French-English code-switching practices when topic or context called for it. This could indicate that LS cannot happen overnight, but over the course of a long period of time, as claimed in Buda (1992). Pauwels (2016), for example, claimed that a short period of stay is less influential on migratory linguistic practices.

In literature, many studies illustrated a growing evidence of LM in migratory settings such as Bortolato (2012), who found out how Italian nationals in Canada retained an attachment to their homeland languages and Perera (2015), among Sri Lankan migrants in Australia. In an Arab context, LM happened among young Moroccan immigrants in the UK (Jamai, 2008), among Algerian nationals in both USA and France (Arfi, 2008), among Arab families in

Manchester (Ottman, 2011), among Arab community in Vancouver (Canada) (Dweik, Nofal and Qawasmeh, 2014) and among two Arab speaking communities in the UK (Bichani, 2015). What could be different is the specific context of this study (short-term mobility rather than migration) and the exploration of LM among other linguistic resources, without being affected by the exclusion (subtractive process). In other words, FL was maintained alongside another embedded language (English), but more used than it. Actually, Bichani (2015) found out a similar datum, where one of the Algerian participants thinks that she uses Arabic as a first language, then French and then English during her daily life in the UK (Bichani, 2015, p.191).

The additive process can support more the basic principle of translanguaging which entails the use of different linguistic resources for the purpose of meaning making (Baker, 2011). This could mean that “meaning making is not confined to the use of ‘languages’ as discrete, enumerable, bounded sets of linguistic resources” (Blackledge and Creese, 2017, p.33). Consequently, one can say that LM/LS in this research are explained better from a translanguaging perspective.

6.2.4 Language Attrition

Beside LM/LS, participants’ views (see *Sonia* and *Souzan* in reported data) may suggest that their skills in FL had declined. Evidence of language attrition strengthens the assumption of the interconnectedness of language attrition, loss and LS (Aikhenvald, 2013). Mazzaferro (2018b) identified language attrition as an important step preceding LS. Some participants conceived that their skills and competence in FL were decreased due to either undertaking an English course (before mobility) or with transition. De Bot and Weltens (1991) similarly claimed that language attrition occurs when individuals change their linguistic habits. In practice, Arfi (2008) found out the attrition of FL proficiency among Algerian nationals in USA due to EL influence. However, Holmes (2013) countered the rapid decline in language proficiency as a result of acquiring another language – as is articulated in some of my data. In this vein, she put “competence in the language does not disappear overnight, it gradually erodes over time’ (p.60). Therefore, exploring linguistic behaviours within short-term mobility can be truly problematic due to the limited time.

6.2.5 Restrictions in the Domains of Use

In addition to the above-mentioned detected phenomena, data also implied restrictions in the domains of FL use. The perceived attitudes revealed that students, upon mobility, seem to encounter fewer domains where they can use FL. Holmes (2013) aligned with this assumption. For her, “with the spread of majority group language into more and more domains, the number of contexts in which individuals use the ethnic language diminishes” (p.60). Holmes addresses a context of migration, but not short-term mobility. On some occasions, participants brought to mention that they use French with AA when interacting with their Algerian fellows (friendship ethnolinguistic groups), a point that I, an insider researcher-student, also view as the most accessible mode of interaction to research the linguistic practices of this professional group in the UK. For them, FL is also used among some maintainers when communicating with other French-speaking students as further data suggested. This would give another possible domain of FL use which is not intragroup (intergroup friendship domain).

In the pre-mobility experience, the setting as a whole, including the topic, purpose, physical setting and interlocutor (discussed in Ritchie and Bhatia, 2013) has an explanatory power over code choice in general and FL use in particular. However, in the new setting, there seems a sharp focus on the interlocutor and the topic of discussion as key factors influencing FL with less regards to the physical setting. This can translate into less exposure, less extent of use, and evidences the restriction in FL-use domains as argued by Holmes (2013).

6.3 The Perceived Push and Pull Factors/Aspirations Indicative to French

LM/LS to English during Languaging

Relying on a cross-case analysis derived from both interviews and questionnaires, I shall discuss the factors which appeared to influence perceived French LM/LS to English. The self-report data from both tools suggested factors that can be much better explained through traditional LM/LS perspectives. Together with evidence from the research literature, one can build a potential typological framework that could help to explore factors influencing minority language use among international students with short periods of stay in general, and French postcolonial communities’ students studying in Anglophone countries, in particular. As briefly

noted earlier, the research subjects provided an interplay of some ‘homeland’ factors and other factors related to the new setting (UK). Notably, despite the overall sociolinguistic stance of participants being LS to English/shifters (according to their attitudes), the factors indicative to both behaviours (LM/LS) have nearly equal relation to the 1st and 2nd categories (See Figure 6.1). Therefore, I shall look at both variables in tandem.

Figure 6. 1: Factors/Aspirations influencing perceived French LM/LS to English among short-term mobility students

It would be worthwhile to mention that the evidence to which I compare my study comes from findings from situations of migration and long-term-settlements. While valuable to do in order to understand new forms of migration, caution needs to be exercised in drawing conclusions.

6.3.1 Homeland Related Factors

6.3.1.1 Personal Histories and Prior Experiences

“most of the Algerian students who live here and do not use French, they don't really use it in Algeria” (Sara)

The background from which Algerian mobile students originated seemed to influence perceived French LM/LS to English according to the data set. In contexts of migration, Perera (2015) highlighted the role that pre-migration experience could have on both LM/LS. At this

point, he argued: "migrants are also a product of particular conditions in the homeland prior to migration" (p.298). According to the participants' own reflections, the pre-mobility positive experience with EL was conceived as a supportive factor among shifters (participants who assumed LS). As previous (EFL) students, who studied English in higher education for almost five years, it could be argued that this period is sufficient in constructing some linguistic background about EL and its use. As a consequence, it is reasonable to include it in their daily verbal repertoires. Following this thread of argument, the mobility of these students to the UK can be seen as a golden opportunity for the use of English alongside AA more than French, because it is a more relevant code to the host environment. Despite that the previous context of use was purely educational, the transition could widen that former use. Clyne (2003), similarly included pre-migration experience as a factor that could support LS in situations of long-stay periods and settlement. Although this is a context of a short-term temporary mobility, perceived data suggested the influence of pre-mobility experience on LS. For example, *Souzan* in interviews and one participant in the questionnaire data (in the additional comments section), claimed that they already shifted to English, when they started learning English. Also, some participants' socio-historical profile indicated that they were EFL high school teachers and students, and therefore used to use some patterns of EL in their daily life course. In addition, other individuals' experiences revealed that they experienced a decline in their FL skills due to EL influence by the time they started learning it, all of which can promote LS. So, the positive pre-mobility experience with EL was somehow extended and even enhanced in the new setting abroad. This seemed to affect the informal interactional aspects of these Algerian students in some intragroup interactions; while the matrix language is AA, English is the predominant embedded language before French for these participants. Actually, this linguistic practice could more represent a case of language choice in general, than LS as it can be a temporary linguistic practice.

Likewise, other participants reported on some positive pre-mobility experiences with FL use. Actually, I previously made a review in the theoretical part on how Algerian speech communities maintained FL in post-colonial era in different domains, be it spoken or written. Benrabah (2007a) fully investigated how French was maintained among the Algerian speech communities in independent Algeria. As for Algerian EFL students in higher education, Kadem (2015) found out that FL was conceived as a language of prestige among Algerian EFL

students. French was also highly used in alternation with AA in different settings, unlike English that was reported as limited in use, among that type of interlocutor.

Other findings from both interviews and questionnaires may suggest some awareness regarding the linguistic competition between French and English in Algeria. Participants seemingly got influenced by this situation. In literature, Stoessel (2002) supported this point. He argued that the status of L1 in the home country can influence immigrants' attitudes about it. As a way of illustration, he studied an important case of Taiwanese immigrants who came from an environment which is characterised with a linguistic struggle between two languages, Mandarin Chinese and Taiwanese. Chinese was imposed on people of Taiwan and that had led the Taiwanese participants in his research to be influenced by the situation back home.

So, as a minority language which was already exposed to competition with another language (English) in mainland Algeria, FL among some participants did not seem to be negatively affected in the new environment, as they already gained experience in dealing with its maintenance back home. Kloss (1966) classified pre-migration experience as a "clear-cut" factor which similarly entails that if a minority language succeeded in its maintenance before migration, this triggers its continued maintenance in a migratory setting (Pauwels, 2016).

6.3.1.1.1 Context of One's Upbringing

As a subset to pre-mobility experience, it is revealed that the context where the participants raised is an important factor influencing the continuity of a FL beside AA in a mobility setting. For Michieka (2012), context of one's upbringing is related to the micro-geographical location as to whether his participants belong to urban or rural areas. Context of one's upbringing is an important indicator for indigenous LM among Kenyan university students or their shift to English, as those from rural areas preserved their indigenous languages more than those from urban areas, who tended to shift to English (Michieka, 2012). One of the participants in interviews similarly related her pre-mobility negative experience of FL use to the rural area where she was raised (See *Souzan* in chapter five: Section 5.1): "(...) I think this is related to the rural environment that I was living in, but if you compare it with an urban area, like my relatives in the city, they are more exposed to French".

In my research, this mini-factor was further expanded to the larger geographical location of participants' backgrounds: coastal, middle and Saharan cities. *Sonia*, for example, viewed that FL use differs from one geographical location to another, and therefore, it is more diffused in the coastal cities than the interior ones. On an anecdotal-evidence basis, Algerian Mediterranean cities citizens, be it from the east or the west, have a more striking use of FL in their daily interactions than people from middle cities and Saharan ones. It can be said that the change in frequency of French use shifts gradually the further from the coast one moves. One may relate it to the past colonisation of Algeria by the French as speculated by Benrabah (2007a, 2013), that the European settlers were more based in coastal Mediterranean strips. Consequently, the Algerians' settlements beside the French-speaking regions (colons), and the social interaction between them has led to reinforcing FL use. Currently, there seems to be more French use in cities that were populated by the French colons, than those that were not settled by the aforementioned European groups, namely middle and Saharan cities.

In the web-based questionnaire, although the majority of participants derive from Mediterranean cities (east of Algeria mainly), their linguistic practices - according to their perceptions - proposed that they are using English as a predominant embedded code beside AA. Despite the fact that these participants are coming from an area with a stronger FL base, they still viewed themselves as shifters (using English as a predominant embedded code alongside AA). This could be related to the mobility effects as well as the academic focus they are involved in.

In observing naturally occurring speech in focus group and observation sessions, participants originating from the Mediterranean cities tended to use French more than those from middle cities. Unfortunately, the very limited number of participants derived from Saharan cities made it hard to explore their perceptions and observed behaviours with regards to FL.

6.3.1.1.2 Micro-ethnicity (Micro-National Grouping)

In the literature review, I explained how Kabyle Algerians as a micro-ethnicity group of Berber tend to valorise the use of French more than Arabs and other Berber ethnicity groups (Benrabah, 2013). In this study, questionnaire data targeted fifteen Berber participants including six Kabyle ones. However, they still view themselves as becoming shifters (using

English as a predominant embedded code). One may get the reverse sociolinguistic stance if the majority of key informants belonged to the Kabyle linguistic minority. In analysing Kabyle speakers' perceptions about their language use in Arab speaking communities, Abdelkader (2013) found out that French is assumed to be the second most preferred and used language among Kabyle speakers, after the Kabyle variety itself. According to some qualitative data in this research, the findings were no exception to this. In describing her current linguistic journey with FL, one of the interview participants (*Sara*) who is originally Kabyle maintained: "(...) I am using French like my native language". One of the Kabyle participants in the questionnaire data produced a supporting point which aligns tightly with this. Speaking about FL and its use, she said "It represents me as a Berber because French is used so much in Kabyle dialect". This can indicate that she assigns multiple practices to her identity as Kabyle and go against the point of "one nation one language", and therefore inform new perspectives in the study of language and multilingualism. Similar findings were mentioned in Pauwels (2019) in her description of temporary linguistic practices.

Hence, the micro-ethnicity from which individuals originate may play a powerful role in language use, of course interethnic situations. In literature, Belmihoub (2012), among other Berber and Arab ethnic groups, posited that Kabyles are more featured as Francophones in Algeria. According to Arfi (2008), Kabyle immigrants in France tend to speak more French especially with their children, than Arabic.

6.3.1.1.3 Family Support

The family support described here belongs to participants' pre-mobility life. According to interview data, participants who were surrounded with a supportive family environment back home regarding FL use assumed more French LM (alongside AA). Interestingly, one of the participants in the questionnaire data put forwards "(...) I personally use the FL because I was brought up in a family that uses a mixture of Arabic and French". So, French was maintained as part of AA.

At the other end of the spectrum, having a negative familial support to FL use seemed to influence participants, by making them assuming LS to English (according to perceptions). One of the participants (*Souzan*), speaking about her family weak support of FL use, expressed: "Not really, because my father is illiterate, my mother is literate, but she was not that

competent in both languages”. In sociolinguistic studies, family is deemed to have a powerful role in LM in the sense that it often has the earliest influence on the language that the children acquire (Stoessel, 2002, Pauwels, 2005, Canagarajah, 2008, Potowski, 2013).

6.3.1.1.4 Language Proficiency

Despite being exposed to a long period of FL learning, language proficiency seems to differ from one individual to another due to several environmental and attitudinal factors. Generally, the participants who claimed FL proficiency viewed themselves as maintainers of FL (as a predominant embedded language alongside AA and English) in the new environment, and those who viewed themselves as less proficient, assumed that they are shifters (using English as a predominant embedded code). In an alignment with scholarly literature, Clyne (2003) placed proficiency in a language as an individual factor of LS (but in contexts of long-term settlements).

6.3.1.2 Post-mobility Factors/Aspirations

6.3.1.2.1 Language Functionality and Status

Because of the guaranteed return that participants have in their mobility, the linguistic interpretations were also related to a post-mobility context. As a future consideration, data from both interviews and questionnaires proposed that EL would be a language that is much more relevant to participants’ future careers as future educators/academics. Using it alongside AA would be then more suitable accordingly. The perceived shift can be also related to the gradual functionality of this language in the near future of Algeria. A stronger presence of English in different Algerian domains is forecasted by scholars such as Benrabah (2014) and Belmihoub (2012, 2015). For language use, Holmes (2013) documented that individuals tend to use a language which has an economic value. As future educators, using English alongside AA would suit them more in their professional domains. It is also viewed in literature that future aspirations have a strong influence on the linguistic behaviours (Wei and Hua, 2013).

However, at the social level, FL is currently highly functional in mainland Algeria as a structural-functional context (Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008). I have illustrated in reviewing literature how FL was deeply maintained and did not lose its status despite succumbing to competition with English (Benrabah, 2007a). It is anticipated by participants that this

functionality will remain active over time in the near future of Algeria, and therefore, they are assuming to maintain FL alongside AA for that reason. Clyne (2003) elucidated that the situation of a language back home can affect minority languages use in the migratory setting.

FL has a higher status than that given to English (Benrabah, 2007a, 2013, 2014). Sociolinguistic studies on Algerian contexts provided plenty of evidence that explains FL status as a second and the first foreign language. FL was also maintained in Algeria partly due to its prestigious status among the Algerian speech community (Benrabah, 2007a), and it is associated by Algerian users with modernity and social success (Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008). So, some participants considered this as a future factor, when they go back to Mainland Algeria.

6.3.2 Factors/ Aspirations Related to the Current Experience

6.3.2.1 Globalisation and the Nature of Mobility

In the first place, this study is part of the new mobility paradigm. Unlike traditional patterns of migration, the participants are described in this project as transnational in the sense of being affected by technological (new technologies), global and transnational processes of migration (Li and Zhu, 2013). The transnational participants are short-stay PhD students, who travelled to the UK in the light of internationalisation of higher education, mobility and exchange programmes. Unlike migrants with a long-term aim to settle down in the host country, these people can be described as sojourners, with a short-term period of stay and have a guaranteed return to the country of origin. In literature, future plans are viewed as a strong indicator of linguistic affiliations and behaviours. Therefore, those with return intents to homelands are thought as linguistically influenced by that: "migrants' intent to their homeland is intimately connected to their linguistic repertoires and identities and vice versa"(Tovares and Kamwangamalu, 2017, p.214).

Recently, studies of mobility and super-diversity stressed the importance of identifying mobility motives in the linguistic practices of communities (Blommaert and Rampton, 2011). This type of mobility (short stay) obviously has specific characteristics among which is what is called in literature recency of arrival and ease to travel to back home (Conklin and Lourie, 1983), cited in Clyne (2013). These two elements can promote traditional LM (Conklin and Lourie, 1983, cited in Clyne, 2013). In relation with this specific nature of mobility, participants

across different UK institutions, are entitled to annual leaves according to the UKVI migration policy. By virtue of accessible travelling opportunities, these transnational movers can establish ordinary connections with former communities back home, a factor which can inform their linguistic dispositions towards maintaining French as a predominant embedded code alongside AA and English.

Short period of stay would also lead to less linguistic impacts (Pauwels, 2016), and that would also trigger LM. The academic focus, however, and circumstances and characteristics of the sample population as a new class of professionals developing their EL skills is interpreted as more influencing LS according to some perceptions (using English as a predominant embedded code). However, that these students started to learn English long ago, before their mobility to the UK, can build an assumption that LS happened before mobility, and mobility to an English-speaking country just reinforced their disposition towards LS. In this section, globalisation and the nature of mobility are discussed as affecting/reinforcing both assumed LM/LS.

6.3.2.1.1 Virtual Network Support through Online Modes of Interaction

With the advent of social media (cyberspace era), as termed in Pauwels (2016), growing social networking sites such as Skype, Messenger and WhatsApp allowed stronger social contacts with family. The latter could trigger preserving community languages as explained before. Some data suggested that participants tend to use more FL (alongside AA) when they get in touch with family back home. In this main respect, Pauwels (2016) claimed: “Scholars of LM identified the ability to regularly connect with one’s linguistic “heartland” as an important LM-enhancing factor” (p.172).

Researchers like Androutsopoulos (2006), Levitt and Jaworsky (2007), Pauwels (2007, 2014, and 2016), Wei and Hua (2013) and Budach and Saint-Georges (2017) highlighted that the virtual space as a result of technologies can allow staying in touch with former communities. As mentioned in data analysis, some participants considered social media platforms as a strategy to maintain FL as part of AA when talking to their family and friends back home. Sallabank (2010) similarly emphasised the role of online communication platforms in the maintenance of endangered languages among Guernesiais in the Channel Islands. Another

set of perceived data revealed that listening to French music on YouTube as a strategy to preserve FL. This goes hand in hand with Pauwels (2016)'s emphasis regarding the internet's role on LM/LS. In a culturally similar linguistic context, Othman (2011) found out that regular virtual interaction between children and parents with people back home via telephone and internet is a reinforcing factor to Arabic LM.

One may assume that social media is a limiting space in LM/LS research leading to outcomes influenced by virtual factors, compared to those studies undertaken within the era of old migration. A population which is researched in pre-cyber space era is different from that in cyber-space era. LM/LS among both populations would not be the same. Thus, one should rethink many concepts in language use, taking into account these technological changes in the world. Actually, this tightly aligns with Canagarajah (2017) that the study of language use and mobility warrants a careful rethinking at different levels.

6.3.2.1.2 A Luxury of Constant and Direct Contact

The research targeted Algerian ethnolinguistic friendship groups who are concentrated in relatively limited geographical areas over different UK higher education institutions: The West of Scotland University, Lancaster, Northampton, Southampton, Canterbury Christ Church, Leeds and Portsmouth. The study, therefore, closely resembles others where the sample are ethnically related groups rather than isolated ones. In migration and long-term settlements' contexts, Jamaï (2008) found out that high concentration of Moroccans all together in London did not result in a strong maintenance of Moroccan Arabic, a minority language. He concluded that high concentration did not necessarily result in LM. In terms of attitudes, results from this study proposed the same point in the sense that the majority of participants in interviews, although geographically concentrated in Paisley (Scotland) viewed themselves as users of English as a predominant embedded code alongside AA and French (assumed LS). In addition to that, the majority of participants who took part in the web-based questionnaire (n=20) viewed that they are currently using English as a predominant embedded code, despite the sample, as explained before, selectively included people who reside together (within the same geographical location). In relation to the nature of the domain, this also matches Pauwels's (2005) claim that the friendship domain is less influential to LM than other domains such as family domain.

The concentration of Algerian students as one ethnic group in Scotland, Paisley – according to the majority’s perceptions – had affected their FL use. However, from focus group and observation sessions, as explained in the section just above, one can notice a greater use of FL over EL within their speech practices. This goes hand in hand with Conklin and Lourie (1983), who argued, although in a different context (long-term migration), that high concentration of immigrants from the same ethnic group would lead to their minority languages being maintained, and low concentration would result in LS (Clyne,2003). Mazzaferro (2018b, p.88) supported the role of concentration of minorities on language use: “In the realm of society, phenomena such as peers’ influence, social networks or the ethnolinguistic vitality of minority communities may influence language choice and use”. The concentration of Algerian students altogether paved the way for their constant interactions, an important strategy in preserving their minority languages (Latham Keh and Stoessel, 2017).

6.3.2.2 Language Functionality and Status

As PhD students, the majority of participants assumed their tendency to use English as a predominant embedded code alongside AA, a language that can fit their current position as international students in an Anglophone country and serves their daily life needs (both at the academia and off academia levels). Language functionality among these people accords well with Wee’s (2003) concept of “linguistic instrumentalism”; that which implies individuals use of a particular language due to its usefulness to achieve some utilitarian goals (Kamwangamalu, 2016). Potowski (2013) similarly illustrated that immigrants abandon their community languages and use the community one due to their fear that using the home languages “impedes them from getting ahead in the mainstream society” (p.323). Among Algerian community in the USA, Arfi (2008) similarly articulated that they are inclined to use a language which they think more functionally important and serves their daily communicative needs. They, therefore, prefer its use among their children, despite their deep awareness that community languages should not be neglected. Even though, it is of importance to note that these studies were conducted in a different context: long-term migration.

The findings may also suggest that some participants assume the maintenance of French because it is still functional in the UK, in the sense that it can be used to socialise with French-speaking people.

6.3.2.2.1 English as a *Lingua Franca*

Some participants conceived LS to English (as a predominant embedded code alongside AA and French) because they think it has a status of a common second language between all Algerian students. The ethnolinguistic friendship groups are PhD students, with an expected advanced proficiency in EL and almost similar experiences with it. Unlike English, the participants do differ in their experiences with FL use depending on different factors. For example, it is argued in interviews that FL is used among Algerians depending on its degree of use back home. LS to English was perceived as happening as long as it is more appropriate as a predominant embedded code choice beside the matrix language Arabic. Some participants then perceived that they are using it as common second language after AA. A striking datum is what was suggested by one participant in the questionnaire findings: "(...) the Algerian students came from a diverse environment where not everyone can understand French words, but definitely they understand English, so I use English as a second *lingua franca* after Arabic (...)". Pauwels's (2007) argument matches this, considering "English as a *lingua franca*" as a threat to minority languages in transnational contexts. Again, the transnational context mentioned by her is likely different in nature than the current context (short-term mobility conditioned by return), one should reflect.

6.3.2.3 Intragroup Concerns

Interestingly, results presented another important conceived LM/LS factor which is social-psychological in nature. Participants' decisions about LM/LS were not only out of individual concerns, but also in relation to the group they are part of. Therefore, how to be a good member of the intragroup was triggered by two imagined communities: an aspiration to achieve a social group cohesion and a willingness to match an aspirational academic identity. Actually, this piece of data can be traced back to the social identity theory in a way that it entails that "we categorise the social world, and hence, perceive ourselves as members of various groups. Such knowledge of ourselves as group members is defined as our social

identity and it may be positive or negative (...)”(Giles and Johnson, 1987, pp.70–71). In this definition, the social identity’s main focus is the intergroup dynamics. However, this can apply to the target group as they have different imagined group identities. Referring back to data, some group members viewed themselves as a community sharing a national state identity as Algerians, and this might have triggered a predominant French LM as a part of a repertoire (positively impacting their minority language, FL). Other members viewed themselves as academics and therefore believed they shifted to English as a predominant embedded code within a repertoire (negatively impacting FL). The social-psychological approach is also concerned with the relationships of members and how their identities are shaped by that (Pauwels, 2016). Consequently, participants in this research shaped their reported behaviours according to imagined identities to fulfil its ethnolinguistic distinctiveness both as a social and an academic community.

6.3.2.3.1 Aspirational Group Cohesion

“(...) It’s a kind of searching identity with each other because we are far from home; in a foreign setting (...)”(Souzan)

Participants, assuming FL maintenance seemed to imagine themselves as an immediate lived community (Algerian friendship group). They thought they preserved the use of French as a predominant embedded code choice in their intragroup interactions to maintain their national state identity as Algerians. Questionnaire data (20/32 participants) as well as many instances of interview data (mainly in *Sonia, Karim, Sara, Amin* and *Schahin*) suggested the interplay between FL use and interlocutor (Algerian ethnolinguistic group).

6.3.2.3.2 Aspirational Academic Identity

“We are English students, that’s why we use more English than French words in our daily interactions (...) what you study all the time can affect your use of language (...)” (Sonia)

Decisions around perceived LS were also informed by the group imagined identity as a community of international academics, as results may suggest. As a factor which is more linked to the group uniqueness, the professional level of participants seemed to influence

their interpretation of their sociolinguistic stance and experience. This community of students is a new class of mobile professionals. They studied in English years ago, some of them have taught in EFL contexts, and now they are conducting PhD research in an English-speaking country. As mentioned in presenting the findings (in both interview and questionnaire), some instances of data showed that participants who assumed LS claimed that they shifted to English as a predominant embedded code choice during their intragroup interactions because it matches their academic identity as PhD students and future educators in higher education. In line with that, García (2009) postulated that multilingual speakers decide who they want to be and choose their language practices accordingly. Their current identity as doctoral researchers and imagined identities as future educators are what might have led them to assume the shift to use English as a predominant embedded code.

So, individuals' linguistic decisions were also influenced by intragroup concerns. Participants shaped their behaviours to match different imagined identities (social and academic). Thus, one can say that decisions in variations are contextualised and therefore inconclusive. Meyerhoff (2002) had a similar view regarding this. Speaking about decisions making in social-psychological theories, she maintained that "self-awareness- as an interplay between more or less personal and group identifications, that vary in contextual salience within conversations and that vary developmentally across time"(p.149).

6.3.3 Maintaining Multiple Practices:

While previous factors could inform more the traditional "dominant framework" of LM/LS, maintaining a set of practices in situations of short-term mobility can be the result of individuals' disposition towards linguistic diversity and their reluctance to identify a set of practices as their first language.

6.3.3.1 "Openness" towards Multilingualism

" (...) I consider French as an important language, any language has its importance(...)The more languages I use, the more I am satisfied about myself, French is no exception to this rule (...)" (Amin)

If reading this perceived data through the lens of new perspectives in LM/LS (LM=maintaining multiple practices), one can say that some participants assumed that they maintained multiple practices, without being restricted to any, because they are more open to multilingualism. So, openness and disposition towards multilingualism and linguistic diversity can be a factor influencing perceived LM.

6.3.3.2 First Language as a Set of Practices

“(…) French is a step in our language, like you cannot speak AA without French” (Sonia)

“(…) it is part of our dialect and the majority use it as it is integrated in our speech” [...] *“(…) it represents me as a Berber because French is used so much in Kabyle dialect (…)* “[...]” (….) *I think that as a Berber, though I am using English more than French since I lived in UK, I may not lose my French because the Berber language, I speak, includes a lot of French words, and I am using it in my mother tongue every day. Thus, I am using French alongside it”*

(Extracts from questionnaire data)

Maintaining a repertoire as a result of a short-term mobility can be interpreted in some perceived data as related to the inability to dissociate one language from another. Participants were assigning multiple languages to their native language. Therefore, when reporting LM, they were speaking about the continuous use of a set of practices instead of one language. Actually, Pauwels (2019), in describing current linguistic practices, mentioned that among the characteristics or temporary linguistic profiles is the “inability or unwillingness of individuals to identify one language as one’s native, first, or heritage language” (Pauwels, 2019, p.248). She further reflected that this characteristic is a significant stumbling block in studying LM/LS from the perspective of dominant framework (traditional perspectives). Furthermore, in Mazzaferro’s (2018b), the idea that heritage language is unchanging and stable is hard to maintain within new linguistic practices in the world.

Figure 6. 2: Perceived factors/aspirations behind maintaining a set of practices among newly-established mobile students

6.4 Expressed Perceptions VERSUS Observed Behaviours

According to Pauwels (2016), the debate around the extent to which attitudes reflect actual behaviours is ongoing. In the study of expressed perceptions-observed behaviours relationship in an Algerian mobility context, findings might have implied both alignment between what was reported and what was actually observed, and also inconsistency between both.

In a general sense, LM/LS practices, captured in perceived data, were not clearly evidenced in actual behaviours data as deterministic practices (focus group and observations sessions), because of the fact that LM/LS application can be challenging in situations of short-term mobility. In other words, what was identified in actual behaviours data as LS can represent evidence of early stages, temporary LS, but not a definite linguistic change. Hence, in this study, LM/LS theory affected more the study of perceptions than behaviours.

The majority of participants in interviews assumed that they shifted to English, while in fact in observed sessions (focus group and observation sessions), there was some evidence of mismatching elements between behaviours and perceptions. This can suggest that LS is challenged in contexts of short-term mobility. In other words, LS within short-term mobility

can be assumed, but might not be actually happening. What they assumed is not a definite change, but can be a moment of temporary change. It can also suggest that these individuals were practicing earlier stages of LS.

The mismatch between behaviours and perceptions could be also interpreted in light of the aspirational academic/nation state identity of mobile students, and therefore, revealed evidence of contextualised decisions during linguistic variations as mentioned in the previous section. In other words, those who assumed LS (using English as a predominant embedded code with their mobility) associated their linguistic behaviours with their academic focus as international academics. Doing a PhD in the UK made them think that their FL is only slipping after it was so dominant. Hence, one may assume that their perceptions are flawed, because they are affected by their circumstances. In other words, because their academic language is shown in English, they may assume that this represents all of their linguistic behaviour, when, in fact, it is a subset. So, their academic focus skews their capacity to reflect on their whole experience. In this case, one may relate perceptions to a desired linguistic practice, instead of reflecting reality. *Karim* and *Amin* in interviews also revealed the desire for a linguistic change, that English will be the second language in the future Algeria. This is in correspondence with Wei and Hua (2013) who assumed that linguistic practices among multilinguals could be also the product of future aspirations (as already mentioned).

Concerning the perceived level of proficiency, the participants' status as language students might have made them more critical of their own performance, and thus not so many have classed themselves as highly competent in French. It might be that they are overly self-critical in this regard. One could speculate that they may under reported their skill levels.

In expressed perceptions, the alignment of participants who assumed LM with their observed behaviours can reinforce the potential and validity of studying LM/LS within short-term mobility from the proposed definitions in this study; i.e. studying both processes in terms of the amount of the embedded code being predominantly used within a repertoire. In terms of new perspectives in the study of LM/LS, this may suggest that maintaining pre-mobility linguistic practices can be evident in situations of short-term mobility, while a fewer linguistic changes can happen as stated by Pauwels (2016, p.17): "Short-term language contact

between individuals or groups is not likely to induce (major) changes in linguistic constellations or the language practices of the speakers (...)”.

Regarding attitudes towards the language, positive attitudes about language seemed to result in its use in actual behaviours as revealed by some cases, such as in *Sara* and *Amin*. In literature, this was articulated by Othman (2011), Dweik and Al-Obaidi (2014) and Dweik, Nofal and Qawasmeh (2014) who emphasised the role of positive attitudes as a prerequisite for LM to occur and that negative attitudes would lead to shift. However, in some occasions of data, some pieces of data proposed that negative attitudes did not result in using English as a predominant embedded code. For example, *Karim* showed genuinely negative attitudes towards FL, while in observed sessions, it was used more than English. Also, the case of *Sonia* who has positive attitudes towards French, but was using English as a predominant embedded code in observed sessions. This is consistent with Potowski (2013)’s own findings that positive attitudes do not necessarily guarantee LM and vice versa.

In brief, the interplay between perceptions and behaviours also gives credit to the social-psychological approach which is used in LM/LS studies to explore how the former shapes the latter (Pauwels, 2016). However, the mismatch between perceptions and behaviours and alignment between both corresponds with Ladegaard’s (2000) conclusion that the relationship between perceptions and behaviours is complex to explore, especially in this specific context. In other words, the complexity triggered by interpreting the relationship between perceptions and behaviours might be also related to the short period of stay of the research subjects.

One can say that experiences differ; each one’s own experience is governed by its own peculiarities. Therefore, one cannot reach a consensus regarding the complex nature of the relationship between expressed behaviours and actual ones. In other words, one may predict, but never be certain, and that is the nature of human psychology.

6.5 The Potential Sociolinguistic Markers Affecting LM/LS within Short-term Mobility

As explained in detail in Chapter 3, LM/LS in the context of this research are differently applied with sensitivity to short-term mobility. While studying the validity of LM/LS in observed

behaviours, the research subjects' practices, in a general sense, suggested fluid linguistic practices, more than LM/LS processes. Data presentation from both focus group and observation sessions suggested that participants made two forms of linguistic practices: those where French was used as a predominant embedded code alongside AA, followed by English and those instances where English was used as a predominant embedded code instead. Both forms were discussed through processes of code-switching (at sentence level) and code mixing (at word level/ intra word switching), according to Kische's definition, and factors behind this code choice. In relation to my previous definition of LM/LS with sensitivity to the short-term mobility context alongside the participants' conceptualisation, one may reflect that French LM was assumed through AA-French-English code-switching (sentence level) and AA-French code mixing (word-level). LS, from the suggested definition, could be identified in actual behaviours data as AA-English-French code-switching and AA-English code mixing. Hence, code-switching and mixing can be markers of LM/LS in situations of short-term mobility.

6.5.1 Translanguaging as an Overarching Term for Code-switching and Mixing

Participants, in their intragroup interactions, seemed to deploy different plurilingual resources. In literature, translanguaging replaces terminology based on an assumption that code-switching occurs between languages that are autonomous and separate entities (Otheguy, García and Reid, 2015). So, translanguaging troubles the concept of code-switching and its application among linguists.

Unlike the traditional perspectives that view translanguaging and code-switching as two opposed poles (Otheguy, García and Reid, 2015, Otheguy, García and Reid 2018, Mazzaferro, 2018b), the present study implied the occurrence of both phenomena in concert with each other, and therefore, a positive perception about the relationship between code-switching and translanguaging was proposed. What is novel in the present study is that code-switching and mixing can be viewed as types of translanguaging accordingly. In this case, the use of different languages could evidence both French LM (as the predominant embedded code after the matrix language: AA-French-English), and LS to English (as the predominant embedded code before French: AA-English-French).

As a matter of similar research study outcomes, Kao, Tsou and Chen (2018) recently identified that code-switching and mixing as types of translanguaging among international students in higher education in Taiwan. Therefore, they suggested the potential typological relationship between them.

At a sublevel, code-switching appeared to affect the sentence level (intra-sentential switching, in correspondence with Kische's (2017) definition. The Algerian linguistic situation is largely based on code-switching phenomenon in mainland Algeria, and crossing borders to the UK suggested some maintenance of this linguistic habit. Identified LM was displayed through AA-French-English code-switching, where AA is the matrix language (the base language), while French is the predominant embedded code (host language). LS, from the suggested definition of the researcher and participants in their perceptions (using English as a predominant embedded code), appeared in actual behaviours data through AA-English-French code-switching and AA-English code mixing. This matches Arfi's (2008) findings, but in a migration context, that code-switching among Algerian nationals in the USA use both AA-French-English and AA-English patterns of code-switching (Arfi, 2008, 2014). While code-switching is seen as both triggering LM/LS in the present project, Pauwels (2005) alluded that code-switching is a linguistic practice which characterised few instances of intragroup interactions of Greek adolescents in friendship domain, pointing further that the community language among this ethnolinguistic group is less preserved (LS). Therefore, code-switching indicated more LS. Clyne (2003) and Mazzaferro (2018b) are also of a similar view. In a similar fashion, Jamaï (2008) strongly viewed that "code-switching must be seen as a marker of language shift" (p.312).

Additionally, data further proposed AA-French and AA-English code-mixing. The former can illustrate a case of LM, while the latter can be a marker of LS. Code-mixing is a linguistic practice which can occur at the word level (intra-word mixing). This categorisation was drawn from a recent conceptualisation of code-mixing, based on Kische (2017). Accordingly, code-mixing involves the interaction of grammatical categories and syntactic rules at word level, unlike code-switching which occurs at a larger space of conversation and does not require the interaction of grammatical rules of used languages (Kische, 2017). In Arfi's (2008, 2014) study, findings illustrating code-mixing was interpreted as borrowing. Debates around the distinction between code-switching, code-mixing and borrowing is ongoing in the scholarly

literature. Each study uses them according to their applicability within the study context. This study does not adopt borrowing, because it is just less precise and covers a wider range of practices.

6.5.2 Factors behind the Predominant Embedded Language Choice within Short-term Mobility

The study also addressed the social meanings around the predominant embedded code choice (French versus English). According to the participants' intragroup interactions displayed in the data analysis section, FL was more used as an embedded variety beside the base language (AA), while other occasions of data proposed that EL was the predominant embedded language. In sociolinguistic analysis, code choice is perceived as underpinned by a bundle of factors such as the participants (backgrounds, attitudes and their relationship), interlocutor (person(s) speaking to), the topic and function of discussion and the locale where the speech event takes place (Fishman, 2003, Coulmas, 2013, Holmes, 2013, Ritchie and Bhatia, 2013, Pauwels, 2016). In this study, these elements were not identified as equally influential to the predominant embedded code choice (French/English).

The speaker and his/her personal histories and backgrounds seemed, to some extent, to affect the predominant embedded code choice. In the previous section, participants' backgrounds were detailed and that different factors can interfere to either promote French use or hinders it such as attitudes, proficiency, and micro-ethnicity, the perceived status and functionality of FL/EL. These factors, all together, can play a great role in code choice (FL/EL). Ritchie and Bathia (2013) postulated language attitudes play a significant role in language choice. Whether the relationship between attitudes and behaviours is consistent or not, has been explained in the previous section.

In this project, the intragroup interactions of Algerian students during their short stay in the UK seemed to influence the predominant use of FL alongside AA, in the sense of promoting social distance and solidarity. In interviews and questionnaires, for example, some set of data showed that FL is used with regards to interlocutor (Algerian ethnolinguistic friendship group). In focus group sessions, FL was used as a predominant embedded code alongside AA in many instances of data and that can be translated as a result of a powerful social distance

and ethnic relationship. Holmes (2013) similarly highlighted solidarity and social distance as important elements in linguistic interaction. For her, “how well you know someone is one of the most important factors affecting the way you talk to them” (p.447).

The physical setting (locale) where the intragroup interactions took place had less impact on the predominant embedded language choice. The gathering of students in whatever setting (according to focus group and observation sessions) suggested more use of FL alongside AA than English, regardless the room they are in. The predominant use of English as an embedded code alongside AA did not seem to be affected by the locale as well. Holmes (2008) conversely pointed to the social context of interaction as an important factor that impinges on language choice. Clyne (2003) countered this point, highlighting the physical setting as a powerful indicator in LS. Gardner-Chloros (1991), further highlighted the formality of the setting as a powerful element influencing code-switching between French and Alsatian in Strasbourg as noted in Matras (2009). However, in my research this element has less effect in comparison to the topic of discussion influence.

Interestingly, the topic of discussion (mode of discourse and functionality) appeared to influence the predominant embedded code more than the other code choice factors (See **Figure 6.3** for a clear image). In the existing research, the topic of interaction is widely viewed as a strong indicator of language choice among different scholars, such as Fishman (2003), Lawson and Sachdev, (2004), Arfi (2008, 2014), Matras (2009), Ritchie and Bathia (2013), Holmes (2013), Buchani (2015) and Pauwels (2016).

6.5.2.1 The Topic of Discussion Influence

Figure 6. 3: Topic role and dimensions in the predominant embedded code choice

i. Discourse Mode

By far and away, FL was predominantly used as an embedded code alongside AA in discussing Algerian-context related issues to index “Algerianness” (See **Excerpts 2, 5, 6, 10, 11, 12, 14, 15, 21, 27, 30, 31, 33, 51, 52, 53, 55 and 56**), while English was predominantly used alongside AA and French in debating current context-related issues (See **Excerpts 3, 7, 11, 13, 14, 19, 28, 43, 45, 48, 52, 53, 54, 57 and 58**). In one of the interaction extracts that may suggest a powerful illustration of shifting to English with changing the context of the topic, one of the participants alternated from using AA-French code-switching patterns to switching with English instead, simultaneously with the shift from speaking about marriage traditions in Algeria to marriage in the UK. Another good example would be when *Schahin* shifted from using French words to English ones, with the shift in context (from addressing his experience with Algerian teachers during his data collection back home to highlighting ethical guidelines at the level of UK higher educations:

“ (...)’w **le malheur{Fr}** ‘ydirlak **vue {Fr}** way5alihalak haka, ana **déjà {Fr}** manaqdarch nafrad ‘3lik **déjà {Fr}** | **ethics** hnaya yqoulak **don’t oblige them to participate**“

Unfortunately, some participants had withdrawn, and what made me pissed off is when they had seen my text and did not reply. I can’t oblige them anyways, aligning with ethics guidelines here!

In a slightly similar scope of findings, Arfi (2014), in a long-term settlement context, found out that Algerian immigrants in the USA use the three languages (AA, French and English) to speak about past situations and code-switch with English to express their present experiences. In her study, the past situation entails the participants’ pre-migratory experience in home land (Algeria), while the present situation is related to the current experience of Algerian American nationals.

ii. The Message Function

The purpose and function of interaction seemed to influence code choice. Holmes (2013) highlighted the function of interaction as a strong determiner in code choice. In this research project, different meanings and functions behind either using of French as the predominant embedded language or English instead can be detected. Using French as a predominant embedded code alongside AA, or using English as a predominant embedded code instead can signal:

- **Affective/social function:** On many occasions FL was used as a predominant embedded variety to indicate belongingness and attachment to L1 culture. In other words, some participants’ utterances suggested that FL was used as an embedded variety alongside AA because it sounds that this switching is more pertinent to the expression of ethnic origin and identity. French was also used as the predominant embedded code choice to express social topics as opposed to formal ones (See **Excerpts 1, 2, 10, 16, 18, 25 and 46**). In some social topics, the participants accordingly seemed very comfortable with the use of FL than English in the sense of allowing a social space between themselves. In Holmes (2013), affective function is used to describe the social relationship between speakers as being warm and friendly in nature than formal one.

- **Referential Function:** On the other hand, English was used as the predominant embedded code choice in instances where the function behind fulfils the expression of professional concerns as researchers and future educators. The shift to EL can be then related to expressing and showing a professional identity, and that implies a referential, formal function. Data might have also implied informative functions in some sentences that were produced either to emphasise or produce quotations (See **Excerpts 3, 4, 8, 9, 18, 19, 36, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 48 and 49** to illustrate both cases). Holmes (2013), in a similar way, argued that high - in information - topics can strongly affect the form of language being used. In a similar fashion, some instances of data may suggest a shift to use English as a predominant embedded code to imply an emphasis function and indicate quoted forms. An illustrative example from data would be **“don’t oblige them to participate”**, where the speaker was talking about research ethics in AA and shifted to English to emphasise some ethical guidelines. The latter entails some seriousness.

6.6 A Summary of the Translanguaging Perspective Traction

Findings may also propose the translanguaging perspective traction on LM/LS in the sense that LM/LS were interpreted as part of other linguistic resources within the communicative interaction. LM/LS were not studied with a view of languages as separate entities, but among other communicative resources (LM: AA-French-English/ LS: AA-English- French) during languaging. The comparison was limited to French and English in terms of low degree of use and high degree of use within the new verbal repertoire. In this, Otheguy, García and Reid (2015, p.281) explained the basic assumption of translanguaging which consists of “the deployment of a speaker’s full linguistic repertoire without regard for watchful adherence to the socially and politically defined boundaries of named (and usually national and state) languages”.

In addition, some instances of data suggested that FL is attached to L1. In Adouane and Dobnik (2017), Modern Algerian Arabic is viewed as a composite of Arabic dialects, classical Arabic, Berber varieties, French, and few other languages like English. This cross linguistic influence opposes the concept of monolingualism, which is becoming challenged in the world recently. Enrica Piccardo, cited in Taylor and Snoddon (2013, p.443), expressed this:

No matter how monolingual we consider ourselves to be, we are fundamentally plurilingual, albeit unconsciously so. No matter how standard and pure we consider each language, it is inevitable that all languages are ensembles of different elements in a dynamic and constantly changing relationship

So, languages are viewed as resources in this study because languages do not exist as real entities, but instead exist as invented ones (Pennycook, 2007, Mazzaferro, 2018b). For Mazzaferro (2018b), they are socio-historically and politically constructed.

Data might have also implied that meaning making is central in the process of interaction. The speakers deployed whatever resources available in their repertoires for the purpose of meaning making (Jørgensen, 2008, Blommaert, 2010, Mazzaferro, 2018b). The inconsistency between perceptions and behaviours suggested spontaneous linguistic practices, a key characteristic of speakers who “ (...) act dynamically by moving back and forth across the resources of their flexible linguistic repertoires in spontaneous and unexpected ways to construct meaning” (Mazzaferro, 2018b, p.91).

6.7 Traditional and New Perspectives in LM/LS: Building Bridges

Among the significant features of the sample of this research is living two contexts (a pre/post-mobility context and a current international one). This study, in questioning the validity of studying LM/LS from the participants’ perspectives and their observed behaviours in a context of short-term mobility, integrated elements from traditional LM/LS and new perspectives in the field. So, it is at a crossroad of tensions between traditional and new LM/LS perspectives. On the basis of the perceived data in hand, structural-functional principles still dominate some participants’ views, who tended to associate the continuous use of FL/ the shift to EL to a structural/ functional society through either aspiring an additive multilingual speech community, or subtractive one (replacing French with English). This interesting link is obvious as they are newly established in the UK and have a guaranteed return to the country of origin. In Martin-Jones (1988), it was stated that these micro choices are a mere reflex of macro-level statuses and structures. Structural-functional perspectives, can be criticised on the basis that they consist of passively observing idealised norms of language allocation, but one cannot overlook the fact that linguistic choices are socially

determined, especially with the impositions of power that generally take place in situations of linguistic struggles (Martin-Jones, 1988).

However, looking at LM/LS from a structural-functional lens did not, by itself, assist in understanding the complexity of language choices made by the participants. The use of French was identified in terms of a set of practices (alongside AA). More than that, actual behaviours data suggested flexible, fluid and dynamic practices where linguistic choices did not seem to be “mere reflections of a community-wide norms”. (Martin-Jones, 1988, p.108). If linked to LM/LS processes, the research subjects seemed to continue using a playful mix of linguistic practices in a very flexible way. That can be identified as LM in Pauwels (2016, p. 184): “LM could be conceived as the maintenance of a multilingual repertoire even if the languages or codes upon which individual or group draws change”. The multilingual set of practices can be also indicative to flexible translanguaging, which consists of using a full repertoire for meaning making in a non-strategic way (Jørgensen, 2008, Blommaert, 2010, Mazzaferro, 2018b). Destructuralist-functionalist views distract the macro-choices during variation. For them:

While it is important to take account of the fact that the communicative resources that bilinguals draw on in their everyday discourse are socially determined, it is also important to emphasize that individual speakers do not just draw on these resources or follow communicative conventions in a mechanical fashion. Individual bilinguals in majority communities draw on the linguistic resources in their repertoire in strategic and creative ways. Language use among bilinguals is complex and variable and generally involves much more than a two-way choice of code. Communicative resources are combined and juxtaposed in subtle ways through code-mixing and code-switching (...)

(Martin-Jones, 1988, p.123)

Data also suggested a positive and a peaceful relationship between code-switching and mixing. Traditionally, code-switching and translanguaging were considered as opposing poles. During languaging practices in actual behaviours data, as discussed previously, it was suggested that code-switching (at sentence level)/ mixing (at word level) (two strategic practices that can be associated more with structural-functional/ micro-interactionist approaches) were interpreted as types of translanguaging. That could be an interesting outcome of mixing between traditional and new perspectives.

This study can provide a fertile ground for the incorporation of both perspectives. Actually, the interesting match can be related to the context of this research (short-term mobility with a guaranteed return to the county of origins). In the subsequent section, I shall discuss the validity of exploring LM/LS in situations of short-term mobility.

6.8 A Critical Reflection on the Validity and the Usefulness of the Application of LM/LS Framework within Short-term Mobility:

From a socio-constructivist view, the results obtained in the context of this research (short-term mobility as a result of study abroad) have led to a different interpretation of LM/LS. Despite the challenges that I predicted earlier regarding the specific study context, the application of these two concepts provided some new insights to the field. Therefore, LM/LS within short-term mobility have some specific features that future researchers should carefully mind:

1. Short-term mobility can present nascent stages of LM/LS

In the context of migration and long-term-settlement, it is believed that LM/LS are deterministic, static and all or nothing unidirectional processes (Mazzaferro, 2018b). When LS happens for example, minority languages cannot find space for use according to this view. Unlike this, newly arrived minorities would not encounter drastic linguistic changes (Pauwels, 2016). In this research, LM/LS did not drastically happen as shown in the findings chapter. Traditional LS was not identified as deterministic LS, but rather discussed in data as “the beginning of the process”. In perceptions, those who assumed LS to English, may actually shift to English in the future on the premise that attitudes about a particular behaviour can truly trigger its occurrence: “Attitudes often manage to summarize, explain and predict behaviour. Knowing someone’s attitude to alcohol, for example, may sum up likely behaviour in a range of contexts over time” (Baker, 1992, P.11).

LM was presented throughout data as its continuous use alongside AA. Of course, English could be used, but would not be used more than French. LS was illustrated by its use as a predominant embedded code alongside AA and French. Rather than definite LM/LS, linguistic practices were deployed in more fluid, flexible and dynamic ways through switching back and forth. So, LM/LS were illustrated through processes of translanguaging, code-switching and code-mixing, instead of a deterministic maintenance and shift. Deterministic shift can happen

with longer periods of stay (Regardless of the adopted perspectives: dominant framework or new ones). With longer periods of stay, these switching and mixing processes may diminish and multiple practices may decline (LS according to Pauwels's (2016) initial suggestion).

II. Towards a post-mobility vision: a forward-looking approach

In situations when the short-term mobility is influenced by conditions of return, mobile students can respond to situations of LM/LS by looking forwards to the future through imagination. This research further developed a new approach during the interpretation of individuals' experiences by focusing on aspirations related to the post-mobility context. Immigrants with long settlements often associate the factors that determine their social behaviours with pre-migratory experience through their look-backward vision (Stoessel, 2002, Clyne, 2003, Pauwels, 2016, 2019). Individuals in situations of short-stay mobility, especially with return plans, do not only have a backward-looking thinking (pre-mobility consideration), during the decision-making about perceived LM/LS. They also have a forward-looking vision towards the future, after they go back to the country of origin. So, among the usefulness of interpreting LM/LS within short term-mobility is that individuals can have that future aspirations related to their future plans, and therefore might be more informed by the linguistic situations in the country of origin. The need to consider the "there" and "then" space and time is highlighted in Tawalbeh (2019) who suggested that "The complexities of LM can be better captured by analysing the interaction between 'here and now' and 'there and then' (...)" (Tawalbeh, 2019, p.38). For him, this forward-looking approach is recommended in the analysis of LM/LS according to the new perspectives.

III. Non-stability: Temporary linguistic changes

In situations of short-term mobility, caution should be paid that any reported change (if evident in perceived behaviours) might not be a definite change, but a moment of temporary change. Individuals could easily switch back to other linguistic practices on return. In the context of this research, changes in language use while in the new context (UK) did not necessarily indicate LS in the way normally described by prominent scholars in the field, but rather LS in progress, as it can be an assumed LS, rather than an actual LS. Participants could easily switch back on return to Algeria, for example. One can reflect that interpreting situations of LM/LS within short term-mobility are characterised by a fusion of longing and

belonging, a tension between who individuals are within the new experience and who they will become after the temporary living situation. Actually, viewing languages as static in space and time is criticised in the new LM/LS perspectives (Tawalbeh, 2019). Individual language users within mobility contexts are not fixed or isolated. They are connected in many levels throughout space and time.

IV. Extended LM/LS

In interpreting LM/LS in situations of short-term mobility, data gained may reflect pre-mobility linguistic practices, mainly in contexts that are characterised by linguistic diversity and linguistic conflicts as in Algeria. In this main regard, mobility can be just a reinforcing factor to both processes. It would thereby of importance to associate any conclusion drawn to a pre-mobility context and any suggested implications can be more addressed to the country of origin especially when the mobility of individuals is conditioned by return. Having said that, caution needs to be addressed with sensitivity to these characteristics to avoid drawing less valid conclusions in the field of LM/LS.

To round off, one may say that it becomes clear that the Algerian student community in Great Britain faced a dilemma regarding two seemingly conflicting languages: English and French. Predictable speech practices occurred as well as contrary practices and a blend of the two. The transition of students, despite being regarded as a short period of stay, revealed that they made complex and contextualised language choices. My discussion has tried to help clarify HOW a linguistic situation looks across geographical frontiers (in a context of short-term mobility), WHAT is the nature the linguistic practices pertaining to that newly established group, and interestingly WHY such practices happened. Many theoretical beliefs have proved to be guiding lines in either supporting the findings or countering them.

It became obvious that LM/LS in a transnational context is a fertile area of research, especially with globalisation and different types of mobility. Although previous research explored LM/LS from different angles, diversity in mobility patterns would allow new lines of inquiry. In the next section, the thesis will close off this research with addressing significant implications and opening avenues for future research.

CHAPTER SEVEN: GENERAL CONCLUSION

In brief, this sociolinguistic thesis questioned the validity of studying LM/LS in a context of short-term mobility. It attempted to reveal the complexities underpinning the use of FL/EL in languaging amongst Algerian transnational students in their everyday life overseas. It explored attitudes towards FL and its perceived status at the level of speakers' verbal repertoires, drawing from pre-mobility experience and current experience in a comparative fashion. In this mini-ethnographic case study, while detailed individual experiences through the lens of interviews were initially drawn, questionnaires' findings investigated to what extent individual experiences could be transferable to a larger student population, and therefore broadened my understanding of French LM/LS to English within short-term mobility. In the subsequent stage, focus group sessions were basically designed to track if, or how, the self-reported behaviours of interviewed participants could be observed in intragroup interactions. The latter were supplemented by observation sessions to validate findings.

From wider Algerian mobility patterns in the UK, the study was oriented to a new class of mobile professionals; a cohort that was uniquely identified by the academic focus to its mobility. The specific transition of students is conditioned by their return according to the mobility scheme they are involved in. Because the research employed this specific sample, it did not try to make strong claims to generalise beyond the studied population, nor to other patterns of transnational mobility.

This research addressed LM/LS as the core of exploration. The application of LM/LS presented challenges in some instances of data. In the meantime, it suggested some usefulness and validity mainly because of the different LM/LS interpretation that can add contributions to the field. In Chapter 3, I explained how LM/LS were used in this research (LM=the continuous use of French as a predominant embedded code within AA alongside English/ LS=using English as a predominant embedded code within AA alongside French). LM/LS in this context were interpreted with sensitivity to the short period of stay, with caution that data could represent earlier/nascent stages of LM/LS and LS can be a temporary linguistic change. Data interpretation did also consider new perspectives in the field.

This thesis focused more on the friendship domain. The target sample, thereby, consisted of students who were living together as communities within the same area in the host country, as important criteria for inclusion. My focus on this specific domain was related to my hypothesis that domains of community languages use in situations of short-term mobility might be subject to restriction in the new host settings, compared to that of the homeland. Therefore, individuals engage with face to face interactions more in this domain.

7.1 Recapitulation of Key Findings

Among the noticeable features of this study is the richness of results derived from different data sets. In spite of that, some data seemed to offer more contributions to the sociolinguistic discussion than others, therefore, it is worth recapitulating:

-Based on the mini-ethnographic case study, the short-term mobility of students appeared to affect their perceptions more than their behaviours. According to self-report data, two sociolinguistic stances were reported: French LM as the predominant embedded language after AA and LS to English as the predominant embedded language. In practice (focus group and observation sessions), findings revealed that there is a discrepancy between what the research subjects conceived they are doing and what they are actually doing. While self-reported behaviours suggested more traditional LS to English, the intragroup interactions revealed that participants were experiencing multilingualism (LM according to the new perspectives). It has also implied that what participants perceived as a change is not a definite change, but a moment of temporary change, which one may associate with the short-term mobility, participants have. Alternatively put, individuals were making choices by a reflex reaction. They were making of the moment contextualised decisions and this entails that their choices are not pre-meditated. Those assuming LS, being influenced by their aspirational identity as professionals, had led them to think they are more shifters. From a critical perspective, this inconsistency over time might have become more consistent and that would require further research.

-The mismatch, in a broader sense, confirmed Ladegaard's (2000) conclusion that the relationship between perceptions and behaviours is complex to explore, and that can go back to the context of this research: short-term mobility. Participants were assuming a linguistic change, drawing from their aspirations and macro societal influences related to their original

social context. Having a temporary stay might have triggered the non-static relationship between what they assume and what they actually do.

-The perceived data proposed different personal and group factors behind perceived French LM/LS to English. These factors can be more interpreted from the traditional LM/LS perspectives. Some of these are recurring in existing western and Arab contexts that I already used as positional beliefs in the literature review. According to the findings, the majority of factors affecting LM are related to Mainland Algeria (pre-mobility and post-mobility factors). Factors that trigger LS, however, seemed to emerge from the current setting such as students' awareness of the global, international status and functionality of English. This research further touched lightly upon LM factors that would inform new perspectives (factors behind maintaining a set of multilingual practices). Within short-mobility contexts, openness towards linguistic diversity and reluctance to associate a set of linguistic practices with the first language were suggested in data as elements influencing maintaining a set of practices.

-The decision-making around maintenance and shift was also related to participants' aspirational identity. Consequently, they were making social-psychological decisions in their minds about how they would be part of the group. As mentioned before, participants were performing their emerging identity as transnational academics. Assuming LS appeared to be affected by their imagined identity as a group of academics, where they think EL is more appropriate to use beside AA. What may confirm this flaw in their logic is that some perceptions and practice were identified to be different as detected in intragroup interactions. Other participants viewed they maintained French (using it as a predominant embedded code alongside AA an English) to fulfil allegiance to an aspirational group cohesion; as long as participants interact with each other as an Algerian community group. So, how to be a good member of this group encouraged both perceived LM/LS: as academics (professional identity) and as Algerians (ethnic social identity). This has confirmed the social-psychological traction on this research. In Giles, Smith and Robinson (1980), it was maintained that language behaviours are the results of attitudes, beliefs and imagined identities.

-What could be unique about this case study is the influence of transnational mobility and its characteristics (short-term conditioned by return), a factor that is more in favour of LM, one

may reflect. Being transnational implies being affected by new features of global connectivity, in a technologically-interconnected era (Wei and Hua, 2013).

In sum, participants' professional/nation state aspirational identity, their special mobility circumstances, personal histories and future aspirations were what shaped their disposition towards languages and linguistic affiliations (assumed LM/LS).

-Deploying a cluster of plurilingual resources was remarkable in the spoken utterances of the speakers, with the use of code-switching and mixing. Both were transferred from the Algerian context. However, findings suggested a more complex use of both practices than they reported in their perceived pre-mobility experience in the sense that code-switching/ mixing did not only occur regarding FL, but also EL.

- In this study, translanguaging did not only present a complex form of linguistic practices, but data also suggested that code-switching and mixing are types of it. The three behaviours occurred in concert with each other. Therefore, this finding did not go in correspondence with the traditional opposing relationship of translanguaging and code-switching, as indicated by Otheguy, García and Reid (2015), Otheguy, García and Reid (2018) and Mazzaferro (2018b).

-In highlighting the factors that govern the predominant embedded language choice in intragroup interactions, the topic (discourse mode and message function), seemed to play an important role, more than other factors. The predominant embedded code choice (French/ English) depended more on whether the mode of discourse is Algerian related context issue/ current context related issue. It was also related to the message function (referential/ affective function), as shown in Holmes (2013).

-Finally, while the application of LM/LS posed some challenges mainly because of the short-term mobility context, they offered new knowledge. Findings discussed earlier/nascent stages of LM/LS, instead of deterministic LM/LS. They can be also extended linguistic practices. These two linguistic behaviours triggered fluid linguistic practices identified as flexible translanguaging. LM/LS were also interpreted with sensitivity to the return plans of participants which created a forward-looking approach towards the future (post-mobility considerations). Because of the conditional return, one can draw a conclusion that what has

been claimed is a moment of temporary change, with perceptions being influenced by the specific circumstances (study abroad experience).

7.2 Key Contributions to the Sociolinguistic Scholarship

The study offered some original contributions to academia in terms of theoretical framework, methodology and findings.

7.2.1 Theoretical Contributions

- ✓ At the widest scale, the thesis broadened the scope of LM/LS and their application. Traditionally, LM/LS were more limited to L1. This study addressed L2 (FL, which is also part of AA, and usually used alongside it) instead. Therefore, it provided new ways LM/LS research can be conducted. French LM/LS to English were studied within languaging rather than isolation (traditionally, either one maintains a language as a whole or shifts to another). They were also studied in a context of short term-mobility, presenting what can be labelled as earlier/nascent stages of LM/LS. By so doing, it would open new lines of thinking in the study of LM/LS, multilingualism, mobility and globalisation. So, adding another suggestion to Pauwels's one, LM/LS were studied among Algerian mobile students by focusing on the continued use of a second language (French) during their study period in the UK. The focus was on the amount of French and English that is embedded within research participants' Algerian Arabic. Pauwels (2019), when forecasting the effectiveness of her new suggestion in studying current linguistic practices in transnational contexts, said " whatever the outcomes of these field-reshaping efforts will be, they are likely to lead to a different interpretation of what constitutes LM and LS" (p.250). This study is no exception to this, one may hope, mainly in terms of presenting findings related to situations of short-term mobility.
- ✓ The study contributed to the growing literature in LM/LS, multilingualism and ethnic minorities in transnational settings. The linguistic practices of Algerian communities in the UK are rarely researched or are perhaps among the ones under-researched. This study is the first to inquire into LM/LS among this specific ethnolinguistic community group. So, the research outcomes can relate to the scholarly literature around the sociolinguistics of the Algerian diaspora.

- ✓ Previous studies on Arabic heritage minorities in Anglophone countries mostly included individuals and groups with long-term mobility i.e. Jamai's (2008) study on the Moroccan minority in the UK, Arfi's (2008, 2014) work on the Algerian community in the USA, Othman's (2011) exploration of Arab communities in Manchester and Bichani's (2015) recent research on two cases of Arab communities in the UK. These studies targeted different types of individuals, regardless of their individual profiles, motives to mobility and other factors. However, as I brought to mention, Blommaert and Rampton (2011) recently raised the awareness of researchers to a recent trend in migration studies which implies focusing on the super-diversity of immigrants and their differences in motives and migration trajectories. In line with this new trend of focus, the present study targeted a community of interest: transnational mobile students, having similar motives and professional profiles. So, this study is central to professional globalisation and how professionals are becoming globalised. The findings are not only transferrable to HE as one professional area, but also to professional communities of interest, i.e. engineering, banking, advertising, International NGO's and other international spaces. The outcomes of this study may inform these internationalised professionals as well.
- ✓ Findings can also relate to the scholarly literature of mobile resources as opposed to immobile resources. The importance to shift from the latter paradigm to the former is addressed by Blommaert (2010) and Canagarajah (2013). It became obvious that the world is moving away from nation state being the predominant defining identity towards communities of interest.
- ✓ More specifically, because this cohort travelled in the light of mobility programmes, the outcomes then can offer some insights to the sociolinguistic consequences of students' transition and their international experience of study abroad in terms of language use, thus yielding findings relevant to internationalisation of higher education, mobility and exchange programmes.
- ✓ There is little documentary evidence on single studies that compare perceived and reported behaviours in LM/LS. This study offered new ways of understanding LM/LS through the incorporation of comparative data (both through self-report and actual behaviours methods).

- ✓ Without denying the traditional fundamentals of LM/LS, the study was also researched from the perspective of a translanguaging approach as a new way which implies more fluidity, flexibility and dynamism; that is, observing LM/LS as they exist within different linguistic communicative resources; from the binary choice of LM/LS which implies either or/ all or nothing process to looking at resources in concert with each other. Therefore, it went beyond the traditional concern of LM/LS which seems to be restricted. This study is based on a more harmonious occurrence of linguistic behaviours, instead of considering translanguaging as an opposing pole to code-switching.

7.2.2 Methodological Contributions

- ✓ At the methodological level, the mini-ethnographic case study methodology that I followed enabled the depth of the study to gain sufficient data with the PhD time frame. It also proved significant in the sense of looking at data from an ethnographic perspective.
- ✓ In sociolinguistics, natural speech data methods usually comprise self-recordings, sociolinguistic interviews, observations, field notes and more elicitation methods. Focus group method is usually used as a self-report method. In this study, it was distinctively employed as a tool to elicit naturalistic data.
- ✓ The sequential design was useful in carrying out the fieldwork, where the design of each method was shaped by findings from the preceding research instrument, responding to its limitations as appropriate.
- ✓ The study elaborated further on Creswell's (2015) original exploratory mixed method sequential design by incorporating a third phase (qualitative).

7.3 Recommendations for the Target Audiences

Despite the fact that the study reflects the findings of a case study, it can inform a particular audience such as policy makers, curriculum designers, institutions and international students.

- ✓ At a broader level, the study's findings are addressed to the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education expecting outcomes from "The New Multi-million Pound Scholarship Programme". Daltry, Director of the British Council Algeria, said of the investment, "I

believe this initiative over the next decade has a great potential to develop English skills in Algeria and greater mutual knowledge and understanding between our two countries more broadly” (British Council, 2014, n.p). At the sociolinguistic level, findings from this study could reinforce the authorities’ efforts to develop EL status and its use among the new generations in Algeria, especially with the new linguistic forms associated with it. In terms of the research sample involved in this mobility programme, as global individuals with an international experience, it would be useful to draw lessons from their linguistic practices, especially with the new attempts that the government is making to integrate itself within global practices at different levels.

- ✓ The policy makers’ initiatives to introduce linguistic reforms in Algeria regarding the status of FL and EL are already underway. Regarding French and English languages, it was already illustrated in chapter two that the population appears to have an inclusive ideology which favours additive multilingualism (Benrabah, 2007b, 2013, 2014, Belmihoub, 2012, 2018a, 2018b). The authorities, however, tend rather to call for developing the status of English at the expense of French (subtractive multilingualism) (Belmihoub, 2012, Benrabah, 2007b, 2013, 2014, Ghanmi, 2019). In this regard, the relationship between both languages was described as one of rivalry based on the policy makers’ own ideologies, but not according to the population’s attitudes. Benrabah (2013, p.98) articulated that “the misrepresentation of the contest between English and French in Algeria relies on top-down language planning activities occurring in a social vacuum. In other words, it does not account for input from the community’s language practices and attitudes”. These research outcomes, if taken into account, would add weight to one side of debates: additive multilingualism ideologies. Referring back to the research findings, as long as FL has been recorded in actual behaviours as more maintained as part of a repertoire among mobile students even in the UK, where English was also used, it would be then a good source of support for additive multilingualism ideologists. In other words, evidence of French LM (alongside other resources rather than in isolation) could be significant in that FL can be preserved even among Algerians in Anglophone countries, and simply reinforces the point that using, or encouraging the use of English, does not necessarily require the exclusion of French. This is mainly because the study illustrated the use of different resources in concert with each other, with no language entirely superseding the other.

Even those research subjects who assumed LS, LS was identified as using English as a predominant language alongside AA, but still French is used, as presented and discussed in previous chapters. Having considered that, the disseminated findings could be an eye-opener for policy makers in Algeria to consider the additive multilingualism practice.

- ✓ Findings encourage the bottom-up planning, alluded to by Benrabah (2013): “(...) a ‘bottom-up’ approach to language planning activities is more likely to suit the population’s multilingual orientations than the current ‘top-down’ unilingual method” (169). Considering the inclusive nature of these findings in future policy debates is worthwhile in the sense of promoting Peace Sociolinguistics, a desired practice that was suggested by Benrabah (2013) and Belmihoub (2015) to alleviate language conflicts in Algeria and to establish linguistic harmony. As long as actual behaviours data did not yield a sense of linguistic exclusion among a group with an international experience, then it would be worthwhile to draw lessons from these international students in the policy making. It is high time for policy makers to draw from the daily life linguistic practices of population as an authentic source in their policy decisions and planning.

Based on the previous point, it is also hoped that the authorities make both have an equal status in various domains as they made Standard Arabic and Tamazight equal in status (*official* languages). As a first initiative, equal implementation of both English and French in primary phase education is recommended among curriculum designers.

- ✓ Lessons from this study could apply to North African countries, sharing similar language conflict issues. Not only this, but also to professional communities of interest around the world. This study is typically representative of a new class of a mobile professionals who translanguage. Accordingly, it evidences translanguaging as a new practice that can inform policy and planning among different communities around the globe. One may also say that this can apply to other communities whose pre-mobility second language is not English.
- ✓ At the level of the host country, the findings of this research could be useful for those aiming to provide institutional supports that foster LM. The intragroup interactions of students from the same national background in different informal social settings would be a good strategy to preserve community languages through their solidarity,

and therefore, can be considered as a good linguistic resource to exploit learning and preserving CL opportunities outside the classroom. In other words, institutions can offer support to preserve community languages through creating informal social sites where students/ pupils from the same heritage background can meet and interact with each other. At the classroom level, it raises the awareness of teaching staff of the multilingual resources in their classes, a point which is emphasised by García (2009).

- ✓ The thesis has also some possible implications for a particular type of readership: international students who want to preserve their community languages without being exclusively subject to shift to the host country linguistic practices. The Algerian students' experiences with language use can raise international students' metalinguistic awareness on how they could act if they want to maintain multilingualism, without excluding any linguistic code and acquire a translingual identity.

7.4 Thesis Main Limitations

Although my original intention was based on a good thinking and practice, some limitations (mostly triggered by time constraints) were raised, and therefore are worth addressing:

- ✓ This research represents findings from a small-scale case study that was only limited to "friendship domain". This has led to a narrowed dimension of inquiry. In other words, it was hard to claim that the findings represent Algerian students experience with LM/LS. Consequently, the elicited findings would never represent the experiences of Algerian students with LM/LS, nor those of other Algerian mobility patterns community in the UK. The results, while not generalizable in that sense, do still suggest lines of inquiry that could be explored for a larger population.
- ✓ It was hard to analyse a sociolinguistic experience whose speakers can neither be treated as full migrants, nor as local people, because of the short period of stay students had in their mobility (as mentioned in the critical appraisal of LM/LS application in situations of short-stay periods). These results may certainly change by the time these mobile students live for longer in the host country. Therefore, it was hard to draw conclusions about the linguistic practices of this community. In this

respect, one may think that this research is inconclusive, given that the results would change with a longer stay sojourn.

- ✓ It was hard to rely only on perceptions related to the pre-mobility experience and compare them to the current mobility perceptions and actual behaviours. While perceptions seem to be the only source to obtain non-virtual daily practices related to pre-mobility, reporting any linguistic change was challenging because language change (LS), might be an assumed one, rather than an actual one. Actually, this stumbling block was already anticipated in Chapter 3 and the force of claims around identifying LS was loosened accordingly (viewing it as a temporary aspirational process, representing nascent stages of the process).
- ✓ The individual interviews, focus group and observation data contained data that took the discussion to another level, beyond the original aims of this research study. Although one should not overlook these, given the focus of this study claims arising from this additional data could not be developed. However, such data could still be used as the basis for a separate inquiry.
- ✓ In this research, methods were comparatively used. The major aim behind the questionnaire was to contextualise interviews' findings, to learn the extent to which data obtained from the larger population reflected those of interviews. Nevertheless, some elements of the interviews were concerned with the lived experiences of individuals to understand them in a unique way. However, the questionnaire was meant to get general data. These two sets of data had created two types of self-report findings. It was hard to generate a meaningful discussion at this level because of the quality of the data generated by two different methods: one precise and more detailed; the other is impersonal and general.

These weaknesses threw up something interesting. Therefore, some of them will be carefully addressed in future research.

7.5 Avenues for Related Research and Future Directions

- Despite all endeavours to analyse the complexity associated with FL use within mobility, the present project could be much more developed by widening the scope of inquiry. It is thereby suggested to include a large-scale sample including individuals,

who crossed borders some time ago and – if possible - lived in different international spaces, to explore deeper effects of transnational mobility. The study can be extended to various domains. It is only in that way that one could yield in-depth understanding around attitudes towards community languages and their use in a transnational setting.

- It would also be illuminating if future sociolinguists use comparative data of FL use among different ethnic groups: for example, Tunisian, Moroccan and Algerian communities. One of the premises is that these communities came from similar socio-historical backgrounds, having all been impacted by French colonisation, and therefore have similar linguistic practices. The aim of the inquiry should be on identifying the differences between FL attitudes and use among these different ethnic communities who share a common linguistic start. This can also apply among micro-national ethnic groups: for example, Kabyle and Arab groups. As explained before, Kabyle people are known by their linguistic affiliation towards this language (Belmihoub, 2012). It would be of significance to limit the exploration to such ethnolinguistic groups.
- This study can be also enhanced with the use of a broader range of comparative data methods that would be used equally, to better capture linguistic variation in multilingual contexts.
- Another possible avenue would be on how changes in the concept of migration which became different from that of the 20th century, affect the field of LM/LS, with the advent of the “virtual space”. It might be enlightening to focus on transnational communities from the 21st century (the case of Algerians, for example) and compare their online and offline use of FL through online and offline ethnographic methodologies. In this main respect, one possible question would be how language use among these individuals adapts to the alternation of social interaction modes (virtual versus real), and how their sociolinguistic competence operates in both contexts, with regards to LM/LS.
- Another possible way of doing this research would be to focus on the repertoire “as a whole” rather than focusing on “one language” within a repertoire, simply because the view of “one nation, one language” became hard to maintain within globalised communicative practices. By so doing, it would fulfil new lines of thinking suggested

by Pauwels (2016): LM (maintenance of multiple practices)/ LS (reduced linguistic practices).

- Finally, future research is planned to track the linguistic practices of interviewed students in the post-mobility phase of the professional careers, after they finish their degrees and go back to Algeria. The main aim is to explore further the reverse linguistic change as well as issues around language use and LM/LS over time and space.

In conclusion, one may think that we need to move away from the concepts of LM/LS in further research. My study begins to suggest that these terms no longer serve the purpose because they retain a binary choice, "EITHER/OR", which presupposes a subtractive understanding of language use. The concept of translanguaging disrupts this binary logic. Perhaps, it is time to think of a new terminology to cope with the new linguistic practices in the field such as LMS (language shift within maintenance). For LM, it is not a pure LM, but additive LM. It seems that there are more complex things that people are doing than using one code at the expense of the other. The field of LM/LS urgently needs to advance theoretically in ways that correspond to linguistic hybridity, flexibility and dynamism triggered by current mobilities and technological developments in the world.

7.6 The Researcher's Own Development as an Academic

In the end of the thesis, I would like to reflect on my experience with what I have learnt within and beyond the scope of my PhD thesis. I have learnt that PhD research is not a checklist of stages to go through in a linear fashion. However, it is more dynamic in the sense that some steps in my research overlapped and influenced each other. On this account, one is not necessarily required to get a particular stage done before moving to the other. Having proceeded in that second option would have saved much time.

Post graduate research is an excellent opportunity for developing PhD students' online and offline academic identity. It is a real change in my identity from a consumer of subject knowledge to critically producing interdisciplinary knowledge. My experience as a PhD student has taught me that research is not just "facing the screen and writing up to 80,000 words thesis limit". For more academic growth, however, I made use of every single opportunity I had the chance to receive during my career. Consequently, the present

undertaken research has not seen the light only through the lens of individual efforts. It further flourished through embracing different voices whose feedback was carefully and constructively taken into account.

I set my first paces towards academic growth through my online involvement in some academia platforms especially Research Gate, where I had the chance to widely exchange my research ideas, develop interdisciplinary communication, and find encounters with similar research interests. At the offline sphere, I built my PDR (Professional Development Record) at the level of university and in other higher education institutions (in the UK and outside the UK). Having the chance to communicate my research at both disciplinary and across-the-field levels, made my vision towards the concept of research widen and widen. In interdisciplinary events, I have learnt how to use the simplest version of my research in order to convey the ideas in a more intelligible way. Communicating research within the field gave me the chance to know how to maintain the balance between gaining insightful sociolinguistic knowledge and embracing different researchers' epistemological stances, having similar basic backgrounds in the field.

This research was particularly inspired by:

- The Second International Conference on Sociolinguistics (ICS.2)
- Language and Borders: Rethinking Mobility, Migration and Space
- Perspectives on Linguistic Diversity (CLARC 2018)
- ELF, Migration and Multilingualism (ELF 11)
- ECQI 2019 - 3rd European Congress of Qualitative Inquiry

At UWS school level, I have acquired the good tips on how to supervise both local and international students (with intracultural and intercultural awareness), being so much inspired by the supervisory team's own approach. The Monthly Research Colloquium which was arranged to unite students and staffs to share their research interests and progress contributed in my own development as an international academic. It allowed for a deep understanding of the different backgrounds these students are coming from, cultural diversity and pedagogies. This latter was a good resource to develop my intercultural awareness.

As a member of a research team in a project developed out of engagements with the Ulab process, I have developed skills around collaborations for a thriving emergent future. The walking inquiry sessions and the mindfulness practice made me self-aware of the various aspects of this unique experience as an international person. It also built my readiness to connect my academic experience to a wider change in the world and to adjust to different situations.

Finally, lessons from this study encourage different kinds of conversations. Evidence of translanguaging/language practices in my findings has affected my own international standing as an academic. As an international student and a member of the mobility group, I acquired an identity which is *trans*. With sensitivity to language awareness, I will consider translanguaging as an instructional strategy to facilitate teaching/learning in my future profession as a teacher educator in higher education, and in my trajectory onwards.

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List of Appendices

Appendix 1: Correspondence between Arabic Letters and Romanized

Arabic (Yaghan, 2008), cited in Cotterell et al. (2014, p.35)

Arabic	Arabizi	Arabic	Arabizi
ا	a	ب	b, p
ت	t	ث	th, s
ج	j, g	ح	7, h
د	7', 5	د	d
ذ	th z	ر	r
ز	z	س	s c
ش	sh, ch	ص	9
ط	9', d	ظ	t
ع	th	ع	3
غ	gh, 3'	ف	f
ق	8, 2, k, q	ك	k
س	l	م	m
ن	n	ه	h
و	w, o, ou	ي	y, i, e

Appendix 2: Socio-demographic Profile: Participants and the Researcher

	<i>Sonia</i>	<i>Karim</i>	<i>Sara</i>	<i>Amin</i>	<i>Souzan</i>	<i>Schahin</i>	<i>The Researcher</i>
Gender	<i>Female</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>
Location of residence in Algeria	Middle cities	Mediterranean cities-east of Algeria	Mediterranean cities-east of Algeria	Middle cities	Mediterranean cities-west of Algeria	Mediterranean cities -west of Algeria	Mediterranean cities -east of Algeria
Ethnicity	Berber (Chaoui)	Arab	Berber (Kabyle)	Berber (Chaoui)	Arab	Arab	Arab
Mother tongue	AA	AA	Kabyle and French	AA	AA	AA	AA
Length of residence in the UK by the time of interviews/ focus group sessions	Around two years	Around two years	Around two years	Around two years	One year	Around one year and few months	Around two years
Length of residence in the UK by the time of observation sessions	Around one year after the aforementioned participants' period of stay						
Perceived level of proficiency	Less competent user	Intermediate	Very advanced	Intermediate	Less competent user	Very advanced	Intermediate

Appendix 3: A Sample from Interviews Earlier Coding

Participant 1: *Sonia*

Pre-mobility experience			
Main points	Initial noting	Sub-themes	Major-themes
Dynamics of Language use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Algerian Arabic in a family context - Algerian Arabic (mixed with French) with colleagues outside classroom and friends (AA-French code switching) - Algerian Arabic, English and French in classroom -French in administration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Interlocutor -Locale 	Setting
French language domination in Algeria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “it depends on the location you live in ...” -Less dominated in interior cities -More dominated in Mediterranean cities 	-Geographical area	

Aspirational identification of pre-mobility FL/EL use	<u>French</u> -Appreciated in administration and easy to sort out your queries by its means - Common second language “they should use Arabic first and then adopt the other code according to what people have as a second language” -In classroom, it facilitates lesson explanation “(...)to speak a whole lesson in English is difficult” <u>English</u> “If you are in classroom and you communicate with your teacher, English should be there”	-Functional in administration -Facilitate communication in public life -Facilitates communication in classroom //	Functionality back home
	<u>French</u> “I grown up in an environment where if you speak French, it means something, it means that you know and it means you are from high class family”	-Prestige -intellectuality	Status
	<u>English</u> -Matter of preference “I like English”	-Positive attitudes	Attitudes and value factors

Frequency of French use (as part of AA) with Algerian colleagues	-Daily used "Believe me it is every day " "Algerian Arabic and French. They go together " "French is like a step in our language, you can't speak Algerian Arabic without French"	-Highly used - Attachment to L1	High status within verbal repertoire
Exposure to French use	- Absence of French use -English language influence "when I started learning English, my level in French has been decreased from what it was before"	- Family support is negative -Language attrition	Beginning of language shift
Feelings about the use of French among colleagues	"We don't want French to go" "It is a good thing to learn three languages"	-Strong attachment to L2 -FL is a plus	Stimulating additive multilingualism

current experience			
Main points	Initial noting	Sub-themes	Super-themes
status of FL in the current verbal repertoire	-French is less used "I started using English more and worrying about my French language" -French language substitution	-reduction in the use of French -AA –English-French code-switching	Language shift

	<p>"I started code switching with Algerian Arabic and English more than French"</p>		
<p>Perceived sociolinguistic stance</p>	<p>"I see myself as a shifter"</p> <p>"I am using French unconsciously"</p>	<p>-A gradual shifter to English</p> <p>-slight maintainer of French</p>	<p>shifter to English</p>
<p>Meaning around the current Linguistic behaviours resulted from the participant and her interaction</p>	<p><u>English: Context impact</u></p> <p>"I started using English most of the time"</p> <p><u>French: Depending on whom to talk to</u></p> <p>"if I feel that the person I am talking with needs me to talk in French"</p> <p>"if I want to talk about something personal and I don't want others non Algerians to understand"</p> <p><u>AA-English Code –mixing</u></p> <p>"We make the word in English suits our speech to make the Arabic sentence looks grammatically correct (...)"</p>	<p>context dependent</p> <p>-aligning with the new context</p> <p>Interlocutor dependent</p> <p>Topic dependent</p> <p>- Personal issues</p> <p>Purpose dependent</p> <p>-Adaption to L1 use</p> <p>Purpose dependent</p> <p>-Depends on the lexis of speaker</p>	<p>Setting</p>

	<p><u>AA-English-French Code-switching with Algerians</u></p> <p>“If I speak with an Algerian fellow I think I would mix between Algerian Arabic, English and French respectively“</p>	-Depending on whom to talk to	
<p>Aspirational identification of shifting to English (as a predominant embedded code alongside AA)</p>	<p>Influence of doing a PhD</p> <p>“We are English students, that’s why we use more English than French words in our daily interactions (...) what you study all the time can affect your use of language”</p> <p>“As a matter of preference , I prefer English”</p> <p>“Because English is taking over, I do prefer it”</p>	-Professional impact	Functionality
		-Positive attitudes	Attitude/value factor

		-dominance and power	Status
Aspirational identification of French language maintenance (as a predominant embedded code alongside AA and English)	“I am going back to my country, I will deal with people from my country and I know I will speak French “	-Future considerations	Functionality
	“It will make my life easier in Algeria”	-facilitating communication	
	“When you speak French it seems you are educated, it gives you very good outlook”	-Intellectuality -Prestige	Status
Maintaining a set of practices	“ (...) for me, more than one language is good”		-Openness towards multilingualism
	“(…) French is a step in our language, like you cannot speak AA without French” (Sonia)		-First language as a set of practices

Appendix 4: The Honeycomb Model- Wilson (2013)

Appendix 5: Interview Schedule

Interviewer: my name is **Hadjer Chellia**, a PhD student in UWS. You are kindly invited to participate in my research. In this interview, you will be asked some questions about your linguistic experience with French language use, both before mobility and currently. It will take approximately 30 to 40 minutes. There are no foreseeable risks associated with this project. However, if you feel uncomfortable answering any questions, you can withdraw from the interview at any point. Your responses will be strictly confidential and data from this research will be coded and displayed anonymously.

N.B. Sub- probing questions are further asked to participants, when required.

SECTION 1: Narratives about your language choice and use

Before your mobility to the UK:

1 -What are the languages that structured your verbal repertoire?

-What was the position of each language within your verbal repertoire?

-When and where were you using each?

With your transition to the UK

2 -Can you compare your old verbal repertoire with the new one? Have you noticed any restructuring at its level?

-What is the position of each language?

3 - During your stay in the UK, when you socialise with other Algerian PhD students?

-What languages do you use?

-Could you rank them according to the degree of use?

SECTION 2: French language use

Before mobility:

4 -For how long have you been studying French in Algeria?

-Are you a competent user of it?

5 -What do you think of French linguistic domination and prestige in Algeria nowadays?

6 - Have you been using French words while interacting with your colleagues (Algerian English language students?)

A-How often have you been using it?

7 - How did you view French language and its use among Algerian English students?

With you transition:

8 -Have you noticed any change in the way you use French during your stay in the UK? How?

9 -While interacting with your Algerian fellows, are you maintaining the use of it?

- If you are a maintainer, how often you use it in your speech currently then?

10-When and where? (Some prompts are required through the provision of different contexts and settings where they are usually found)

11- What are the issues that you think you use more French while discussing with your Algerian fellows? (Some prompts are also provided here)

12- What motivates you to prefer to continue operating with French language use?

-What strategies are you using to preserve your French use?

13 -If you think you stopped using French while interacting to your Algerian fellows, why?

Does English play any role in this?

14 -What do you think of your Algerian fellows when they keep using French?

15 -How can you describe your experience with French language use in the UK?

Appendix 6: Web-based Questionnaire Schedule

Key Sociodemographic information

Please answer the following questions either by ticking the appropriate box or filling the gaps

1. Gender: Male Female
- 2-Ethnicity: Arab Berber others
- 3-If you are Berber please further specify the micro-ethnicity
- 4-The geographical part of Algeria where you grew up ?
 - Mediterranean cities (East of Algeria)
 - Mediterranean cities (West of Algeria)
 - Middle cities
 - Saharan cities
- 5-Length of residence in the UK
- 6- Travelling to Algeria from one time to another
 - Yes
 - No
- 7- Self-reported French language proficiency
 - Very advanced
 - Advanced
 - Intermediate
 - Elementary
 - Beginner

Participants' linguistic history and current language use

8- Languages that your family mostly use in their daily conversations? (Tick more than once if applies)

- Algerian Arabic
- Berber dialects
- French
- English
- Others (please specify).....

9. Languages that you were informally using with their Algerian colleagues before mobility

(Tick more than once if applies)

- Algerian Arabic
- Berber dialects
- French
- English
- Others (please specify).....

10-languages that you are currently using while interacting with their Algerian PhD

colleagues (Tick more than once if applies)

- Algerian Arabic
- Berber dialects
- French
- English
- Others (please specify).....

11- Frequency of French language use before mobility

- Never
- Rarely
- Occasionally
- Often
- Always

12- Frequency of French language use in the UK

- Never
- Rarely
- Occasionally
- Often
- Always

13- Participants' self-perceived sociolinguistic stance with transition

- More maintainers of French
- More shifter to English

14- Why do you think you are perceiving yourself as (maintainer/ shifter?)

.....

15- (Optional) Reasons why you think you preserved the use of French language in your repertoire

- It has a prestigious status in Algeria
- It indicates being a bilingual /multilingual
- It facilitates interaction with your Algerian PhD colleagues
- It can be used as a code to socialise with French students
- It is very functional in some domains in mainland Algeria
- It is attached to L1

Others (please specify).....

16- (Optional) strategies that you (assuming LM) use to preserve FL use in the UK

- Using it while talking to your family /relatives /friends in Algeria via social media
- Interacting constantly with your Algerian fellows
- Interacting with French students in the UK
- Using it to post, blog and comment in social media platforms
- Others (please specify)

17- The existing relationship between language use and the topic being discussed

- Yes
- No

18- The existing relationship between French language and the physical setting where interaction with Algerian students takes place

- Yes
- No

19- The existing relationship between French language use and the person interacting with (interlocutor)

- Yes
- No

20-(Optional) your motivations behind shifting to English (for participants assuming LS)

- As a matter of preference, you like English
- English is a language of prestige
- Living in the UK is more relevant to English language use
- English is more important in relation to your present and future career
- English is more important as an international language

-English is more functional back home

-Others (please specify).....

21- Your description of their experience with French language use

- Complex

-Positive

-Negative

22- Any further details if you wish to add

Appendix 7: Observation checklists as parts of the field notes

Participant 1: *Sonia*

- Estimated time of observation: 3 hours on 25 min

- Dominant event at that time: "Aid" (an Algerian religious cultural event)

Name: Sonia (P1) Date: 14.06.2018

Language use and behaviours		TOPIC		INTERLOCUTOR		SETTING and the type of activity the participant was doing
		Topic function	Discourse mode	Arab	Berber	
		Referential function (informative)	Algerian context related issues	Chaoui	kabyle	University
Code-switching (alternating between Algerian Arabic, English, French) A-A English French	Referential function (informative) ✓	Algerian context related issues	Research related (her challenges in reviewing for friend's dissertation)	③	①	She was preparing evening Snacks in her kitchen for Algerian friends who visited her
	AA French English	Affective (social) ✓	Algerian preparation in Algeria			
Code-switching AA English French			Algeria in the UK			
	AA English French	Using quotations that imply more religious reference				
Code-switching AA English French			before English reference for foot ball			
	AA English French					

Participant 2: Karim

Estimated time of observation: 2 hours (roughly)
 Dominant event at that time: The world cup (2018)

Name: Karim (P2) Date: 28/06/2018

Assessed Criteria						
Language use and behaviours	TOPIC		INTERLOCUTOR		SETTING and the type of activity the participant was doing	
	Topic function	Discourse mode	Arab	Berber	Accommodation	University
	Referential function	Affective (social)	British/ Current context related issues	Chaoui	kabyle	
AA French English (very few) English (from)	✓ with a sense of humour talking	food preferences in his daily life in the UK	②	①	having dinner in the accomodation kitchen with other Algerians including myself	
AA French English (at least 20 words)	✓ with a strong sense of humour	the tenancy and agreements of the accomodation				

Participant 3: Sara

Estimated time of observation: 50 minutes (roughly)
 Dominant event at that time: Ramadan "a religious cultural Algerian event"

Name: Sara (P.3) Date: 10/06/2018

Assessed Criteria		TOPIC		INTERLOCUTOR			SETTING and the type of activity the participant was doing
Language use and behaviours	Topic function		Discourse mode		Arab	Berber	Accommodation
	Referential function	Affective (social)	Algerian context related issues	British/ Current context related issues	Chaoui	Kabyle	
Cot-switching AA + French English AA + French AA + English	more social feelings of (sarcasm) using	how people built home related to success	British/ Current context related issues	1	1	a casual visit to her while she was organically her room	University
AA French English and Switched to AA English French	more informative function	describing for success	A address a address a address				

Name: Sara (P.3) Date: 24-06-2018
 Estimated time of observation: 2 hours and 55 minutes
 Dominant event at that time: A friend's wedding (Algerian one)

almost

Assessed Criteria						
Language use and behaviours	TOPIC		INTERLOCUTOR		SETTING and the type of activity the participant was doing	
	Discourse mode		Arab	Berber		
	Referential function	Affective (social)	Algerian context related issues	British/ Current context related issues	Chaoui	Kabyle
(AA) French English Kabyle	Referential function Affective (social) cooperation Referential function manner	Algerian context related issues pre-migration accent (Algerian one)	British/ Current context related issues current accent (Algerian one)	Arab ③	Berber Chaoui ③	Kabyle ①
(AA) French Swabian	Referential function Affective (social) cooperation Referential function manner	Algerian context related issues pre-migration accent (Algerian one)	British/ Current context related issues current accent (Algerian one)	Arab ③	Berber Chaoui ③	Kabyle ①

Participant 4: Amin

Name: Amin (P.U) Date: 26-06-2018
 Estimated time of observation: 3 hours
 Dominant event at that time: The three minutes Hairs competition (3MT)

Assessed Criteria									
Language use and behaviours	TOPIC			INTERLOCUTOR		SETTING and the type of activity the participant was doing			
	Topic function	Affective (social)	Discourse mode	British/ Current context related issues	Arab		Berber		
	Referential function (inframotive)		Algerian context related issues		Chaoui	kabye			
AA French English AA French	✓			The 3MT criteria of assessment	①	①	Accommodation	University	he was preparing dinner in the accommodation
AA French English	✓			research					he was preparing dinner in the accommodation
AA French English AA French	✓			Schengen States Visa France Paris especially					
AA French AA French		✓		Research UK France Paris					

Participant 5: Souzan

Estimated time of observation: 2 hours and 30 minutes
 Dominant event at that time: Preparing for her wedding party and passing her upgrade event

Name: Souzan (P.S) Date: 23-06-2018

Assessed Criteria				INTERLOCUTOR		SETTING and the type of activity the participant was doing	
Language use and behaviours	TOPIC		Discourse mode	British/ Current context related issues	Arab	Berber	University
	Referential function	Affective (social)			Algerian context related issues	Chaoui	
SAA English French Café switching	✓		Upgrade event feedback	②			Souzas applying beauty products in cafe preparing for her wedding party visit to her room preparing for her wedding party
SAA English Café switching	✓	non-Algerians on her stress and her partner because of wedding preparation					
SAA French English Café switching	quo. reference on her stress non-Algerians	✓ Expressing appreciation wedding party					

Participant 6: Schahin

Estimated time of observation: 2 hours and 15 minutes
 Dominant event at that time: The Algerian day of independence (5th of July)

Name: Schahin (P.6) Date: 05 - 07 - 2018

Language use and behaviours		TOPIC			INTERLOCUTOR			SETTING and the type of activity the participant was doing	
		Topic function	Affective (social)	Discourse mode	Arab	Berber	Accommodation	University	
Code switching AA French	Referential function	✓	network connection yachhome	British/ Current context related issues	(4)	(2)		for was having a chat break time in the University Cafe with other Algerian friends	
		✓	has intolerance with some French people because of historical reasons						
	✓		Common socially imposed						

Name: Sahlin (P6) Date: 28-07-2018

Estimated time of observation: 20 minutes
 Dominant event at that time: preparing to go back home (annual leave)

Language use and behaviours		TOPIC		INTERLOCUTOR		SETTING and the type of activity the participant was doing					
		Referential function	Affective (social)	Discourse mode	British/ Current context related issues	Arab	Berber	Chaoui	kabyle	Accommodation	University
Code switching AA English French	more referential		Algerian context related issues	offering instructions about flat rent	②	①					he was interacting to another Algerian friend in their break time at the University Cafe
	AA French English	✓		modelling the reservation							
Code switching AA French				AA French English and other American slang							

English and reservation during the moment in the UK -10-

